

A Comparative Study of the Application of Glowworm Swarm Optimization Algorithm with other Nature-Inspired Algorithms in the Network Load Balancing Problem

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Abstract-Vast amounts of data are transferred through communication networks resulting in node congestion, which varies according to peak usage times. The Glowworm Swarm Optimization (GSO) algorithm is inspired by the rummaging and courtship behavior of glowworms. The glow intensity of glowworms is a measure of fitness that attracts other glowworms in its neighborhood. This work applies the GSO algorithm to the computer network congestion problem in order to lessen the network burden by shifting loads to the fittest neighborhood nodes, thereby enhancing network performance during peak traffic times, when the response of systems on the network would go down. The proposed solution aims to alleviate the burdened nodes, thereby improving the flow of traffic throughout the network, improving the users' experience and productivity, and efficiency. In this paper, three swarm algorithms, namely Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Cuckoo Search (CK), and GSO have been employed to solve the network load balancing problem. The results produced by GSO show improvement of 71.17%, 74.14%, and 84.15% in networks consisting of 50, 100, and 200 nodes in peak hour load, while PSO shows 13.87%, 11.75%, and 23.72%, and CK 10.61%, 3.19%, and 6%. The results prove the superior performance of GSO.

Keywords-network congestion; load balancing; GSO; throughput; swarm intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

The decentralized computer network system is a mixture of heavily and lightly loaded nodes, with the heavily loaded nodes becoming bottlenecks, thereby reducing traffic flow rate,

causing system sluggish response on the networks. Load balancing addresses this issue to improve the network throughput by routing packets to adjacent edges having lesser traffic load. It enables the reasonable distribution of resources on computer networks and thereby a more efficient utilization of resources. The network burden at an edge depends on the queue of tasks that need to be processed through that node. The queue length is related to the response time of the jobs and is an important indicator of load burden on a computer network [1].

The effectiveness of conventional algorithms for load balancing in computer networks (such as the round Robin task scheduler and least connection [2]) will be adversely impacted due to the explosive increase of data coming from mobile devices or tablets. Data usage is expected to soon exceed 142 Exabyte a month [3]. Additionally, it is estimated that there will be 57.7 billion electronic and IoT devices linked to the Internet by 2023 [4]. All these devices will link to the network via technologies like 2G, 3G, 4G, LTE,5G and Machine-to-Machine (M2M) with wireless options like Bluetooth, Wi-Fi and Zig-Bee. Various approaches have been used to address this problem.

The meta-heuristic approach to optimization problems, such as the use of nature-inspired algorithms [5], has attracted the attention of researchers. The term Swarm Intelligence was introduced by Beni and Wang in 1989 in the global optimization framework of cellular robotics [6]. Swarm Intelligence follows the distributed methodology of governing

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of work in chronological direction. This strategy is motivated from the behavior of ants searching for food in collaboration in appropriate order with nest mates. A swarm is an enormous group of homogeneous agents that are locally interacting among themselves. There is no central control and they are globally distributed in a decentralized manner. The idea of Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm comes from the movement of Ants foraging for food and its delivery into the nest [7-9]. The ACO is applied for finding the shortest route by emitting chemical substances (pheromones), updating the following path, therefore all ants move like a trail bridge. It is applicable in the travelling salesman problem for calculating the optimal path among different cities. A novel approach of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) was introduced in 1995 [10, 11] which is inspired from flocks of birds and schools of fish and their social behavior. The PSO is used for accessing a target with minimal duration by updating the particle's current velocity and position from its neighborhood. The Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm's [12] inspiration is the behavior of honeybees foraging foods to make honey in a nest. It transfers a message to its nest mate with the help of a waggle dance. The Cuckoo Search (CK) algorithm is based on the cuckoo bird's life and breeding scheme [13]. Glowworm Swarm Optimization (GSO) is investigated in this paper with regard to network load balancing. The idea is to mitigate the traffic load burden during peak hours using a meta-heuristic approach about network optimization in IoT. Due to increasing massive amounts of data traffic on computer network the decentralized approach is attracting the researchers' attention. The main objective of load balancing method is to allocate the traffic load uniformly dispersed to achieve best performance on homogeneous and heterogeneous data networks. Load balancing is used to enhance user fulfillment, better utilization of resources, execution time, and waiting time of task coming from several locations/nodes. To do this, a load balancer needs to be able to predict the load on those edges having lesser amounts of traffic. It can be a static or sequential distribution of tasks among the machines in the neighborhood. One drawback is that all nodes can become overloaded. A dynamic technique in swarm intelligence based approach, such as ACO, is one in which data would be segregated on to those nodes that are having the highest amount of pheromone evaporation created as a path. The ants find the shortest route to achieve traffic in minimum amount of time. The Honey Bee in ABC uses another approach to optimize traffic on the optimal path. The main strategy for finding food location, to pass the message to other nest mates is by a waggle dance to find good food sources.

In both wired and wireless media, network packets are moved between nodes by routing. Routing techniques are of two types: static and dynamic. Routing can be based on centralized or decentralized techniques. In the centralized method all nodes are linked into a star configuration [14]. Compared to decentralized systems, centralized systems do not require replication. However, the disadvantage is that when the midpoint of a star network is down, the entire network becomes detached. The swarm intelligence algorithms follow the decentralized scheme of operation. The GSO algorithm is based on multimodal functions to find a set of local optimal

solutions. Applying the analogy of glowworm behavior to communication networks, the network traffic can be shifted to neighborhood glowworm nodes having the highest luminance levels [15, 16].

Large quantities of data from diverse devices and applications traverse through a network. Network optimization has benefits such as faster information rate, information recovery, and elimination of redundant records enabling perceptible improvement in load balancing which plays a crucial role in network performance. The goals of this investigation are:

- To reduce the queue length and thereby divert network traffic to adjacent lighter loaded nodes which in turn would improve network performance.
- To increase the throughput and decrease response time and delay in network systems through the application of GSO.
- The comparison of load balancing via GSO and other nature-inspired algorithms.

Load balancing is a mechanism that distributes a fair allocation of resources among the network nodes. Load balancing methods can be implemented either in hardware or in software. In hardware balancing, there are four layers in a computer network. Switches offer server redundancy and load balancing. Software balancing is used to calculate usage and allocate resources. Furthermore, load balancing can be static and dynamic. In static load balancing, the predictable load is segregated among nodes which are connected directly or indirectly to the network. Dynamic load balancing is used to deal with unpredictable load which can be adjusted on various conditions of homogeneous and heterogeneous data passing through hybrid networks. Static load balancing utilizes the surveying strategy (the round Robin approach). The technique disperses data sequentially to each designated host, however it can be unbalanced among various virtual machines during data distribution [17]. The dynamic load balancing method is primarily based on the associated task, processing time and computational cost of each server that decide the distribution of information in order to acquire the processing time for the tasks. It will lead to uneven server distribution. It can be classified into several sub groups [18-22].

Data traversing through the computer network for choosing the shortest routes is highly beneficial when the data delivery is more important than the overall network lifetime [23]. For minimizing network traffic, uniform load balancing is used to maximize network throughput and reduce queue length [24]. For segregating network traffic, the sub-network load balancing approach, which is constructed on the greedy growing method is developed with strong emphasis on utilizing the on-board batteries of the sensor nodes effectively. It is the best approach for transferring traffic on neighboring nodes [25]. A biased energy and haphazard movement based technique [26] spreads the network traffic among multiple routes in the resource constraint environment. A tree-based load balancing method is introduced, where a leaf of a tree or child node finds one of its parent nodes [27]. The different parameters, i.e. packet delivery, packet loss, and energy

consumption are considered when transferring packets from start to end node. A stochastic distributed approach based on node settlement and load optimization approach is proposed in [28] to balance the energy consumption through the network.

II. LOAD BALANCING PERFORMANCE MEASURES

The performance of load balancing is measured by the following parameters:

- Throughput: The number of packets transferred per unit time span. The performance of computer network is enhanced if throughput is maximized.

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{\text{Data traffic}}{\text{Time}} \quad (1)$$

- Fault Tolerance: Recovery from state when a process is abnormally disconnected or in failure mode.
- Migration Time: it is the period required to transfer packets from a source node to the destination node.
- Traffic Reduce Rate: The traffic rate is calculated as the total reduction in traffic divided by the total data packets transferred from that node multiplied by 100.

$$\text{Traffic Reduce Rate} = \frac{\text{Traffic_reduce}}{\text{Total_traffic}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

- Response Time: The total time-to-live when transferring a packet from one node to another. It is minimized with increase in throughput.

$$\text{Response time} = \frac{1}{\text{Throughput}} \quad (3)$$

- Queue Length: The unprocessed tasks are accumulated into a waiting stage. It is processed for decreasing accumulated task to improve response time and maximizing throughput.

$$Q(m) = Q(m) + L(m) - \frac{T\mu}{fs} \quad (4)$$

where $L(m)$ is the predictable amount of requests allocated to server m in T interval, $T\mu/fs$ is the mean of the new arrival request in the time interval that the server is continuously in busy state.

III. GLOWWORM SWARM OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

A glowworm has the ability to spread randomly in a search space. It is attracted to the glowworm with the highest glow intensity in its neighborhood [29]. Each glowworm broadcasts its glow intensity and is attracted to its neighbors on the basis of a fitness function. The glowworm moves towards the neighboring glowworm having the most glow intensity. The fitness is proportional to the function being optimized.

IV. STEPS OF THE GLOWWORM SWARM OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

The steps of GSO algorithm are depicted in Figure 1. On initialization, all glowworms contain the same amount of Luciferin l_0 . Every cycle of the algorithm passes through three stages: Luciferin modify stage, association stage, and community array update stage. The Luciferin modify stage denotes the function assessment at the glowworm position.

Every glowworm updates its level from its prior Luciferin level:

$$l_i(t + 1) = (1 - \rho) l_i(t) + \gamma J(x_i(t + 1)) \quad (5)$$

where $l_i(t)$ denotes the Luciferin level of the i^{th} glowworm at time t , ρ represents the Luciferin degeneration variable ($0 < \rho < 1$), γ is the Luciferin enhancement variable, and $J(x_i(t))$ denotes the cost of the objective function or the prior level of Luciferin of the i^{th} glowworm at time t .

Stages of Glowworm Life Cycle

Fig. 1. Stages of GSO.

In the Movement period, each glowworm determines the probability to move in the direction where an adjacent glowworm has Luciferin quantity greater than its own, so the glowworm would move towards where the intensity of the radiance is the highest. The probability of moving towards a glowworm at the adjacent j^{th} position is given by:

$$p_{ij}(t) = \frac{l_j(t) - l_i(t)}{\sum_{k \in N_i(t)} l_k(t) - l_i(t)} \quad (6)$$

where $j \in N_i(t)$, $N_i(t) = \{j: d_{ij}(t) < r_d^i(t); l_i(t) < l_j(t)\}$ at neighborhood of glowworm i in time span t , $d_{ij}(t)$ the Euclidean distance between glowworms i and j in time span t , and $r_d^i(t)$ indicates the adjacent array related to glowworm i in time span t . So, the glowworm i selects a glowworm $j \in N_i(t)$ with $P_{ij}(t)$. The prototype for the glowworm arrangement [30] is specified as:

$$y_i(t + 1) = y_i(t) + \left(\frac{y_i(t) - y_j(t)}{\|y_i(t) - y_j(t)\|} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $y_i(t) \in R^m$ is the position of glowworm i in time span t in the m -dimensional real space R^m , $\|\cdot\|$ represents the Euclidean norm operator and $s > 0$ is the step size.

In the neighborhood range update stage, each glowworm i has a neighborhood in its radial range r_d^i ($0 < r_d^i \leq r_s$), where

r_s is the glowworm sensor range. Each glowworm's neighborhood range is updated as:

$$r_d^i(t)(t+1) = \min \{ r_s, \max \{ 0, r_d^i(t) + \beta (n_i - |N_i(t)|) \} \} \quad (8)$$

where β is a constant and n_i is the number of neighbors.

V. MULTI-MODAL FUNCTIONS

The multi-modal function is a branch of optimization concerned with finding good solutions. It is defined as a function having multiple local optima. A local optimum is a solution which is better than all its neighboring solutions. These functions also have multiple global minima scattered throughout the search space. It is also defined as a statistical distribution of values with multiple peaks.

The GSO algorithm captures the multiple optima of the multi-modal optimization function [31]. In the context of load balancing on computer networks, the traffic is shifted towards either balanced or under loaded nodes. These problems are introduced for continuous data of equal (balanced nodes) or unequal (under loaded and over loaded nodes) peaks. The cases considered for multi-modal function during peak times of traffic are: unequal peaks, equal peaks, and peaks of concentric circles located at irregular intervals. It is much more helpful to optimize data in computer networks when the response time is increasing with increase in queue length. Using the GSO algorithm, the network traffic can be shifted towards the path to the fittest neighborhood with the lighter traffic [32]. The problem is to find the local optima having equal and unequal values. The multi-modal function contains maximum and minimum number of traffic during the passage of data [33-35].

Fig. 2. GSO Circle function: each glowworm is attracted to its neighboring glowworm.

The multi-modal functions used in GSO regions are: (i) Rastrigin's function, (ii) Circle function, (iii) Equal-peaks-A function, (iv) Equal-Peaks-B-function, and (v) Equal-Peaks-C-function [36]. The Circle function is the most appropriate in application to load balancing. The Circle function contains multiple concentric circles as the region of local maxima is depicted in Figure 2. The concentric circles share the same center point, therefore circular lines of local peaks present an infinite-peak case unlike other multi-modal functions such as Rastrigin's function, two dimension exponential function, and Gaussian distribution functions where the peak is located on a single point. The circle function is given as:

$$J_4(y_1, y_2) = (y_1^2 + y_2^2)^{0.25} ((\sin^2(50(y_1^2 + y_2^2)^{0.1})) + 1.0) \quad (8)$$

VI. EXPERIMENT

This section presents the determination of load burden on computer network and the shifting of load towards neighboring nodes having lesser burden. It studies the performance of GSO algorithm and compares it with the performance of other nature-inspired algorithms such as PSO and CK. In the designed setup, all devices are connected from any location in a network and transfer data packets over it. The details of all the devices, such as device identification number, device name, and device geographical location is saved on the internet data repository [37]. The test model is depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Network topology of load balancing using T-GSO segregated on three layers.

Users' requests are coming from a number of IoT devices. The requests are segregated onto virtual machines via a load balancer (T-GSO) and are finally saved in a central repository. The load is mitigating queue tasks to be fetched on priority basis with increased throughput, thereby minimizing response and latency times. Data pass through the GSO to find the Luciferin level and compute the fitness function given in (4). The glowworms find the fittest neighbor on the basis of probability, so they move data packets towards fittest neighbor, having highest value of fitness function. It selects the network packet and transfers it to the least congested nodes. The parameters of GSO, CK, and PSO set for the experiment are depicted in Tables I-III. These parameters can be further adjusted for tuning the performance of the system. Experiments were conducted for network configurations of 50, 100, and 200 nodes. At the initial stage, data are extracted from a PRTG network monitoring tool configured on computer network for visualizing network traffic. The data are uploaded into the data repository. Then, the data are subjected to GSO, PSO, and CK algorithms and the performance is noted.

TABLE I. GSO VARIABLES

	Parameter	Fixed value
ρ	Rho	0.4
γ	Ghama	0.6
s	Sensor	0.03
n_t	Neighborhood nodes	5.00
l_o	Luciferin	5.00

TABLE II. CK PARAMETERS

	Parameter	Fixed value
npar	Quantity of enhancement	100
varLo	Minimum value of band	-5.0
varHi	Maximum value of band	5.0
numCuckooS	Initial quantity	5.0
numNewCuckooS	New quantity	0.0
minNumberOfEggs	Least quantity of eggs	2.0
MaxNumberOfEggs	Extreme quantity of eggs	4
maxIter	Highest repetitions	100
knnClusterNum	Quantity of clusters	1
motionCoeff	Lambda variable, default=2	9

TABLE III. PSO PARAMETERS

Parameter	Fixed value
Problem dimensions	2
Number of Particles	5
Inertia weight	0.729
Cognitive weight	1.49445
Social weight	1.49445

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance results of GSO, PSO, and CK algorithms in terms of throughput and queue length are presented in this section. Figures 4-7 show the results of GSO. The result of the comparison of GSO with PSO and CK algorithms is depicted in Figure 8. The behavior of Fitness Function vs. the Number of Iterations is given in Figure 4. The less loaded node would have a high value of Luciferin level, therefore more data packets are delivered through this node. The load balancer routes data traffic towards neighboring nodes having higher Luciferin than its level. The Euclidean distance should be less than the radial sensor ranges of neighboring glowworm, e.g. from Table I, the radial sensor range is 0.22Mb/s therefore the highest probability of data packets shifted towards adjacent node (Node number 1). The number of iterations was computed for 358 time slots over 50, 100, and 200 nodes, and Luciferin level has stabilized at similar levels for all nodes (Figure 4) indicating load balanced over the nodes.

The comparison of traffic data packets and optimum load (GSO-X, GSO-Y) is depicted for 50, 100 and 200 nodes. The trend shows that the node capacity is maximized which would be segregating a large number of data packets on the virtual machine, therefore the load is mitigated on a neighboring node. The incoming and outgoing data packets are 20Mb/s and 13Mb/s. The load is optimized by T-GSO load balancer executing the iterations, thereby GSO-X and GSO-Y are 16Mb/s and 15Mb/s in node 1. The proposed T-GSO scheme shows improved network throughput during peak traffic for networks of 50, 100, and 200 nodes.

Fig. 4. Fitness Function vs. Iterations under (a) 50, (b)100, (c) 200 nodes

Fig. 5. Data traffic vs. optimum load under (a) 50, (b) 100, (c) 200 nodes.

Considering Traffic-In and Traffic-Out, Figure 5 shows the traffic at nodes indicated at the start of the GSO algorithm. GSO-X and GSO-Y give the resulting position on completion of iterations of GSO algorithm. It can be seen that the input traffic at nodes was reduced and the output traffic was increased in the completion of the GSO algorithm. Furthermore, the number of nodes increased, the resultant load GSO-X, GSO-Y appear more balanced.

Figure 6 shows queue length vs. iterations. The network performance depends upon important indicators of load balancing, such as the queued tasks that are to be executed on each node. If the queue processes are increased, the network throughput reduces, which may cause request timeout and time delay. Queue length is recorded on each node with respect to time. The queue length is reduced with the help of GSO algorithm for diverting traffic. The highest value of Luciferin level is corresponding with the minimum value of queue length on an adjacent node. The trend shows that the queue task is released when the number of nodes is increased, therefore network load was mitigated on adjacent nodes having maximum value of fitness function.

Fig. 6. Queue length vs. load for: (a) 50, (b) 100, (c) 200 nodes.

In GSO algorithm, each glowworm finds the optimal path where the glow intensity is maximum. The Luciferin level of that node is indirectly proportional to the traffic accumulated on the node. The highest Luciferin level on an adjacent node indicates the lowest number of data packets is delivered on every node. In Figure 7, at 10pm the Luciferin level is 3.1nm and Traffic-In and Traffic-Out are 1.94 and 0.2, which

indicates inverse relation between fitness value and data bandwidth. The trend of the plot in Figure 7 shows that when the number of nodes increases, the Luciferin level is maximized, therefore the load is mitigated on that node.

Fig. 7. Luciferin and data packets accumulated under: (a) 50, (b) 100, (c) 200 nodes.

Fig. 8. Comparison of Luciferin and data packets accumulated under: (a) 50, (b) 100, (c) 200 nodes.

The performance comparison of GSO with PSO and CK algorithms for network load balancing is given in Figure 8. The results demonstrate the achievement of reducing node traffic in peak network usage periods. The GSO gave 71.79%, 61.17%, and 57.17% improved performance on 50 nodes, 74.14%, 70.95%, and 62.38% on 100 nodes, and 84.15%, 78.14%, and 60.42% on 200 nodes respectively, showing its superiority.

GSO picks the fit neighborhood where the traffic is lighter and forwards traffic to under loaded and normal loaded nodes. The GSO algorithm worked as a distributed mechanism by decreasing response time and overhead in addition by increasing throughput to improve the performance.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The explosive growth of data on the internet from the increasing numbers of IoT and M2M devices has the impact of diminishing the network performance, efficiency, and data delivery. The results from this work show that nature-inspired meta-heuristic approaches can be applied to the network load balancing problem and model network traffic. GSO is a more recent algorithm than PSO and CK. From the study of performance comparison of these three nature-inspired algorithms on the basis of node queue length, throughput, and response turnaround time, GSO showed better performance over PSO and CK. The comparison of GSO with PSO showed improvement in traffic reduce rate by 13.87%, 11.75%, and 23.72% for 50, 100, and 200 nodes respectively. Likewise, in comparison with CK, GSO improved the traffic reduce rate by 10.61%, 3.19%, and 6.00% respectively. Furthermore, it appears that performance improvement is scaling with increase in nodes. The GSO algorithm therefore seems more suited to mitigating the load balancing problem. For future work the following are proposed:

- Improvement of the GSO algorithm through study of different multi-modal functions depending on the basis of network topology.
- The multi-modal function parameters would be studied to find setting for optimal performance in different traffic scenarios.
- A hybrid model of GSO with another optimization algorithm such as the Genetic Algorithm.

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Functionally Graded Material Production and Characterization using the Vertical Separator Molding Technique and the Powder Metallurgy Method

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Abstract-Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) are advanced customized engineering materials that gradually and continuously change their composition. The current study investigated the production feasibility and some post-production mechanical/physical properties of B₄C particle-reinforced (avg. 40µm) AA7075 matrix (avg. 60µm) FGM composites with the vertical separator molding technique using the high-temperature isostatic pressing powder metallurgy method. FGMs produced consist of three (0 – 30 – 60 wt. % B₄C) and four (0 – 20 – 40 – 60 wt. % B₄C) layers. The powders were mixed in a power blender mixer for 2h and were placed in the mold sections with a vertical separator. The lid was closed, and a pre-pressure of 10Mpa was applied. The FGM green sheet was transferred from the vertical separator mold to the hot work tool steel with a press. In this mold, FGMs were sintered at 560°C for 30 min under a pressure of 325MPa. Microstructural examinations did not reveal any separation or crack formation in the layer transition regions of the FGMs. In addition, a relatively homogeneous B₄C reinforcing distribution was observed in the layers with a low reinforcement ratio (wt. 20% and 30%) compared to the other layers. The highest hardness was 170 HBN in one layer of the four-layer FGM containing 40% by weight B₄C reinforcement. The highest transverse rupture strength was measured in the test performed from the region with the most reinforcement of the four-layer FGM at 482MPa.

Keywords-functionally graded material; powder metallurgy; hot pressing; transverse rupture strength

I. INTRODUCTION

FGMs are widely used in various fields such as aerospace, automotive, electronics, defense industry, gas turbine engines,

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and engineering applications. They have emerged as a relatively new material class [1, 2]. The FGMs are materials that change their composition and structure and seriously alter their material properties gradually along with their height [3, 4]. Functionally Graded Metal Matrix Composites (FGMMCs) with metal and ceramic content have great potential and importance for the fabrication and design of components and structures. FGMMCs have superior features to bring advanced engineering components to a better level along with material design. Specific properties such as high-temperature surface wear resistance, thermal mismatch correction, reduction of interfacial stresses, minimization of thermal stresses, increased metal-ceramic interfacial adhesion, delayed crack formation, and increased fracture toughness can be obtained by utilizing FGMMCs [1].

Aluminum Matrix Composite (AMC) is considered one of the most promising materials due to its lightweight and high specific strength values [5-7]. Among the existing AMCs, AA7075 is a matrix material with high strength, sufficient toughness, and corrosion resistance [8]. The vast-majority of reinforcing materials of AMCs are non-metallic ceramic materials. Al₂O₃, SiC, and B₄C are the most commonly used ceramic reinforcements in AMCs [9]. B₄C reinforcement material stands out among ceramics due to its good chemical inertness, high hardness, high elastic modulus, and high melting properties [10].

One of the most important areas in FGM research is the production method [1]. Many different fabrication methods have been developed to fabricate FGMs, such as gas-based

methods, liquid-phase methods, solid-phase methods, and biopolymeric-based functionally graded structures. Powder metallurgy, one of the solid phase methods, is a good method for obtaining a homogeneous and graded structure in FGM production [11, 12]. The powder metallurgy method offers advantages such as low processing temperature, ease of obtaining the final product, continuity in product quality, and low cost with its suitability for mass production compared to melting methods [13, 14]. In FGM production by powder metallurgy method, powders are gradually laid into the mold according to the reinforcement ratio [15]. This process is mostly carried out based on one's dexterity. It is difficult to obtain a smooth transition surface between layers in such manual procedures. In FGM production with another powder metallurgy method, the powder is laid in the mold for each stage and subjected to pre-pressing [16, 17]. This adversely affects the formation of the desired bond structure on the layer transition surfaces during the sintering phase. Vertical separator molding technique has been developed in order to obtain a smoother transition zone, to create the desired bond structure in the layer transition zones, and to provide the layer transition zones in the desired two-dimensional geometric structures.

In this study, a two-stage mold consisting of a vertical separator, a filling chamber, and a hot-pressing mold was designed and manufactured for FGM production under the high temperature isostatic pressing technique of the powder metallurgy method. The availability of planeness of transition surfaces of the B_4C reinforced AA7075 matrix FGMs with 3 (0-30-60% wt.) and 4 (0-20-40-60% wt.) layers of the same thickness as the manufactured mold was examined, along with the post-production metallurgical and mechanical properties.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out for FGM production. The chemical composition of AA7075 matrix (avg. $60\mu m$) is presented in Table I. Reinforcement material B_4C (avg. $40\mu m$) powder was used.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF AA7075

Element	Zn	Mg	Cr	Cu	Fe	Si	Mn	Ti	Al
%Avg.	5.5	2.5	2.5	1.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	Bal.

The Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of matrix and reinforcement are shown in Figure 1. SEM investigations showed that AA7075 powder was relatively spherical in shape and variable in grain size. It has been observed that the reinforcement B_4C powder was composed of particles with complex geometry and sharp edges, whose aspect ratio is relatively close to each other.

In determining the percent weight ratio of the reinforcement of the FGM layers, one side is designed in a brittle structure with a high reinforcement ratio (high hardness, high wear resistance, high compressive strength), and the other side is designed in a tensile structure without reinforcement (high toughness, high % elongation). Information about the number of layers and reinforcement content of the produced FGMs are presented in Table II.

Fig. 1. SEM images of the powders used in FGM production: (a) AA7075, (b) B_4C .

TABLE II. LAYER AND REINFORCEMENT RATIOS OF THE PRODUCED FGMs

Number of layers	3	4
Layer reinforcement rates (% wt.)	0 – 30 – 60	0 – 20 – 40 – 60

Under the ratios in Table II, matrix and reinforcement powders were weighed on a precision balance at suitable values for the mixing ratio of each layer. In order to obtain a homogeneous powder mixture, it was mixed in a power mixer for 2 hours. The mixed powders were filled into mold chambers (3 layers $60 \times 60 \times 8$ mm, 4 layers $60 \times 60 \times 6$ mm), whose layer areas were separated in equal volume by vertical steel separators. After the powder filling process, the steel separators were removed, the upper surface of the mold was closed, and a pre-compression force of 10MPa was applied under uniaxial hydraulic press. The pre-compression force was applied from the surface of the layer with the highest reinforcement ratio (60% wt. B_4C). Pre-compressed green sheet FGM was transferred into a separate mold made of hot work tool steel using a hydraulic press to carry out high-temperature isostatic pressing and sintering processes. Green sheet FGM samples were heated up to $560^\circ C$ in a hot work tool steel mold and waited for 30min. Then, sintering was carried out at this temperature for 30min under a pressure of 325MPa and the samples were left to cool in the mold at room temperature. At

least two FGM samples were produced from each layer number. The samples were $60 \times 60 \times 12.7 \pm 0.13$ mm in size. The produced FGM samples and the cross-sectional macro views of the 3 and 4 layered samples are shown in Figure 2. The microstructure characterization of the produced FGM samples was investigated using the FEI QUANTA FEG 250 SEM located in Kastamonu University Central Research Laboratories and Research Center. The hardness values of the layers of the FGMs were determined by the Brinell hardness measurement method using the QNESS Q250M type hardness measuring device at Karabuk University's Iron and Steel Institute.

Fig. 2. FGM sample images: (a) After sintering, (b) 3-layer cross-sectional view, (c) 4-layer cross-sectional view.

FGM hardness measurements were carried out using 2.5mm diameter steel balls under a 62.5kg load. At least 5 measurements were made for each layer of the FGM, and the average determined the hardness value for the general layer. The produced FGMs were cut according to the ASTM B528-05 standard ($31.9 \times 12.7 \times 12.7 \pm 0.13$ mm) and turned into transverse rupture strength test specimens. Transverse rupture strength tests were performed on the cut samples in a 50kN capacity INSTRON 3369 tension/compression device. Transverse rupture strength tests were performed at a deformation rate of 2mm/min. Transverse rupture strength load was applied separately to the layer surface of the FGM with the highest reinforcement and to the layer surface without reinforcement. The transverse rupture strength test results were determined by the average of the measurements after at least 4 measurements in each direction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Microstructure Results

SEM images of each layer and the interlayer transition zones were taken to determine the microstructure properties of the produced FGMs. SEM images are given in Figure 3 for the 3-layer FGM and Figure 4 for the 4-layer FGM.

Fig. 3. SEM microstructure images of 3-layer FGMs: (a) 0% to 30% wt. B_4C transition surface image, (b) 30% to 60% wt. B_4C transition surface image.

It was determined that B_4C reinforcement in FGMs settled at grain boundaries and showed a relatively homogeneous distribution in low-rate layers. It was observed that B_4C reinforcement accumulated at the grain boundary with increasing reinforcement ratios. It is not easy to obtain a homogeneous distribution while producing composite materials with the powder metallurgy technique because the reinforcement can settle at the grain boundaries.

In addition, it has been reported that the porosity increases due to the increasing reinforcement ratio [1, 18]. It was determined that agglomeration and micropores increased as the amount of reinforcement increased in the layers of the produced FGMs. When the transition zones between the layers of the produced FGMs were examined, no delamination was observed. It has been observed that the transition of FGM between layers is continuous and has structural integrity.

B. Hardness Results

It has been reported that the hardness value increases with the increase of the ratio in the reinforcement structure in composite materials up to certain values [19-22]. The hardness measurements performed on the layers of the produced FGM samples showed that the hardness value increased up to 40% wt. B_4C , and after this value, it decreased depending on the decreasing matrix amount and increasing porosity. Similarly, in [15], the measured hardness value was 40% wt. Graphs of change in the hardness (Brinell; HBN) values of each layer depending on the number of layers of FGMs are presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. SEM microstructure images of 4-layer FGMs: (a) 0% to 20% wt. B_4C transition surface image, (b) 20% to 40% wt. B_4C transition surface image, (c) 40% to 60% wt. B_4C transition surface image.

Fig. 5. Layer hardness of FGMs: (a) 3-layer, (b) 4-layer.

It can be seen in Figure 5 that the hardness increases to a certain extent (30% wt. B_4C in 3 layers and 40% wt. B_4C in 4 layers) depending on the increase of layer reinforcement. Suppose a composite is produced with success within the desired limits (homogeneous distribution property, porosity amount, etc.) of composite materials. In that case, it is expected

that the mechanical properties and hardness values will increase according to the mixture theory as the reinforcement ratio increases up to a certain value. Equation (1) presents the mathematical expression used to theoretically calculate the hardness of the composites according to the mixture theory.

$$H_k = H_m f_m + H_t f_t \quad (1)$$

where H_k is the hardness of the composite, H_m is the hardness of the matrix, f_m is the weight ratio of the matrix, H_t is the reinforcement hardness, and f_t is the reinforcement by weight ratio.

It was determined that the layer with the highest hardness value of the produced FGMs was the third layer of the 4-layer FGM reinforced with 40% wt. B_4C . The hardness of this layer was measured as 170HBN. The lowest hardness value was 94HBN in the layer with the highest reinforcement ratio (60% wt.) of the 3-layer composite. When the SEM images of the 3- and 4-layer FGMs in Figure 3 and Figure 4 are examined, it was seen that the 60% wt. B_4C reinforced layer had the highest porosity. Therefore, Brinell's hardness decreased in layers containing 60% wt. B_4C reinforcement.

C. Transverse Rupture Strength Tests Result

In order to determine the breaking strength of FGMs, transverse rupture strength test was performed on reinforced and non-reinforced layer surfaces under test conditions prepared under the ASTM B528-05 standard. The flexure stress-strain graphs obtained as a result of the experiments are presented in Figure 6. It can be seen in Figure 6 that the transverse rupture strength of FGMs differs according to the region where the load is applied. The measured transverse rupture strength of the FGM was higher (~153% in the 3-layer, ~65% in the 4-layer composite) with the application of the fracture load from the dense region of the reinforcement, because composites are more resistant to compressive stresses [23]. The highest obtained transverse rupture strength was 482MPa, from a 4-layer FGM applied to the load region with the highest number of reinforcement. In Figure 6(b), 4-layer FGM transverse ruptured from the region with less reinforcement showed brittle fracture than the 3-layer FGM due to the decreased amount of matrix due to the layer increase. The increase in strength in composite materials according to the law of mixtures [24, 25].

$$\sigma_K = \sigma_m f_m + \sigma_t f_t \quad (2)$$

where σ_K refers to the mechanical strength of the composite, σ_m refers to the mechanical strength of the matrix, f_m refers to the weight ratio of the matrix, σ_t refers to the mechanical strength of the reinforcement, and f_t refers to the weight ratio of the reinforcement. This equation predicts the strength values when the composite is produced within the desired limits without exceeding the ideal production conditions. As the ratio of the side with a higher strength value compared to others increases, the strength of the composite also increases.

It was observed that the porosity increased as the amount of reinforcement increased, in accordance with [1, 15]. The highest Brinell hardness in FGM was obtained in the 40% wt.

B_4C layer. As the reinforcement ratio increased, the hardness of the composite decreased. Similar results were found in [1]. The best results in the transverse rupture strength test were obtained on the reinforced layer surface. Similar results were obtained in [15].

Fig. 6. FGM transverse rupture strength graphics: (a) 3-layer, (b) 4-layer.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study produced 3 (0-30-60% wt.) and 4 (0-20-40-60 wt.%) layers of B_4C reinforced AA7075 matrix FGM with the vertical separator moulding technique. The following results were obtained in this study, in which the microstructure characterization, hardness and transverse rupture strength of the produced FGMs were examined.

- With the vertical separator moulding technique, FGMs with smooth surface transition were successfully produced without any delamination in the transition areas.
- It was determined that the distribution of B_4C reinforcement in the layers of FGMs with a low reinforcement ratio (wt. 20% and 30%) was relatively homogeneous compared to the other layers.
- No delamination was observed between the layers of FGM.

- The highest porosity was observed in the layer containing 60 wt.% B₄C. The lowest measured Brinell hardness was 92HBN in the 3-layer FGM containing 60% wt. B₄C reinforcement.
- The highest measured Brinell hardness was 170HBN in the 4-layer FGM containing 40% wt. B₄C reinforcement.
- In terms of transverse rupture strength, the tests applied to the reinforcement layer surface gave better results than the tests applied to the non-reinforcement layer surface (~153% in three layers, ~65% in four layers).
- The greatest measured transverse rupture strength was 482MPa due to the application of the load from the region of the 4-layer FGM with the highest reinforcement.

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Monitoring and Analysis of Agricultural Field Parameters in Order to Increase Crop Yield through a Colored Object Tracking Robot, Image Processing, and IOT

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Abstract-Adequately watering plants is a challenging task. Over- and under-watering may harm plants and seeds, as excess or restraint watering reduces crop production and yield. This study presents a method to remotely monitor and efficiently water agricultural fields to increase crop production by utilizing advanced technologies such as internet things, robotics, image processing, and neural networks. Accurate smoothing and image segmentation techniques were employed to study the plants' conditions. Color median, Gaussian, and hybrid median filters were employed to preprocess the data before segmentation and classification. The hybrid median filter and multilevel luminance grading system were employed to increase the quality of the image. The k-means clustering approach was used for image segmentation. The signal-to-noise ratios of the original and recreated images were compared and analyzed.

Keywords-image clustering; hybrid median image smoothing; IoT; robotics; agricultural applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Throughout most of history, farmers used to water plants manually through canals. It is not easy to analyze the amount of manual required drenching, and water the plants to their exact need. Both over- and inadequate watering may lead to the degradation of crop production and reduce crop yield. The current work is a combination of robotics, Internet of Things (IoT), and image processing to reduce the manual effort of the farmers and provide an optimal solution to agricultural field watering. This work was designed for an Arduino board, fitted with different types of sensing and processing units. The motor driver L293D was interfaced with the Arduino board to control a water pump. The robot's movements were controlled using the OpenCV software. The built-in camera captures images and processes them using Gaussian, median, and hybrid median filters to improve their quality. K-means clustering segmentation was used for image segmentation. The objective was to give farmers the ability to analyze remotely the soil conditions and drench the appropriate amount of water

depending on soil and plant conditions. This work is more accurate than similar studies. It utilizes three filter stages for image smoothing and k-clustering for image segmentation.

II. RELATED WORK

A prototype fuzzy rule-based irrigation controller that helps farmers save water by providing an ideal watering environment was demonstrated in [1, 2]. Two control units were designed, a wireless sensor and a wireless information processing unit. The wireless sensor unit determined the climate and clay constraints. During summer the water evaporation in soil increases [3, 4]. Based on weather and soil conditions, the sensor detects the water level and sends a signal to the controller. The wireless information processing unit analyzed the information received from the sensor regarding the water level conditions [5, 6]. Based on the obtained parameters, it enables the actuator devices to supply the plants with the required amount of water. The results showed that it reduced the water loss by 27% and increased the yield by 40%. Due to the scarcity of water, different kinds of diseases can be noticed in various plants. In [7, 8], the leaf disease of the guava plant was analyzed using the DCNN framework. In [9, 10] the soil and weather-related features were determined by analyzing various types of soil conditions. Various sensors were used to examine the quality and conditions of various soil types. This study also defined soil suitability for various crops and analyzed the crop production, irrigation, and soil type and condition. Accurate information for the farmers regarding the soil and water conditions was presented in [11, 12]. Various water monitoring and conservation techniques were presented in [13-17].

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system model consists of the functional blocks shown in Figure 1. Initially, real-time videos are acquired through the device's built-in camera. Image smoothing is carried out using median, Gaussian, and hybrid median filters. The region of

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interest is captured and image segmentation is performed. After the segmentation, the edges are detected and the contours are identified. Soil moisture, temperature, and humidity are monitored, and finally, plants are appropriately watered by the robot vehicle control.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed work.

A. Image Smoothing

Image filtering and smoothing techniques improve an image's quality by removing noise. Gaussian filter reduces the salt and pepper noise. Noise can be appropriately minimized by keeping the image's edges through median filtering [18]. The brightness of the pixel can be enhanced through median filtering. Figure 2 shows a leaf image before and after applying the median filter. In hybrid-filter, images can be extended symmetrically in horizontal and vertical directions. Additional columns can be added to the left and the right and additional rows can be added at the bottom and the top. Due to this adaptability in image size, this filter is more suitable for fast-moving image smoothing. The block diagram shown in Figure 1 of [19] depicts the hybrid median filter used to recover the image. Impulse noise is added to the input image. Then, the hybrid median filter is applied to the noisy image and effectively eliminates the impulse noise.

Fig. 2. Images before and after applying the median filter.

In the hybrid median filter, the original pixel values are considered to frame + and x-shaped sub-neighborhoods. The first ranking stage is created by considering the + and x sub-neighborhoods. The second stage is created by taking the pixels from the first stage and the original pixel. The new pixel value is determined using the median values from the sub-neighborhoods and the original pixel. This filter removes the

impulse noise effectively and preserves the edges. The hybrid-median filter performs three-stage operations on pixels to preserve the edges better than the median filter [19].

The calculated median values were:

- Median of horizontal and vertical pixels (MHVP)
- Median of diagonal pixels (MDP)
- Centre pixel (CP)

For an $N \times N$ matrix, considering $N=5$, the output pixel is the median of {MHVP, MDP, CP}.

Noise is removed using a Gaussian filter. Gaussian smoothing has a similar effect to the median filter in smoothing a picture. The standard deviation determines the degree of smoothing as shown in (1) and (2). Low-pass filtering suppresses high-frequency noise while maintaining the low-frequency elements of an image. The Gaussian filter output is shown in Figure 3.

$$G(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-(x^2+y^2)/(2\sigma^2)} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Image before and after applying the Gaussian filter.

B. Creating Binary Mask Image

The pixels in the Region of Interest (ROI) are set to logic 1 and the remaining pixels of the image are set to logic 0.

C. Image Thresholding and K-means Clustering Segmentation

Segmentation of a captured image is the process of breaking it down into its constituent parts using edge detection, threshold processing, areas-based segmentation, and other techniques. A simple picture segmentation approach is image thresholding. This approach divides foreground from background pixels when converting a greyscale or color image to a binary. The threshold values are compared with the pixel values. Logic 0 is set for the pixels which exceed the cut-off value. If the pixel value falls below the cut-off, then it is set as the logic high value. The k-means unsupervised clustering algorithm was used to classify the dataset.

The following steps define the k-Means set of rules. Figure 4 shows the flowchart representation of the k-means clustering algorithm.

Fig. 4. Flow chart showing the k-means algorithm

D. Color Detection, Extraction, and Grid Formation

Color is extremely important in image processing. Each image made up of an $M \times N$ pixel array is split into M rows and N columns. The red, green, and blue values of each pixel are unique. The RGB colors are identified using thresholds. The intended color of the image is identified using the color recognition process. Figure 5 shows grid formation and robot vehicle control. The user controls the motion of the robot by creating a 3×3 grid matrix. The robot's movement in different directions such as right, left, top, and bottom is controlled by sending commands.

Fig. 5. Color detection, extraction, grid formation, and robot vehicle control.

E. Edge Detection and Contour Finding

Edge detection and contour finding were conducted using OpenCV and Python. As shown in Figure 6, many dots with the same color are joined to form a curve. The different shapes formed are triangle, rectangle, and square by drawing curves, which joins the subsequent points. The following steps are used to identify the shape:

- Create a grayscale version of the image.
- Make a binary representation of the image.
- Determine the contour.

Fig. 6. Edge detection and contour finding.

F. Monitoring Parameters

Parameters such as soil, weather, temperature, humidity, and moisture level of the soil are sensed by different sensors. The sensors capture the data and send them to the data processing units. The image smoothing filter is applied to the captured images and then they are segmented and analyzed properly.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSIS

The camera records a photograph which is a point of reference for the specified user interface. The robot moves forward, backward, left, and right according to the obtained instructions. The movements of the robot are recorded and stored in memory by connecting a WiFi module to the Arduino board. The required object is tracked from the captured image. If the object is red, the robot is moved accordingly in the grid. The block diagram shown in Figure 7 explains the procedure to find the number of clusters.

Fig. 7. The process of finding the clusters.

The procedure for the experimental analysis is shown in Figure 9. Figure 8 depicts the number of clusters versus the WCSS list. As shown in the bar graph below, as the number of clusters increases, the sum of squares decreases.

Fig. 8. Number of clusters vs WCSS_list.

The implementation of the prototype model is shown in Figure 10. In this prototype model, the image is captured using the webcam of a laptop. The region of interest is selected and red color is identified. The grid is formed to control the movements of the robot. The chosen parameters are monitored and analyzed.

Fig. 9. Flow chart of the experimental procedure.

Fig. 10. Prototype implementation.

V. RESULT DISCUSSION AND COMPARISON

The obtained results were analyzed. The captured image signal-to-noise ratio was 30.12dB and the noisy image's SNR was 12.3dB. After passing the noisy image through the median filter, the obtained SNR was 27.7dB. The output of the median filter was applied to the hybrid median smoothing filter. The SNR of the hybrid-median filter was 29.999dB. The SNR of the original and the final processed image were approximately the same. These results were compared with [18]. Table I shows the comparison of SNR of the original with the filtered images. The SNR of the proposed method was 99.59%, whereas the SNR of the previous work was 98.78%. This method improved the SNR value compared to the previous work. The SNR values are graphically represented in Figure 11.

TABLE I. SNR COMPARISON OF ORIGINAL WITH FILTERED IMAGE

Parameters	SNR in dB	
	[18]	Current paper
Captured /original image	20.1408	30.12
Noisy image	13.4343	12.3
Median smoothing Filter	19.1523	27.7
Hybrid Median Filter (HMF) smoothing	19.8964	29.999
Percentage increase	98.78 %	99.59%

Fig. 11. Signal to noise ratio of the proposed method.

VI. CONCLUSION

An irrigation system using IoT and robotics completes the prototype design. In this work, robotics, IoT, and image processing are utilized. The designed robot is user-friendly and data from different units can be accessed with less delay in real-time. In the image smoothing process, the picture is passed through a median filter, a Gaussian filter, and a hybrid-median filter to remove noise and improve its quality. The raw captured image was filtered by a median filter since it smoothens the image without blurring it. A hybrid-median filter removes effectively the impulse noise, keeps corner features, and does not delete outer boundary lines. The SNR of the captured image was compared with the SNR of the noisy image, median smoothing, and hybrid-median smoothing. The SNR of the captured, noisy, median, and hybrid-median smoothing images was 30.12, 12.3, 27.7, and 29.999 respectively. The SNR of the proposed method was 99.59%, while the SNR of [18] was 98.78%. These results indicate that the proposed method is a feasible alternative for practical applications including picture restoration, medical image de-

speckling, and image enhancement. The k-means clustering algorithm was employed since it gives a better result in terms of accuracy as compared to traditional methods. The proposed method offers a viable solution to problems associated with agricultural applications.

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Voltage Regulation in a Radial Microgrid with High RES Penetration

Approach-Optimum DVR Control

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Abstract-Increasing installation of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) in microgrids and distribution system feeders benefits the power system in many ways, such as increasing power availability and reliability, but they also cause various power quality issues, such as overvoltage and undervoltage, due to their intermittent nature. The sensitive loads, such as Constant Power Load (CPL), are affected by these voltage fluctuations. The approach proposed in this paper is to install a Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR) adjacent to the RES to suppress the voltage issue caused by it while leaving the sensitive load operation unharmed. The proposed concept is duly endorsed with analysis and simulations in MATLAB/Simulink environment.

Keywords-DVR; intermittent RES; CPL; voltage regulation; microgrid

I. INTRODUCTION

Penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs), such as solar, wind, hydro energy, etc. has been increased in the distribution systems due to increased demand, availability, and the environmental concerns caused by the conventional sources [1]. When the penetration is increased, a part of the distribution feeder needs to be controlled and monitored separately by the distributed system operator. This part of the feeder may be regarded as a microgrid [2-3]. The increased penetration of RESs and their independent control gives to the system many advantages, such as increased available power, lesser generation from conventional power sources, increased power reliability, etc.. However, the increased penetration of RESs in the feeder may give rise to some power quality issues, in which variation in voltage level due to the intermittent nature of the RES is of major concern, especially today, when many of the loads connected in the distribution system require constant power for their better operation and behave like Constant Power Loads (CPLs) [4-7]. The power consumed by a CPL remains constant regardless of the voltage at the point of common coupling. If the voltage drops, the current level rises and vice versa. When tightly regulated, power electronic converters such as dc/dc converters feeding a load such as a battery, or dc/ac inverters driven loads are presumed to be CPLs. Furthermore, switching power supplies, which are found

in the majority of mobile systems and inverter-based motor drive systems, act in the same way as CPLs [3, 5-6].

The power requirement of these CPL loads is unaffected by voltage variations at the terminal. When the voltage at the CPL terminals is increased, the current demanded by these loads decreases, resulting in negative impedance characteristics as observed by the feeder. This type of CPL characteristic could exacerbate the voltage rise issue in the feeder. As the current requested by the CPL drops, the overall drop in the feeder lowers as well, resulting in a higher voltage at the CPL's terminal and greater current reversal towards the main grid source. These factors may reduce the voltage stability of the microgrid. If the number of such CPLs connected in the microgrid increases, a cascading effect could occur, causing instability in the micro-grid/distribution feeder [8]. To minimize such issues, the voltage at the CPL terminals should be kept within tight restrictions, and be such that the RES intermittency has the least impact on CPLs. There are numerous devices reported in the literature that can be used to regulate voltage in the distribution system, including Dynamic Voltage Restorers (DVRs), Static Synchronous Compensators (STATCOMs), etc. [9-12]. A DVR is a custom power device that is connected in series with the line and injects/absorbs a series voltage. In this paper, a radial microgrid voltage regulation approach is presented, in which the DVR is situated near the RES, minimizing the issue produced on the CPL connected in the radial microgrid by the intermittent nature of the RES. The voltage at the DVR's terminals is regulated by injecting/absorbing a voltage in series with the feeder. The proposed method is backed up by analysis and is tested in Matlab/Simulink environment.

II. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

Figure 1 depicts the system diagram for the grid-connected radial microgrid with CPL and intermittent RES. The RES unit comprised of an RES source such as a rooftop PV or a wind turbine and is connected to the micro-grid/distribution system via a Voltage Source Converter (VSC) that is connected to the feeder as a current source. The RES is placed very close to the

CPL in order to witness and study the worst effects of RES intermittency. The DVR is installed adjacent to the RES, so that it can absorb extra power and provide a small percentage of power, if needed, to regulate the voltage. Batteries can be used to extend the DVR's regulatory and compensation limits [13]. The grid is represented by the source V_S , while the feeder impedance is represented by the Z_S . The feeder in consideration is a distribution type feeder with an R/X ratio of around 8 [14].

Fig. 1. Single line diagram of the considered system.

III. ANALYSIS OF THE CONSIDERED SYSTEM

The analysis of the considered microgrid system is conducted in two stages: At first, the impact of the RES on the CPL is investigated, and in the second stage, the way the existence of DVR may ameliorate the situation is investigated. The RES is considered to be situated very close to the CPL, and thus the feeder impedance between them can be overlooked.

A. Impact of RES on CPL

The equivalent circuit diagram for the considered system with only RES and CPL is shown in Figure 2(a). The Voltage at the terminals of CPL can be calculated with the help of superposition theorem and is given by:

$$V_{CPL} = \frac{Z_{CPL}(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S)}{Z_S + Z_{CPL}} \quad (1)$$

The impedance of the constant power load is dynamic in nature and can be written as:

$$Z_{CPL} = \frac{V_{CPL}^2}{P_{CPL}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) rewritten and simplified with value of Z_{CPL} obtained from (2) gives:

$$V_{CPL}^2 - V_{CPL}(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S) + Z_S P_{CPL} = 0 \quad (3)$$

If the RES current is known, then for a particular CPL load the voltage at the terminals of CPL can be estimated by solving (3):

$$V_{CPL} = \frac{(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S) \pm \sqrt{(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S)^2 - 4Z_S P_{CPL}}}{2} \quad (4)$$

B. With DVR Compensation Unit

In this stage the DVR is connected to the system as shown in Figure 2(b). The voltage at the terminal of RES can be regulated close to the rated value through DVR. The voltage at the terminal of CPL obtained from (3) is taken into consideration for the estimation of the voltage to be supplied/absorbed by the DVR. The new voltage at the terminal of CPL after the insertion of DVR can also be

estimated with the help of superposition theorem and is given by:

$$V_{CPL(New)} = \frac{Z_{CPL}(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S + V_{DVR})}{Z_S + Z_{CPL}} \quad (5)$$

After putting the value of Z_{CPL} , (5) can be rewritten as:

$$P_{CPL}Z_S + V_{PCC}^2 = V_{PCC}(V_S + I_{RES}Z_S + V_{DVR}) \quad (6)$$

If the voltage injected by the DVR is known, then the voltage at the terminals of the CPL can be calculated by solving the above quadratic equation. This equation can also be used in another way, for the estimation of voltage to injected/absorbed by the DVR as mentioned in (7).

$$V_{DVR} = \frac{P_{CPL}Z_S + V_{CPL}^2}{V_{CPL}} - V_S + I_{RES}Z_S \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit diagram of the considered system (a) without any regulation from the DVR, (b) with DVR.

IV. CONTROL OF DVR

The control strategy for generating gating pulses of the voltage source inverter of the DVR is depicted in Figure 3. The synchronous reference frame theory is being used to control the DVR. The DVR injects or absorbs voltage in series to regulate the voltage at its terminal. It accomplishes this by sensing the voltage at the terminal, comparing it to the reference value of the voltage, and passing it to the Proportional Integral (PI) controller, which generates a voltage reference value for the quadrature axis (q-axis) component of the DVR. Initially, the DVR tries to keep the voltage underneath the range by using only the reactive component, resulting in only the q-axis component (V_q). However, if V_q reaches its maximum value, the q-axis component is reduced and the d-axis component is increased, resulting in a signal that may be used to estimate the voltage required to regulate the voltage with both d-axis (V_d) and q-axis (V_q) component at the DVR's terminal. To estimate the reference signal for the DVR's VSI, the reference d-axis and q-axis components are transformed into reference abc components via reverse parks transformation. To generate the gating pulse for the VSI switches, the reference signal is now routed through the pulse width modulator. The VSC then uses the obtained gate pulses to operate the switches.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

To validate the proposed concept, the considered system is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink. The simulation diagram of the system is shown in Figure 4. The system parameters used in the simulations are mentioned in Table I. To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed design, the system is tested under two conditions: (i) RES intermittency and (ii) load perturbation. For the sake of evaluation convenience, the initial transients that emerge in the simulation are ignored.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETER USED

Parameter	Parameter Values
Source/Grid Voltage	415V line to line
Feeder impedance	0.642+j0.083Ω/km [14], feeder length =0.5km
RES rating	10kW
CPL rating	3.75kW
Constant impedance load	2.5kVA to 7.5kVA, 0.8 pf lagging load
DVR rating	2kVA, maximum injection upto 100V

Figure 5 depicts the influence of RES intermittency on the voltage level in the microgrid and the ability of DVR to regulate the voltage during these intermittencies. RES injects a current of $I_{RESpeak} = 10A$ from $t = 0$ to 0.5s. Since the DVR is not injecting/absorbing voltage from $t = 0$ to 0.25s, the voltage observed (V_{CPL}) is lower than the rated value. The DVR is switched into the circuit at 0.25s, and the voltage at the DVR terminal is regulated to the rated value by injecting voltage ($V_{DVR} = 71V$) into the microgrid. Since RES penetration is low during this period, the DVR can regulate the voltage with only reactive power. The DVR is switched off at 0.5s, and the RES increased to more than double the initial value ($I_{RESpeak} = 20A$) causing the voltage at the terminal of the CPL (V_{CPL}) to rise

over the rated value, as shown in Figure 5 V_{CPL} ($t = 0.5s$ to 0.75s). The DVR is turned on again at 0.75s, and this time it absorbs the extra voltage ($V_{DVR} = 100V$) to regulate the voltage at the CPL's terminal to the rated value. Since the DVR is unable to regulate the voltage using solely reactive power, therefore, both real (d-axis component V_d) and reactive (q-axis component V_q) components are used. Also, the DVR is absorbing the excess power in this case, so it can store it in the battery and use it whenever it is needed. The waveforms in Figure 6 are used to investigate the effect of a load connected at the feeder's end being perturbed. With $I_{RES} = 10A$, the penetration of RES is kept constant throughout the simulation. From $t = 0$ to 0.5s, the load connected at the end of the feeder is approximately 6.25kVA (3.75kW CPL load and 2.5kVA linear constant impedance load). The RES generates power that is close to the demand from local loads, therefore there isn't much voltage drop across the CPL load. The DVR can control the marginal variation from the rated value with the q-axis component only ($V_{DVR} = 15V$) from 0.25 to 0.5s. This is further supported by the zoomed waveform from 0.15s to 0.4s. From 0.5 to 1s, the load connected rises significantly with the CPL load remaining the same at 3.75kW, while the constant impedance load rose to 7.5kVA. As the local demand increased beyond the capacity of RES generation, the variation from the rated voltage rose significantly, requiring the DVR to regulate the voltage using a combination of real and reactive power with $V_{DVR} = 100V$, as shown in Figure 6 from 0.75 to 1s. This is backed even more by the zoomed waveform. As the DVR supplies real power into the system, it is depleting its real power stock that it had built up during the excess RES generation. As a result, the voltage at the CPL terminal is regulated.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the control scheme of the DVR.

Fig. 4. MATLAB/Simulink simulation diagram of the system under consideration.

Fig. 5. Voltage and current waveform showing the efficacy of DVR during intermittency of the RES.

Fig. 6. Voltage and current waveform for showing the efficacy of DVR during load perturbations.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the presence of intermittent RES, voltage regulation in a radial microgrid feeding a sensitive CPL load has been investigated and demonstrated. Analysis was carried out to determine the value of the voltage at the CPL terminal in the absence of the DVR, as well as the value of voltage to be injected by the DVR. The Matlab/Simulink environment was utilized to simulate and control the proposed system. The simulation results for the intermittency of the RES source and the perturbation of load on the feeder were used to establish the performance of the DVR for voltage regulation. The demonstrated simulation results ensure that the voltage at the CPL terminal is relatively unaffected and settles in a short time. This allows the microgrid to benefit from greater RES penetration without compromising the operation of sensitive CPL loads.

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The New Dataset MITWPU-1K for Object Recognition and Image Captioning Tasks

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Abstract—In the domain of image captioning, many pre-trained datasets are available. Using these datasets, models can be trained to automatically generate image descriptions regarding the contents of an image. Researchers usually do not spend much time in creating and training the new dataset before using it for a specific application, instead, they simply use existing pre-trained datasets. MS COCO, Flickr, and Pascal VOC, are well-known datasets that are widely used in the task of generating image captions. In most available image captioning datasets, image textual information, which can play a vital role in generating more precise image descriptions, is missing. This paper presents the process of creating a new dataset that consists of images along with text and captions. Images of the nearby vicinity of the campus of MIT World Peace University-MITWPU, India, were taken for the new dataset named MITWPU-1K. This dataset can be used in object detection and caption generation of images. The objective of this paper is to highlight the steps required for creating a new dataset. This necessitated a review of the existing dataset models prior to creating the new dataset. A sequential convolutional model for detecting objects on a new dataset is also presented. The process of creating a new image captioning dataset and the gained insights are described.

Keywords—convolutional model; dataset; image captioning; image labelling; object detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Many image datasets (e.g. MS COCO, Flickr, PASCAL) are available and can be used in image captioning systems. We wanted to explore the background and preprocessing required while creating such a dataset. For this purpose, we started to create a new dataset, called MITWPU-1K, of our university, MIT World Peace University, campus. Currently, the dataset consists of around 1500 images which are object labeled and captioned manually. These labels are classes of objects present in the image. Our dataset model is trained using the CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) architecture to detect objects present in an image. The validation while consideration of image selection is also presented. Currently, the MITWPU-1K dataset is having 4500 image descriptions, i.e. for each image, an average of three image annotations is provided. This dataset has a total of 68 objects and we are still working on its

expansion. Before creating a new dataset, we studied some of the prominent existing datasets used in image captioning.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many architectures have been proposed for generating captions for a given image. The reviewed research papers belong to the domains of Machine Learning and Neural Networks. Most of the datasets which are used in object recognition tasks are developed by considering the task of object classification, detection, and labeling. In the image caption domain, the MS-COCO [1] dataset is considered a benchmark, in which object recognition is enhanced by advancing scene understanding and by piping the annotation via picture labeling, instance spotting, and instance segmentation pipelines. In the MS-COCO dataset, there are 91 frequent object types with 25,00,000 labeled instances in 3,28,000 images. The training set consists of 82,783 photos, whereas the validation set contains 40,504 images, and the testing set 81,434 images. The Pascal VOC [2] dataset consists of 11,000 pictures divided into 20 object groups, having 2,501 images in the training set, 2,510 images in the validation set, and 4,952 images in the testing set. Imagenet [3] contains 14,197,122 images and almost 21,000 object classes. ImageNet is built upon the hierarchical structure provided by WordNet. CIFAR-10 [4] dataset and contains 100 categories with almost 60,000 images. They have performed object classification on tiny images of size 32×32 . The authors explain how they have trained a two-layer convolutional Deep Belief Network (DBN) on a 1.6 million tiny images dataset.

While analyzing these different dataset models, we come across the Yolo architecture [5] and Caffe framework [6]. Yolo architecture is used for object detection. Classification is done using CNNs along with localization using regression. Caffe convolutional architecture is used in Region-Based CNNs (RCNNs) for quick feature embedding framework. Caffe has already been employed in several academic research projects. Along with these papers, we also find some latest review papers on object detection methods used in deep learning [7, 8] which provide the metrics used for object detection along with the datasets used. The detailed review of many object detection survey papers is summarized in [7]. The authors observed that

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for object detection, deep learning methods provide a prominent approach. The authors also highlight the future work that can be done in visual object detection like multi-domain object detection, silent object detection, and unsupervised object detection using a deep learning approach. In [8], authors provide the categorization of existing image captioning systems and commonly used datasets for image captioning. They provided the detailed statistics of the following datasets: MS COCO, Flickr30K, Flickr8K, Visual Genome, IAPR TC-12, Stock3M, and MIT-Adobe FiveK dataset. Table I presents the details of some of the existing datasets mostly used in image captioning.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF PROMINENT EXISTING DATASETS USED IN IMAGE CAPTIONING

Dataset	Images	Objects / classes	Training set	Validation set	Testing set
MS-COCO [1]	3,28,000	80 categories	82,783	40,504	81,434
Pascal VOC [2]	11,000	20	2,501	2,510	4,952
ImageNet [3]	14,197,122	21,000 classes	1.2 million	150,000	-
CIFAR-10 [4]	60,000	100	-	-	-

III. METHODOLOGY USED IN DATASET CREATION

After analyzing the existing dataset models, we have started creating our new dataset which consists of images of the nearby

vicinity of the MIT World Peace University campus. We are creating a new dataset which can be further used in object recognition with labeled data and captions for the image. The flow of the creation of the dataset is shown in Figure 1 and can be summarized as:

- Image collection and validation
- Interface to provide image description/annotations
- Labeling objects

These steps are explained in the following sections.

A. Image Collection

For creating the new dataset, we collected images having diversity. The main objective of collecting diverse images was to properly train the dataset to avoid the problem of over fitting or under fitting during training. So, we tried to collect diverse images, like images with different brightness levels, having different foreground and background, containing multiple objects, etc. We took images that include different activities and events carried out on the MITWPU campus. While building this dataset we considered the images of posters and banners of various events on campus which contain some text information. The main goal was to use these textual data from the image to provide more detailed image descriptions during the caption generation task. Initially, we collected the images with the use of a smartphone and a professional camera, due to which the gathered images have different resolution, size, and orientation. After collecting several images, we found that all images could not be considered for the new dataset, so the rectification of these collected images are carried out as mentioned below.

Fig. 1. System flow of dataset creation.

B. Validation

Images from different sources were collected (via a professional camera, smart phones, etc.) from which many had low resolution, poor brightness, whereas some images were redundant, i.e. captured with multiple clicks on the same view. While preparing the dataset we observed that images should provide a good representation of the classes which can further help in the classification process. To achieve this, these images were removed using manual filtration. After validating the selected images at present, we had 1500 images in the dataset. Further, to speed up the process, the images were resized. Some sample images are shown in Figure 2.

We also considered images containing text, like banners and posters, so that in the future we can develop an image captioning system for generating the description of an image along with text extraction as shown in Figure 12.

C. Interface to Provide Image Description

As the dataset that can be utilized in an image captioning system was developed, we added descriptions for each image. To accomplish this task, a user interface was created in python as shown in Figure 3. Using this interface manually we provided captions for every image, which were stored in the form of csv and json files, and can be further used to train our dataset for image captioning (Figure 4). While providing the

manual captions we took care to provide different captions for the same image considering all visual elements of the image. For this, we provided a minimum of three captions for each images. Finally, along with each new image, an image description file containing the image annotations was provided.

Fig. 2. Sample mages from the dataset.

Fig. 3. Dataset creation module.

Fig. 4. Interface providing image description.

D. Image Description Format

With the image identification number we keep track of its associated descriptions or annotations. We maintained track of image file as {"file_name": "IMG_100.jpg", "id": 100}, and the included annotations for each image were in the format mentioned below in either csv or json file format:

- {"image_id": 100, "id": 1, "caption": "Description 1"},
- {"image_id": 100, "id": 2, "caption": "Description 2"},
- {"image_id": 100, "id": 3, "caption": "Description 3"},

This way, in the new dataset two folders were maintained, one which contains all the images and another that includes the manually assigned annotations for each image.

For creating the MS COCO dataset [1], huge crowdsourcing was involved in the annotation task and by using the Precision-Recall metric the quality of the annotation task was measured. We measured the quality of annotations of our dataset by applying the same concept. The quality of annotations was analyzed by a group of people including the authors of the paper. In some cases, we observed low precision and recall value, so we tried to search the false positive and false negative patterns and again perform the annotation correction task. For validation purposes, after assigning descriptions to all the images, we manually checked for redundancy the descriptions and verified them. Presently, the new dataset contains 1500 images with 4500 descriptions/annotations. Some image samples with the assigned captions are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Sample images with assigned captions from the created dataset.

E. Object Labelling

After acquiring images and their associated descriptions, the next task was to perform object detection, but before that,

we performed labelling on the images as shown in Figure 6. When multiple appearances of the same object occur in one image, only one label will be considered. Before using the new dataset, we performed object detection. Identifying objects from an image becomes complex when the image contains multiple objects. For this, we used the TensorFlow object detector [9] and done the review process used during the ImageNet dataset creation for detecting objects present in the image (Figure 7) [3]. The process involves visually checking the objects assigned with the images in order to check the classification accuracy of the new dataset.

- Build the model
- Compile the model
- Train the model with the new dataset
- Validate the model
- Measure the model's performance in terms of accuracy

The classifier model summary is shown in Figure 8. As already mentioned, in order to detect the 68 different object types present in our dataset, we have used a dense layer size (68). The model is trained to identify more than one object in an image. Some samples of object detection are shown in Figure 9. We initially started with bigger size objects, then proceeded towards smaller size objects. Our trained classification model detected objects like monitor, mouse, and keyboard in the given image shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 6. Labelling the objects of an image.

Objects	Table	Chair	Poster	Computer	Printer
Review 1	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
Review 2	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
Review 3	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Review 4	Y	Y	Y	Y	N

Fig. 7. Review method of identifying objects present in the image.

After performing the review method thoroughly, a complete list of classes in the new dataset was acquired. At present, our dataset contains 68 different object classes, such as person, chair, room, garden, plant, car, road, door, window, building, globe, printer, pen, notebook, bag, cupboard, book, bench, table, staircase, etc.

IV. BUILDING AND TRAINING THE CLASSIFICATION MODEL

To perform image classification, there are many existing pre-trained architectures available which are trained on huge size image datasets like MS COCO [1] and ImageNet [3]. Instead of using these available pre-trained architectures, we have come up with a simple convolutional classifier model which was trained on the new dataset. The main reason to come up with a different convolutional classifier was to avoid the over fitting problem because currently our dataset size is limited. We have created a sequential convolutional model, which gives the flexibility to keep adding different layers to the model as per requirements. The basic steps we followed while creating our classifier model which was trained on the new dataset are:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 110, 110, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 55, 55, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 53, 53, 124)	71548
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 27, 27, 124)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 90396)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 68)	6146996
Total params: 6,237,936		
Trainable params: 6,237,936		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Fig. 8. Model summary of the sequential classifier.

Fig. 9. Results of multiple detected objects.

A. Results

The new dataset was created for image captioning tasks, but it can also be used in object detection. To perform object detection, we performed labelling on the images which are further used during the training phase. Instead of using any pretrained classifier model, we presented the sequential classifier model. To check and compare the accuracy of the

presented sequential model, we performed the review method of [3]. Object detection with the sequential classifier model provided 84% accuracy. The comparative analysis graph plot of the review method and the sequential classifier model is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Object detection accuracy comparison.

TABLE II. MITWPU-1K DATASET SUMMARY

Dataset	Images	Objects	Image descriptions/annotations
MITWPU-1K	1500	68	4500

Fig. 11. Sample images of identified objects in the MITWPU-1K dataset.

Fig. 12. Sample images containing poster/banner.

Our dataset contains 1500 images with 68 different objects and 4500 image descriptions (Table II). These objects are mostly present in any college or university campus. Some of the samples of the identified objects in the created dataset are

shown in Figure 11. The dataset contains some images which contain text in the form of a banner or poster as shown in Figure 12. Using this dataset, we proposed a new deep learning model [10] for performing image captioning and text extraction. The obtained results of image captioning, including textual information present in the image, were satisfactory, giving accuracy up to 83% and performed as well as the state of the art methods.

The new dataset MITWPU-1K can be used in a wide range of applications such as object detection, caption generation, text detection, etc. Regarding future work, the size of the dataset will be increased by adding some domain-specific images along with captions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the followed process while creating a new image dataset for image captioning generation. The main purpose was to explore the processing behind creating a dataset that can be used in generating image captions. Before and during the creation of this new dataset, existing dataset models were studied in detail. At present, the new dataset consists of 1500 images and its name is MITWPU-1K in line with the current trend to name the dataset in a particular manner. The dataset includes 4500 annotations as we have assigned the minimum of three annotations for each image. The dataset has a subset of images that include text, so along with image description, text extraction can be done to further extend its application in domains like image captioning or other similar tasks.

Using a sequential convolutional model, we performed object detection tasks on the MITWPU-1K dataset. The dataset creation model can be extended to include all images of a particular domain such as sports, night vision images, animals, automobiles, computers, etc. In the application of image captioning, all available datasets are mostly generic. The accuracy of such systems can be improved by creating or using domain-specific image datasets.

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Castellated Beams with Fiber-Reinforced Lightweight Concrete Deck Slab as a Modified Choice for Composite Steel-Concrete Beams Affected by Harmonic Load

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Abstract-The behavior investigation of castellated beams with fiber-reinforced lightweight concrete deck slab as a modified choice for composite steel-concrete beams affected by harmonic load is presented in this study. The experimental program involved six fixed-supported castellated beams of 2140mm size. Three types of concrete were included: Normal Weight Concrete (NWC), Lightweight Aggregate Concrete (LWAC), and Lightweight Fiber-Reinforced Aggregate Concrete (LWACF). The specimens were divided into two groups: the first comprised three specimens tested under harmonic load effect of 30Hz operation frequency for 3 days, then the residual strength was determined through static load application. The second group included three specimens identical to those of group I, tested under static load only. The results show that LWAC was more influential than LWACF under harmonic load. The reduction in the residual strength of LWACF and NWC deck corresponding to the harmonic load was 0.94 and 0.7% respectively. The outcome proved that using LWACF as a deck for the castellated steel beams affected by harmonic load presents a significant choice with weight reduction of 16% compared to NWC. Steel fiber's tensile strength 1700MPa enhanced the absorbed energy and the ductility factor by 0.4 and 0.5% respectively.

Keywords-harmonic load application system; operation frequency; steel fiber; castellated beam

I. INTRODUCTION

A dynamic load usually changes with time in magnitude, direction, and position. Structures are often subjected to at least one type of dynamic load during their service life [1]. Structural dynamics is a form of structural analysis that investigates the way a structure behaves when subjected to dynamic (high-acceleration) loads. People, wind, waves, traffic, earthquakes, and explosions are all examples of dynamic loads. Dynamic loading can occur to any structure. To figure out how dynamic displacements move over time, things like dynamic analysis and modal analysis are being used, among other things [2]. Harmonic loading occurs when an

applied load changes as a sine or cosine function. Harmonic motion is seen in the vibrations produced by an unbalanced rotating machine, the vertical motion of an automobile on a road surface, and the oscillations of a tall chimney induced by vortex shedding in a constant breeze. Structural engineers have been seeking a way to convey the structure's ability to withstand imposed loads and usage for a long time, not only with aiming at lightness and economy but also with the goal of becoming aesthetic landmarks and meeting the current sustainability demands [3]. Some of these ways used open web expanded steel beams. Recent structures are developed using classic design principles, with components such as beams, columns, and other structural elements designed to transmit loads quickly, but at a high cost. Because of the above disadvantages, a new form of beams known as castellated beams was developed. By modifying just the pattern, these beams become cost-effective and have a high load-bearing capability. When an I-beam is cut longitudinally along the web of the beam and then rebuilt with a deeper web using a particular pattern, it separates the web and reassembles the beam with the deeper web [4]. In steel design, castellated beams unite beauty, adaptability, and economy. They've long been recognized as advantageous structural members for many reasons, including lighter sections, higher strength-to-weight ratios, on-site utility line adoption, lower foundation costs, lower painting and maintenance costs, and better aesthetics and appearances [5]. The term "lightweight concrete" refers to concrete that has a low density of 1120-1920kg/m³ and compressive strength of at least 17MPa [6]. Adding fibers to lightweight concrete enhances the density to reach 2000kg/m³ [7].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Regarding the castellated structures, there are many studies that investigate the effect on these structures by various types of static loads. Authors in [8] studied composite concrete-open web expanded steel beams under combined flexure and torsion.

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The experimentation required 18 composite specimens with 300mm open web extended section depths made from IPE-200 standard rolled sections, separated into two groups. Each set had 9 composite specimens with hexagonal or circular openings. All beams span 2900mm in basic support with 2 equal concentrated loads. The first strengthening technique enhanced the load capacity of the specimens with castellated holes by 26.08% and circular openings by 21.88% under pure bending, 16.36% and 33.33% under combined flexure and torsion, and 5.6% and 4.44% under pure torsion. The second strengthening technique increased the load capacity of castellated and circular hole specimens by 186.95 and 134.38% respectively, for pure bending, 136.36 and 116.66% for combined flexure and torsion effect, and 6.58 and 4.88% for pure torsion. To study failure modes, authors in [9] tested 6 composite-castellated beams with solid slabs of various lengths. The torsional buckling of web posts in response to a long crack in the concrete slab was found to be the cause of the failure of the tested beams. Shear and flexural behavior of composite concrete-steel castellated beams was investigated in [10]. Different composite castellated beams with different lengths and shear to moment ratios were investigated. Longer flexural beams failed when most of the studs in one half of the span failed, leading to lateral-torsional buckling of the suddenly unrestricted compression flange, whereas shear study beams buckled due to lateral-torsional buckling of the web post.

Most previous studies have focused on dynamic loads caused by quakes and offshore waves. However, not enough research has been conducted regarding the effects of machine vibration on structures. Modern industry has introduced massive machines that significantly affect the performance of structures, causing a new type of vibration load. Machine vibration should be treated as an engineering problem, regardless of size or kind, and should be designed using sound engineering principles. In the last 30 years, there have been many studies on infinite periodic vibration on structures, with an emphasis on free vibration propagation and forced vibration induced by stationary harmonic loads. Authors in [11, 12] presented an experimental and theoretical study on the structural behavior of bubble deck reinforced concrete slabs under the effect of harmonic loads. The results showed that the distribution of bubbles had a significant effect on the structural behavior in the dynamic analysis, and the numerical model used was in good agreement with the experimental data. For the lightweight concrete, in monotonic and cyclic loads, the effect of steel fiber ($L=30\text{mm}$ and aspect ratio=60) on the properties of LWAC made of expanded clay was studied in [13]. When LWAC was strengthened by steel fiber of 0.5, 1, and 2 volume fraction, the improvement in compressive strength in monotonic load was near 22, 29, and 38% respectively, and in cyclic load near 23, 28 and 41% respectively. Authors in [14] studied the influence of steel fibers on the compressive strength of a sanded LWAC made with sintered pulverized fuel ash LWA. The specimens had a compressive strength of 90MPa after 28 days and a density of 2015kg/m^3 . Many researchers have investigated the behavior of the fiber-reinforced lightweight concrete structure and the results of [15-19] agree with the results in [14].

It is well known that the dynamic response is highly related to the weight and ultimate strength of the structure. In order to improve the structural behavior of the composite beam under harmonic load, a castellated beam was considered in this study instead of a plain steel section to increase the ultimate strength and reduced the self-weight. Moreover, Normal Concrete Weight (NWC) deck slab was replaced by lightweight concrete. Two proposals are being considered regarding the concrete deck slab. These are: lightweight concrete with no fiber reinforced (LWAC) and fiber reinforced concrete (LWACF).

III. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

A. Tested Specimens

Six composite castellated steel-concrete specimens with a span of 2140mm were fabricated according to [20] and were tested as fixed-end supported beams. Since the overall height after castellation was set at 400mm, a steel I-beam section (IPE 200) with 100mm concrete deck slab was used. The composite system's components were fully bonded together. Shear connections were placed perpendicularly at 187mm c/c from the upper flange of the steel I-beam, constructed of steel channel section with dimensions of $60\text{mm}\times 30\text{mm}\times 5\text{mm}$ and a total length of 50mm. On both sides of the steel beam, $284\text{mm}\times 47.2\text{mm}\times 6\text{mm}$ steel stiffeners were arranged in the center and at the two ends of the web. Deformed 10mm steel bars spaced at 125mm c/c were used to reinforce the concrete deck in both directions. Figures 1 and 2 show the details of the specimens. Table I shows the mechanical properties of the steel component.

Fig. 1. Fabrication and cast of the composite castellated beams.

There were two concrete mixes, the first was normal weight concrete that was prepared using ordinary Portland cement type CEM I 32.5 R according to [21] and crushed stone of maximum size of 10mm, and zone 2 fine aggregates, conferring to [22]. The aggregate: sand: cement designed proportions by weight were 1.6:1.33:1 with a water-cement ratio equal to 0.29 according to [23]. The second one was lightweight concrete, with mix proportions shown in Table II. The ratios of all the constituent materials were compatible with the standard of the

Regular Practice for Structural Lightweight Concrete Collection Proportion according to [24]. Light Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA) as shown in Figure 3 was adopted to cast the lightweight concrete as ASTM C330 [25] coarse aggregate. The coarse aggregate's grain size was 10mm [26]. One type of fiber was adopted in this work as hooked steel fibers of 30mm

length with a volume fraction of 1.5%. The steel fiber properties are illustrated in Table III. The compressive strength of each specimen was determined by testing three standard 150×300mm concrete cylinders according to [27], with a target value of 40MPa.

Fig. 2. Castellated beam details. All dimensions are in mm.

TABLE I. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF STEEL COMPONENT

Sample	Thickness (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)	Ultimate stress (MPa)	Elongation %
Web plate	5.6	420	518.9	26.6
Plate for top and bottom flange	8	415	515.88	27.15
Stiffener's plate	6	400	520.5	26.36
Shear connectors plate	5	250.14	332.29	29.26
Welding wire	6	456.6	615.7	20.12
Reinforcement	10	410	520	23.4

TABLE II. THE ADOPTED LIGHTWEIGHT CONCRETE MIX

Material	Proportion
Cement	677 kg/m ³
Water	237 kg/m ³
Coarse aggregates (LECA)	210 kg/m ³
Fine aggregates	884 kg/m ³
Silica fume	170 kg/m ³
Superplasticizer	7 litter/m ³

Fig. 3. Light Expanded Clay Aggregate (LECA).

TABLE III. STEEL FIBER PROPERTIES

Fiber type	Diameter (mm)	Length (mm)	Aspect ratio	Tensile strength (MPa)	E (GPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
Hook	0.5	30	60	1700	200	7800

B. Groups of the Tested Specimens

Six composite castellated beams were cast and evaluated. All specimens were 2140×500×400mm in length, width, and total depth respectively. They were categorized into 2 groups: The first group consisted of 1 NWC deck slab and 2 specimens with lightweight concrete deck slabs, one of plain LWAC and the other with reinforced LWACF with hooked steel fibers of 1.5% volume fraction. The specimens of group I were subjected to a harmonic load of 30Hz vibration frequency before being subjected to concentrated load up to failure. The harmonic load was applied continuously for 3 working days, each lasting 6hr. The second group comprised of 3 specimens identical to those of group I, but they were only exposed to static concentrated load until failure.

IV. TESTING PROCEDURE

For the first group, there were two loading stages. In the first stage, the adopted harmonic load was applied and an advanced digital data logger was connected to a computer device given a specific program to record and save the data in an spreadsheet. This instrument has a rate of 1000 records/s and contains 24 channels divided into 4 groups that can record strain values, vibration amplitude, and the applied load as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Digital data logger.

Calibrated piezo (vibration type) was considered to measure the harmonic applied force and the vibration wave at the specimen center-line as shown in Figure 5. The application system of the harmonic load consists of a vibration motor of 3HP, combined with a steel mass of 278kg. The specimen was set to the test frame so that it behaved as a fixed-end supported beam. The fixed system comprised two steel plates 600mm×100mm×400mm connected by a steel thread rod with a diameter of 25mm, in such a way that they prevented the specimen from any movement (Figure 5). The application system of the harmonic load and the Piezo sensors were set in the adopted position shown in Figure 6. The time duration of the applied harmonic load was 6hr/day for 3 days. To achieve the main goal of this study (i.e. checking the amplitude variation), the data were recorded at an interval of 2hr for a period of 120s for all the testing days. Table IV shows the details of the tested specimens. For the second stage of Group I and Group II, by using a load control test at a rate of 250N/step, all specimens were exposed to a static load up to failure. The measurements included mid-span deflections and strain across the section depth.

Fig. 5. Specimen set up for Group I (first stage).

Fig. 6. The application system of the harmonic load.

TABLE IV. DETAILS OF THE TESTED SPECIMENS

Specimen	Deck slab type	Group	f'_c (MPa)	Density kg/m^3	f_r^* (MPa)	E_c (MPa)	Load type
HS-RL0	LWAC	Group I	37	1640	3.0	20407	Harmonic +static
HS-RN0	NWC		40	2400	3.4	28333	
HS-RL1.5	LWACF		40	2000	3.5	23584	
S-RL0	LWAC	Group II	38	1600	3.2	20407	Static
S-RN0	NWC		42	2400	3.54	28333	
S-RL1.5	LWACF		40	2000	3.7	23584	

* According to ASTM C496/C496M-17[28].

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results of the Dynamic Part for Group I (First Stage)

This group consists of 3 composite castellated steel beams of NWC, LWAC, and LWACF concrete deck slab types. The specimens were exposed to a harmonic load of 30Hz. The vertical vibration magnitude and vibration sine wave for the applied harmonic load at the selected frequency were evaluated using the outcome of the piezo sensors. Figure 7 shows the noise-removing process with computer software that modified the piezo recordings by removing the noise.

1) Load -Time History

The harmonic load is considered dynamic in this study. In general, the mathematical formula for this load comprises two components. The first is the harmonic load's amplitude ($2me\omega_0^2$), while the second is the sine wave ($\sin(\omega t)$) term, [29].

$$p_d = 2me\omega_0^2 \sin(\omega t) \quad (1)$$

where p_d is the dynamic load (N), m the eccentric rotating mass (3kg), e the eccentric distance (0.08m), and ω_0 the operating frequency of the machine (rad/s). The recorded load time histories for the adopted load frequency are shown in Figure 8 and Table V.

Fig. 7. Noise removal process: (a) Before and (b) after noise removing.

TABLE V. AMPLITUDE OF THE HARMONIC LOAD ($2me\omega_0^2$)

Frequency (cyc/s)	Frequency (rad/s)	Amplitude force (N)
30	188.5	17055

Note: The magnitudes of m and e are measured experimentally

Fig. 8. Recorded load time history for the adopted load frequency.

2) *Vibration-Time History (First Stage).*

Table VI and Figure 9 show that the LWCA had significantly the highest response when subjected to the 30Hz harmonic load for 3 days. Cracks appeared in the tension face of the specimen HS-RL0 during the first day of the vibration test. As seen in Table VI, the data of the vibration wave were collected every 2hr of the loading period. Figure 10 shows that as the load time increases, new cracks continue to form and propagate in the center zone of the slab. The variation in amplitude between the specimens HS-RL0 and HS-RN0 also increased day by day as shown in Table V. As for the fiber-reinforced concrete specimen HS-RL1.5, when compared with HS-RN0, it showed a slight difference in the amplitude on the first day of operation by about 18%, while during the last two days of operation, the amplitude values began to remain stable at 0.33mm. On the last day, the variation became less. The fiber-reinforced lightweight concrete behaves slightly similar to NWC under harmonic load. This behavior may be attributed to the fiber presence, which enhanced the mechanical properties of lightweight concrete [19] so that it became an alternative to normal weight concrete (Table IV). Regarding the generation of the crack in the fiber-reinforced specimen, no cracks appeared during loading.

Figure 9 and Table VI show that the amplitude values of the vibration were mostly determined by the percentage of compatibility between the natural frequency of the specimen and the operating frequency of the vibrating motor. They indicate that the value of vibration amplitude was slightly constant for the HS-RL1.5 specimen during the operation time since the natural frequency was far from the operating

frequency by about 77%. Moreover, the steel-fiber presence advanced the specimen's strength. Regarding the lightweight concrete, the values of the peaks differ from one reading to another due to the crack generation that decreased stiffness.

Fig. 9. Vibration-time history under harmonic load.

Fig. 10. Crack pattern of the specimen HS-RL0 due to harmonic load.

B. *Results of the Static Part for Group I and Group II*

After removing the continuous harmonic load, a concentrated load was applied to the specimens of group I (stage two) and group II to evaluate the dissipated energy caused by the harmonic load. As illustrated in Tables VII and VIII, the failure loads for all the tested specimens in the first group were less than those of the corresponding specimens in the second group by about 0.7, 24, and 0.9% for NWC, LWAC, and LWACF specimens respectively.

TABLE VI. MAXIMUM AMPLITUDE OF THE SPECIMENS UNDER HARMONIC LOAD

Days	Specimens	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	Variation% (HS-RN0)	HS-RL1.5	Variation% (HS-RN0)
	Natural frequency Hz	128.24	130.75	1.96	125.93	-1.8
	Time (hr)	Amplitude (mm)	Amplitude (mm)	Variation% (HS-RN0)	Amplitude (mm)	Variation% (HS-RN0)
1	2	0.27	0.49	81.48	0.32	18.51
	4	0.28	0.50	78.57	0.327	16.78
	6	0.28	0.57	103.57	0.327	16.78
2	2	0.35	0.57	62.86	0.327	-6.57
	4	0.35	0.60	71.43	0.33	-5.71
	6	0.35	0.60	71.43	0.33	-5.71
3	2	0.35	0.64	82.86	0.33	-5.714
	4	0.35	0.77	120	0.33	-5.714
	6	0.35	0.77	120	0.33	-5.714

1) *Crack Pattern, Load Capacity, Ultimate Deflection, and Failure Mechanisms*

The cracks started and spread along the fixed support path in group II, which changed the structure from a static

indeterminate structure to a static determinate one. According to the collected data, the percentage of load required to produce such cracks varied from 38.5% to 70.8% of the corresponding ultimate load as shown in Table VII. The outcome presented a significant enhancement in cracking load and the ultimate load

for the lightweight aggregate concrete when the fiber was added to the mix compared with the specimen without fiber as shown in Table VII. Figure 11 shows the crack pattern for the specimen S-RL1.5.

Fig. 11. Crack pattern of specimen S-RL1.5.

TABLE VII. CRACKING AND ULTIMATE LOAD OF GROUPS I AND II

Specimen	Group	P_{cr} (ton)	P_{ul} (ton)	Variation in P_{ul} %	P_{cr}/P_{ul} (%)	Failure modes
HS-RN0	I	----	42.5	---	---	Web post-buckling, Saint-Venant, and concrete crush
HS-RL0		----	29	-32	---	Concrete crush .
HS-RL1.5		----	42.1	-0.95	---	Web post-buckling, Saint-Venant, and concrete crush
S-RN0	II	25	42.8	---	58.4	Web post-buckling, Saint-Venant, and concrete crush.
S-RL0		15	38	-12.6	39.5	Web post-buckling and concrete crush .
S-RL1.5		30	42.5	-0.71	70.6	Web post-buckling, Saint-Venant, and concrete crush.

TABLE VIII. LOAD CAPACITY REDUCTION

Group II			
Specimen	S-RN0	S-RL0	S-RL1.5
P_{ul} (ton)	42.8	38	42.5
Group I			
Specimen	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	HS-RL1.5
P_{ul} (ton)	42.5	29	42.1
Reduction %	0.7	23.7	0.94

Table VIII shows that the rate of reduction in the failure load varied from 0.7% to 24%, indicating that the lightweight concrete deck slab specimen is more influenced by the harmonic load than the other specimens. This reduction belongs to the harmonic load effect, which caused damage presented by crack generation as shown in Figure 10. The reduction percentage of carrying load capacity between the two groups regarding the fiber-reinforced lightweight aggregate concrete (specimen HS-RL1.5) was slightly similar to the specimen HS-RN0. This reflected the steel-fiber contribution in enhancing the lightweight concrete characteristics (LWAC). It improved the overall structural behavior and decreased the ultimate load variation compared to the normal weight concrete by no more than -0.95 % and -0.71 % as shown in Table VII. In summary, the specimen HS-RL1.5 was not significantly affected by the harmonic load, just like the NWC specimen.

Figures 12-17 show the failure type in the tested specimens at the end of the tests.

As shown in Table IX, the same influence was noticed regarding the ultimate deflection. The percentage of deflection reduction was 3.1, 16.66, and 2.7% for specimens of NWC, LWAC, and LWACF deck slabs respectively. Concerning the behavior of the castellated steel beams, two behaviors were observed: the first was for the lightweight concrete deck slab (specimen HS-RL0), where the harmonic load had a clear effect on concrete from the first day of the test. This effect reduces the concrete strength so that the local failure of the deck occurred before the yielding state of the castellated steel beam, which indicates that this section is non-economic due to the earlier failure of the deck affected by the harmonic load while the generated stresses in the steel beam were very small. The other behavior was completely opposite to the previous one, especially for the fiber-reinforced specimen: The steel section was affected faster than the concrete deck, due to the concrete strength and the bearing improvement caused by steel fiber adding. Table X shows the reduction in the yielding strength of the specimens. It is clear that the presence of fiber and the use of LECA as an alternative coarse aggregate in the HS-RL1.5 specimen have a significant effect on the behavior of the whole structure. The reduction in yielding strength was close to the specimen with NWC as deck slab by 0.58% and 0.63% for HS-RN0 and HS-RL1.5 respectively.

TABLE IX. REDUCTION IN ULTIMATE REFLECTION

Group II			
Specimen	S-RN0	S-RL0	S-RL1.5
Δ_d (mm)	13.59	11.4	14.6
Group I			
Specimen	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	HS-RL1.5
Δ_d (mm)	14	13.3	15
Reduction %	3.1	16.66	2.7

TABLE X. ULTIMATE LOAD CORRESPONDING TO THE INITIAL STEEL YIELDING

Group II			
Specimen	S-RN0	S-RL0	S-RL1.5
Ultimate load (ton)	35	35	35
Group I			
Specimen	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	HS-RL1.5
Ultimate load (ton)	34.8	----	34.78
Reduction %	0.58	---	0.63

Fig. 12. Failure mode of the specimen S-RL1.5.

Fig. 13. Failure mode of the specimen HS-RL1.5.

Fig. 14. Failure mode of the specimen S-RL0.

Fig. 15. Failure mode of the specimen HS-RL0.

Fig. 16. Failure mode of the specimen S-RN0.

Fig. 17. Failure mode of the specimen HS-RN0.

2) Absorbed Energy and Ductility

Toughness is defined as the ability to absorb energy [30], and it is evaluated from the region below the flexural load-deflection curve. Table XI shows the reduction percentage of the absorbed energy. The HS-RL0 specimen showed strength reduction while no significant effect was detected in the other specimens. It can be concluded that adding fibers to the LWAC induced a considerable enhancement in the concrete toughness index, which is considered good for NWC [31]. The ductility factor reduction for the HS-RL1.5 specimen was the smallest, indicating that this specimen is the most ductile, due to the steel fiber's high tensile strength of 1700MPa (Table XII).

TABLE XI. ABSORBED ENERGY

Group II			
Specimen	S-RN0	S-RL0	S-RL1.5
Absorbed energy (ton. mm)	1206.75	938.60	1213.40
Group I			
Specimen	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	HS-RL1.5
Absorbed energy (ton. mm)	1200.00	657.7	1201.90
Reduction %	0.56	42.70	0.95

TABLE XII. DUCTILITY FACTOR

Group II			
Specimen	S-RN0	S-RL0	S-RL1.5
Ductility factors	1.199	1.06	1.2
Group I			
Specimen	HS-RN0	HS-RL0	HS-RL1.5
Ductility factor	1.19	0.9	1.197
Redaction %	0.75	15.1	0.25

VI. CONCLUSION

The outcome of the tested specimens can be concluded to:

- The concrete deck slab type has a significant effect on the response and structural behavior of the castellated composite beam under harmonic load.
- The fiber-reinforced lightweight concrete behaves similarly to normal weight concrete under harmonic load. When fibers were added to the mix, the outcome showed a significant improvement in cracking load, ultimate load, concrete toughness index, and ductility, so adding fibers is considered a good choice for NWC.
- The fiber-reinforced lightweight concrete is a suitable choice in the deck of the castellated beam under harmonic load. This choice provides a structural part with smaller weight (approximately 16%), which presents an advantage process for castellated beams that is widely used for low-loaded structures.
- The lightweight concrete specimen HS-RL0 exhibited a clear effect from the harmonic load from the first day of the test. This effect was evident through the cracks' appearance and the increase in their number with time.
- Local failure of the deck occurred before the yielding state of the castellated steel beam for the HS-RL0 specimen,

indicating that this section is not economical as a result of the earlier failure of the deck affected by harmonic load while the generated stresses in the steel beam were sufficient.

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Multi-Objective MPSO/GA Optimization of an Autonomous PV-Wind Hybrid Energy System

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Abstract-This article presents a study of the optimal sizing of an autonomous hybrid energy system (PV-wind-battery) as a power source for a typical household in an isolated village in Adrar, Algeria using the multi-objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MPSO) algorithm and Genetic Algorithm (GA). This study presents a new approach to obtain an optimal configuration and sizing of the main components integrated into the autonomous hybrid system (PV/wind) which meets the requirements of the desired system. In the first phase, the reliability criterion (LPSP) is met with the lowest Energy Cost (EC) value (min Total Net Present Cost (TNPC)). The required storage bank must have a low rate of aging in order to extend the battery life, which contributes to the reduction of the overall cost of the system.

Keywords-autonomous hybrid system; optimization and sizing (PV/wind); minimum energy cost; TRNSYS

I. INTRODUCTION

Many isolated sites are powered by autonomous electricity generation systems, using local renewable sources, such as photovoltaic (PV) panels, wind turbines, and micro turbines. Electricity from renewable sources is intermittent, dependent on weather conditions. These renewable generators are coupled to a storage system ensuring the continuous availability of energy. The renewable generators selected for our study is a hybrid system (PV/wind) with storage. Generally, the storage is ensured by batteries which currently consist one of the most used solutions. The batteries have very good yields, around 80-85%, and have a very competitive price, if we consider lead technology. The optimization of these systems is based on sizing criteria, maximizing the power generated to have a good yield and cost minimization. Knowing that the main research goal is the overall improvement of the performance of PV and wind conversion systems, the equivalence between the admissible efficiency and the average operating cost determines the degree of efficiency of use of these systems. Several criteria for optimizing the efficiency of hybrid systems (PV/wind) as well as techniques have been applied in order to have a good adaptation and a high efficiency.

Authors in [1] recommended an optimal design model for the design of hybrid solar-wind-battery systems for powering a telecommunication relay station. To assess the optimal system

configuration and ensure that the annualized cost of the system is minimized while satisfying the probability of loss of required power. The five decision variables for Loss of Power Supply Probability (LPSP) included in the optimization process are the PV module number, PV module slope angle, wind turbine number, installation height of the wind turbine, and battery capacity. An iterative method to determine the optimal dimensioning of autonomous photovoltaic (PV-battery) is proposed in [2, 4], linear programming is used in [3] to design and optimize the components of a hybrid system (PV/wind/micro-hydro) which minimize the size and initial cost. A new approach to designing an autonomous hybrid wind PV/battery system is proposed in [5] taking into account both economic and ecological aspects. A technical-economic analysis of the complete study of the hybrid system (PV/diesel generator/battery) was done by the authors in [6] to minimize the cost and meet charging requirements and the optimal tilt angle of the PV panel in order to increase the energy generated by the use of a genetic algorithm. In [7], feasibility study and techno-economic evaluation of an autonomous hybrid system (PV/wind) with battery energy storage for a remote island were conducted using the HOMER software to obtain an optimal configuration of the autonomous system in terms of energy cost (COE) and system Net Present Cost (NPC). An iterative approach following the Total Energy Deficit (TED), the Total NPC (TNPC), and EC was developed in [8] to size the components of an autonomous hybrid system (PV/wind/diesel/battery) to satisfy the charge demand in a more cost-effective manner. An iterative optimization technique was used in [9] to determine the optimal configuration of an autonomous system (PV/wind/hydrogen) supplying a desalination unit which would guarantee a reliable energy supply with the lowest initial investment cost for any site. Optimal sizing and techno-economic evaluation of the pumped storage-based PV power generation system was presented in [10] to maximize power supply reliability and minimize lifecycle cost. The Pigeon Inspired Optimization (PIO) algorithm was used for optimization sizing of a PV-wind hybrid power system in [11]. Several thermal insulation solutions have been proposed [12-14] in order to ensure excellent thermal comfort of a home and to minimize energy needs while improving energy efficiency.

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This paper presents a comprehensive and integrated study divided into two phases.

At first, a study of the optimal sizing of an autonomous hybrid energy system (PV/wind/battery) as a power source for a typical Algerian village household is conducted using MPSO and GA. This work relates to the development of a technical and economic analysis and evaluation methodology carried out for a hybrid system (PV/wind). The results are compared and discussed. Our study is based on two models: the reliability model developed according to the concept of LPSP and the economic model based on TNPC and the battery aging model. In order to achieve our objective, we proposed two essential contributions which are MPSO algorithm and GA. A case study is being investigated for the analysis of an autonomous hybrid system (PV/wind) intended to supply a village of habitats in Adrar Algeria. The simulation results relating to the different system configurations and their corresponding costs are presented. The type of storage used in our system is the lead acid battery.

In the next phase, in order to guarantee the state of health of the storage batteries, we have chosen a configuration which ensures longer battery lifetime and minimum aging rate from a study of its State of Charge (SOC). The application of the Rainflow algorithm allows extracting the number of cycles of the signal with its corresponding depth of discharge. The operating cycles used to study the aging of the battery were based on the battery life given by the manufacturer.

II. MODEL OF THE HYBRID SYSTEM COMPONENTS

The solar/ wind hybrid energy production system consists of a PV generator, a wind turbine, a storage battery bank, AC/DC converters, DC/DC converters, a controller, and cables. In order to predict the performance of the hybrid system, the individual components must first be modeled.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the hybrid system.

The power delivered by the different energy sources depends on several parameters. For the solar generator, the

parameters influencing the power supplied by the generator are: The metrological data of the site: ambient temperature T_a and irradiation I_r and the A_{pv} surface of the solar panel field.

For the wind generator, the supplied power is influenced by the metrological data of the site: Ambient temperature T_a and wind speed w_s and the surface swept by the rotor of the wind turbine A_{wt} .

A. Modeling of the PV System

The model of the solar generator is given by [5, 15, 17, 18]:

$$P_{pv} [w/m^2] = \eta_G A_{pv} I_r \quad (1)$$

where η_G is the overall efficiency of the generator given by:

$$\eta_G = \eta_r \eta_{pv} [1 - \beta_t (T_c - T_{NOCT})] \quad (2)$$

where η_r is the reference efficiency of the solar generator, η_{pv} is the degradation factor of the solar generator according to its lifetime, β_t is the coefficient of the influence of the temperature of the PV cells on the efficiency of the generator.

The temperature of the junction or the cell of the PV panel is given by:

$$T_c = 30 + 0.075(300 - I_r) + 1.14(T_a - 25) \quad (3)$$

where T_{NOCT} is the nominal operating cell temperature and I_r the irradiation or solar sunshine.

B. Modeling of the Wind Generator

The power model of the wind generator is given by the following expressions [5, 15]:

$$P_{wg} = \frac{1}{2} C_p \eta_{gb} \eta_g \rho A_{wt} w_s^3 \quad (4)$$

$$P_{wg} = \frac{1}{2} \eta_G \rho A_{wt} w_s^3 \quad (5)$$

where C_p is the turbine efficiency, η_{gb} is the efficiency of the speed variator (drive controller), η_g the Generator efficiency, $A_{wt} [m^2]$, is the surface swept by the rotor of the turbine, $w_s [m/s]$ the wind speed, $Z [m]$ is the altitude, T_a is the ambient temperature, and $\rho [kg/m^3]$ the air density:

$$\rho = (353.049/T_a) \cdot \exp(-0.034(Z/T_a)) \quad (6)$$

C. Modeling of the Storage System

The charge-discharge expression of the lead-acid battery is given by the following expression:

$$SOC_{bat} = SOC_{bat}(t - 1) + \left(E_{pv}(t) * \eta_{acdc} + E_{wt}(t) * \eta_{acdc} - \frac{E_{ld}}{\eta_{inv}} \right) * \eta_{cha} \quad (7)$$

where $E_{pv}(t) = P_{pv}(t) * \Delta t$, $E_{wt}(t) = P_{wt}(t) * \Delta t$, $E_{ld}(t) = P_{ld}(t) * \Delta t$, and $P_{pv}(t)$, $P_{wt}(t)$, $P_{ld}(t)$ are respectively the PV generator power, the wind generator power, and the load demand in an instant t . Δt is the step time of the simulation, η_{inv} is the inverter efficiency, η_{cha} is the battery charging efficiency, which generally depends on the charging current and is between [0.65 and 0.8].

When the load demand is greater than the available generated energy, the battery bank is in discharging state. Thus, the SOC_{bat} at instant t can be expressed as:

$$Soc_{bat} = Soc_{bat}(t - 1) + \left(E_{pv}(t) * \eta_{dc} + E_{wt}(t) * \eta_{acdc} - \frac{E_{Ld}}{\eta_{inv}} \right) * \frac{1}{\eta_{disch}} \quad (8)$$

where η_{disch} is the battery discharging efficiency, it is supposed to be equal to 1. In all cases the state of batteries charging must satisfy the following condition:

$$Soc_{bat_min} < Soc_{bat}(t) < Soc_{bat_max}$$

where Soc_{bat_min} and Soc_{bat_max} are the limit states of battery charging. Soc_{bat_max} is considered as the nominal capacity of the storage system:

$$Soc_{bat_max} = C_{bat_n}$$

The inferior limit is given by:

$$Soc_{bat_min} = DOD * C_{bat_n}$$

where DOD(%) is the battery Depth Of Discharge [17].

III. SIZING AND OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

The developed process was used to calculate the optimum value of the PV module area, the wind turbine, and the optimal battery capacity for a standalone PV/wind hybrid system.

A. Enunciation of the Optimal Sizing Problem

The estimate of the hybrid PV/wind energy/battery size is formulated as an optimization problem where the express of the objective function is according to the constraints and the performances of the system. The objective function and the constraints are detailed in the following subsections.

B. Objective Function

The objective functions of the optimization problem must minimize the total economic cost of the TNPC and EC of the system and to satisfy the energy needs. We are focused on finding the best combination of multiple sources for a hybrid system, i.e. the PV panel surface (A_{pv}), the area swept by wind turbines (A_{wt}) and the nominal storage capacity of the battery bank (C_n).

1) Economic Evaluation

This assessment is based on the concept of the current global net cost: the cumulative cost of a product throughout its life cycle, from the start of its conception until its dismantling. It includes the initial cost (acquisition + installation) of all system components, the cost of all component replacements required during the lifetime of the system, and the cost of maintenance. The lifetime of the system is usually considered to be the lifetime of the element with the longest lifetime. In this article, the economic approach used based on the TNPC and the EC taking into account the lifetime and replacement costs of each element of the system.

2) Total Net Present Cost

The current TNPC in \$, can be expressed as follows according to [8]:

$$TNPC(\$) = IC + PW_{crec} + PW_{cnonrec} \quad (9)$$

where IC is the initial cost of the system components.

$$IC = C_{ipv} * P_{pv} + C_{iw} * P_w + C_{ibat} + C_{iinv} \quad (10)$$

where C_{ipv} is the initial cost of the photovoltaic system, C_{iw} the initial cost of the wind system, C_{ibat} the initial cost of the storage system, C_{iinv} the initial cost of the inverter. P_{wrec} and $P_{wnonrec}$ are factors for the conversion of the recurring and non-recurring costs to their present value, defined by [8]. The component cost assumptions on which we based our calculations are given in Table I [6, 8].

TABLE I. COST OF THE SYSTEM COMPONENTS

Component	Unit price (US\$/W)	Maintenance cost during the first year (%)	Life time (years)	Interest rate d (%)
PV array ^a	2.29	1% of price	25	8
Wind turbine ^b	3.00	3% of price	20	
Battery ^a	0.213	1% of price	4	
Inverter ^a	0.711	0% of price	10	

^a <http://www.solarbuzz.com>.

^b Mean value of the literature data.

3) Energy Cost (\$/kwh)

The cost per kWh of the EC produced in \$/KWH can be determined by the ratio of the annualized total cost (TAC) to the annual energy produced by the system [7-9, 15,16]. EC can be calculated according to (11), (12).

$$EC \left(\$/kwh \right) = \frac{TAC}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{pr}(t)} = \frac{TNPC * CRF}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{pr}(t)} \quad (11)$$

CRF is the recovery factor, expressed as:

$$CRF(i, n) = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (12)$$

where i is the interest rate and n the lifetime of the system in years. For this study, we have assumed an interest rate of 8% and $n = 20$ years.

C. The Constraints

To find solutions for the optimization problem, a set of constraints must be satisfied with any feasible solution throughout the system operations as follows:

The SOC of the battery bank must satisfy the following constraints at any times:

$$Soc_{min} < Soc < Soc_{max}$$

The system's LPSP must be less than the allowed LPSP reliability index:

$$LPSP < LPSP_{index}$$

1) Reliability Estimation According to LPSP

LPSP is defined as the fraction of all energy losses and energy demand in a defined period of operation (in our study we used $t = 1$ year) [16]:

$$LPSP = P_r \{ E_{bat} \leq E_{bat_min} \} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T LPSP(t)}{\sum_{t=1}^T P_L(t) * \Delta t} \quad (13)$$

LPS (Loss of Power Supply) can be calculated with the following relation:

$$LPS(t) = (P_i(t) - P_w(t)) * \Delta t - (P_{pv}(t) * \Delta t + C_{bat}(t - 1) - SOC_{bat,min}) * \eta_{inv} \quad (14)$$

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PSO ALGORITHM

PSO is a new evolutionary algorithm, which was originally inspired by the regularity of the cluster activities of birds. Thus, a simplified model using group intelligence was established. PSO is initialized as a set of random particles, each particle having its own position and velocity vectors. The optimal solution is searched for iteratively. In each iteration, the particles update themselves by tracking two "extremes". The first extreme, called *pbest*, is the best solution found by the particle itself. The other extreme, called *gbest*, is the best solution currently found by the entire swarm [21-25]. The position and velocity vectors of each particle can be calculated as:

$$V_i(t + 1) = mV_i(t) + (C_1r_1(pbest_i(t) - X_i(t)) +$$

$$C_2r_2(gbest_i(t) - X_i(t)) \quad (15)$$

$$X_i(t + 1) = X_i(t) + V_i(t + 1) \quad (16)$$

$$m = \frac{2}{2 - \varphi - \sqrt{\varphi^2 - 4\varphi}} \quad (17)$$

$$\varphi = C_1 - C_2 \quad (18)$$

$$\varphi > 4 \quad (19)$$

C_1 and C_2 are the cognitive and social parameters respectively in this study $C_1=C_2=1$. r_1 and r_2 are random numbers between 0 and 1. In this article, the objective functions are defined as minimum {*EC*, *TNPC*}, under the constraint of inequality, the main program is developed in Matlab.

V. SITE DESCRIPTION

The meteorological data used in this study have been recorded at the New Energy Algeria (NEAL) station installed at the roof top of the Research Unit in Renewable Energies in the Saharan Medium (URERMS) located in Adrar (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. NEAL station.

Fig. 3. Algeria wind map.

Adrar is the administrative capital of Adrar Province, the second largest province in Algeria. The commune is sited around an oasis in the Tuat region of Sahara Desert. According to the 2008 census, it has a population of 64,781, with an annual growth rate of 4.0%. Adrar lies at an elevation of 258m above sea level. Its geographical coordinates are 27°52'N, 0°17'W. Adrar has a hot desert climate, with long, hot summers and short, warm winters, and averages just 15mm of rainfall per year. Summer temperatures are consistently high as they commonly approach 40°C. The temperatures at night are still hot at around 27°C. Even in early May or in late September, daytime temperatures can rise up to 45°C. Figure 3 shows the annual wind map.

A. Wind Potential

To evaluate the wind potential of the site, measurements of wind speeds were taken on site during the year 2015, with half hour intervals. Figure 4 shows the wind profile during January.

Fig. 4. Wind profile during January, 2015.

B. Solar Potential

Measurements of the solar irradiation were also taken on site, by using the orientation and inclination of the PV modules, the latitude of the place, and the values of the global radiation

were calculated. The quantity of the global irradiation received per day for 1m of horizontal surface is indicated, the mean value of the radiation measured every hour of January and July is given in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Global irradiation in (a) January and (b) July.

C. Potential Analysis

The annual solar irradiation profile for the proposed site shows that there is a marked seasonal variation in solar irradiation (greater in summer). The Adrar region has an acceptable wind potential. This feature has led the region to favor initiatives in wind energy generation.

D. Load Profile

The exact identification of the consumer's charge profile will facilitate the determination of the size of our generators. The system under study is supposed to supply a load for domestic use. The power demanded by a particular kind of household is not fixed throughout the year. The time of maximum loading of the energy system by the load varies according to the season as a consequence of the variation of the duration of the day. For our part, we consider that the total load demand for usable electrical energy for lighting, refrigeration, air conditioner, TV, radio, hair dryer, and iron is 6.126kWh/d. The load profile taken into account in our study is for a typical Adrar village household. Figure 6 illustrates the monthly electrical energy demand.

Fig. 6. Monthly load profile.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to find the optimum design of the hybrid system (PV/wind/battery), the proposed algorithm is implemented using Matlab/Simulink. The optimal sizing results for the desired loss of LPSP of 5% in both cases of optimization are presented in the following paragraphs. The fitness function is defined as the minimum cost of electricity produced by the hybrid system. In the case of a single-objective optimization using the PSO and GA optimization algorithms, we have considered the following parameters:

- Lower and upper limits of decision variables:

$$S_{pvmin} < S_{pv} < S_{pvmax} \quad (20)$$

$$S_{wmin} < S_w < S_{wmax} \quad (21)$$

$$C_{bmin} < C_b < C_{bmax} \quad (22)$$

where $S_{pvmin}=1m^2$, $S_{pvmax}=12m^2$, $S_{wmin}=1m^2$, $S_{wmax}=12m^2$, $C_{bmin}=150Ah$, $C_{bmax}=200Ah$

- Maximum probability of dissatisfaction of the tolerated demand LPSP <5.

The sizing results using PSO algorithm for different value of tolerated LPSP are given on Table II.

TABLE II. PSO RESULTS

LPSP	Spv	Sw	Cb	LPSP	Cost \$/kwh*10 ⁻¹
<2	7.45	8.91	155.2	1.99	2.70
<3	6.50	8.47	154	2.99	2.47
<4	6.04	7.76	150	3.97	2.44
<5	6.03	6.63	150	4.95	2.74

To validate the optimization method and ensure the good convergence of the algorithm, we applied another optimization algorithm, the GA. The results are shown in Figure 6. They show that the obtained solution is indeed in the optimal zone. The solution was obtained at the 40th iteration starting from the initial conditions after 80 evaluations of the objective function. The simulation results given by the GA algorithm are summarized in the Table III for LPSP <5.

Fig. 7. GA convergence.

TABLE III. GA RESULTS

LPSP	Spv	Swt	Cb	LPSP	Cost \$/kwh *10 ⁻¹
<2	8.88	6.11	166	1.96	2.62
<3	8.68	5.59	156.74	2.63	2.42
<4	6.9	6.4	154	3.86	2.66
<5	6.7	5.57	153.15	4.98	2.34

The simulation results show that the cost, the size of the generators (PV, wind), and the battery capacity depend on the desired LPSP. They are important for low LPSP values. In view of establishing optimal system dimensioning, another parameter was proposed, which allows the estimation of the rate of aging of the battery for each configuration.

VII. CALCULATION OF THE NUMBER OF CYCLES ACCORDING TO THE DEPTH OF DISCHARGE

The study is based on the mathematical model of a GEL VRLA SOLAR type plate battery given by [26, 27]:

$$N_{c(DOD)} = 12850e^{-(9.738 \cdot DOD)} + 3210e^{-(1.429 \cdot DOD)} \quad (23)$$

To extract the number of cycles (NC) and the corresponding DOD, the Rain flow algorithm has been applied to the SOC of our system .

A. Calculation of Aging

The aging rate per cycle ($A_{r/c(DOD)}$) is calculated based on the life cycle of the battery and the DOD. The expression is written in the following form [26, 27]:

$$A_{r/c(DOD)} = \frac{1}{N_{c(DOD)}} \quad (24)$$

B. Simulation Results

TABLE IV. PSO/GA RESULTS

LPSP	PSO		GA	
	AR %	AR (year)	AR %	AR (year)
<2	6.11	16.36	8.07	12.39
<3	7.47	13.38	8.80	11.36
<4	7.39	13.53	7.73	12.92
<5	8.08	12.38	9.12	10.96

In our case and for a LPSP $\cong 5$ we choose the results given by the PSO algorithm which gives a lifetime of 12.38 years and an aging rate of 8.08%. The surface of PV panels installed was $A_{pv}=6.03m^2$, the surface swept by the rotor of the wind turbine was $A_{wt}=6.63 m^2$, and the storage capacity was $C_b=150Ah$. To see the effectiveness of the optimal result found, we present the SOC of the batteries during the year in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. SOC vs time.

This curve shows the complete exploitation of the batteries in the unfavorable period. The wind energy produced is equal to 2471.9KW per year, i.e. 8.58W per hour on average, which represents 56% of the energy demanded by the consumer. The PV energy produced by the panels is equal to 1760.4kW. Comparing to the energy demanded (4386.6kW per year), we find that there is an excess energy at an annual level. The latter is explained by the random nature of the renewable energy sources.

Fig. 9. The new SOC.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Given the geographical location, the nature of the terrain and the duration of the sunshine, Algeria is a most suitable country for the production of renewable energy. The work presented in this article concerns the production of electricity from a hybrid system (PV/wind) with a completely autonomous storage system to supply the households of an isolated village in the Adrar region of southern Algeria. The objective was to maintain a high level of reliability with a minimum cost thanks to the optimal dimensioning of the hybrid system for a load and a given probability of energy loss under the criteria of a minimum ecological and economic cost of the system and low battery aging rate. Optimal dimensions of the PV module and the wind turbine as well as the capacity of the battery were calculated after the modeling of the different components of the system and calculating the hourly power produced by the aerogenerator and by the PV generator for an analysis period of one year at the Adrar under Matlab/Simulink.

To validate the simulation results, a comparative study was made between the two optimization algorithms, PSO and GA. The obtained simulation and optimization results show that the chosen methods give good estimates of the desired reliability criterion (LPSP), low EC and TNPC, and low battery aging rate.

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An Evaluation of Cost Optimization Strategies for BRT Projects in Pakistan

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Abstract-In developing countries like Pakistan, economic instability, improper planning, non-optimal design, delays in construction, and unsustainability during the operations of transportation megaprojects cause an unnecessary burden on the national exchequer. Recently, several Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) projects have been initiated in Pakistan. The detailed evaluation of the cost and capacity of BRT projects in Pakistan revealed that their cost could have been optimized. This research evaluated the first BRT project in Karachi for potential cost optimization through proper alignment of the BRT. One of the major segments of the Green-Line BRT from Surjani to Nagan was evaluated, which is presently designed as an elevated section. Other possible options such as curb-side, two-way side, and median alignments were explored in detail. The study showed that the cost of this section could have been reduced from the existing USD 75 million to USD 61 million by providing a two-way side aligned or curb-side aligned BRT infrastructure without affecting existing capacity. This case study shows that it is necessary to critically evaluate all the possible options while planning and designing transportation megaprojects.

Keywords-public transport; mass transit; transportation economics; sustainable transport; BRT Capacity

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Bank, more than 50% of the world's population lives in urban areas, and it is predicted that it would increase to 68% by 2050 [1]. Rapid urbanization has become one of the major global challenges, resulting in population influx and urban sprawl. Urban sprawl and population growth cause an increase in travel demand and urban mobility [2, 3]. The major problems associated with the high demand for mobility are: traffic congestion, economic loss, travel time increase, fuel consumption, and air pollution [4-6]. Short-term solutions to these problems include increasing the existing capacity of the road network by introducing new

infrastructure facilities such as flyovers, underpasses, more lanes, and improving traffic controls. Long-term solutions include changes in land-use patterns, introducing new modes into the transportation network, and increasing the share of public mass transit systems [7]. Among the existing solutions, mass transport is considered one of the key solutions for the provision of high mobility and for the resolution of traffic problems by providing reliable, affordable, and sustainable means of transportation [8]. The selection of an appropriate mass transport system depends on the demands and characteristics of the city [9].

Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) is considered one of the optimal solutions due to its ability to deal with high demand at a relatively low cost compared to other mass transit solutions, such as rail transport [10]. BRT was first introduced in Curitiba, Brazil with a 9Km long corridor in 1972 [11], and is now spread at approximately 74Km serving around 721,500 passengers per day [12, 13]. The TransMilenio Bogota BRT is considered one of the most efficient systems in the world with a capacity of 49,000 passengers per hour per direction (pphd) through 117 trunk corridors and is accessible by 107 feeder routes that serve more than 2.2 million passengers per day [12, 14-15]. The efficient BRT experience in Latin America has been introduced to many other countries. Transport planning in megacities of many developing countries focuses on facilitating the use of private vehicles by increasing road network capacity [16]. Therefore, the incorporation of transit systems causes various land-use problems. The need for extensive planning for BRT systems was discussed in [15], as BRTs may fail due to fewer passengers and higher operating costs.

Pakistan is the fifth most populous country, having approximately 39.5% of the total 212 million population living in urban areas [17]. The inadequate and poor provision of public transportation in megacities of Pakistan urges each

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individual to own a private vehicle to meet his travel needs, causing an increase in private vehicle ownership [18-19]. One of the main reasons for the degradation of public transport in most developing countries is the continued investment in road infrastructure while ignoring the improvement in the mass transport systems [20]. Only commuters from low-income groups depend on public transport to fulfill their travel needs. Therefore, there is a need to improve the existing public transport system in Pakistan and other developing countries [18, 21]. In 2013, Pakistan initiated the first BRT project in Lahore, followed by many other similar projects in other cities, including the Islamabad-Rawalpindi Metrobus, Multan Metro, Karachi Metrobus, and Peshawar Metro. Many BRT projects started without considering their future impacts on the economic conditions of the country [17, 22-23]. In 2020, the Orange-Line transit project built in Lahore consumed Rs 1.9 billion in electricity to remain operational, which is a huge investment for a developing country [24].

It has been observed that various mass transit projects are executed without considering the cost optimization aspect. This study briefly analyzes the Global BRT data to evaluate the performance of BRTs in Pakistan. Furthermore, a detailed evaluation of a selected elevated segment of the first BRT project constructed in Karachi, Pakistan, was performed. This study also examines other possible alignments of the selected segment, including median, curb-side, and two-way side alignments. The cost and capacity of each of the proposed alignments were estimated to show that the total infrastructure cost of the BRT project could be significantly reduced by considering other alternatives without compromising the capacity of the corridor.

II. GLOBAL DATA AND BRT IN PAKISTAN

Global BRT data is a public platform developed by BRT+CoE and EMBARQ WRI Brazil, in collaboration with ITDP [12]. The database consists of more than 300 data points from different cities. However, data from only 50 BRT corridors are considered for analysis in this study due to the unavailability of the BRT cost or peak load parameters. The Global BRT data provide information on peak load, which is the maximum number of passengers traveling in buses per hour along the most loaded segment, and therefore can be considered as the transport capacity of the BRT [12, 25]. Based on this data, about 62% of the BRT corridors around the world are median-aligned while only 7% have a grade-separated row.

Figure 1 relates the peak load served (capacity) with the infrastructure cost incurred in the construction of BRT corridors around the world. The most used BRT alignment is median, achieving 49,000 pphpd capacity in Bogota, Colombia, and constructed with USD 12.7 million per Km. Around USD 46 million per Km was invested for the grade-separated corridor in Nagoya, Japan, serving a peak load of 750 pphpd. Figure 1 shows the data points of the BRT projects around the world, including Pakistan. The 27 Km route of the Lahore Metrobus was constructed with an infrastructural cost of USD 11.5 million per Km and serves 10,000 pphpd. This BRT model was based on Istanbul Metrobus, serving around 30,000 pphpd and constructed with USD 9 million per Km. A 23 Km long BRT corridor was constructed to connect the twin cities of

Islamabad and Rawalpindi (Islamabad-Rawalpindi Metrobus), being grade-separated, and median busways constructed with an infrastructure cost of USD 20 million per Km and serving only 2,100 pphpd.

Fig. 1. Comparison of cost and capacity of corridors around the globe.

The third operational BRT project in Pakistan was constructed in Peshawar for USD 22 million per Km and serves 15000 pphpd [26-27]. The Green-Line project in Karachi costs US \$13.8 million per Km and has a capacity of 9708 pphpd. The detailed estimation of the Green-Line BRT capacity and its cost are examined below. The higher capital investment for the construction of BRT corridors in Pakistan shows less efficient planning, which is reflected in the higher construction cost to serve comparatively fewer commuters. This is a critical concern, especially for the developing countries where the limited budget must be efficiently utilized in development and construction. Most of these projects were built by acquiring loans from various funding agencies. The higher project cost increases the debt burden and reduces the resources that could have been used in human development. Furthermore, a significant amount is also consumed for BRT operations and providing subsidized fares to commuters [12, 22, 28].

III. TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE IN KARACHI

Karachi is a commercial and economic hub having a population of more than 20 million and generates up to 25% of Pakistan's GDP [29-30]. The increase in population and the expansion of the city without sustainable means of transportation have increased traffic congestion [30]. The traffic count on four main arterials conducted in Karachi shows that only 15% of commuters travel in public transport, while the remaining 85% of commuters travel using private vehicles [31]. The poor condition of the public transport systems has led commuters to use private vehicles. This causes a significant increase in traffic on the main arterials, leading to congestion, accidents, and pollution [32]. The Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) proposed five rapid transit lines (Green, Yellow, Orange, Blue, and Red) and the rehabilitation of the Karachi Circular Railway to improve transportation [33]. The construction of the Green-Line BRT corridor started in February 2016 with estimated completion by December 2017.

However, due to various reasons, the BRT started its operations in January 2022.

IV. EVALUATION OF GREEN-LINE BRT CORRIDOR

A detailed survey was conducted to examine the layout and infrastructural characteristics of the existing Green-Line BRT. This section describes the evaluation based on the route survey, capacity, and cost estimate of the existing Green-Line BRT corridor.

A. Route Survey and Layout

The Green-Line BRT route extends from Surjani to the Municipal Park. The Green Line will travel from Surjani passing famous landmarks including Nagan, AO Clock Tower, Lasbela Chowk, Gurumandir, and Numais. The route is approximately 17.8 Km, about 58% of the corridor is grade-separated, and the remaining 42% has physically separated median aligned bus lanes. It consists of 21 stations, out of which 12 are grade-separated (2 stopping bays), and 9 at-grade (3 stopping bays). A fleet of 80 buses was obtained, each with a capacity of 160 passengers per vehicle [34]. Figure 2 shows the details of the alignment of the route and the locations of the bus stations on a GIS map.

Fig. 2. Green Line route map with stations (left) and intersections (right).

B. Capacity Estimation

Capacity is the maximum number of passengers that can be carried past a point in a direction, during a given period along the critical section of the BRT under specific operating conditions [35]. This research uses the BRT Planning Guide for the estimation of the corridor capacity along with the saturation level for the Green-Line BRT route [36]. Equation (1) was used to calculate the capacity in pphpd, containing the main attributes that affect the capacity of BRT systems including the capacity of the vehicle, load factor, frequency, and the number of stopping bays provided. The load factor of 0.9 is used considering the peak period conditions. The cycle time for a complete round trip is calculated by estimating the journey time from the origin to the destination. Equation (2) was used to determine the headway in minutes between two consecutive buses. Using headway, the service frequency for operations is

calculated by (3). Equation (4) is used to determine the saturation level of the Green-Line BRT corridor from the estimated frequency.

$$Cc = Cb * LF * SF * Nsp \quad (1)$$

$$H = \frac{Tc}{Fo} \quad (2)$$

$$SF = \frac{60}{H} \quad (3)$$

$$X = \frac{SF * Td}{3600} \quad (4)$$

Table I shows the estimation of possible capacities that can be achieved in the infrastructure constructed for Green-Line with two and three stopping bays along with the corresponding saturation levels. The optimum saturation level is considered between 0.3 to 0.6 for BRT systems. A saturation level greater than 0.6 creates a risk of congestion and may lead to crowding of buses at stations [36]. The maximum possible crushing capacity for the Green-Line can be 24270 pphpd with a fleet size of 200 buses, while the optimal capacity achieved for its operations with smooth flows is 14562 pphpd.

TABLE I. VARIOUS POSSIBLE OPERATIONS FOR THE GREEN-LINE BRT CORRIDOR

Fleet Size	Headway (min)	Frequency (bph)	Saturation level	Corridor capacity (pphd)
80	0.89	67.4	0.37	9708
100	0.71	84.3	0.47	12135
120	0.59	101.1	0.56	14562
140	0.51	118.0	0.66	16989
160	0.45	134.8	0.75	19416
180	0.40	151.7	0.84	21843
200	0.36	168.5	0.94	24270

C. Existing Infrastructural Cost

The critical elements that increase the infrastructural cost for BRTs are the design type of running ways and stations. The cost per unit of elements in the Green-Line BRT corridor was obtained from the Sindh Infrastructural Development Corporation Limited (SIDCL), which was the authority responsible for the execution of this project. The total cost for the existing alignment was estimated based on the cost per unit in PKR million per Km at 552 and 203 for elevated and at-grade busways respectively. For one elevated and at-grade station, the cost was PKR 288 and 141 million respectively.

TABLE II. COST ESTIMATION OF EXISTING ALIGNMENT

Section	Surjani to Nagan		Nagan to Golimar		Golimar to Gurumandir	
	Elevated	At-grade	Elevated	At-grade	Elevated	At-grade
Length (Km)	5.86	0.51	1.66	6.6	2.8	0.4
Cost PKR million per Km	3235	104	916	1340	1546	81
Stations	8	2	-	7	4	-
Cost PKR million (each station)	2304	282	-	987	1152	-
Cost PKR million per Km	930		393		868	
Cost USD million per Km	5.85		2.47		5.46	

Table II shows the complete cost estimation for the Green-Line BRT corridor. The segment between Surjani and Nagan was the most expensive segment, constructed for USD 5.85 million per Km. The grade-separated segment is 5.86Km long, having 10 stations along the segment. The per Km cost of the Nagan-Golimar corridor was estimated at approximately USD 2.47 million, which is 2.3 times lesser than the unit cost of the elevated segment. The unit cost of the Golimar-Gurumandir segment was USD 5.46 million per Km.

V. OPTIMIZATION OF GREEN-LINE BRT ROUTE

The cost estimation and the evaluation of various BRT segments shown in Table II indicate that there is a potential to reduce infrastructure costs without compromising capacity. The various options to reduce the cost of the Green BRT line infrastructure are explored below.

A. Gurumandir- Golimar

The existing route length of this segment is 3.2 Km with 2.8 Km elevated and 0.4 Km as an at-grade median corridor. The cross-section of the existing alignment of the Green BRT line for the Gurumandir-Golimar segment is shown in Figure 3. Around 90% of the width of the segment is less than 40 m while 10% of the width is more than 40 m, showing the possible difficulty of constructing an at-grade alignment for this segment. Figure 3 shows the median aligned corridor as evaluated for this segment. The segment may become more congested for general traffic if the BRT is constructed in a median alignment. An at-grade busway along this corridor would significantly reduce the width of the carriageway for general traffic from 11 to 7.3m. The reduction in the right-of-way can truncate the number of lanes for general traffic, causing traffic pressure with a greater possibility of traffic congestion.

Fig. 3. Gurumandir-Golimar cross-section with existing elevated (top) and proposed median (bottom) alignment.

B. Golimar-Nagan

The existing route length for this segment is 8.26 Km, with 6.6 Km median aligned and 1.66 Km elevated section. All the intersections in this segment are grade-separated and the

remaining segment is at-grade median aligned. Hence, the existing design of this section was evaluated as a cost-optimal design and no further optimization was possible without compromising capacity.

C. Nagan-Surjani

The existing Nagan-Surjani segment has a route length of 6.37 Km, with 5.86 Km elevated and 0.51 Km median aligned. Around 84% of the segment width is between 81-100m, 12% is less than 80m, and 4% is more than 100m, showing a clear possibility of construction for an at-grade alignment along the segment. Figure 4 shows the cross-section of the existing alignment. The median alignment was considered difficult to be constructed by authorities because of the 5-8 m pylons (electric poles) on the median of the roadway. The two-way side and curb-side alignment possibilities were studied for this segment. The available right-of-way for the Nagan-Surjani segment is approximately 63 m. The available space provides an opportunity for its utilization as a BRT corridor. Therefore, it is possible to construct two-way and curb-side aligned corridors for this segment. The two-way side aligned right-of-way for BRT would be a feasible option to deal with the pylons and would not reduce the width of lanes for general traffic. One major benefit of this alignment could be that it would increase accessibility for one side of commuters. The possibility of providing a curb-side alignment is also shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Nagan-Surjani cross-section with existing elevated alignment (top), proposed two-way side alignment (middle), and curb-side (bottom).

D. Existing and Proposed Intersections

The existing infrastructure of BRT has grade separation at intersections. The intersection on the BRT route must be

treated so that its capacity is not affected at the intersections. The two possible ways to deal with intersections, while maintaining sufficient capacity of the corridor, could be signalized intersections with bus priority and grade separation. Signalized intersections may cause delays to the general traffic as well as the BRT. Therefore, it is proposed that all major intersections should be grade-separated along the corridor, leaving its capacity unaffected.

VI. PROPOSED OPTIMAL ALIGNMENTS

The Surjani-Nagan segment was identified as one of the most expensive segments of the Green BRT line. The detailed evaluation of the corridor also showed that this is the segment with the highest potential for cost optimization. Table III shows that providing an at-grade carriageway for this segment could reduce its cost by USD 14.36 million. The possible cost saving by providing a median-aligned busway in the section of Gurumandir to Golimar could be USD 6.69 million. However, reducing the right-of-way for general traffic could adversely affect the travel time and speed of other vehicles.

TABLE III. ALTERNATIVE BRT BUSWAYS

Parameters	Nagan to Surjani		Gurumandir to Golimar	
	Existing	Curb-side/ Two-way side	Existing	Median
Length elevated (km)	5.86	2.3	2.8	1.02
Length at-grade (km)	0.51	4.01	0.4	2.17
No of elevated stations	8	1	4	1
No of at-grade Stations	2	9	-	3
Intersections	Elevated	Elevated	Elevated	Elevated
Accessibility	Low	Medium	Low	Low
Effect on general traffic carriageway	-	-	-	Reduction in ROW
Effect on capacity	-	-	-	-
Cost (USD Million)	37.26	22.9	17.47	10.78

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF EXISTING WITH OPTIMAL ALIGNMENTS

	Existing Green-Line	Alternative 1/2 Green-Line	Alternative 3 Green-Line
Surjani-Nagan	Elevated	Curbside/Two- way side aligned Green-Line	Curbside/Two- way side aligned Green-Line
Nagan-Golimar	Median	Median	Median
Golimar- Gurumandir	Elevated	Elevated	Median
Percent elevated	58	38	28
Percent at-grade	42	62	72
Cost (USD million)	75.12	61.02	54.33

The two-way side-aligned busways from Surjani to Nagan were the most suitable and feasible. They can significantly decrease cost without affecting capacity along with making BRT stations more accessible to users. Although the curbside alignment has an almost similar cost, it may not be feasible, as the transition from the curbside alignment (Surjani-Nagan) to the median aligned segments (Nagan-Golimar) may increase cost. Two elevated flyovers are required to join both sides of the curb-aligned to the median, but for the two-way side alignment, it could be possible to use a one-sided elevated

flyover. Table IV shows the difference in cost between the existing and proposed alignments. Increasing the proportion of elevated segments in the corridor causes a significant increase in cost. As the existing corridor is 58% elevated, it increased the total cost by USD 14.1 million in comparison with the proposed two-way side alignment.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Several BRT projects have been initiated in Pakistan during the past decade. The evaluation of the cost of BRT projects in Pakistan and its comparison with BRT systems around the world reveal that those constructed in Pakistan offer comparatively lower capacity and utilization. Due to high construction and operational cost and unjustified delays, the economic impact of the BRT projects has increased. Uneven city planning and local conditions often cause delays in the construction of these megaprojects. Due to the high demand for sustainable and affordable means of transport, the need for mass transit projects is also increasing in a developing country like Pakistan.

Green-Line was the first BRT project started in Karachi. Construction of the infrastructure for the Green-Line BRT was delayed and caused a significant increase in its initial estimated cost of PKR 25 billion. This research investigated this project in detail to evaluate the potential for cost optimization. The proposed Green-Line BRT alignment consists of 58% of elevated sections, which have the highest cost among all possible alignments. Detailed field surveys were conducted to examine the feasibility of other possible alignments, such as curb-side, median-aligned, and two-way side aligned BRT infrastructure. The capacity of each of the proposed alignments was also evaluated, and it was concluded that by designing the Nagan-Surjani segment using a two-way side aligned option, the existing cost of this section could have been reduced from USD 75 million to USD 61 million, which is a 20% saving on the original cost without compromising the system's capacity. Planners and policymakers should investigate the alternatives in detail to optimize the cost. The efficient at-grade BRT with the same capacity is still an option for developing countries where the primary need is to invest resources most optimally. This solution could also benefit the government to consider various strategies to alleviate the huge investments in the construction of mega transportation projects.

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An Investigation of Magnetic Field Influence in Underground High Voltage Cable Shields

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Abstract-Magnetic fields and the shielding efficiency of the shields of underground high voltage cables are studied in this paper regarding several shielding configurations and materials. Shielding efficiency and magnetic fields are computed for shields with the same mesh but from different shielding materials, such as aluminum, ferrite, metal, and steel. In order to get the best shield configuration depending on the source characteristics and the material, a conducting ferromagnetic region with various thickness values is considered as shielding. A finite element model is introduced to investigate the influence of the parameters of magnetic fields and the shielding efficiency of underground high voltage cables. Furthermore, the reduction of the magnetic fields with or without shieldings is also presented. The developed method is performed with the magnetic vector potential formulations and validated on a practical problem.

Keywords-shielding efficiency; magnetic fields; eddy currents; underground power cables; finite element technique

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic fields cause a considerable disturbance of the operation and accuracy of sensitive electrical and electronic devices [1], while they pose an important issue to public health [2-5]. New regulations involving a drastic reduction of the allowable limits of exposure have been developed. Unfortunately, the conclusion for that problem is not clear and, even if it is, it is still disputed. It cannot be concluded surely that there is no relation between magnetic fields and certain

diseases. In addition, a lot of shield configurations can be used as magnetic shielding for underground high voltage cables such as open and closed shield structures. As proposed in [6], the use of thick and large flat sheets above underground high voltage cables gives a good shielding performance. This is also right for a minimal distance between shields and high voltage cables. In addition, good shielding efficiency is demonstrated for closed shield structures [7-9]. In [10], a unimoment method has been proposed to analyze the magnetic shielding of a source within a steel pipe made of ferromagnetic material. In [11], an analytic method has been developed for computing the losses in steel casting with an arbitrary cable arrangement. In [12], the power losses have been computed following the statistical theory. For the above reasons, remarkable efforts have been devoted to research activities aiming at studying suitable techniques to achieve the desired reduction of the magnetic fields generated by electrical systems. In many cases this can be done by simple and effective solutions that do not mean costly additional investments.

Magnetic Fields (MFs) can be generated by high voltage transmission underground cables. Several methods have been applied to compute the MFs. They are generally categorized as internal and external shielding methods [12-15]. Although the obtained results from these methods are successful to a great degree in some cases, these techniques have also some drawbacks.

In this paper, the influence of the parameters of the MFs on the shieldings covering underground high voltage cables with different cases of several configurations have been analyzed and simulated via finite element method. This will be presented with the magnetic vector potential formulations to compute and investigate the influence of the MFs and the reduction factor in the proximities due to the field sources. The developed method is validated on the practical problem.

II. MAGNETIC SHIELDING PROBLEMS

A. Shielding Problems of Underground High Voltage Cables

Shielding is the most efficient solution to reduce the MFs generated by underground high voltage cables. Two different shields can be considered: open shields and close shields. The open shield consists of a cover (flat) plate located above the high voltage cables (Figure 1), and the close shield consists of a cable tray surrounding the cables (Figure 1). The second case is more expensive than the first case, which is usually employed to reconfigure existing systems. The conductive materials for both cases can be made of aluminum, copper, or ferromagnetic materials. This selection is very important, because each material provides different shielding. There are two scenarios: If the shielding is a high conductive material, the reduction of the field is based on eddy current cancellation. This means that the eddy currents are induced in the conductive plate due to the MFs that partially cancel those of the source as pointed out in Figure 2. If the shielding is a material with high permeability, the mechanism is known as flux shunting. This means that the magnetic flux density generated by the source is diverted into the magnetic material and away from the region to be shielded, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 1. (a) Open shield, (b) close shield.

Fig. 2. Eddy current distributions in a cover plate.

These two scenarios are characterized by different Boundary Conditions (BCs) which have to be analyzed in each configuration. From the above analysis, it is clear that it is not important to decide which shielding technique is the best to

mitigate the field caused by an underground high voltage cable, because the shielding effectiveness depends on the configuration of the cables, with issues such as the distance between the cables and the shield, the thickness and width of the plate, etc. Depending on the different properties of materials, the results obtained with magnetic materials differ from those obtained using conductive materials. The close shield usually gives a high field reduction near the source, whereas the open shield provides better results far from it. This is also strongly influenced by the arrangements (locations) of the cables. High conductive open shields are suitable for flat lines. However, for the vertical lines, the open shields made of ferromagnetic materials perform better [1]. Moreover, it should be noted that magnetic materials are usually more expensive than conductive materials. For the above reasons, a full study/analysis of the parameters involved directly with the effectiveness of shields is presented in this paper to give a selection of suitable configurations for electrical systems. The considered shield parameters are:

Fig. 3. Flux shunting shielding.

- Thickness and profile of the plate.
- Value of magnetic permeability and electric conductivity.
- Different types of materials used.
- The distance from the source and the relationship with the dimensional characteristics of the source.

B. Canonical Magnetodynamic Problems

A canonical magnetodynamic problem is defined in a domain Ω , with boundary $\partial\Omega = \Gamma = \Gamma_h \cup \Gamma_e$. The Maxwell's equations considered in the frequency domain and behavior laws are written in Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 [16-18]:

$$\text{curl } \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J}_s, \text{curl } \mathbf{E} = -j\omega \mathbf{B}, \text{div } \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (1a-b-c)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{J} = \sigma\mathbf{E} \quad (2a-b)$$

where \mathbf{H} is the magnetic field (A/m), \mathbf{B} is the magnetic flux density (T), \mathbf{E} is the electric field (V/m), \mathbf{J}_s is the current density (A/m^2), μ and σ are the relative permeability and the electric conductivity (S/m).

The BCs defined on Γ are expressed as:

$$\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{H}|_{\Gamma_h} = \mathbf{j}_f, \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{B}|_{\Gamma_e} = \mathbf{b}_f \quad (3a-b)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit normal exterior to Ω , with $\Omega = \Omega_c \cup \Omega_c^c$. The domains Ω_c and Ω_c^c are respectively the conducting and non-conducting regions. Equations (1a) and (1b) are solved

with BCs taking the tangential component of \mathbf{H} in (3a) and the normal component of \mathbf{B} in (3) into account.

The fields \mathbf{H} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{E} , and \mathbf{J} are defined to satisfy Tonti's diagram [9]. This means that $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbf{H}_h(\text{curl}; \Omega)$, $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbf{H}_e(\text{curl}; \Omega)$, $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbf{H}(\text{div}; \Omega)$, and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbf{H}_e(\text{div}; \Omega)$, where $\mathbf{H}_h(\text{curl}; \Omega)$ and $\mathbf{H}_e(\text{div}; \Omega)$ are function spaces containing the BCs and the fields defined on Γ_h and Γ_e of the studied domain Ω . The fields \mathbf{j}_f and \mathbf{b}_f in (3) are generally equal to zero for classical homogeneous BCs. The field \mathbf{b} in (1c) is derived from a vector potential \mathbf{a} such that:

$$\mathbf{b} = \text{curl } \mathbf{a} \quad (4)$$

By combining (4) with (1b), we have $\text{curl}(\mathbf{e} + \partial_t \mathbf{a}) = 0$, which leads to the definition of an electric scalar potential v such that:

$$\mathbf{e} = -\partial_t \mathbf{a} - \text{grad } v \quad (5)$$

C. Magnetic Vector Potential Weak Formulations

Based on the weak form of Ampere's law (1a), the weak formulation of magnetic problems is written as [17-21]:

$$(\mu^{-1} \mathbf{b}, \text{curl } \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega} - (\sigma \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega_c} + \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{a}' \rangle_{\Gamma} = (\mathbf{j}_s, \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega_s}, \quad \forall \mathbf{a}' \in \mathbf{H}_e^0(\text{curl}, \Omega) \quad (6)$$

By substituting the magnetic flux density \mathbf{b} from (4) and the electrical field \mathbf{e} from (5) into (6), we get:

$$(\mu^{-1} \text{curl } \mathbf{a}, \text{curl } \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega} + (\sigma \partial_t \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega_c} + (\sigma \text{grad } v, \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega} + \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{a}' \rangle_{\Gamma_h} = (\mathbf{j}_s, \mathbf{a}')_{\Omega_s}, \quad \forall \mathbf{a}' \in \mathbf{H}_e^0(\text{curl}, \Omega) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_e^0(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ is a function space defined on Ω containing the basis functions for \mathbf{a} as well as for the test function \mathbf{a}' . Notations (\cdot, \cdot) and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ are respectively a volume integral and a surface integral of the product of their vector field arguments.

The surface integral term $\langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{a}' \rangle_{\Gamma_h}$ on Γ_h in (8) accounts for natural BCs that can be locally specified. This is the case for a homogeneous Neumann BC, e.g. imposing a symmetry condition of "zero crossing current", i.e.:

$$\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{h}|_{\Gamma_h} = 0 \Rightarrow \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{b}|_{\Gamma_h} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{j}|_{\Gamma_h} = 0 \quad (9)$$

III. PRACTICAL TEST

The test problem considered for the 2D model is a shielding problem with different configurations.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF SHIELDING MATERIALS [5, 8]

Material	Conductivity (σ) S/m	Relative permeability (μ_r)
Aluminum	3.8×10^7	1
Steel	10^7	500
Metal	1.64×10^6	15,120
Ferrite	2	10,000

Three different cases of a flat arrangement of the underground high voltage cables were considered (Figure 4): (a) a cover plate shield (horizontal plate shield) located above the three conductors, (b) a reverse- U shield, and (c) close

shield surrounding the three conductors. In all cases, the three conductors are supplied by balanced currents of 100A at a frequency of 50Hz and Voltage of 132kV. Cable depth is fixed at 80cm, with a separation between cables of 25cm and conductor diameters of 20mm.

Fig. 4. Geometry of high voltage cables with different configurations: (a) no shield, (b) reverse U-shield, and (c) close shield.

Fig. 5. Field lines in cover shield of (a) aluminum and (b) ferrite.

The influence of geometrical parameters of the high voltage cables and the shield in the field generated at 1m height above the ground has been studied. The influence in the shielding factor (also called the reduction factor) can be defined as:

$$RF = \frac{B_0}{B} \quad (10)$$

where B_0 is the root mean square (RMS) value of the field density without the shield, and B is the RMS value of the field with the shield in place. By another way, SF can be considered as a position function of the shield. The biggest the SF is, the more significant the magnetic field reduction. The properties of shielding materials are given in Table I [5, 8].

Fig. 6. Magnetic flux density distribution for different material shieldings (horizontal shield).

Fig. 7. Reduction factor process with different thicknesses.

Two different cases are now considered for testing: Without and with cover shield. The distribution of the field lines for the different material shields is presented in Figure 5, where field lines can divert in the proximity of the cover shielding due to the different materials. The value of magnetic flux density along the shield at 1m above the ground is pointed in Figure 6, for the cases without shield and with shields from different materials (aluminum, ferrite and steel). From the obtained results, it can be seen that the magnetic flux density distribution is very high for the cases without shield and with aluminum shield in comparison with the cases of the ferrite and steel shields, because the massive fields mostly focus on these materials with a little flux leakage to the surrounding air. This means that the magnetic inductions are almost refracted into these shields. The influence of magnetic flux density distribution in the final cost of the cover shield depends on its thickness. Thus, there are several cases of thickness values

from 1mm to 10mm for the considered materials which have to be examined. The relation of the RF with the shield thickness given in (10) is indicated in Figure 7. It should be noted that the value increases when the thicknesses varies from 1 to 5mm for ferrite materials. From 6 to 10mm, the value of RF reduces noticeably. The influence of steel thickness increases noticeably from 1 to 10mm, while the thickness influence of aluminum material can be ignored. For the case of reverse-U shield, the field lines of aluminum and ferrite are illustrated in Figure 8. The process of RF with different materials and thicknesses is presented in Figure 9. The RF for steel, metal, and ferrite increases noticeably with thickness from 1 to 10mm as shown in Figure 10. On the other hand, the influence of the aluminum shielding is weak and not worth considering. Similarly with Figure 6, the reluctances of ferrite and steel are smaller than the air's (no shield case). Due to this, massive fields mostly focus on these materials with a little leakage flux.

Fig. 8. Field lines in reverse-U shield of (a) aluminum, (b) ferrite.

Fig. 9. Magnetic flux density distributions with different material shieldings (reverse-U shield).

Regarding the closed shield, the field lines on magnetic vector potentials are presented in Figure 11. The magnetic flux density distribution with different material shieldings is shown in Figure 12. It can be seen that the results of metal and ferrite materials are improved, getting similar to those obtained from the case of reverse-U shield (Figure 9).

Fig. 10. Process of RF with different materials in reverse-U shield.

Fig. 11. Field lines in closed shield of (a) aluminum, (b) ferrite.

Fig. 12. RF with different material shieldings (closed shield).

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the influence of magnetic flux density distribution on shielding efficiency for underground high voltage cables has been investigated with the magnetic vector potential formulations for several shielding configurations. Regarding the shielding materials, the obtained results illustrated the influence of magnetic fields at 1m for the cases without shield and with shields from different materials, and the evolution of RF with thickness. High RF can be also obtained by increasing shield thickness when open shield made of high conductive materials is used. In the case of ferromagnetic materials, increasing shield thickness has a low

effect. As a result, we can say that shield size has a relatively small effect on shielding: a larger shield decreases slightly the shielding efficiency of ferromagnetic shields, and increases it for shields made from aluminum. In fact, with increasing shield thickness, the shielding effectiveness improves without causing higher losses. In particular, it should be noted that if the best shielding effectiveness for a given thickness is required, a high permeability material is preferred. If a low cost per meter of shield is required, a ferromagnetic grade with lower permeability can be used. If low magnetic losses in the shield are important, aluminum is preferred.

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GIS-Based Analysis of a Rainwater Harvesting System in the Multipurpose Hall of Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science, and Technology

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Abstract-Drinking water availability has become a major issue. Rainwater Harvesting Systems (RHSs) amass and store rainwater for future use. In Pakistan, drinking water availability has become a major issue. Rainwater can be used as a constant alternative to clean water resources. Google Earth Pro (GEP) is utilized in this paper to select suitable locations for the installation of RHSs. The decision must not be too excessive, must fit in buildings that have small available space, and must cover the needs of bigger buildings. The required capacity for an RHS to cope with an unusually high water shortage in the study area was calculated using GEP and ArcGIS. The total estimated amount of rainwater harvesting potential during the average annual monsoon period from 2012 to 2021 is 1064.056 m³ from the 13452.05 m² available area from rooftops and plain surfaces. The capacity of storage containers is primarily based on day-to-day spills and breadth.

Keyword-rainwater harvesting system; ArGIS; Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD); Google Earth Pro; potential demand of water

I. INTRODUCTION

A Rainwater Harvesting System (RHS) is an adaptation to climate change that helps improving local livelihoods and conserve water that can be used for future use [1]. In Nawabshah, there is a frightening decline of the available drinking water, making the saving of water essential in order to overcome the present and forthcoming water crisis [2]. A large number of countries rely on RHSs for conserving water due to urbanization and imprudent extraction of drinking water from aquifers [3].

Rainwater Harvesting (RWH) can be defined as catching and storing the excess seasonal runoff and diverting it for domestic and agricultural purposes. This activity has been developed for use in arid and semi-arid regions, in rural or urban settings, and can be used as a primary or secondary water supply [4]. RWH is not a new technique. Humans have been harvesting rainwater for drinking and non-drinking purposes for more than 4000 years [5]. In many places, rooftop rainwater collection is still used to supply water demands. Rainwater can

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be captured as a means of preventing flooding roadways, recharging aquifers, increasing water tables, and meeting the requirements of the growing population [6, 7]. Compared with most unprotected ordinary water sources, drinking rainwater from well-maintained roof catchment typically represents a substantial enchantment [8]. RHSs add safety to the city water supply system in the event of unexpected failures [2, 9].

The main purpose of this study is to determine the possibility of rainwater collection for storage and use at household level. This strategy is advantageous for minimizing groundwater overuse and conserving it, particularly in Nawabshah, where there will be a water-scarcity in the coming years. Therefore, this research study entails a thorough examination of the necessity for and application of rainwater collection in the QUEST Nawabshah multipurpose hall. For the RWH analysis, the Geographical Information System (ArcGIS) and Google Earth Pro (GEP) tools were used. This research work suggests steps to be taken at a local level to deal with the issue of water shortage in communities and at the individual level.

A. General Aspects of Rainwater Harvesting

The RHS mounted to collect rainwater from the roof areas of the three dormitories would be ample for the flushing consumption as 2831m^3 of water that can be amassed annually with a reliability of 93% [9]. The volume of rainwater that can be gathered from a roof, is based on its measurement and texture. The catchment floor will have an effect on the rainwater via the contaminants that might be present on the surface [10, 11]. Furthermore, the groundwater will be recharged with the aid of RWH [8]. Some details about filters used in RHSs, calculations, and the set up price are discussed in [11, 12], where, additionally, the calculation and format of the RWH device was introduced and price analysis was given. Rainfall of high quality via water treatment technologies, such as photovoltaic collector disinfection, is needed to minimize health risks. The manageable of RWH structures on lowering runoff goes with the flow height for households in southern Italy, and simulation outcomes exhibit that, with the aid of the usage of tank-based RHSs, there is a top-notch discount in runoff peak, between 30% and 65%, depending on the dimensions of rainwater tanks [13]. A linear programming method for a single residential housing unit to decide the top-quality rainwater storage tank volume for RWH and storage was established in [14]. A lifecycle cost-benefit model and a nonlinear metaheuristic algorithm to optimize RHSs was presented in [15]. Furthermore, an optimization-based model for the utilization, storage, and distribution of rainwater aiming for cost-efficiency and water saving was proposed in [16]. An analyzed model was used in [17]. This model can analyze the most useful graph variables, price, and overall environmental performance of RHSs, and make comparisons with other models, such as the Aqua Cycle and the Rain Cycle.

B. Potential of Rainwater Harvesting

RWH is the collection of rainwater which can be used for irrigation or to replenish groundwater supplies [12, 15, 18, 19, 22]. As the demand for water for industrial and household usage continues to rise, RWH is becoming increasingly important [19]. It is considered to be a low-cost and a better

option than other strategies for increasing water supply in the near future. Due to the frightening decline of the water table in Nawabshah, conserving water is essential to deal with the existing and upcoming water crisis [15, 18]. It is possible to define RWH as capturing and storing seasonal excess runoff and diverting it for domestic and agricultural use. Creating a rainwater collection system is a simple method for conserving rainwater for future use. The majority of global population will be affected by the global water crisis by 2025 [18]. RWH has become a necessity in the current arid climate. Currently, RWH is an easy solution to unregulated urbanization and rising water demand. RWH is a concept for conserving fresh water and using it for potable and nonpotable applications that has been proven practicable and practical all over the world. It can also be used in Nawabshah to replace the city's diminishing water table, which is quickly dwindling.

C. Treatment Techniques for Rainwater Harvesting

The fundamental categories are heat and UV-based methods, chemical treatment procedures, and bodily elimination operations [19]. Moreover, RWH structures intended for potable use must be screened, settled, filtered, and disinfected before use [20]. The utilization of satellite images and GIS data for particular land-cover classification of rooftops is extremely important for superior city runoff simulation and estimation of the feasibility of rainwater storage and harvesting systems [21]. The reliability of RWH structures for exclusive situations below the local weather conditions is primarily based on the water balance model to find out the most effective rainwater storage tank extent of the RWH structures serving a common six-member family [22, 23]. A daily water stability model of the overall performance of RWH structures under climate change was established in [18]. The set-up of RWH structures comes collectively with a number of direct and indirect fees and benefits [24]. Mass stability methodology, Ripple sketch method, analytical approach, and the sequent height algorithm were used to determine the extent of water. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was utilized to determine which RWH technique was the best for the considered area. AHP can be an effective tool for assessing RWH procedures and structures [25]. Microfinance institutions may play an important role in the spread of domestic RHSs.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Description of the Study Area

The study area, as shown in Figure 1, using an ArcGIS map of the rooftop and the plain surface area surrounding the multipurpose hall building of the Quaid-e-Awam University of Engineering, Science, and Technology (QUEST), Nawabshah, is located on the outskirts of the city, near the airport road, at latitude $26^{\circ}14'9.38''\text{N}$ and longitude $68^{\circ}23'24.24''\text{E}$. The total area of the multipurpose hall building is $11,453.403\text{ft}^2$, while the total area of the university is 457 acres on both sides of the main Sakrand Road.

B. Rainfall Data Collection

The Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD) in Nawabshah collected precipitation data for the city of Nawabshah for 10 years (2012-2021) [26, 27]. In our study

area there is not a particular rain gauge station. So, precipitation data from the PMD station at the airplane terminal of Nawabshah (OPNH-417490) were utilized to assess the water volume. Only the monsoon period is considered in this study. As presented in Table I, the annual monsoon rainfall data (2012 to 2021) and the minimum to maximum total monsoon rainfall data for the last 10 years are noted as 179.07, 277.3, 284.61, and 389.43mm in the months of June, September, July, and August respectively. Minimum to maximum average rainfall data are 17.90, 27.73, 28.46, and 38.9mm in June, September, July, and August respectively as shown in Figure 2. The maximum annual monsoon precipitation occurred in 2019, which was 274.90mm. The average annual monsoon precipitation within the period of 2012 to 2021 was 277.3mm. The minimum annual monsoon precipitation happened in 2018 and was 4.42mm.

Fig. 1. Study area (ArcGIS map).

TABLE I. ANNUAL MONSOON RAINFALL DATA OF NAWABSHAH (2012 TO 2021)

Year	Monthly data				Total (mm)
	June	July	August	September	
2012	0.00	0.00	15.20	163.50	178.70
2013	19.00	7.50	39.00	3.50	69.00
2014	0.00	0.00	11.20	0.00	11.20
2015	37.20	69.00	0.00	0.00	106.20
2016	58.00	4.00	63.20	0.00	125.20
2017	58.86	33.17	65.71	4.40	162.15
2018	0.01	1.71	2.70	0.00	4.42
2019	0.00	152.20	41.70	81.00	274.90
2020	0.00	1.03	150.72	12.90	164.65
2021	6.00	16.00	0.00	12.00	34.00
Average (mm)	17.90	28.46	38.9	27.73	
Total (mm)	179.07	284.61	389.43	277.3	

C. Catchment Area

A catchment area is a surface, of any kind, where rainwater can be collected. The rooftop surface and plain surface area are catchment regions that get precipitation. The catchment area of

the Multipurpose Hall Building and its surroundings is estimated. This estimation was done physically with the assistance of a measuring tape. The equation for spillover catchment region estimations is :

$$\text{Plain surface area} = \text{Total surrounding surface area} - \text{Area of Multipurpose hall and total grass area} \quad (1)$$

D. Runoff Coefficient C_r

The runoff coefficient is a proportion of the amount of precipitation and the rate of spillover. There are certain factors that are determined by taking into account that not all rainwater can be collected. In some cases, there is a constant loss of overflow from the catchment area due to vanishing or holding at a superficial level. The runoff coefficient is calculated using:

$$C_r = \frac{V_r}{V_i} \quad (2)$$

where V_r and V_i are the runoff volume and the total precipitation volume on a superficial level. The calculated factors of runoff coefficients for several forms of catchments are given in Table II.

TABLE II. RUNOFF COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT CATCHMENT AREA TYPES

C_r factor	Catchment type
0.7 to 0.9	Corrugated-metal sheets
0.8 to 0.9	Tiles
0.5 to 0.6	Brick concrete
0.6 to 0.8	Concrete
0.2 to 0.5	Rocky natural catchments
0.0 to 0.3	Soil on slopes less than 10%
0.05 to 0.10	Green area

E. Rainwater Harvesting Potential

In a particular area, the whole amount of water that was mainly received as rainfall is the rainwater endowment. The amount of rainwater that is commendably harvestable is the RWH potential. The RWH potential for the study area is estimated with (3):

$$S = R \times A \times C_r \quad (3)$$

where S , R , A , and C_r are the runoff potential of rainwater harvesting (m^3), the average annual rainfall (m), the area of the catchment (m^2), and the runoff coefficient (%) respectively.

F. Weekly Discharge and Volume of Storage Tank Calculation

The volume of the storage tank is calculated based on the expected discharge. Catchment area and weekly rainfall are used to calculate weekly discharge. Monsoon weekly rainfall will be calculated by multiplying the daily monsoon rainfall with 7. The daily monsoon rainfall is calculated by dividing the maximum average annual monsoon rainfall by 122 as there are 122 days in the monsoon period every year (June, July, August, and September). The maximum average monsoon rainfall is 274.90mm which occurred in 2019. As a safety precaution, the tank should be built larger than the storage volume required.

G. Specifications of the Rainwater Harvesting Treatment System

Rainwater is collected in drain pipes on the roofs of buildings. After that, the rainwater is filtered to make it safe to drink. A first rain separator, or first flush, can be used to remove most pollutants from the rain water before it enters the filter. Rainwater can be collected and stored in one or more connected tanks, either below or above the ground. Rainwater is either pumped to an internal holding tank or delivered directly where it is needed on demand. Figure 2 shows the diagram of the Multipurpose Hall Building's rooftop RHS.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the rooftop RHS.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Digitization of Rooftop and Plain Surface Area with Google Earth Pro

The rooftop and the plain surface area of the surroundings of the multipurpose hall building were digitized in Google Earth Pro (GEP) using the available polygon tool. RWH is an attractive source of drinking water in urban areas due to the scarcity of conventional sources and their limited capacity [9]. In water-scarce areas, the system could be used to secure water demand locally and commercially. When the water quality parameters are met, rainwater harvested from rooftops could be used as supply water [10, 11]. The surface areas of rooftops (1642.130m²) and the total plain surface (11788.989m²) were digitized in GEP, they were saved as KML files and are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

B. Calculation of the the Rooftop and Plain Surface Area using ArcGIS

The saved KML files were imported into ArcGIS as layers. The KML layers have been converted to shape files because each shape file coordinate system has been changed to a projected coordinate system that is actually separate for each country (EPSG: 32644-WGS 84/UTM zone 43N) to calculate the areas of digitized rooftops and plains with the help of an

available geometry calculation tool (Figure 5). Figure 5 shows the projected shape file in ArcGIS, as well as the digitized rooftop and plain surface area catchment shape files.

Fig. 3. Rooftop and plain surface area digitized with (GEP).

Fig. 4. The shape files of the projected coordinates in ArcGIS.

Fig. 5. Calculation of the areas of digitized rooftop and plain surface catchments using ArcGIS.

C. Estimated Rooftop and Plain Surface RWH Potential

Table III shows the estimated average monsoon annual runoff from 2012 to 2021 from the rooftop of the multipurpose hall and the plain surface area surroundings. The maximum average annual monsoon runoff was 932.509m³, collected from the plain surface area surroundings of the multipurpose hall. The minimum average monsoon runoff was 129.892m³, collected from the rooftop of the multipurpose hall building.

TABLE III. ESTIMATED RAINWATER HARVESTING POTENTIAL OF THE STUDY AREA (2012 TO 2021)

Catchment type	Runoff (m ³ /year)	Average annual monsoon rainfall (m)	C _r	Area (m ²)
Rooftop	129.892	0.113	0.7	1642.130
Plain surface	932.509	0.113	0.7	11788.989
Total	1062.401			13431.119

D. Estimated RWH Potential (Runoff) on a Yearly Basis

Figure 6 shows the results of the estimated RWH potential (runoff) from the study area on a yearly basis. The maximum estimated amount of runoff water that could be collected from the rooftop and the plain surface area is 2584.550m³ during 2019 and the minimum estimated amount of runoff water was 41.367m³ during the year 2018. ArcMap 10.4.1 was used to calculate the RWH potential for the roofs of buildings. It is also proposed to use the RWH model at the household level with its utilities. Uncontrolled urban sprawl, rapid population growth, and uncontrolled immigration contributed to extensive groundwater extraction. Therefore, in addition to other sources such as rooftops, roadways provide a significant opportunity for rainwater harvesting as a viable solution to urban flooding.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the estimated annual monsoon runoff from the study area.

E. Estimated Weekly Discharge and Volume of Storage Tank

Table IV shows that a weekly monsoon discharge of 210.868m³ from the rooftop and the plain surface area can be obtained. A tank size of 330m³ per week is required for this discharge.

TABLE IV. ESTIMATED MONSOON WEEKLY DISCHARGE AND THE REQUIRED VOLUME OF THE STORAGE TANK

Catchment type	Weekly discharge (m ³)	Volume of storage tank per week (m ³)
Rooftop	25.781	40
Plain surface	185.087	288
Total	210.868	330

IV. CONCLUSION

An analysis was made in this study to determine whether rooftop and plain surface RWH can meet the general water demands in the study area. GEP was used for digitizing and

ArcGIS was used to calculate the rooftop and the plain surface areas surrounding the multipurpose hall. The total estimated amount of RWH potential during an average annual monsoon period (2012 to 2021) is 1062.401m³ for the 13431.119m² considered area. The results proved the abundant potential for exploitation of RWH from the rooftop and the plain surface area surrounding the Multipurpose Hall is possible in QUEST. Rooftop RWH is a good alternative for educational institutions because these buildings usually have extensive roof surfaces and the amount of water stored will provide a viable solution to the water requirements.

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Behavior and Strength of Composite Columns under the Impact of Uniaxial Compression Loading

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Abstract-The Concrete Filled Steel Tube Column (CFST) is classified as a composite structural element. This type of column was adopted as the main loaded member in many buildings due to its excellent mechanical properties. CFST columns have high strength and ductility behavior, and they can sustain heavy loads with high performance. These led to their adoption in many countries. In the current study, the behavior and strength of CFST columns under the effect of axial compression load with parameters such as the diameter to thickness ratio and the height to diameter ratio were investigated. Strength carrying capacity and axial and lateral deformations with axial and lateral strains were explored. The test results showed that smaller heights within the same material gave higher strength capacity. The stiffness of the CFST is more than concrete and hollow steel section specimens' due to its capability of high strength capacity with low displacement. Also, the composite action of CFST gave more stiffness.

Keywords-composite column; CFST; compression load; strength column capacity; column deformation

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete Filled Steel Tube Columns (CFSTCs) are classified as main structural elements that can carry different types of loading when used as structural members in buildings. This type of structural element has high stability and stiffness due to its superior mechanical properties due to the composite action [1]. Concrete column jacketing is done by steel tubes or Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) sheets with the fibers oriented around the concrete column in order to work like stirrups so that they provide confinement to prevent the formation of plastic hinges, splitting, and buckling [2]. The main purpose of concrete column confinement by steel tubes is to form a composite structural member. The benefits of confinement of a concrete column by steel tubes are increased stiffness, stability, increased strength capacity, and reduced buckling. The presence of steel tubes increases the concrete compressive strength and the column becomes more resistant, not only against gravity loads, but also against lateral loads such as wind or seismic. Authors in [3] studied the influence of confinement by rings around the steel tubes of CFST columns subjected to

axial load. The main objective of the proposed methodology is to restrict the elastic lateral dilation of concrete casted inside the steel tube. The test results showed that the suggested ring configuration enhanced the axial load-capacity of CFST columns, improved stiffness, and decreased the strength degradation rate. The presence of steel rings reduced the lateral deformation of CFST columns. Authors in [4] reviewed the applications and development of CFST members. It was shown that this structural member type enhanced stiffness, increased strength, and improved ductility due to the composite action between concrete and steel. Authors in [5] studied the performance of CFST columns under the effect of axial load. Variables like steel tube thickness and reinforcing bars and columns with and without foundations were considered. The experimental tests showed that the presence of reinforcing bars made the composite columns stronger. Bending failure occurred when the weld strength of the casing was greater than the limit of the axial compression load, whereas when the weld strength was less than the limit of the applied load, the failure became open splitting of the steel casing. Authors in [6] studied the mechanism of CFST failure with circular and square cross sections. The full scale of CFST columns under the effect of uniaxial compression load was considered. Finite element analysis was utilized to check out the test results. It was found that the contact pressure at the interface between the concrete core and the surrounding steel tube was uniform. As was pointed out in the experimental tests, the failure mode of the CFST column circular cross section was drum but local buckling occurred in the case of square CFST column. The simulation results showed that the confinement of the steel tube that surrounded the concrete core affected the ultimate load carrying capacity and the ductility of square and circle CFST columns. Authors in [7] studied the effects of steel rings around the external steel tube of the CFST column. The larger Poisson's ratio of steel led to the delamination at the interface between the concrete core and the surrounding steel tube. Theoretical models that predicate and estimate the load-strain as lateral and longitudinal curves were simulated and experimentally tested. The theoretical model results were close to the experimental test results. Authors in [8] studied the

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influence of concrete grade of CFST confinement column under axial load. The considered parameters were concrete compressive strength (infill) and diameter/thickness ratio of the steel tube in a total of six specimens. The conducted tests were focused on the strength capacity of the CFST column, stresses in concrete and steel tube, and confinement of column specimens. The test results showed that concrete with low compressive strength had more ductility and confinement. The presence of steel tubes surrounding the concrete core gave passive confinement to the concrete column. Authors in [9] reviewed the stiffening of CFST columns experimentally and theoretically. Authors in [10] studied the performance of CFSTs with high-strength concrete core subjected to axial compression load. Authors in [11] investigated the behavior of CFST columns subjected to axial compression load. Concrete core size, steel tube shape, and diameter/thickness ratio were considered. The experimental tests showed that the most significant parameter affecting the strength capacity of the CFST column was the thickness of steel tube which also had more impact on the degree of confinement of the concrete core. In addition, the load-deformation of circular specimens showed strain-hardening or perfectly plastic behavior after yielding. Authors in [12] proposed a finite element model to predict the performance and strength of CFST columns under the effect of axial load. The predicted behavior of the modified model was verified with experimental data. Authors in [13], studied the behavior of slender columns under the effect of combined loading by simulating the performance of different slender columns under the impact of eccentric axial force. They concluded that concrete strength, level of axial load, and column slender ratio were the most important factors affecting the reduction coefficients and the effective bending stiffness. Authors in [14] estimated the column capacity by testing 9 sandwich column specimens under axial compression load. The columns were made of normal strength concrete, whereas column portions were made from comparatively higher strength concrete. The test results showed that the aspect ratio affects the strength of such columns.

Summarizing the literature review, composite columns have higher strength capacity, stability, and stiffness than reinforced concrete columns or plain steel columns.

II. AIM OF THE CURRENT STUDY

The aim of the present study is to investigate the behavior and strength of concrete-filled steel tubes subjected to uniaxial loading and to compare them with control samples of concrete and steel tube columns. The mechanical properties of the studied concrete and steel tubes, such as compressive, flexural, splitting, and tensile strength and the modulus of elasticity by the stress-strain curve of the tested samples were explored. For the steel section, yielding and stress-strain behavior were studied to obtain the steel modulus of elasticity. The investigation focused into the behavior of the tested specimens and recorded the experimental data that represent column capacity strength, buckling, and longitudinal and lateral displacements. Different specimens were prepared and tested considering different parameters such as slenderness ratio and confinement steel tube sections.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Material Preparation

Three columns with different heights (400, 800, and 1200mm) were designed with steel tube thicknesses of 1.35mm and concrete core diameter of 76mm. The specimens were tested under the effect of uniaxial compression load. The concrete and steel tube's mechanical properties are listed in Table I, in which the concrete mechanical properties are based on [15] for compressive strength, [16] for splitting tensile strength, [17] for modulus of rupture, and [18] for modulus of elasticity. The mechanical steel tube by tensile test was based on [19]. Water - cement ratio for concrete core was 0.38 and the average of 3 specimens for each tested concrete was adopted.

TABLE I. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Concrete			Steel tube	
f_c' (MPa)	E_c (MPa)	f_r (MPa)	f_y (MPa)	E_s (MPa)
48	41500	7.55	295	205000

TABLE II. MODEL MARKS

Mark	Description	Specimen geometry						
		Concrete core diameter (mm)	Steel tube (mm)					
			Do	t	Di	$\frac{h}{(\times 10^2)}$	ht/Do	Do/t
CC	Concrete	73.3	-	-	-	4	5.46	-
						8	10.91	
						12	16.37	
HSC	Steel	-	76	1.35	73.3	4	5.26	56.3
						8	10.53	
						12	15.79	
CFST	Composite	73.3	76	1.35	73.3	4	5.26	56.3
						8	10.53	
						12	15.79	

In Table II, Do is the outer diameter, t is the steel tube thickness, Di is the inner diameter, and h is the specimen height. Figure 1 shows the specimens of hollow steel section, concrete and composite respectively, while Figure 2 present the specimen setup under the machine test.

B. Preparation of Specimens

Each hollow steel tube specimen was prepped carefully by cutting the required specimen height (400, 800 or 1200mm) and then making the end smooth and level to ensure that the applied load was distributed symmetrically. Concrete was inserted in the mold after it was oiled to prevent the adhesion between the concrete surface and the inner mold. For CFST specimens, the steel tubes were cleaned from unrequired materials such as dust to ensure there is suitable interaction between them and concrete. The bottoms of the steel tubes were closed with silicone and thick steel plates that were removed before testing the specimen and after the concrete was poured. The top of each specimen (rounded 5mm) was left empty to level the concrete by epoxy. Each specimen was placed at the center of the testing machine to avoid eccentric loading. Then, compressive load was applied at a constant rate. Axial and lateral displacement and strain were recorded for each applied load step up to failure for each column type (HSC, CC, and CFST).

Fig. 1. (a) Steel specimens (HSC), (b) concrete specimens (CC), and (c) composite specimens (CFST).

Fig. 2. Specimen setup.

IV. TEST RESULTS

Figures 3-14 show the axial and lateral load-displacement and longitudinal and lateral load-strain for all tested specimens. All tested specimens behaved nonlinearly up to the inflection point that depends on the parameters and specifications of each specimen. This inflection point relies on many parameters such as slenderness ratio, column type, and applied load. Each specimen reached maximum load capacity and after that the applied load dropped down, but they gave displacement at failure greater than the displacement at maximum load.

Fig. 3. Applied load-axial displacement variation for h= 400mm.

Fig. 4. Applied load-axial displacement variation for h=800mm.

Fig. 5. Applied load-axial displacement variation for h=1200mm.

Fig. 6. Applied load-lateral displacement variation for h=400mm.

Fig. 7. Applied load-lateral displacement variation for h=800mm.

Fig. 8. Applied load-lateral displacement variation for h=1200mm.

Fig. 9. Applied load-axial strain variation for h=400mm.

Fig. 10. Applied load-axial strain variation for h=800mm.

Fig. 11. Applied load-axial strain variation for h=1200mm.

Fig. 12. Applied load-lateral strain variation for h=400mm.

Fig. 13. Applied load-lateral strain variation for h=800mm.

Fig. 14. Applied load-lateral strain variation for h=1200mm.

The ductility of a structural member is the ability to bear or endure considerable deflection before failure. The ductility of a structural element is a very important quality indicator because it provides signs of collapse or failure, so the total collapse of a structural member may be prevented while the member can undergo more deformations (large deformations) without fail. Concrete is a brittle material, so the presence of steel tubes that surrounds the concrete core enhances its properties. The ductility U for all tested specimens is calculated by dividing the deflection at ultimate load Δ_u by the deflection at yield Δ_y :

$$U = \frac{\Delta_u}{\Delta_y} \quad (1)$$

The stiffness of the tested specimens is the resistance of an elastic body to deflection or deformation by an applied force. The stiffness μ is defined as the ratio of the ultimate load P_u to ultimate load deflection Δ_u :

$$\mu = \frac{P_u}{\Delta_u} \quad (2)$$

Figures 15 to 18 show the axial and lateral ductility and stiffness of all tested specimens. Concrete specimens have a constant ductility because concrete is a brittle material so that there is a plastic zone so the displacement at failure is approximately the same with the one at maximum load. The ductility of HSC specimens is more than concrete specimens' with the same height because steel is a ductile material. The CFST specimen with 1200mm height has longitudinal (axial) ductility more than the other specimens. Regarding the lateral displacement, the ductility of concrete was about the same, the HSC specimen with 800mm height had more than the other specimens, and the CFST with 1200mm height was the highest among the CFST specimens.

TABLE III. TEST RESULTS-AXIAL DISPLACEMENT AND STRAIN BASED ON MAXIMUM AND FAILURE LOAD

Mark	Height (mm)	Test results					
		Max. load (kN)	Failure load (kN)	Max. axial displacement (mm)	Axial displacement at failure (mm)	Max. strain	Strain at failure load
CC	400	224.00	225.00	3.00	3.02	2019	2053
	800	196.64	197.00	2.66	2.68	2025	2050
	1200	171.30	171.60	3.65	3.68	2575	2595
HSC	400	104.66	91.78	2.47	3.04	1876	1900
	800	99.40	69.56	2.27	3.63	1672	1700
	1200	96.08	78.04	3.15	3.75	1844	1875
CFST	400	415.08	402.98	3.76	4.55	4159	4300
	800	358.86	338.06	5.59	7.94	11832	11880
	1200	327.81	275.51	6.99	10.19	3296	3330

TABLE IV. TEST RESULTS-LATERAL DISPLACEMENT AND LATERAL STRAIN BASED ON MAXIMUM AND FAILURE LOAD

Mark	Height (mm)	Test results					
		Max. load (kN)	Failure load (kN)	Max. lateral displacement (mm)	Lateral displacement at failure (mm)	Max. strain	Strain at failure load
CC	400	224.00	225.00	1.16	1.17	700	755
	800	196.64	197.00	0.90	0.91	307	365
	1200	171.30	171.60	4.03	4.05	408	470
HSC	400	104.66	91.78	0.8	1.15	585	625
	800	99.40	69.56	4.05	5.28	785	920
	1200	96.08	78.04	1.17	1.22	380	420
CFST	400	415.08	402.98	2.08	2.21	2913	3784
	800	358.86	338.06	8.44	10.08	5936	9986
	1200	327.81	275.51	11.87	28.06	2190	3125

TABLE V. AXIAL AND LATERAL DUCTILITY AND STIFFNESS

Mark	Height (mm)	Ductility (axial)	Stiffness (axial) (kN/mm)	Ductility (lateral)	Stiffness (lateral) (kN/mm)
CC	400	1.01	74.67	1.01	193.10
	800	1.01	73.92	1.01	218.49
	1200	1.01	46.93	1.00	42.51
HSC	400	1.23	42.37	1.44	130.83
	800	1.60	43.79	1.30	24.54
	1200	1.19	30.50	1.04	82.12
CFST	400	1.21	110.39	1.06	199.56
	800	1.42	64.20	1.19	42.52
	1200	1.46	46.90	2.36	27.62

Ductility (Axial)

Fig. 15. Axial ductility variation of all specimens.

Ductility (Lateral)

Fig. 16. Lateral ductility variation of all specimens.

Stiffness (Axial)

Fig. 17. Axial stiffness variation of all specimens.

Stiffness (Lateral)

Fig. 18. Lateral stiffness variation of all specimens.

The axial stiffness of the concrete specimen was higher when its height was 800mm, while regarding the HSC and CFST specimens maximum axial stiffness was measured at 400mm. Maximum lateral stiffness of CC, HSC, and CFST was measured for specimen height of 400mm, 800mm, and 400mm respectively.

V. MODES OF FAILURE

The failure modes of all specimens are illustrated in Figure 19. The concrete specimens exhibited shear failure that caused cuts in plain concrete. The HSC specimens exhibited local buckling due to the end effect. The CFST specimens exhibited steel yielding and global buckling. When the applied load is increased, large axial strain is developed and the steel tubes fracture. In the CFST specimens, the presence of steel tubes provides confinement to the concrete core and worked as a composite that led to buckled failure mode.

Fig. 19. Failure modes of the tested specimens.

VI. DISCUSSION

Based on the experimental results, the strength capacity of each specimen is compared with the others of its group (Table VI) and with the other groups for specimens of the same height (Table VII). The smallest height within the same material gave the highest strength capacity because short specimens have low slenderness ratio. The CFST specimen gave higher strength than the others because they have higher stiffness due to the higher moment of inertia and equivalent modulus of elasticity due to the composite action between the concrete core and the surrounding steel tube. HSC exhibited the smallest strength carrying capacity because it has solid cross section.

TABLE VI. STRENGTH CARRYING CAPACITY WITHIN THE SAME MATERIAL

Mark	Height (mm)	Maximum load (kN)	% Decrease in load capacity
CC	400	224.00	---
	800	196.64	12.21
	1200	171.30	23.53
HSC	400	104.66	---
	800	99.40	5.03
	1200	96.08	8.20
CFST	400	415.08	---
	800	358.86	13.54
	1200	327.81	21.02

TABLE VII. STRENGTH CARRYING CAPACITY FOR SAME SPECIMEN HEIGHT

Height (mm)	Mark	Maximum load (kN)	% Increase in load capacity
400	HSC	104.66	---
	CC	224.00	114.03
	CFST	415.08	296.60
800	HSC	99.40	---
	CC	196.64	97.83
	CFST	358.86	261.03
1200	HSC	96.08	---
	CC	171.30	78.29
	CFST	327.81	281.18

Axial (longitudinal) displacement for long specimens (800 and 1200mm) increased as the height increased because axial displacement relies on the load and on the height (PL/AE), so for the same rigidity (AE) the displacement increased. Figure 3 shows that for the same load, the axial displacement developed in the HSC specimen was more than the other specimens' and the displacement of CFST was less. The same phenomena were observed and plotted for lateral displacement. Axial strain and lateral strain for CFST specimens were less than the other specimens' (CC and HSC) for the same reasons. The ductility of CFST specimens was more than the HSC and CC (brittle material-less ductility) specimens because the steel tubes surrounding the concrete core gave more strength without sudden failure and the displacement at failure load became more (large deformation). The stiffness of the CFST is more than the CC and HSC specimens' due to its capability of high strength capacity with low displacement. Also the composite action of CFST gave more stiffness (EI) due to its increased equivalent modulus of elasticity and transformed moment of inertia.

VII. CONCLUSION

The test results of the strength of composite columns under the effect of uniaxial compression loading, indicated that the shorter columns of the same material had higher strength capacity. The stiffness of composite specimens was higher than the concrete and hollow steel specimens'. The behavior and strength of composite column differed from steel and hollow steel due to the composite action between concrete and steel that gave higher strength and more realistic behavior. More study is required in order to investigate steel fiber concrete confined by steel tubes.

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Application of the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm in Solving the Economic Emission Dispatch Problem Integrating Renewable Energy

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Abstract-The Economic Emission Dispatch (EED) is a multi-objective optimization problem that seeks to find the optimal balance between the reduction of the generation costs and the pollutant emissions of power thermal plants while respecting power balance and several operational restrictions. This balance could be carried out by proper scheduling power generation of the committed units to fulfill the power demands considering emissions. This paper presents a novel application of the conventional Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA) optimization approach to solve the EED problem with the integration of renewable energy. Wind and solar energy were chosen to be injected into the system's power balance constraint. The combined EED objective function with Valve Point Effects (VPE) consideration was modeled using price penalty and weight factors. This study showed the effectiveness of the chosen optimization technique and the influence of injecting renewable energy along with traditional power resources on reducing total cost and pollutant emissions. The proposed method was applied to the IEEE 9-bus test system and tested in Matlab.

Keywords-economic emission dispatch; Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm; wind; solar; valve point effects

I. INTRODUCTION

More than 80% of total consumed energy is derived from fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and gas [1]. Fossil fuels are expensive to extract, finite, and their use emits a variety of harmful pollutants [2]. Thermal power plants can respond to sharp and sudden power demands quickly. Economic Dispatch (ED) is a necessary task in fuel-based power production systems. It is a computational optimization problem where the overall required generation is distributed among the committed thermal power units to minimize the total generation cost, no matter the harmful emissions produced. However, alternative

strategies are required to respond to the increasing demands for environmental protection [3]. Economic Emission Dispatch (EED) is one of these strategies that has received considerable attention. EED aims to simultaneously reduce total generation costs and pollutant emissions, such as SO₂, NO_x, and CO₂. Emissions could be considered within the economic dispatch problem by being incorporated as a constraint [4, 5], or as a weighted quantity within the objective function of the problem.

Renewable energy is environment-friendly and sustainable with low production cost. Once built, renewable facilities cost very little to operate. However, it is difficult for renewable energy to generate power on the same large scale as fossil fuels. The most common renewable resources are solar and wind. Both these energy sources are intermittent, as they depend on climate parameters such as solar radiation, temperature, and wind speed and they are challenging to schedule [6]. Several tools have been explored considering renewable energy in the EED problem. In [7], EED with solar and wind power was solved using harmony search. The results were carried out for one level of power demand and the influence of integrating renewable energy was studied. Artificial neural networks were applied in [8] to predict and solve EED with the integration of renewable energy, reaching an optimum in real-time. The effectiveness of the PSO-based strategy was shown in [9] by solving the EED problem by considering VPE and including wind energy sources for a 10-unit system. The results were investigated for both cases, with and without wind power penetration.

Among the various existing optimization techniques to solve power system problems, this study investigated the use of the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA) [10-12]. LMA is a hybrid numerical optimization approach that uses both the

Gauss-Newton algorithm and the steepest descent search to converge to the optimal solution. This technique is particularly effective in solving systems with non-linear equations [12]. This paper proposes a novel application to LMA for solving the static lossy non-convex multi-objective EED problem with solar and wind power penetration. The results showed the influence of integrating renewable energy to reduce total production costs and pollutant emissions. This method was tested and simulated on an IEEE 9-bus system via the Matlab environment.

II. EED FORMULATION WITH WIND AND SOLAR POWER

Two objective functions were considered: minimization of the total generation cost and of the NO_x emissions of the committed power units.

A. Objective Functions

The EED problem is defined as a constrained multi-objective optimization problem that minimizes simultaneously total power cost and emissions of pollutant gases while satisfying power balance and operational constraints.

1) Cost Function with VPE

The basic form of the thermal generation units' cost function was approximated by a smooth quadratic function, as in [13]. However, in practice, multiple steam valves exist in large turbines, whose role is to maintain the power balance in thermal units by being opened and closed to reach a specific load. This operation contributes to the non-convexity of the fuel cost function, which is known as Valve-Point loading Effects (VPE) and is modeled as an additional sinusoidal component [14]. The fuel cost curve with VPE is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Fuel cost curve with and without valve point effects.

The total generation cost of thermal power units can be expressed as:

$$\text{Minimize}(F_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} C(P_{Gi})) \quad (1)$$

where F_T is the total generation cost function, $C(P_{Gi})$ is the cost of the i^{th} generation unit, P_{Gi} is the real power output of the i^{th} generation unit, and N_G is the number of dispatchable generation units.

$$C(P_{Gi}) = a_i + b_i P_{Gi} + c_i P_{Gi}^2 + |d_i \sin[e_i(P_{Gi}^{min} - P_{Gi})]| \quad (2)$$

where a_i , b_i , and c_i are the cost coefficients of the i^{th} generation unit, and d_i , e_i are the valve-point effects coefficients of fuel cost for the i^{th} generation unit.

2) Emission Function

NO_x is a serious global concern. In this study, it is one of the numerous dangerous gases generated by the production units. The emission function is a quadratic function, described as [15]:

$$\text{Minimize}(E_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi})) \quad (3)$$

where E_T is the total emission function measured in kg/h, and $E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi})$ is the NO_x emission of the i^{th} generation unit.

$$E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi}) = \alpha_i + \beta_i P_{Gi} + \gamma_i P_{Gi}^2 \quad (4)$$

where α_i , β_i , and γ_i are the NO_x emission coefficients of the i^{th} generation unit. The above bi-objective combined economic emission dispatch problem was converted into a single optimization problem by introducing a price penalty factor. The weighted objective function is represented as:

$$FO = \omega F_T(P_{Gi}) + h(1 - \omega) E_T(P_{Gi}) \quad (5)$$

where ω is the weight factor in the range of [0,1], used to balance cost and emissions. h is the price penalty factor which is the ratio between the maximum fuel cost and the maximum emissions of the corresponding generator [16]:

$$h_i = \frac{C(P_{Gi}^{max})}{E_{\text{NO}_x}(P_{Gi}^{max})} \quad (6)$$

B. Modeling Renewable Energy

1) Solar Power

The maximum power a solar panel can deliver (P_s) is determined as [7-8]:

$$P_s = P_1 E_c [1 + P_2 (T_j - T_{jref})] \quad (7)$$

where E_c is solar radiation, T_{jref} is the reference temperature of the panels in 25°C , and T_j is the cell junction temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$). k_1 represents the characteristic dispersion of the panels and is between 0.095 to 0.105, and $k_2 = 0.47\%/^\circ\text{C}$ is the drift in panels temperature. Including a third parameter P_3 in the solar power equation improves the results:

$$P_s = P_1 E_c [1 + P_2 (T_j - T_{jref})] (P_3 + E_c) \quad (8)$$

Having only 3 constant factors P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 and a simple equation, this simplified model can predict the maximum power generated by a group of solar panels, given the panel temperature. A thermal solar power plant is made up of a solar system that generates heat and feeds it to turbines in a thermal cycle to generate electricity.

2) Wind power

The power provided by a wind turbine P_w is expressed as [7-8]:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_p A v^3 10^{-3} \quad (9)$$

where A is the area traversed by the wind (m^2), ρ is the air density ($1.225kg/m^3$), V is the wind speed (m/s), and C_p is the efficiency factor which depends on the wind speed and the architecture of the system. Wind turbines should be built considering a mechanical adjustment to develop nominal power from a nominal wind speed in a way to avoid mechanical overloads.

C. Problem Constraints

The objective function is minimized under the following operational constraints.

1) Power Balance Constraint

The total generation power must meet demand while also accounting for transmission losses. Solar and wind power are injected into the system power balance constraint, where P_{ren} is the sum of solar and wind power and P_d is the power demand.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_G} P_{Gi} + P_{ren} - P_D - P_L = 0 \quad (10)$$

The transmission lines' network power loss P_L could be calculated by solving the power flow problem [17]. The total real power losses can be calculated using the total net injected real power at all buses using [18]:

$$P_L = \sum_{k=1}^{Nl} g_k [V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)] \quad (11)$$

where Nl is the number of transmission lines, g_k is the conductance of the k^{th} line that connects bus i to bus j , V_i is the voltage magnitude at bus i , and δ_i is the voltage angle at bus i .

2) Real Power Operating Limits

To ensure reliable operation, each unit's power generation should be provided concerning its minimal and maximal boundaries.

$$P_{Gi}^{min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{max} \quad (12)$$

Using the Lagrange function, the above-constrained optimization problem was converted into an unconstrained problem. The objective function henceforth is expressed as:

$$L(P_{Gi}, \lambda) = FO + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} (P_{Gi} + P_{ren} - P_D - P_L) \quad (13)$$

III. LEVENBERG-MARQUARDT ALGORITHM

LMA is a mathematical-based optimization approach based on a combination of the directions of the Gauss-Newton algorithm and the gradient descent search. $V(x)$ is assumed to be the function to minimize considering the parameters vector x . Newton's update for this vector is [19]:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - [\nabla^2 V(x)]^{-1} \nabla V(x) \quad (14)$$

where $\nabla^2 V(x)$ is the Hessian matrix and $\nabla V(x)$ is the gradient. The function $V(x)$ is assumed to be a sum of squares function:

$$V(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2(x) \quad (15)$$

where $e(x)$ is the difference between the target and the network output. Then it can be shown that:

$$\nabla V(x) = J^T(x)e(x) \quad (16)$$

and

$$\nabla^2 V(x) = J^T J + S(x) \quad (17)$$

The Jacobian matrix $J(x)$ is:

$$J(x) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial e_1(x)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial e_2(x)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_n(x)}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial e_2(x)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial e_2(x)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_n(x)}{\partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial e_n(x)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial e_n(x)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_n(x)}{\partial x_n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

and

$$S(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i(x) \nabla^2 e_i(x) \quad (19)$$

The Gauss-Newton method assumed that $S(x)=0$, so the equation becomes:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - [J^T(x)J(x)]^{-1} J^T(x)e(x) \quad (20)$$

The Levenberg-Marquardt modification to the Gauss-Newton method is modeled as follows, where the characteristic μ_k is generally set to 0.01 as a starting point:

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - [J^T(x)J(x) + \mu_k I]^{-1} J^T(x)e(x) \quad (21)$$

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - [H(x) + \mu_k]^{-1} \nabla V(x) \quad (22)$$

This algorithm sets μ_k at 0.01 as a starting point and then it's multiplied by 10 whenever a step results in an increased $V(x)$, otherwise, if $V(x)$ decreases μ_k is divided by 10. To adapt LMA to this problem, $x = [P_{Gi}, \lambda]$ and $V(x) = L(P_{Gi}, \lambda)$.

A. Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm

- Step 1: Read the given data cost coefficients (a_i, b_i, c_i), VPE coefficients (d_i, e_i), NO_x coefficients ($\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i$), power demand (P_D), and unit's power limits ($P_{Gi}^{min}, P_{Gi}^{max}$).
- Step 2: Read the forecasted wind and solar power (P_{ren}), where $P_{ren} < 0.3P_D$.
- Step 3: Run power flow analysis and calculate transmission lines' power losses (P_L).
- Step 4: Set the initial values of the Lagrangian multiplier λ^0 , the active generated power P_{Gi}^0 , and the Levenberg-Marquardt characteristic μ_0 .
- Step 5: Calculate the Lagrange function $L(P_{Gi}, \lambda)$.
- Step 6: Calculate the Jacobian matrix:

$$J(P_{Gi}, \lambda) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial L_1}{\partial P_{g1}} & \frac{\partial L_1}{\partial P_{g2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial L_1}{\partial P_{gn}} & \frac{\partial L_1}{\partial \lambda} \\ \frac{\partial L_2}{\partial P_{g1}} & \frac{\partial L_2}{\partial P_{g1}} & \dots & \frac{\partial L_2}{\partial P_{gn}} & \frac{\partial L_2}{\partial \lambda} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial L_n}{\partial P_{g1}} & \frac{\partial L_n}{\partial P_{g1}} & \dots & \frac{\partial L_n}{\partial P_{gn}} & \frac{\partial L_n}{\partial \lambda} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

- Step 7: Calculate the Hessian matrix:

$$H(P_{gi}) = J^T(P_{gi})J(P_{gi}) \quad (24)$$

- Step 8: Update the power generation following (23):

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{gi(k+1)} \\ \lambda_{(k+1)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P_{gi(k)} \\ \lambda_{(k)} \end{bmatrix} - \Delta P \begin{bmatrix} P_{gi} \\ \lambda \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

- Step 9: Calculate the new value of $L_{k+1}(P_{Gi}, \lambda)$ for each generating unit.
- Step 10: Update the Levenberg-Marquardt characteristic μ_k :
If $L_{k+1} \geq L_k$ set $\mu = \mu \times 10$
else if $L_{k+1} < L_k$ set $\mu = \mu / 10$.

- Step 11: Check generation limits for each unit:

$$\text{Set } P_{Gi} = P_{Gi}^{min} \text{ if } P_{Gi} < P_{Gi}^{min}$$

$$\text{Set } P_{Gi} = P_{Gi}^{max} \text{ if } P_{Gi} > P_{Gi}^{max}$$

- Step 12: Calculate the power mismatch ΔP_g

$$\Delta P_g = \sum_{i=1}^{N_g} P_{gi} - P_{ren} - P_d - P_L \quad (26)$$

- Step 13: If $\Delta P_g \leq \epsilon$, where ϵ is the convergence criteria set to 0.01, then stop the calculation and move to step 15. Otherwise, go to the next step.
- Step 14: Repeat the procedure from step 5.
- Step 15: Calculate the cost function and the emission quantity using the optimal values of P_{Gi} and λ_{opt} .

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Dispatch simulation was carried out for 3 different cases:

- Case study 1: ED with VPE consideration.
- Case study 2: EED without VPE consideration.
- Case study 3: EED with VPE consideration in the presence of renewable energy.

The performance of LMA was tested on an IEEE 9-bus system for these cases. The considered network system consists of 9 buses, 3 power generators, 3 power transformers, 6 transmission lines, and 3 loads, as shown in Figure 2. Table I shows the units' data for all cases. The proposed approach was programmed using Matlab.

Fig. 2. IEEE 9-bus system.

TABLE I. IEEE-9 BUS COST AND EMISSION DATA [20]

Network data		Generating Unit		
		1	2	3
Cost coefficients	a	0.001562	0.001940	0.004820
	b	7.920	7.85	7.97
	c	561	310	78
	d	300	200	150
	e	0.0315	0.0420	0.0630
NO _x coefficients	α_i	0.043732540	0.055821713	0.027731524
	β_i	-9.4868099 e-05	-9.7252878 e-05	-3.5373734 e-04
	γ_i	1.4721848 e-07	3.0207577 e-07	1.9338531 e-06
Unit's limit (MW)	P_{Gi}^{min}	100	100	50
	P_{Gi}^{max}	600	400	200

A. Case Study 1

In this case, the single-objective ED problem was solved by setting the weight factor to $\omega=1$, thus considering only the cost function. The power demand to be met by the 3 generating units was 850MW, and the transmission lines' power losses were neglected. The ED results using the LMA and other methods are presented in Table I. LMA was compared with SDE [21], GA [22], and MPSO [23]. LMA succeeded in finding the generation outputs that give the minimum cost while meeting the total power demand. From Table II, it is clear that the proposed approach reported the global optimum solution over other algorithms.

TABLE II. RESULT COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 1

Unit	Method			
	SDE [21]	GA [22]	MPSO [23]	LMA
P_{G1} [MW]	400.0000	400.000	400.0000	402.4788
P_{G2} [MW]	300.2669	300.000	300.2700	312.5117
P_{G3} [MW]	149.7331	150.000	149.7400	135.0095
Cost [\$]	8241.50	8234.60	8234.07	8232.50

B. Case Study 2

In this case, the multi-objective EED problem was solved without considering VPE, which means that the cost function was considered in its convex form. The power demand to be met by the 3 generating units was 850MW, and the transmission lines' power losses were taken into account. Table III shows the best compromise solutions to reduce simultaneously cost and NO_x emissions found by LMA, CSA [24], and NSGA II [15].

TABLE III. RESULT COMPARISON FOR CASE STUDY 2

Unit	Method		
	CSA [24]	NSGA II [15]	LMA
P_{G1} [MW]	470.9502	470.957	442.2904
P_{G2} [MW]	280.7243	280.663	306.8524
P_{G3} [MW]	113.6211	113.675	116.1568
P_L [MW]	15.2950	15.2940	15.2996
Cost [\$]	8349.722	8349.72	8339.80
NO _x Emissions [kg/h]	0.09654	0.09654	0.09770

The best solution for LMA was determined by running the program for all possible values of the weight factor in the range of [0, 1] with a step of 0.1. LMA provided a profit of 9.92\$/h in terms of cost. CSA and NSGA reported a minimum solution

for NO_x emissions with a profit of 0.1% compared to LMA. It seems that LMA converged to a near-global solution in this scenario.

C. Case Study 3

In this case, the multi-objective EED problem considering VPE and the presence of renewable energy was resolved for different demand levels. Hence, power demand was randomly changed at the different network load buses in a wide range of units' power limits. The first step consisted of performing Newton-Raphson power flow analysis to calculate the power losses of the transmission lines using the generators and the data of the lines from [25]. The penetration of solar and wind power was randomly generated in a way to be limited to up to 30% of power demand due to the stochastic availability of these resources. The weight factor was set to 0.5 to give the same importance to the two objective functions considered. Several levels of power demand were generated with intermittent renewable energy power. For each level of power demand, the LMA was run to converge to the optimum values of generating power, and λ_{opt} , cost, and emissions quantities were calculated. The proposed approach structure is illustrated in Figure 3. The LMA solutions for various values of power demand are presented in Table IV.

Since there is a lack of studies with the same criteria (multi-objective, VPE, Power losses, wind and solar power, IEEE-9

bus system), the simulation results were compared only with and without the presence of renewable energy.

Fig. 3. The proposed LMA architecture flowchart.

Table IV shows that both cost and emissions decrease significantly when integrating renewable energy. It is obvious that when the penetration of renewable energy is high, the reduction in cost and emission is more considerable. As an example, for the case of 761MW power demand, penetration of renewable energy led to a reduction in cost and NO_x emissions of about 60% and 21%, respectively. Therefore, the enhancement of the EED problem is more efficient with the presence of renewable energy.

TABLE IV. EED WITH VPE USING LMA WITH/WITHOUT RENEWABLE ENERGY PENETRATION FOR $\omega=0.5$

Power Demand [MW]	P_{ren} [MW]	P_{G1} [MW]	P_{G2} [MW]	P_{G3} [MW]	Cost [\$]	Profit in cost [%]	Emission [kg/h]	Profit in emissions [%]
451	-	162.1612	193.0458	102.0527	7.3932e+03	17.3%	0.0923	1.2%
	15.0481	176.1747	169.8884	96.1484	6.1163e+03		0.0912	
505	-	168.3291	224.7244	119.8273	8.5375e+03	51.8%	0.0943	2.0%
	62.8873	161.8538	203.5875	84.552	4.1135 e+03		0.0924	
615	-	229.0195	283.5452	116.0003	1.3820e+04	40.3%	0.0950	0.84%
	20.132	319.0071	141.7072	147.7186	6.2000e+03		0.0942	
761	-	241.5953	350.9251	198.3037	3.2606e+04	62.0%	0.1219	21.0%
	53.6624	347.9706	316.3517	72.8395	1.2377e+04		0.0961	
835	-	326.6593	368.3790	195.3959	5.2899e+04	38.8%	0.1219	8.3%
	195.0715	271.5196	225.4007	198.4422	3.2358e+04		0.1118	

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new application of the mathematical-based method Levenberg-Marquardt for solving the static multi-objective non-convex EED problem for the IEEE 9-bus network incorporating solar and wind energy. The proposed approach was applied to two other case studies. The results provided by LMA were compared with those obtained by SDE, GA, MPSO, CSA, and NSGA II. The comparison showed that LMA provided a better solution for the case of the single-objective problem. For the multi-objective problem, LMA reported a near-global optimum in terms of emissions compared to the heuristic methods. For the EED problem with wind and solar power, LMA was investigated for several levels of power demand and compared to results provided without the penetration of renewable energy sources. LMA proved its efficiency in finding the best compromise of cost and emissions in a short execution time. However, it's important to note that LMA suffers from high sensitivity to the initial parameters. The integration of renewable energy has a significant impact on reducing both the total cost and emissions.

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The Combined Strengthening Effect of CFRP Wrapping and NSM CFRP Laminates on the Flexural Behavior of Post-Tensioning Concrete Girders Subjected to Partially Strand Damage

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Abstract-The studies on unbonded post-tensioned concrete members strengthened with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) are limited and the effect of strengthening on the strain of unbonded pre-stressed steel is not well characterized. Estimating the flexural capacity of unbonded post-tensioned members using the design methodology specified in the design guidelines for FRP strengthening techniques of bonded post-tensioned members does not provide a reliable evaluation. This study investigates the behavior of unbonded post-tensioned concrete members with partial strand damage (14.3% and 28.6% damage) and strengthened with CFRP laminates using a near-surface mounted technique with and without U-wrap anchorages. The experimental results showed that the use of CFRP laminates significantly affects strand strain, especially with the use of anchors. The CFRP reinforcement affected flexural strength, crack width, and midspan deflection. However, the flexural stiffness of strengthened members during the serviceability phases is critical as strand damage ratios increase. In comparison with the nondamaged girder, the NSM-CFRP laminates enhanced the flexural capacity by 11% and 7.7% corresponding to strand damage of 14.3% and 28.6% respectively. Additionally, semiempirical equations were proposed to predict the actual strain of unbonded strands whilst considering the effects of FRP laminates. The suggested equations are simple to apply and provide accurate predictions with little variance.

Keywords-NSM-CFRP laminates; post-tensioned concrete; strand damage; strengthening

I. INTRODUCTION

Most standard investigations on the repair and strengthening of prestressed concrete members utilizing CFRP materials have recently concentrated on Pre-tensioned Concrete (PC) members, especially deteriorated or damaged due to corrosion or collision from overheight vehicles [1-3]. According to experimental tests, the use of CFRP strengthening techniques enhanced the stiffness and flexural strength of PC members, and reduced crack spacing and crack width [4-7].

The FRP reinforcement design guidelines cover two types of techniques. The first kind is External Bonded (EB), which involves bonding CFRP sheets or laminates to the tension surface of the concrete member. The second is the near-surface mounted technique, which requires extending CFRP bars or laminates into concrete cover grooves and attaching them with epoxy [8, 9]. The above techniques have many advantages, the most notable of which is that they are light-weight and improve flexural capacity, the Near-Surface Mounted (NSM) technique is gaining popularity since it is less prone to weather fluctuations and has the potential to delay or prevent FRP debonding [10]. The ACI 440-R of FRP strengthening has extensively documented the strengthening of prestressed concrete members, including bonded post-tensioned and pre-tensioned members, but unfortunately, these guidelines did not cover unbonded concrete members on the one hand, and these guidelines for strengthening were limited to the externally bonded technique on the other [11]. Unlike bonded post-tensioned members, which use the same concepts of equilibrium and strain compatibility to determine the strains in each of the pre-stressing steel, concrete, and CFRP components, the challenge for unbonded post-tensioned members is determining the pre-stressing steel strain increase due to the loss of strain compatibility between the pre-stressing steel and the surrounding concrete. Nonetheless, several researchers were able to develop methodologies that allowed them to predict the strain increase in unbonded post-tensioned members strengthened with EB techniques [4, 5, 12, 13]. The use of NSM-CFRP is commonly accompanied by the concrete cover separation, which limits the reinforcing elements' contribution to increasing flexural capacity and reducing ductility. As a result, the use of U-wrap anchorages, which prevent the concrete cover from separating, is effective in increasing the strains of each of the reinforcing elements, resulting in considerably improved flexural behavior of the reinforced concrete members [10, 14, 15].

The current study is a part of an investigating research regarding the efficiency of strengthening techniques that is performed at Baghdad University (Civil Engineering Lab) [20]. This paper focuses on the strengthening with the use of CFRP near-surface mounted technique.

II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND METHODOLOGY

A. Design of the Tested Girder

The experimental program includes 7 UPCs simply supported girders with heights (h) of 300mm, widths (b) of 200mm, lengths (L) of 3000mm, and an effective length (L_0) of 2800mm. The concrete cover was 25mm, except for tensile rebars, which use a cover of 35mm. Compressive and tensile strength, and the modulus of elasticity of concrete were obtained according to ASTM C39, ASTM C496-04, and ASTM C469 respectively. The compressive and tensile strengths of the concrete estimated in 10 concrete cylinders (150mm×300mm) were 44.6MPa and 5.1MPa. The concrete had a slump of 118 ± 10 mm (Table I). Four girders strengthened with CFRP laminates using the near-surface mounted technique were tested along with a nondamaged reference girder (REF) and two sub-reference girders (PC1R and PC2R) with damaged strand ratios (SDR) of 14.3% and 28.6%. The patterns of strand damage are illustrated in Figure 1. Two types of steel reinforcement with diameters of 16mm and 10mm, as shown in Table II, were used for all girders in tension and compression zones respectively. The appropriate amount of steel was used for shear reinforcement to avoid the occurrence of shear failure before flexural failure. Accordingly, closed stirrups with a diameter of 10mm and a spacing of 100mm c/c were placed along a length of 500mm from the girder's edges and 200mm c/c for the remaining middle length. Two seven-wire low relaxations strands with 12.7mm diameter and Grade 270 were used for each UPC girder (Table II) with a constant eccentricity of 70mm extended inside PVC tubes as unbonded pre-stressing steel. Strand wires were carefully damaged as a result of the spiral form by fastening the two ends of the strand with metal cages and using an electric saw to achieve the specific ratio. Wedge-anchored prestressing strands were directly supported on a steel bearing plate (200mm [width] × 80mm [depth] × 12mm [thickness]) attached to the ends of the girder. Two holes were formed on the steel plate to facilitate the application of prestressing. The steel plate was then installed on the formwork before pouring the concrete to ensure the centrality of strands and achieve complete contact with the concrete.

Four damaged girders were strengthened using the near-surface mounted technique utilizing two CFRP laminates with dimensions of 1.2mm width, 25mm depth, and 2000mm length (Table III) CFRP properties. In addition, two of these girders were strengthened with CFRP U-wrap sheet anchors at the ends of the CFRP laminates with 250mm width and 280mm height (Table IV). The details of the tested girders are presented in Figures 2-4 and Table IV CFRP properties. Girders were post-tensioned by strands (according to the specific damage ratios of each strand) with a straight trajectory after 28 days of casting and immediately before the strengthening process. The initial jacking stress in each strand was $0.6f_{pu}$ (Figure 5). The CFRP laminates were installed one day after the tensioning of girders and before installing the strengthening material, groove

locations are first marked on the girders, which have been turned upside down. The concrete was cut to the required dimensions with a concrete saw. An air and water pressure jet was subsequently used to remove the remaining concrete particles in the grooves. CFRP laminates were then inserted after the application of an adhesive layer. The adhesive was leveled with the concrete surface with a scraper (Figure 6). Each strengthened girder contained grooves with dimensions of 30mm (depth) × 6mm (width), as recommended by the ACI 440.2R-17 [11]. The cross-sectional edges of the girders were rounded to a radius of approximately 13mm before applying the carbon panels. Using a grinder, the surface of the specimens was cleaned and prepared for installation. This was done to get rid of laitance and open up the pores in concrete. After that, a primer was used to seal all the possible openings and cracks, and the CFRP sheets were applied using adhesive, according to the manufacturer's instructions (Figure 6).

Fig. 1. Patterns of damaged strands in the tested girders.

Fig. 2. Details of steel reinforcement and girder profile for the tested girders (all dimensions are in mm).

Fig. 3. Details of CFRP-NSM strengthened girders (all dimensions are in mm).

Fig. 4. Details of the CFRP-NSM strengthened girders with U-wrap anchors (all dimensions are in mm).

Fig. 5. Posttensioning process of the tested girders.

Fig. 6. Strengthening stages of the tested girders.

capacity was used. A load cell with a 50-ton capacity was used to detect the load. The load was applied in increments of 15kN until the cracking load was reached. Then the load was applied in increments of 30kN until failure. Each beam took 2 to 3 hours to complete the test. Two dial gauges were used, one at the end of each strand, to check whether any strand slip occurred during the loading process.

Fig. 7. Test setup of the experimental girders.

TABLE I. CONCRETE PROPERTIES

Compressive strength f'_c (MPa)	Tensile strength f_{ct} (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity E_c (MPa)
44.6	5.1	31,220

TABLE II. STEEL REINFORCEMENT PROPERTIES

Type	Dia (mm)	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate strength (MPa)	Maximum elongation (%)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)
rebar	10	518.2	658.97	12.2	200
rebar	16	577.3	710.74	13.4	200
strand	12.7	1725	1860	5	197.5

TABLE III. CFRP PROPERTIES

Material	Thickness (mm)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Ultimate elongation (%)
laminates	1.2	170	3100	2
sheets	0.167	220	3500	1.59

B. Instrumentation and Testing Procedures

The UPC girders were examined under two-point loading, as presented in Figure 7. The load was applied at a distance of 1100mm from the closest support. The strain of the CFRP laminate was detected using strain gauges (with resistance of 119.5±0.5Ω), which were glued to the surface of the CFRP laminate at midlength. The tendon strain was measured using three strain gauges (119.5±0.5Ω) mounted at midlength and loading locations. Notably, grooves were cut in the steel plate before installing anchors to prevent damaging the strain gauge wires. The strain of steel reinforcement was measured using one strain gauge (118.5±0.5Ω) glued at the midlength, whilst two strain gauges (120±0.5Ω resistance and 60mm gauge length) were surface-attached at compression and tension zones to monitor concrete strain. In addition, LVDTs were used to determine the girders' deflection. The data were automatically collected using a computerized data collecting system. To progressively raise the load, a hydraulic jack with 50-ton

TABLE IV. SUMMARY OF THE TEST PARAMETERS

Girder ID	SDR (%)	A_{ps} (mm ²)	ρ_p (%)	ρ_s (%)	CFRP laminate $n \times (b_f \times h_f)$ (mm)	U-wrap anchor	
						W_f	H_f
REF	0.0	197.4	0.49	0.81	---	---	---
PC1R	14.3	169.2	0.39		---	---	---
PC1N		169.2			2x1.4x25	---	---
PC1NE		169.2			2x1.4x25	250	280
PC2R	28.6	141.0	0.32		---	---	---
PC2N		141.0			2x1.4x25	---	---
PC2NE		141.0			2x1.4x25	250	280

Note: SDR: Strand Damage Ratio; n , b_f , and h_f : width, and height of CFRP laminates; W_f and H_f : width and height of sheet anchors

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Failure Mode

Flexural failure was observed in reference and sub-reference girders, with tensile steel reinforcing yielding, followed by concrete crushing in the compression zone, as shown in Figures 8(a)-8(c). Compared with the strengthened girders, cracks develop faster, in fewer numbers, and with a wider crack width in the reference and sub-reference girders. The first flexural crack appears in the midspan of sub-reference girders PC1R, and PC2R, with cracking loads of the reference girder's cracking load at approximately 94%, and 85% respectively. It was noticed that the cracking load decreases with increasing Strand Damage Ratio (SDR). The failure modes of the NSM-CFRP-strengthened girders were yielding of the tensile steel reinforcement and concrete cover separation after that (Figures 8(d)-8(f) **Error! Reference source not found.**). The failure of this type of strengthening showed higher brittleness, more cracks, and smaller crack widths than the corresponding sub-reference girders (Figure 9). The first flexural crack appears at the midspan of NSM-CFRP-strengthened girders PC1N, and PC3N, with an increase in the cracking load of 11%, and 13% respectively, compared with those of sub-reference girders. Similar to the reference girders, the strengthened girders with end CFRP U-wrap sheet anchorages failed due to tensile steel reinforcement yield

followed by concrete crushing in the compression zone with more ductility as a result of exploiting the greatest amount of high tensile stress in CFRP laminates before concrete crushing (Figures 8(e), 8(g)). The CFRP U-wrapped anchors, on the other hand, did not affect the tested girder's cracking load. In comparison to the sub-reference girders, flexural cracks arise in the mid-span of the girders PC1NE and PC3NE, with a 13.5% and 13% increase in cracking load. The CFRP U-wrap sheet anchors change the failure mechanism of CFRP NSM laminates significantly. Without CFRP U-wraps, all NSM strengthened girders failed by separating the concrete cover, whereas CFRP U-wraps shift the failure mode to crushing concrete in the compressive zone. A crushing sound indicated the debonding of the CFRP laminate at approximately 85% of the ultimate load. However, the separation of the concrete cover occurred close to the end of CFRP laminates and developed rapidly along the shear span. According to the observations, concrete cover separation was caused by the significant increase of diagonal shear cracks that caused slip along the longitudinal steel reinforcement and the concrete cover. Concrete cover separation or cover delamination and debonding of FRP from the concrete substrate are two failure modes associated with FRP strengthening. They are discussed in detail in [11].

Fig. 8. Failure patterns of the tested girders.

Fig. 9. Concrete cover separation and debonding of CFRP laminates.

B. Load–Deflection Response

The flexural behavior of the studied girders, as shown in Figure 10, was investigated at 3 loading stages: elastic uncracked, allowable load at the serviceability state, and ultimate load. The load-displacement relationship of the studied girders exhibited an elastic linear behavior up to the cracking load. During this stage, as the ratio of damaged strands grows, the stiffness of the reference girders decreases slightly, whereas there was no noticeable change in the stiffness of the strengthened girders compared to their counterparts from the sub-reference girders. However, when the applied load exceeds the crack load, the sub-reference girders exhibit a significantly higher rate of stiffness degradation as a result of the reduction in the pre-stress force, and thus an increase in the rate of crack development, increasing deflection. Meanwhile, the flexural-strengthening CFRP NSM laminates demonstrated their effectiveness in delaying the development of cracks and postponing the degradation of the strengthened girders' stiffness [16, 17]. As a result, for the same level of applied load, the strengthened girders showed lesser deflection than the reference girders.

The applied load of the reference girder was $P_{ser,REF} = 0.79P_{u,REF}$ when it increased to a load level that caused a deflection corresponding to the permissible deflection ($L_o/250=11.2\text{mm}$) at the serviceability state. This load is denoted by the allowable load at the serviceability state ($P_{ser,REF}$). At the service load ($P_{ser,REF}$), the deflection of sub-reference girders PC1R and PC2R increases by 6.2% and 30.4% respectively, over the reference girder REF. In comparison with their sub-reference counterparts, the deflection of PC1N and PC2N NSM strengthened girders without anchors was reduced by 15.5% and 17.2% respectively, whereas the deflection of PC1NE and PC2NE strengthened girders with anchors was reduced by 14% and 25% respectively. The flexural strength of the strengthened girders was much higher than that of the reference girder (Table V) and the strength increased with the use of CFRP U-wrap anchorages. During this period, the CFRP U-wrapped anchorage system eliminated the relative slippage and concrete cover delamination of the CFRP laminates and thus significantly enhanced the FRP-strengthening effectiveness and the flexural strength of the girders. In comparison with the reference girder, the flexural capacity of girders PC1R and PC2R was reduced by 5.7% and 11.8% respectively. Compared to their counterparts from the sub-reference girders, the flexural capacity of the strengthened girders without anchors increased by 17.3% and 20.4% respectively, and the flexural capacity of the strengthened girders with anchors increased by 27.9% and 30.1% respectively. It is evident from the results that the effectiveness of the FRP-strengthening increases with the increase in the ratio of damaged strands.

It is essential to compare the behavior of the strengthened girders and the reference girder because it was found that after cracking load, the strengthened girders PC1N and PC1NE (with an SDR of 14.3%) behave similarly to the reference girder until the steel reinforcement yields, resulting in a significant increase in deflection in the reference girder due to the rapidly increasing crack width, while PC1N and PC1NE

maintain a large portion of their stiffness even after yielding of the reinforcing steel until concrete cover separation occurred. Moreover, the deflection of the strengthened girders PC2N and PC2NE (with an SDR of 28.6%) after cracking load is larger than that of the reference girder at the same load level for a load of 85% of the reference girder's ultimate load, which is approximately equal to the yield load of the reinforcing steel. This finding suggests that evaluating the serviceability requirements of prestressed concrete members with more than 14% of damaged strands before implementing repair techniques is crucial despite the restoration of flexural capacity.

Fig. 10. Load-deflection relationships at mid-span of the tested girders.

TABLE V. SUMMARY OF THE TEST PARAMETERS

Girder ID	P_{cr} (kN)	P_u (kN)	$\delta_{u,mid}$ (mm)	M_u (kN.m)	Reduction in FS relative to RFP (%)	Increase in FS relative to RFP (%)	Failure mode
REF	55	166.24	26.9	91.43	---	---	SY-CC
PC1R	52	157.25	25.5	86.49	5.7	---	SY-CC
PC1N	58	184.56	23.4	101.51	---	11	SY-CCS-CC
PC1NE	59	201.20	26.9	110.66	---	21	SY-CC
PC2R	47	148.72	29.9	81.80	11.8	---	SY-CC
PC2N	53	179.10	25.4	98.51	---	7.7	SY-CCS-CC
PC2NE	53	193.62	28.1	106.49	---	16.5	SY-CC

P_{cr} : first cracking load, P_u : ultimate load, δ_u : ultimate deflection, M_u : ultimate load, FS: flexural strength, SY: bonded steel yielding, CC: concrete crushing, and CCS: concrete cover separation

C. Strain in CFRP Laminates

Load versus strain of CFRP laminates is presented in Figure 11. Before the breaking load, the strain in CFRP laminates is minimal and roughly equal, and it is independent of the fastening systems. After the cracking load, the strain rises noticeably and the rate of strain development increases

dramatically after the bonded steel reinforcement yields. On the other hand, the strain increases in CFRP laminates with and without anchors were nearly the same, whereas the maximum strain in CFRP laminates with anchors was substantially higher than in those without anchors. The maximum strain of the CFRP laminates in the girders without anchors, PC1N and PC2N, was 0.667% and 0.86% respectively, corresponding to 33.35% and 43% of the rupture strain from coupon tests ($\epsilon_{ftr}=2\%$). On the other hand, the maximum strain of the CFRP laminates in the girders with anchors, PC1NE and PC2NE, was 0.78% and 0.96% respectively, corresponding to 39% and 48% of the rupture strain from the coupon tests. Furthermore, the use of FRP strengthening had a considerable influence on concrete strain. CFRP laminates, as previously stated, successfully reduced cracks and delayed their development. This behavior resulted in a higher compressive concrete zone height for NSM-CFRP-strengthened specimens, resulting in lower concrete strain in the strengthened girders at the same loading level as sub-reference girders.

D. Strain in Strands and Influence of CFRP Laminates

The flexural strength remained unaffected by the strands before the occurrence of the first crack because of the small strain increases. Notably, the strand strain increase was determined by subtracting the initial strain ($\approx 0.46\%$) from the actual strain, as illustrated in Figure 11. The behavior of strands was very similar amongst the investigated specimens during this stage. The strain of strands began to increase significantly after cracking. The increase in strand strain of sub-reference specimens was higher than that of the reference girder. However, at the same loading level, the increase in strand strain of NSM-CFRP specimens was less than that of the sub-reference specimens. At the reference girder's permissible load ($P_{ser-REF}$), the increase in the strand strain was about 0.0693% whereas the corresponding increase in strand strains in sub-reference girders, PC1R and PC2R, was 0.0752% and 0.0896% respectively, which showed an increase of 8.6% and 29.5% in comparison with the reference girder REF. Similarly, the strand strain increase in strengthened girders without anchors, PC1N and PC2N, was 0.0651% and 0.0731%, with a reduction of 15% and 22% compared with their counterparts in the sub-reference girders. On the other hand, the strand strain increases in strengthened girders with anchors, PC1NE and PC2NE, was 0.0621% and 0.0712%, with a reduction of 20.7% and 26% compared with their counterparts in the sub-reference girders.

In the loading phase, after the allowable load at the serviceability state, the strand strain increase in the strengthened girders was much smaller than that in the reference girder at the same loading level. For instance, at the maximum load of the reference girder ($P_{u,REF}$), the strand strain increase in the strengthened girders without anchors, PC1N and PC2N, was smaller by 42% and 25.5%. Similarly, the strand strain increase in the strengthened girders with anchors, PC1NE and PC2NE, was smaller by 52.6% and 29%. The CFRP laminates and CFRP U-wrapped anchorages have a considerable influence on the behavior of the strands. Again, the CFRP laminates were able to arrest cracks and delay crack development and they slowed down the degradation of the girder stiffness.

Fig. 11. Load-strain curves of CFRP laminates and strands.

IV. STRAIN INCREASE OF THE STRANDS

Determining the increase in a strain of unbonded strands is a critical case in estimating the flexural strength of unbonded post-tensioned members strengthened with near-surface mounted CFRP laminates. Unfortunately, the design guidelines have only proposed one approach to evaluate the increase in the strain of bonded strands in bonded post-tensioned and pre-tensioned members strengthened with EB-CFRP sheets, whereas the corresponding approaches for unbonded strands in members strengthened with NSM-CFRP laminates are not included. Additionally, the experimental results have exhibited that NSM-CFRP laminates significantly influence the unbonded tendons' behavior. The strand's strain increase of the unbonded post-tensioned members strengthened with CFRPs was evaluated using Tam and Pannell's equations for unbonded tendons in normal reinforced concrete members. For members without end CFRP U-wrapped sheet anchorages, we have:

$$\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} = \Omega \epsilon_c \left(\frac{d_p - c}{L_0} \right) \times \left(1 + 100 \frac{A_f E_f \epsilon_{fe}}{A_c E_c \epsilon_{fu}} \right)^{0.59} \quad (1)$$

For members with CFRP U-wrapped sheet anchorages:

$$\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} = \Omega \epsilon_c \left(\frac{d_p - c}{L_0} \right) \times \left(1 + 100 \frac{A_f E_f \epsilon_{fe}}{A_c E_c \epsilon_{fu}} \right)^{1.35} \quad (2)$$

After that, the overall strain of the unbonded strands $\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}}$ is calculated as:

$$\epsilon_{ps,CFRP} = \epsilon_{pe} + \Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{fe} is the initial strain of strands not including strain losses = $F_p / (E_p A_p)$, F_p (N) is the actual tensile force in strands, A_p (mm^2) and E_p (MPa) are the cross-sectional area and the elasticity modulus of a strand respectively, $\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}}$ is the increase in the strain of strands, ψ is the length of the plastic zone divided by the height of the compressive concrete zone: $\Omega = 10.5$ [18] for simply supported unbonded post-tensioned members which are un-cracked and reinforced with CFRP laminates, and $\Omega = 9.8$ [4] for the pre-cracked unbonded post-tensioned members reinforced with EB-CFRP sheets. ϵ_c is the maximum strain at concrete compression fiber as per ACI 440.2R-17 [11], d_p (mm) is the distance between the compressive concrete zone's furthest point and the centroid of the strand cross-sectional area, c (mm) is the compressive concrete zone's height as per [19], L_0 (mm) is the effective span of the members, and ϵ_{fe} is the actual strain in CFRP laminates at the ultimate applied load.

V. THE PROPOSED FORMULA'S EVALUATION

Equations (1)–(13) were applied to the estimating flexural strength of the 23 unbonded post-tensioned members reinforced with CFRP laminates including the 7 simply supported members reinforced with EB-CFRP laminates investigated in this manuscript and 16 slabs and girders from [4]. The predicted flexural strength, $M_{u,pred}$ was calculated as per ACI 440.2R-17 [11] considering the materials and strength reduction factors to be equal to 1.0, as follows:

Step #1: Estimation of the compressive concrete zone depth (c). The depth of the neutral axis, c (mm), is initially assumed, which could be $h/10$ as per [11], where h is defined as the concrete cross-section height.

Step #2: Evaluating the strain in CFRP laminates, concrete, and strands. The CFRP laminate strain ϵ_{fe} , for failure detected by concrete crushing is given by:

$$\epsilon_{fe} = \epsilon_{cu} \left(\frac{d_f - c}{c} \right) - \epsilon_{bi} \leq \epsilon_{fd} \quad (4)$$

where d_f is the effective CFRP laminates depth, ϵ_{cu} is the concrete's ultimate compressive strain which is equal to 0.003, c is the compressive concrete zone depth, and ϵ_{bi} is the initial strain in substrate:

$$\epsilon_{bi} = \frac{-F_p}{E_c A_c} \left(1 + \frac{e y_b}{r^2} \right) + \frac{M_{DL} y_b}{I_c A_c} \quad (5)$$

where F_p (N) is the initial prestressing force after excluding the losses, e (mm) is the prestressing force's eccentricity concerning the concrete cross-centroid section, y_b (mm) represents the distance from the gross-centroidal section (ignoring steel rebars) to the farthest bottom fiber, r (mm) represents the radius gyration of the member section = $(I_c / A_c)^{0.5}$, I_c (mm^4) represents the moment of inertia of concrete cross concerning the neutral axis, M_{DL} (N.mm) is the applied dead load's moment, and ϵ_{fd} is the strain's debonding described by:

$$\epsilon_{fd} = 0.41 \sqrt{\frac{f'_c}{nE_c t_f}} \leq 0.9 \epsilon_{ffu} \quad (6)$$

$$\epsilon_{fd} = 0.7 \epsilon_{ffu} \quad (7)$$

where f'_c is the concrete strength, ϵ_{ffu} , t_f , and E_f are the ultimate strain, thickness, and elasticity modulus of CFRP respectively, and n represents the CFRP layers numbers. According to [11], (6) is replaced by (7) to determine the debonding strain of NSM-CFRP in this study.

The strain in CFRP laminates, ϵ_{fe} , for failure caused by rupture of strands is:

$$\epsilon_{fe} = (\epsilon_{pu} - \epsilon_{pi}) \left(\frac{d_f - c}{c} \right) - \epsilon_{bi} \leq \epsilon_{fd} \quad (8)$$

where ϵ_{pu} is the strands rupture strain which is equal to 0.05 and ϵ_{pi} is the strand initial strain, which can be estimated as:

$$\epsilon_{pi} = \frac{F_p}{E_c A_c} + \frac{F_p}{E_c A_c} \left(1 + \frac{e^2}{r^2} \right) \quad (9)$$

Step #3: Estimation of the steel rebars strain ϵ_s :

$$\epsilon_s = (\epsilon_{fe} + \epsilon_{bi}) \left(\frac{d - c}{d_f - c} \right) \text{ for tensile rebars} \quad (10)$$

Step #4: Recalculation of the depth of the compressive concrete zone c using the equilibrium of forces:

$$c = \frac{A_p f_{ps} + A_s f_s + A_f f_{fe}}{\alpha_1 f'_c \beta_1 b} \quad (11)$$

where f_{fe} (MPa) is the CFRP laminates stress = $E_f \times \epsilon_{fe}$, f_{ps} (MPa) is the strands stress = $E_p \times \epsilon_{ps} \leq f_{py}$, and f_s (MPa) is the tensile rebars stress = $E_s \times \epsilon_s \leq f_y$.

Step #5: Checking the depth of the compressive concrete zone c . If the assumed value of c (c_{assu}) and re-calculated one (c_{calc}) meet the presented convergence criterion in (12), the appropriate value of c is obtained. If not, the value of c_{assu} is recalculated and the process is repeated starting at the second step until convergence is achieved.

$$\text{Criterion of convergence} = \frac{|c_{assu} - c_{calc}|}{c_{assu}} \leq 0.1\% \quad (12)$$

Fig. 12. Experimental vs. predicted values of flexural capacities.

Step #6: Evaluating the flexural strength of NSM-CFRP strengthened members. Finally, the flexural strength of NSM-CFRP strengthened unbonded post-tensioned members, M_{u-p} , can be calculated as per (13):

$$M_{u-p} = A_p f_{ps} \left(d_p - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + A_f f_{fe} \left(d_f - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + A_s f_s \left(d - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) \quad (13)$$

The predicted-to-experimental flexural strength ratios M_{u-p}/M_{u-E} are illustrated in Table VI and **Error! Reference source not found.** Figure 12. The mean value is 0.948 and COV=0.066 (Coefficient Of Variation). They describe the accuracy of the theoretical strand strain values and their suitability for the prediction of the flexural strength of the NSM-CFRP unbonded post-tensioned members with and without anchorages.

TABLE VI. TABLE I: THE PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL FLEXURAL CAPACITIES

EB CFRP-strengthened UPC members El Meski and Harajli			
Specimens	M_{u-p}	M_{u-E}	M_{u-p} / M_{u-E}
Girders			
UB1_H_F1	41.36	41.80	0.99
UB1_H_F2	51.38	54.30	0.95
UB1_P_F1	34.75	41.40	0.84
UB1_P_F2	51.68	55.60	0.93
UB2_H_F1	54.85	50.50	1.09
UB2_H_F2	63.86	65.50	0.97
UB2_P_F1	50.79	58.50	0.87
UB2_P_F2	58.91	63.30	0.93
Slabs			
US1_H_F1	22.37	21.40	1.05
US1_H_F2	27.32	26.90	1.02
US1_P_F1	19.70	21.60	0.91
US1_P_F2	28.31	30.10	0.94
US2_H_F1	25.44	26.60	0.96
US2_H_F2	30.69	35.80	0.86
US2_P_F1	27.42	29.80	0.92
US2_P_F2	31.68	37.40	0.85
Average			0.941
Standard of deviation			0.070
COV			0.075
NSM-CFRP strengthened UPC girders (current study)			
REF	90.72	91.43	0.992
PC1R	85.72	86.49	0.991
PC1N	99.88	101.51	0.984
PC1NE	100.65	110.66	0.909
PC2R	80.50	81.80	0.984
PC2N	96.05	98.51	0.975
PC2NE	96.79	106.49	0.909
Average			0.964
Standard of deviation			0.038
COV			0.039
For all members			
Average			0.948
Standard of deviation			0.062
COV			0.066

M_{u-p} is the predicted moment capacity and M_{u-E} is the experimental moment capacity

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of post-tensioned concrete girders subjected to partial strand damage and strengthened by NSM-CFRP laminates with and without CFRP U-wrap sheet anchorages

was researched and evaluated in this work. The following conclusions are derived from this study's experimental results:

- The flexural capacity of post-tensioned girders reduces as the SDR increases. The flexural strength was reduced by 6% and 12% for girders with strand damage of 14.3% and 28.6% respectively. On the other hand, at all loading stages, the deflection increases as the SDR increases.
- Near-surface mounted techniques using CFRP laminates enhance flexural capacity by controlling crack development. In comparison with the nondamaged girder, the NSM-CFRP laminates enhanced the flexural capacity by 11% corresponding to strand damage of 14.3%, whereas the flexural capacity increased by 7.7%, corresponding to strand damage of 28.6%.
- The use of U-wrap anchorages eliminates the cover separation and effectively enhances the flexural strength for strengthened girders. In comparison with the nondamaged girder, the NSM-CFRP laminates enhanced the flexural capacity by 21% corresponding to strand damage of 14.3%, whereas the flexural capacity increased by 16.5%, corresponding to strand damage of 28.6%.
- The CFRP laminates significantly affect the behavior of the strands. At the same loading level, the strain increase of the strands in the strengthened girders was much smaller than that of the damaged girder. For example, at the service load of the undamaged reference girder, the increase in strand strain of the strengthened girders is reduced by 15% and 22% respectively, compared to the increase in strand strain of the corresponding damaged girders. On the other hand, this effect increases considerably when using U-wrap anchorages.
- The proposed procedure for predicting strand strain rises in unbonded post-tension girders enhanced with NSM-CFRP laminates, effectively predicts flexural strength with high accuracy and minimal variation (average = 0.956 and COV = 0.064).

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Enhancing Voltage Profile and Power Loss Reduction Considering Distributed Generation (DG) Resources

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Abstract-In recent years, Distributed Generation (DG) has received attention due to its benefits on the distribution network. In this paper, the influence of DG along with several techniques for mitigating the detrimental impact on voltage profile and power losses was examined. The test system of 132 KV residential test feeder was selected, examined, and modeled in the Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP). Various tests were carried out to determine the influence of DG on the distribution network. Results were compared with, and with-out DG, taking into account the voltage profile. When injecting DG with unity power factor at different buses in a radial test system, it was discovered that when the right DG size and type is injected at the ideal position, the voltage profile improves while the power losses are reduced. When an un-deterministic DG is injected at multiple points on the test feeder, no improvement in voltage profile was observed. When the cross sectional area of conductors is increased and a DG is injected at optimal locations, a positive impact on voltage profile is observed while a detrimental impact on power losses were also analyzed. These findings may be useful for many distribution firms regarding the future expansion of the power systems and the proliferation of DG.

*Keywords-*distributed generation; voltage level; power losses; synchronous and induction generator

I. INTRODUCTION

Electricity consumption is quickly expanding in all the sectors of global economy. Currently, a number of factors are creating significant challenges to the power supply, including pollution, depletion of local energy supplies, and the need to improve the energy infrastructure. Promoting the broad use of Distributed Generation (DG) is a strategy to fulfil the continually expanding demand for power [1]. The government's energy policy aims of reducing emissions, ensuring a dependable energy supply, and promoting competitive markets will all benefit from increased deployment of DG technologies.

DG may work as a single construction, such as a home or a firm, or it can be part of a small grid (that is also linked to the larger power distribution network), e.g. at a huge industrial site, military base, or college campus [2, 3]. DG can support the distribution of clean, dependable power to additional consumers while also reduces power losses along the distribution and transmission lines when inserted to the electric utility's lesser voltage distribution lines. Some of the benefits of installing DG include increased electric system reliability, improved power quality, reduced system energy loss, and improved voltage profile. DG can work both as conventional energy sources (non-renewable) and non-conventional energy sources (renewable) [4]. Wind energy, PV energy, and small hydro energy are the most capable renewable energy resources in DG, while coal, petroleum, and natural gas are all non-renewable energy sources [5].

Nowadays the need for electricity is rapidly rising, while one of the most significant challenges for power and electrical engineers is to produce power from non-conventional energy sources in order to meet the rising demand while minimizing the environmental impact of power generation. However, whenever a new generation is linked with the power distribution system, issues come up because traditional distribution systems were built to run radially, without taking into account the new generation's future integration [6, 7]. Using DG is necessary to assure reliable power generation and dropping power losses, while, on the other hand, extensive use of these technologies brings additional challenges to power systems such as voltage regulation, optimal location, and power loss issues [8]. The installation of DG may destabilize the system voltage and create over-voltage and volatility. If management is not appropriately achieved, the inserting of DG may raise the system losses in the distribution network, depending on the network structure, the penetration level, and the nature of DG technology [9, 10].

In this research paper, various cases are considered in order to see their effect on voltage level and power losses. Six-bus bar distribution systems were considered as test cases. They were designed and examined in the Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP). Firstly, results were obtained without the injection of a DG unit. This case is used as a model for the other cases. In the second case, a DG unit (synchronous generator) is injected at busbar-3 and in the third case a DG unit (synchronous generator) is injected at busbar-6. In the fourth case, a DG unit (induction generator/wind generator) is injected at busbar-3 and in the fifth case a DG unit (induction generator/wind generator) is injected at busbar-6. Moreover, two more cases were considered as "injecting un-deterministic DG in a distribution system" and "increasing a cross sectional area of the transmission cable". The results were compared in order to determine the best DG size and location.

II. THE IMPACT OF DISTRIBUTION GENERATION

The term "Distributed Generation" (DG) refers to energy generation close to the point of consumption. Because of its good impact on the electrical distribution system, DG has received a lot of attention. DG has the potential to improve grid dependability by lowering transmission losses, providing greater voltage support, and enhancing power quality. Because DG uses renewable energy resources, it has lower initial cost and reduces greenhouse gas emissions, resulting in more clean and efficient energy [11]. Tiny combustion and micro turbines, micro steam turbines, battery storage, comparatively tiny hydro dams, photovoltaic (PV) panels, wind turbines, power storage systems, and other power generation technologies are being developed or are now in use [12]. Distributed Resources (DRs) can reduce T&D system losses, enhance service performance and stability, improve voltage strength, and reduce T&D system crowding [13]. The connection of DG may vary the voltage level along a feeder by varying the direction and amplitude of actual and reactive power flows. Furthermore, the effect of DG on voltage parameters might be positive or negative depending on the distribution network, the distributed generator features, and the DG site. Due to the immense injection of active and reactive power, overvoltage may occur when DG units are installed along with power distribution feeders [14, 15]. DG is the best option to satisfy the increasing requirements of power and improve voltage profile. This is dependent on the DG injection site and the kind of DG that is to be inserted in the power system or grid. If a DG is inserted into the power system in an ad hoc manner, voltage profiles may vary [16].

DG has a big impact on power losses as well. DG must be properly coordinated with the distribution system in order to have a positive impact. Because DG and its effect on the system are proportional to feeder requirements and ability, the injection of DG into the system should be precisely enhanced to avoid this kind of problems [17]. The DG is a significant standard that has to be examined in order to be able to get a better consistency of the system with reduced losses. DG has negative impact as well: if not injected in a proper way, it may result in power losses [8].

III. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

Because of the slow changing nature of power networks, steady state analysis is used. In the steady state, disruption-induced transients are supposed to be unchanged. The operational technique for the steady state analysis is called power flow analysis. The voltage magnitude and phase angle, as well as the flow of active and reactive power across the network at all buses, may all be found using load flow analysis. The Newton-Raphson method is discussed below as one of the approaches for solving the power flow equations. The approach begins by solving the issue with only two equations and two variables. After that, the study will be extended to the solution of the load flow equation. Consider the following equation for a two-variable function Z_A and Z_B equal to a constant C_A as:

$$F_A(Z_A, Z_B) = C_A \quad (1)$$

$$F_B(Z_A, Z_B) = C_B \quad (2)$$

$$C_A = F_A(Z_A, Z_B) = F_A(Z_A^{(0)} + \Delta Z_A^{(0)}, Z_B + Z_B^{(0)}) \quad (3)$$

$$C_B = F_B(Z_A, Z_B) = F_B(Z_A^{(0)} + \Delta Z_A^{(0)}, Z_B + Z_B^{(0)}) \quad (4)$$

Expanding (3) and (4) in Taylor's series we have:

$$C_A = F_A(Z_A^{(0)} + Z_B^{(0)}) + \Delta Z_A^{(0)} \frac{\partial F_A}{\partial Z_1} \Big|^{(0)} + \Delta Z_B^{(0)} \frac{\partial F_A}{\partial Z_2} \Big|^{(0)} + \dots \quad (5)$$

$$C_B = F_B(Z_A^{(0)} + Z_B^{(0)}) + \Delta Z_A^{(0)} \frac{\partial F_B}{\partial Z_1} \Big|^{(0)} + \Delta Z_B^{(0)} \frac{\partial F_B}{\partial Z_2} \Big|^{(0)} + \dots \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_A - F_A(Z_A^{(0)}, Z_B^{(0)}) \\ C_B - F_B(Z_A^{(0)}, Z_B^{(0)}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial F_A}{\partial Z_1} & \frac{\partial F_A}{\partial Z_2} \\ \frac{\partial F_B}{\partial Z_1} & \frac{\partial F_B}{\partial Z_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta Z_A^{(0)} \\ \Delta Z_B^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta C_A^{(0)} \\ \Delta C_B^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} = J^{(0)} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta Z_A^{(0)} \\ \Delta Z_B^{(0)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

For a total of N buses, the intended voltage at any bus A and P_1 and Q_1 are given as:

$$V_A = \frac{1}{Y_{AA}} \left[\frac{P_1 - jQ_1}{V_A^*} - \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \right] \quad (9)$$

$$P_1 - jQ_1 = (Y_{AA} V_A + \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n) \quad (10)$$

$$P_1 - jQ_1 = V_A^* \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \quad (11)$$

$$P_1 = V_A^* \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \quad (12)$$

$$Q_1 = -\text{Im} \{ V_A^* \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \} \quad (13)$$

The Voltage at bus and line entries in polar form is:

$$V_A = |V_A| < \delta_A; V_n = |V_n| < \delta_n; Y_{an} = |Y_{kn}| < \theta_{An}$$

By exchanging these in (11):

$$P_1 - jQ_1 = \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n < \theta_{An} + \delta_n - \delta_A \quad (14)$$

$$P_1 = \sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \cos(\theta_{An} + \delta_n - \delta_A) \quad (15)$$

and:

$$Q_1 = -\sum_{n=1}^N Y_{An} V_n \sin(\theta_{An} + \delta_n - \delta_A) \quad (16)$$

Now by relating (8) with the power system we have:

$$\Delta C_A^{(0)} = \Delta P_1 = P_{1spec} - Q_{1calc}$$

$$\Delta C_B^{(0)} = \Delta Q_1 = Q_{1spec} - Q_{1calc}$$

$$\Delta Z_A^{(0)} = \Delta \delta_A^{(0)}$$

$$\Delta Z_B = |V_A^{(0)}|$$

The partial derivative of real and reactive power is contained in the Jacobian "J." The following is the fundamental iterative procedure:

- Start with the previous case's outcome.
- Calculate the dispersion and stop when the acceptance value's bound exceeds it.
- Calculate the Jacobian's power flow, update the value, and return to the previous step.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this research, different cases were analyzed/investigated. In the first case, the power flow was tested on the test scheme without injecting a DG unit. Voltage profile and power losses on each bus bar were monitored. Furthermore, synchronous generator and induction generator were injected on two optimum points which were selected by the hit and trial method, which resulted to finding that Bus bar 3 and Bus bar 6 were suitable for the installation of DG. Furthermore, an undeterministic DG was injected and voltage level and power losses were monitored. As a result, disturbance occurred in the overall network. Finally, the conductor's cross sectional area was raised, and the influence on voltage profile and power losses was noted.

V. TEST CASES

A. Case-1: Without DG Unit Injection

The load flow evaluation of the radial distribution system in Case 1 is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Without inserting a DG unit.

In this case, there is no injecting DG unit and the load demand is met by the electricity grid. This situation is used as a model for future cases. The voltage profile at various buses is displayed. The red color demonstrates critical situation of buses. We can see that Bus bars 4, 5, and 6 are in critical situation. Table I shows the power losses at various points of the distribution system. The entire active power losses in this situation are 542.7KW, whereas the total reactive power losses are 1048.6KVAR.

TABLE I. TOTAL POWER LOSSES WITHOUT DG INJECTION

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	158.9	31.7
Line-2	217.9	32.1
Line-3	95.8	14.1
Line-4	44.7	6.6
Line-5	3.4	0.5
T1	3.3	146.5
T2	2.1	92.4
T3	4.3	192.2
T4	4.1	183.4
T5	3.1	141.1
T6	2.8	110.1
T7	2.4	97.8
Total	542.7	1048.6

B. Case-2: Synchronous Generator Inserted at Bus-3

Power flow analysis of case-2 is illustrated in Figure 2. During this case, a DG unit is inserted at Bus bar 3. A DG unit (synchronous generator) of 2.5MW is attached in the system at Bus bar 3 and the load demand is achieved by the electricity grid. The voltage level is enhanced at various buses when linked to the previous case, as illustrated in Figure 2. In this case, Bus bar 5 and Bus bar 6 are in critical state. Table II shows the power losses at various points of the distribution system. The entire active system losses are 376.8KW, whereas the overall reactive system losses are 1025.4KVAR. When compared to the previous case the power losses are reduced.

Fig. 2. A DG unit (synchronous generator) is inserted at Bus-3.

TABLE II. POWER LOSSES WHEN A SYNCHRONOUS GENERATOR IS INSERTED AT BUS BAR 3

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	155.0	39.2
Line-2	108.2	27.4
Line-3	68.5	13.0
Line-4	22.0	5.6
Line-5	1.7	0.4
T1	3.3	146.6
T2	2.0	90.7
T3	4.2	188.4
T4	4.0	178.3
T5	3.0	135.8
T6	2.7	106.1
T7	2.3	93.9
Total	376.8	1025.4

C. Case-3. Synchronous Generator inserted at Bus-6

The power flow study of Case 3 is illustrated in Figure 3. A DG unit (synchronous generator) of 2.5MW is inserted in the network at Bus bar 6 and the load demand is met by the power grid.

Fig. 3. A DG unit (synchronous generator) is inserted at Bus 6.

TABLE III. POWER LOSSES WHEN A SYNCHRONOUS GENERATOR IS INSERTED AT BUS BAR 6

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	153.6	38.9
Line-2	107.1	27.1
Line-3	26.7	11.2
Line-4	10.1	5.0
Line-5	0.8	0.4
T1	3.3	146.5
T2	2.0	90.7
T3	4.2	188.4
T4	3.9	176.1
T5	3.0	133.4
T6	2.6	104.4
T7	2.3	92.2
Total	319.5	1014.2

In this situation, the DG source and the power grid work together to meet the load requirements. The voltage level is enhanced at various buses when compared to the previous case. Table III shows the overall power losses in the distribution network at various locations. The entire active power losses when a synchronous generator unit is inserted at Bus bar-6 are 319.5KW, whereas the entire reactive power losses are 1014.2KVAR. These losses are decreased when compared to DG unit placed at Bus Bar-3.

D. Case-4: Induction/Wind Generator inserted at Bus-3

The load flow study of case 4 is shown in Figure 4. A DG unit (induction/wind generator) of 2.5MW is linked with the network at Bus bar 3 and the load demand is met by the grid. The electricity grid and the DG source work together to meet the load requirements. In this case Bus bars 4, 5, and 6 are in critical state. Table IV shows the overall power losses in the distribution network at various locations. The entire active power losses are 621.7KW when the 2.5MW induction generator unit is linked at Bus 3, whereas the total reactive power losses are 1046.9KVAR. Compared to the prior examples, the losses are increased.

Fig. 4. A DG unit (induction/wind generator) is inserted at Bus 3.

TABLE IV. POWER LOSSES WHEN INDUCTION/WIND GENERATOR IS INSERTED AT BUS BAR 3

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	296.6	39.8
Line-2	189.2	27.9
Line-3	95.0	14.0
Line-4	44.3	6.5
Line-5	1.7	0.4
T1	3.3	147.8
T2	2.0	91.8
T3	4.2	190.8
T4	4.0	181.9
T5	3.1	140.0
T6	2.7	109.2
T7	2.4	96.8
Total	621.7	1046.9

E. Case-5: Induction/Wind Generator inserted at Bus-6

The load flow examination of case 5 is illustrated in Figure 5. A 2.5MW DG unit (induction/wind generator) is attached to the network at Bus bar 6 and the electricity grid and the DG source work together to meet the load demand. Table V shows the overall power losses in the distribution network at various locations. The entire active system losses are 445.0KW, whereas the entire reactive system losses are 1012.8KVAR. These losses are improved when compared to case 4.

Fig. 5. A DG unit (induction/wind generator) inserted at Bus 6.

TABLE V. POWER LOSSES WHEN INDUCTION/WIND GENERATOR IS INSERTED AT BUS BAR 6

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	264.5	39.0
Line-2	68.7	22.8
Line-3	45.3	11.5
Line-4	27.1	6.9
Line-5	18.2	4.6
T1	3.3	147.6
T2	2.0	90.4
T3	4.2	187.8
T4	3.9	175.2
T5	2.9	132.4
T6	2.6	103.6
T7	2.3	90.9
Total	445.0	1012.8

F. Case-6: Inserting a Small Un-Deterministic DG Unit

In this situation, a small DG is inserted in the system and its effect on voltage level and power losses are examined. The power flow analysis for this situation is shown in Figure 6. The red color indicates the critical state of buses. Bus bars 4, 5, and 6 are in critical state. Table VI shows the overall power losses in the distribution network at various locations. The entire active power losses in this situation are 518.7KW, while the entire reactive power losses are 1031.5KVAR.

Fig. 6. Load flow analysis when inserting un-deterministic DG in the distribution system.

TABLE VI. INJECTION OF UN-DETERMINISTIC DG IN THE DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	274.8	40.5
Line-2	97.0	24.6
Line-3	82.1	12.1
Line-4	29.8	5.7
Line-5	13.4	2.0
T1	3.3	148.6
T2	2.0	91.6
T3	4.2	190.3
T4	4.0	179.6
T5	3.0	136.4
T6	2.7	106.6
T7	2.3	93.6
Total	518.7	1031.5

G. Case-7: Increasing the Cross Sectional Area of the Conductor

In this case, the Cross Sectional Area (CSA) of the transmission cable is increased in order to analyze the effect of voltage profile and power losses. By considering the CSA of the conductor, its resistance is equal to:

$$R = \rho L / A$$

where ρ is the resistivity, L the length, and A the CSA.

The above equation shows that CSA A is inversely proportional to the resistance R and by increasing the CSA, the R will be decreased and maximum current will flow. Figure 7 illustrates the findings of the load flow analysis. The power grid and the un-deterministic DG unit meet the load requirements. Table VII shows the overall power losses in the distribution network at various locations. The overall active power losses are 426.7KW and the total reactive power losses are 1019.7KVAR. Comparing with the power losses from the previous situation, we see that the power losses are much improved.

Fig. 7. Total power losses of the system by increasing the CSA of the conductor.

TABLE VII. INCREASING THE CSA OF THE ONDUCTOR

Branch/Circuit ID	Losses	
	KW	KVAR
Line-1	270.5	40.0
Line-2	95.5	24.2
Line-3	23.5	9.9
Line-4	11.5	4.8
Line-5	3.9	1.6
T1	3.3	148.5
T2	2.0	91.5
T3	4.2	190.2
T4	3.9	177.4
T5	3.0	134.2
T6	2.6	105.0
T7	2.3	92.5
Total	426.7	1019.7

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the obtained results and Voltage profile analysis and power losses analysis from different cases are discussed in detail.

A. Voltage Profile Analysis

When various kinds of DG units are inserted to the radial distribution network, they have various impacts on the voltage level. The entire results are illustrated in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII. RADIAL FEEDER VOLTAGE ARRANGEMENT

Bus bar no	Case (1)	Case (2)	Case (3)	Case (4)	Case (5)	Case (6)	Case (7)
1	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
2	10.81	10.8	10.81	10.75	10.75	10.7	10.71
3	10.51	10.64	10.64	10.56	10.66	10.57	10.58
4	10.31	10.49	10.58	10.36	10.61	10.44	10.53
5	10.17	10.42	10.54	10.22	10.59	10.39	10.5
6	10.13	10.4	10.53	10.19	10.62	10.42	10.5

1) Voltage Level without DG Injection

In this case, no DG is inserted. Figure 8 illustrates the radial fall in voltage level from the source to the load. The decrease in voltage profile is caused by the impedance of the line.

2) Effect on Voltage Profile when a DG (Synchronous Generator) is Inserted at Bus-3 and Bus-6

Figure 9 shows the voltage level at different Bus Bars when a synchronous generator is injected at Buses 3 and 6. It can be seen that the voltage profile improves when the synchronous generator is injected at Bus-6.

3) Effect on Voltage Level when a DG (Induction/Wind Generator) is Inserted at Bus-3 and Bus-6

Here, the voltage comparison is made at different Bus bars when an induction generator is injected at Bus-3 and Bus-6. It is shown in Figure 10 that the voltage profile is improved when the induction generator is injected at Bus-3 and Bus-6 as compared to the base case, but when compared to the previous case, the synchronous generator injected at Bus 6 gives the best result.

Fig. 8. Voltage level when no DG is injected.

Fig. 9. Voltage profile when a synchronous generator is inserted at Bus 3 and Bus 6.

4) Effect on Voltage Level when Injecting an Un-Deterministic DG Unit and Increasing the Conductor's CSA

In this case an undeterministic DG unit is injected and the CSA of the conductor is increased and its impact on the voltage

level is observed. It is shown that Voltage level is improved when the CSA of the conductor is increased. The result obtained is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 10. Voltage profile when an induction generator is inserted at Bus 3 and Bus 6.

Fig. 11. Voltage profile when an un-deterministic DG is inserted and the CSA of the conductor is increased.

B. Power Losses Analysis

When various kinds of DG units are linked to the radial distribution system, different effects on power losses occur.

1) Total Power Losses in the Base Case

In this case, the power losses are observed without injecting a DG unit. The total losses are shown in Figure 12. Impedances in the lines cause these losses. No DG unit is inserted and all power is supplied by the electrical grid. Each cable carries current from the grid to the customer locations, resulting in significant power losses.

2) Power Losses when a DG (Synchronous Generator) is Inserted at Bus 3 and Bus 6

Figure 13 shows the total power losses in KW when a synchronous generator is inserted at Bus 3 and Bus 6. It is seen that the power losses are reduced when the generator is injected at Bus 6.

Fig. 12. Total power losses of the base case.

Fig. 13. Total power losses when a synchronous generator is inserted at Bus 3 and Bus 6.

3) Power Losses when a DG Unit (Induction/Wind Generator) is Inserted at Bus Bars 3 and 6

Figure 14 shows the total power losses when an induction generator is injected at Buses 3 and 6. It is seen that the injection caused increase in power losses due to the absorption of reactive power by the induction generator.

Fig. 14. Total power losses when an induction generator is injected at Buses 3 and 6.

Inserting a synchronous generator at Bus 6 has an outstanding result in comparison with the other cases. As a result, injecting a DG unit at an optimal position, such as Bus bar 6, and a DG type, such as the synchronous generator, will have positive impact on power losses.

4) Power Losses when an Un-Deterministic DG is Inserted in the Distribution System and the Conductor CSA is Increased

In this case, an un-deterministic DG unit is injected and the CSA of the conductor is increased and the impact on power

losses is observed. It is seen that the power losses will be reduced when the CSA of the conductor is increased. The entire power losses are shown in Figure 15.

Fig. 15. Total power losses when an un-deterministic DG is injected and the CSA of the conductor is increased.

The novelty of this research work is that a real test system of 132KV residential test feeder is modeled in ETAP. Various tests were carried out to determine the influence of DG on the distribution network. Various researchers work on IEEE built-in systems and very limited work has been conducted by taking or selecting a real test system. DG was injected at multiple points on the test feeder, and improvement in voltage profile and reduction in power losses were observed. These findings will be useful to many distribution firms around the world, and specifically in Pakistan, in the future expansion of the power systems and the proliferation of DG.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this research paper, the effect of DG on voltage level and system losses in a radial test system was observed and different cases were considered. It was concluded that by connecting a synchronous generator at Bus 6, the voltage level improved and power losses were reduced the most. Attaching an induction/wind generator considering as DG unit close to a load improves the voltage profile, but, due to the immersion of reactive power by the induction generator, the power losses will be increased. Moreover, it was concluded that when an un-deterministic DG unit is inserted in the distribution system, it will cause disturbance in the whole system. Inserting un-deterministic DGs has negative effect on the voltage level and power losses. Furthermore, it was concluded that by increasing the CSA of the conductor, the voltage level can be elevated and power losses can be reduced. The effects of various conventional and non-conventional DG units can be examined more in the future, considering harmonics and reliability.

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A Real-Time Application of Singular Spectrum Analysis to Object Tracking with SIFT

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Abstract- This study combined SIFT and SSA to propose a novel algorithm for real-time object tracking. The proposed algorithm utilizes an intermediate fixed-size buffer and a modified SSA algorithm. Since the complete reconstruction step of the SSA algorithm was unnecessary, it was considerably simplified. In addition, the execution time of a Matlab implementation of the SSA algorithm was compared with a respective C++ implementation. Moreover, the performance of the two different matching algorithms in the detection, the FlannBasedMatcher and Brute-Force matcher algorithms of the OpenCV library, was compared.

Keywords- object tracking; object detection; computer vision; SIFT; SSA

I. INTRODUCTION

Object tracking or visual tracking has been employed, studied, and commercialized in a broad spectrum of applications such as Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM), traffic surveillance, pedestrian counting, hand gesture recognition, tracking the path of protein stress granules in cells, and video compression [1]. Object tracking can be defined as dynamic object detection [2]. The main problems of object tracking are common with object detection, such as occlusion, clutter in the background, viewpoint changes due to affine transformation such as translation and rotation, scale changes (zoom in and out), and photometric deformation such as distortion, blur, and illumination changes. The most important challenge is still the speed or real-time performance of the online tracker, such as the tracker used in visual servoing in robotics [3]. On the other hand, object tracking has some problems of its own. An optimal algorithm for visual tracking can vary depending on the camera's position, the number of cameras, and the number of moving objects. In the case of a stationary camera, background removal can simplify the task by eliminating the stationary pixels [4]. If the number of moving objects and the target object increase, then the task becomes complicated. Object tracking consists of two important steps: detecting the object of interest and tracking it in the following frames [5]. Object detection can be defined as template matching in which a template or a model is detected within a scene. Typically, a template is the picture of an object

of interest. Detection can be defined as enclosing a given template in the scene in a rectangle. In object tracking, the basic task is to track the object as long as it exists in the scene.

Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) is one of the most robust local descriptors which can be used in object tracking [6-8]. It has been utilized in a broad spectrum of applications, such as face recognition, gender recognition [9], and smoke detection [10]. It is a good candidate to tackle the problems of tracking, such as translation, rotation, occlusion, and scale. A method was proposed in [11] to track objects by combining SIFT with mean shift. In [12], SIFT was utilized with Kanade-Lucas-Tomasi Tracker (KLT) [13] for UAV-based applications. In this approach, the object was detected with SIFT, and its location was computed with KLT. Since the algorithms are not perfectly robust to all image transformations and deformations, the object of interest can be lost or detected with low accuracy during any object tracking task. In such cases, the pose can be recovered or improved by using filters or smoothing. Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA) is a method of time series analysis based on multivariate statistics. It is also known as the principal component analysis of time series [14]. SSA is considered to be a non-parametric (model-free) filtering technique. However, it can also be used for modeling [15]. It has been mainly used in applications that require post-processing [16, 17]. SSA was combined with the Kalman filter to smooth real-time positioning data obtained from the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) in [18]. However, there is no description of how SSA was implemented in real-time. A rank-one eigenvector update was proposed in a recursive framework in [19] for the identification of structural damage detection in real-time by utilizing First-Order Perturbation (FOP) for the Henkel matrix.

This paper proposes an object-tracking algorithm utilizing SIFT and SSA. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that employs SIFT and SSA in object tracking. As SSA always requires a batch of data, its real-time implementation was carried out using a fixed-sized buffer. Since the real-time implementation of SAA does not require a full reconstruction step by diagonal averaging, the reconstruction algorithm was considerably simplified.

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II. METHOD

This section investigates the SSA algorithm, provides the real-time implementation, describes object tracking with a template matching algorithm, and provides the details of the experiments.

A. Singular Spectrum Analysis

The SSA algorithm can be summarized in four steps: embedding, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), grouping, and finally, reconstruction. In the embedding step, a Henkel matrix was constructed from the input signal. Each column of the Henkel matrix is a portion of the signal obtained by windowing with a selected window length. This process is also called a caterpillar since it behaves as such. If the length of the raw signal is n and the window length is l , the size of the Henkel matrix is $l \times k$, where l is the rows, k is the columns, and $k = n - l + 1$. Figure 1 shows an example of the embedding step. In this example, a Henkel matrix is created from an input signal. The size of the signal is 10, and the window length is 4. Therefore, the size of the resulting matrix is 7×4 .

Fig. 1. An example of the embedding step.

In the SVD step, the singular value decomposition of the trajectory matrix is computed. If X is the Henkel matrix, then the trajectory matrix is XX^T , where X^T is the transpose of X . The Henkel matrix can be written as a sum of different and independent matrices with the aid of SVD. This decomposition can be stated as follows:

$$X = X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_m \quad (1)$$

where each X_i is called an elementary matrix. Each elementary matrix X_i is calculated as follows:

$$X_i = \sqrt{\lambda_i} U_i V_i^T, i = 1, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

where U_i denotes the eigenvectors of SVD, and each vector V_i is calculated as follows:

$$V_i = X^T \frac{U_i}{\sqrt{\lambda_i}}, i = 1, \dots, m \quad (3)$$

Each elementary matrix X_i corresponds to one of the eigenvalues of SVD. It should be noted that:

$$\|X_i\|^2 = \lambda_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (4)$$

The contribution of each elementary matrix to X is proportional to its corresponding eigenvalue λ_i . The eigenvalues are sorted in decreasing order. In SSA, elementary matrices corresponding to small eigenvalues are considered to be the noise portion of the signal. This portion is excluded in the grouping step:

$$\hat{X} = \sum_{i=1}^r X_i \quad (5)$$

where $r < m$. The value of r is decided by looking at the ratio of the sum of the first r eigenvalues to the sum of all eigenvalues. If the value of this ratio is greater than a certain threshold, the sum of the first r elementary matrices (5) is considered to be an optimal approximation of the Henkel matrix X . Finally, in reconstruction, the optimal approximation of the Henkel Matrix, \hat{X} is converted to a time series. The reconstruction operation should be considered to be the inverse operation of the construction of the Henkel matrix from the raw signal. This inverse operation is performed by diagonal averaging on the approximated Henkel matrix (Figure 1). The diagonal averaging is realized in three steps: top diagonalization, center, diagonalization, and tail diagonalization on the approximated Henkel matrix as follows:

$$b_t = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{t+1} \sum_{i=1}^{t+1} a_{i,t-i+2}, & \text{if } 0 \leq t < L^* - 1 \\ \frac{1}{L^*} \sum_{i=1}^{L^*} a_{i,t-i+2}, & \text{if } L^* - 1 \leq t < K^* \\ \frac{1}{N-t} \sum_{i=t-K^*+2}^{N-K^*+1} a_{i,t-i+2}, & \text{if } K^* \leq t < N \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $a_{i,j}$, $1 \leq i \leq L$, $1 \leq j \leq K$ denote entries of the approximated Henkel matrix and, b_t , $0 \leq t < N$, are entries of the reconstructed time series.

Two parameters affect the result of SSA: the window length L and the reconstruction parameter r . The last one is determined by the eigenvalues as explained above. In general, the first or at least the sum of two eigenvalues constitutes the largest portion of the sum of all eigenvalues. However, there is no rule on how to select L . The choice of L affects the result of the filter. If L increases, the smoothing effect of the filter increases. This value can be determined by test and trial.

B. Real-Time Implementation of SSA

The real-time implementation of SSA was conducted by using a fixed-size buffer (Figure 2). At first, this buffer is filled with data. The size of the buffer is determined beforehand. So, this method requires a time delay to start filtering. Once the buffer is full, the filtering operation starts. As new frames arrive, the buffer is updated. However, for the real-time implementation of SSA, there is no need for full reconstruction by diagonal averaging. Since the last frame is written on the last element of the buffer, it is sufficient to recover only the last element of the approximated trajectory matrix, as follows:

$$f = \hat{X}(l-1, k-1) \quad (7)$$

where f is the data filtered and the size of the approximated Henkel matrix \hat{X} is $l \times k$. It is assumed that the first index starts from zero. Thus, using (7), the reconstruction algorithm is significantly simplified by omitting diagonal averaging, compared to (6). This method is called Real-Time SSA (RT-SSA).

Fig. 2. Fixed-size buffer used for real-time implementation of SSA.

C. Object Tracking with Template Matching

Template matching is the task of detecting a given template within a given scene. Typically, a template is the picture of an object of interest. Detection can be defined as enclosing a given template in the scene in a rectangle. Figures 3 and 4 show the template used in this study and the detection task respectively.

Fig. 3. A matched sample frame from the video.

Fig. 4. A detection example from the video.

This study used SIFT for object detection. SIFT is a local descriptor, typically invariant to local occlusion [20]. SIFT has two main parts: keypoint detection and feature description. Keypoints (or salient points) are detected on the Gaussian scale-space pyramid [21, 22]. This kind of keypoint detection makes the algorithm scale (zoom in and out) invariant. A dominant orientation of each keypoint is computed using the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG). This computation makes the algorithm orientation invariant. Finally, a feature vector for each keypoint is calculated using HOG [23]. The normalization of the feature vector makes it invariant to changes in illumination. In summary, SIFT is invariant to translation, rotation, scale change (zoom in and out), partial occlusion, and illumination change. The runtime performance of SIFT mainly depends on the size of the image and the number of the extracted keypoints. In this study, SIFT was implemented using OpenCV 4.5.5.

Once the keypoints and features are computed both on the template and scene, the following task is matching. For the matching algorithm, the FlannBasedMatcher of OpenCV can be utilized. The Fast Library for Approximated Nearest Neighbor (FLANN) speeds up the matching task by using the k-nearest neighbor [24]. If the number of the extracted keypoints is low, the Brute-Force matcher of OpenCV can alternatively be utilized. Figure 3 shows the SIFT keypoints on both the template and the scene, as well as the matched keypoints. Once the matching pairs between the template and the scene are detected, the template's corners should be projected on the scene. A homography matrix is needed for this projection. The OpenCV findHomography function was used to obtain the homography matrix using the RANSAC algorithm. Finally, the OpenCV perspectiveTransform function provides four corners of the rectangular polygon that encloses the template in the scene.

D. Experimental Setup

An Everest SC-HD03 webcam was used to capture the video. In the video, the template (a penholder) was moved by hand. It was mobilized, moved away from the camera, zoomed in, rotated, and twisted in different directions. During this process, the pixel coordinates of the center point of the detected four corners of the template in the scene were considered to be the pose of the object. This center point is shown by a blue circle in Figure 4. The video consists of 1439 frames. The size of each frame was 640×480.

A C/C++ code was written for SSA and RT-SSA, using the Eigen library [25], with floating-point arithmetic. The C/C++ code is available in [26]. On the other hand, Matlab utilizes double-point arithmetic by default. The C/C++ code was compiled with GCC 9.4.0 on Ubuntu 20.04 LTS and run on an Intel i9-10850K CPU @3.60GHZ with 16GB RAM. The parameters, notations, and abbreviations used in the results are shown in Table I. As was observed, the first eigenvalue always constituted more than 90% of all. So, the reconstruction parameter r of SSA was taken as 1 for all tests.

TABLE I. NOTATIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS USED IN RESULTS

Notation/Abbreviation	Explanation
Pose	Position of the object (x and y coordinates)
FLANN	FlannBasedMatcher of OpenCV
Brute-Force	Brute-Force matcher of OpenCV
Filter-30-3	RT-SSA with a buffer of size 30, and window length of 3
Filter-30-9	RT-SSA with a buffer of size 30, and window length of 9

III. RESULTS

This section, initially, presents the results of template matching according to two different matching methodologies, FLANN and Brute-Force. Then, the results of the execution time of SAA are provided. Finally, the results of the application of real-time SAA to object tracking are summarized.

A. Template Matching

Figure 5 shows the results of FLANN and Brute-Force matching. As shown, FLANN lost the pose of the object in frame 562. However, the Brute-Force graph shows no loss at

any frame. The average number of keypoints on the scene is 67, which is considered low. Therefore, it is more feasible to use the Brute-Force matcher. FLANN should be preferred when the number of keypoints is high. The average matching time with the Brute-Force matcher was about 3ms, while the average detection time of SIFT was about 33ms.

Fig. 5. Results of the FlannBasedMatcher and Brute-Force matching algorithms.

B. Execution Time of SSA

Figure 6 shows the speed of the C++ and Matlab SSA implementations. As shown, when the data length is 1K, the C++ implementation of SSA reaches 1000FPS. This speed meets the requirements of many real-time applications.

Fig. 6. Speed of C++ and Matlab implementations of SSA algorithm for data length (1K=1024). Execution time is expressed in FPS.

Fig. 7. Speed-up ratio of a C++ over a Matlab implementation of SSA.

Figure 7 shows the speed-up ratio of a C++ over the Matlab implementation of SSA. The C++ implementation of SSA is up to 18 times faster than Matlab. However, Matlab code can still meet the speed requirements of many applications.

C. Application of SSA to Real-time Object Tracking

Figures 8 and 9 show the x and y coordinates of the pose of the object when it is filtered with the real-time SSA. Figures 10-12 show the scaled points A, B, and C marked in Figure 8. These Figures show that as the window length increases, the filter smoothing effect increases, and fluctuations smooth out. However, when the object changes its directions (Figure 10), the filter may considerably move away from the actual pose because of over smoothing. Therefore, the extensive parameters of the filter can be avoided.

Fig. 8. Application of real-time SSA to object's x coordinate obtained with Brute Force matcher.

Fig. 9. Application of real-time SSA to object's y coordinate obtained with Brute Force matcher.

Fig. 10. Zoom in point A of Figure 8.

Fig. 11. Zoom in point B of Figure 8.

Fig. 12. Zoom in point C of Figure 8.

IV. CONCLUSION

SIFT and SSA are two different methods that have become popular in the last two decades. SIFT is a local object detection algorithm. On the other hand, SSA is a filtering technique that utilizes some methods of multivariate statistics, such as PCA. This study combined SIFT with SSA for real-time object tracking. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- The results of two different feature matching methods, FlannBasedMatcher and Brute-Force matcher, were compared.
- SIFT and SSA were used in a real-time object tracking application for the first time.
- A C++ implementation of SSA was coded using the Eigen library.
- The performance (execution time) of C++ and Matlab implementations of SSA were compared.
- A novel method for the real-time implementation of SSA was presented, simplifying the reconstruction step.

Performance comparison showed that the classic SSA algorithm has enough speed for many real-time implementations and that the C/C++ code was faster than Matlab. As the proposed real-time method did not require full reconstruction, it simplifies the SSA reconstruction step. Moreover, instead of updating the raw data buffer, the Henkel matrix can be updated by omitting the embedding step of SSA, which could be future work. On the other hand, it was also observed that the performance of the object detection algorithm heavily depends on the matching algorithm. It was concluded that if the number of keypoints is low, then the Brute-Force matcher should be preferred instead of the FlannBasedMatcher.

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Improving the Accuracy of Surface Roughness Modeling when Milling 3x13 Steel

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Abstract-In this study, a milling experiment was performed, with 3x13 steel selected as the experimental material along with TiAlN coated inserts. The Box-Behnken method was used to design the experimental matrix with a total of eighteen experiments. Cutting speed, feed amount, and depth of cut were selected as the input parameters. Three regression models of surface roughness have been established, one using the experimentally measured surface texture, one using the Johnson transform to convert the surface texture data, and one using Box-Cox transformation to convert the surface texture data. A comparison of the accuracy of the three models was performed. The results show that the model using the Box-Cox transformation has the highest accuracy, followed by the model using the Johnson transformation. In addition, the influence of cutting parameters on surface roughness is also discussed in detail.

Keywords-milling; 3x13 steel; surface roughness; regression model; Johnson transformation; Box-Cox transformation

I. INTRODUCTION

Experimental research to build a regression model representing the relationship between the input and the output parameters is a commonly used practice in general and in the research on mechanical machining processes in particular. This method has been used for a long time, but it is still not obsolete because its results can be applied directly in the production process. Regression models after being built will be used for many different purposes, such as determining the influence of input parameters on the output parameters, predicting the output from defined values of input parameters, or to determine the value of input parameters that ensure a certain purpose of the output parameters. However, those jobs only achieve high efficiency if the regression model has a high accuracy. The four parameters commonly used to evaluate the accuracy of a regression model include the coefficient of determination $R-Sq$, the coefficient of determination $R-Sq(adj)$, the Percentage of Absolute Error (PAE), and the Mean Square Error (MSE) of the results calculated by the regression model and the experiments [1, 2]. The significance of these coefficients has been discussed in [1-3]. The regression model has high accuracy when the two parameters $R-Sq$ and $R-Sq(adj)$ are as large as possible, and close to 1, while PAE and MSE are as small as possible.

Two data transformations, Johnson and Box-Cox are known for being able to improve the accuracy of the regression model [4, 5, 8]. The Johnson transformation has been used to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model when milling AISI 1045 steel [6]. In this study, the regression model of surface roughness without data transformation has $R-Sq$ equal to 0.8571, PAE equal to 12.11%, and MSE equal to 2.54%. Meanwhile, this model using Johnson transform has $R-Sq$, PAE , and MSE values of 0.8686, 9.22%, and 2.25% respectively. The Box-Cox transformation has been used to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model when centerless grinding of SCM435 steel [7]. The value of $R-Sq$ in the model without data transformation and in the model using data transformation is 0.7801 and 0.8322 respectively. The PAE of the model without data transformation is 17.59%, while it is 13.66% when using the Box-Cox transformation. The value of MSE in the model without data transformation is 5.71% and for the model using data transformation, it is 4.15%. In [9], the Box-Cox method was also used to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model when milling AISI 1019 steel. Parameters $R-Sq$, $R-Sq(adj)$, PAE , MSE of the model without metric transformation had values of 0.898, 0.8899, 14.2%, and 4.53% respectively, while they were equal to 0.9326, 0.927, 8.7%, and 2.28% in the model using Box-Cox transformation. Both the Johnson and the Box-Cox metric transformations were used to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness regression model when surface grinding 65G steel [10]. In this study, three regression models of surface roughness, namely the model without data transformation, the model using the Johnson transformation, and the model using the Box-Cox transformation were built. The conclusion was that the regression model using the Box-Cox transformation has the highest accuracy, and the regression model that does not use the data transformation has the lowest accuracy.

In [11], both Johnson and Box-Cox metric transformations were used to improve the accuracy of the shear force model when milling SCM440 steel. It was found that the two models had similar accuracy, and are more accurate than the model without data transformation. Authors in [12] also applied both Johnson and Box-Cox transformations to improve the accuracy of surface roughness model when turning 3x13 steel. It was noted that the surface roughness model using the Johnson

transformation had higher accuracy than the model using the Box-Cox transformation, and the model not using a metric transformation had lower accuracy. Both Johnson and Box-Cox metric transformations were applied to improve the accuracy of surface roughness modeling when turning 9XC steel [13]. This study determined that the model that uses the Box-Cox transformation has the highest accuracy, while the model that does not use the metric transformation has the lowest accuracy.

Johnson and Box-Cox transformations have been successful in improving the accuracy of the regression model (mostly the surface roughness model). However, when applying both transformations, it was found that each of them showed different conclusions. For every study that suggests that the Johnson transformation is better than the Box-Cox transformation, there is a study with the opposite conclusion. Thus, in order to improve the accuracy of the regression model, it is necessary to use both transformations to determine the regression model with the highest accuracy. 3x13 steel (according to GOST standard) is commonly used to make parts in shipbuilding, petroleum, chemical technology, food processing technology, etc. [15]. Research on surface roughness when processing this steel or equivalent steels has been carried out in [12-16]. However, up to now, no studies have been found that apply the Johnson transformation and (or) the Box-Cox transformation to improve the accuracy of the surface texture model when milling 3x13 steel. So, in this study, 3x13 steel milling experiments were conducted. Two metric transformations, Johnson and Box-Cox were used to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model. The main purpose of this study is to build a surface roughness model with higher accuracy.

II. MILLING EXPERIMENT

The 3x13 steel samples used in the experiment are box-shaped steel blocks with dimensions of 70x40x45mm. All six surfaces of the samples were rough milled on prior to testing. A 3-axis CNC milling machine was used for this experiment

(Figure 1). TiAlN coated cutting inserts and 42mm diameter tips were used. TiAlN coated cutting pieces are better than many other cutting inserts such as TiN coated chips and TiCN coated cutting pieces in improving milling quality and productivity [17]. Each of the 4 cutting pieces was used for one test to reduce the error of tool wear to surface roughness. The basic parameters of the cutting piece are: L-type cutting insert, 0.3mm tip radius, 0.8mm back cutting edge length, 3.59mm cutting thickness, and 90° main cutting angle [17]. Three easily adjustable parameters, namely cutting speed, feed amount, and depth of cut were selected as input parameters for the experimental process. The selected values of the cutoff parameters at each level are shown in Table I [17, 18]. The experimental matrix was designed according to the Box-Behnken method. This type of design is commonly used to design experimental matrices in optimization research [1, 2]. Of course, building a regression function representing each relationship between input and output parameters is the basis for optimization, so in this study, the Box-Behnken method was also used to design the experimental matrix. With three input parameters, each parameter has three levels of values, so the number of experiments of the experimental matrix is 18, as shown in Table II. Surface roughness was measured with an SJ-301. The roughness probe has a diameter of 0.005mm, 0.8 is the standard length installed for the gauge. Each test specimen was measured at least 3 times to determine the surface roughness as the average of 3 consecutive measurements. In addition, a water-based emulsion solution was used during the experiment, with a flow rate of 12lt/min [12].

TABLE I. INPUT PARAMETERS

Parameter	Sign	unit	Value at level		
			1	0	1
Cutting velocity	v_c	m/min	168	240	312
Feed rate	f_z	mm/tooth	0.075	0.150	0.225
Cutting depth	a_p	mm	0.14	0.20	0.26

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL MATRIX AND RESULTS

Trial	Code value			Real value			Response		
	v_c	f_z	a_p	v_c (m/min)	f_z (mm/tooth)	a_p (mm)	R_a (µm) in experiments	After Johnson transformation	After Box-Cox transformation
1	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	0.99	0.24407	1.02030
2	-1	0	1	168	0.150	0.26	1.14	0.68393	0.76947
3	1	0	-1	312	0.150	0.14	0.75	-1.36782	1.77778
4	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	0.96	0.12678	1.08507
5	1	1	0	312	0.225	0.20	1.37	1.11439	0.53279
6	-1	0	-1	168	0.150	0.14	0.92	-0.05376	1.18147
7	0	1	-1	240	0.225	0.14	2.11	1.85155	0.22461
8	1	-1	0	312	0.075	0.20	0.81	-0.78032	1.52416
9	-1	1	0	168	0.225	0.20	1.33	1.05213	0.56532
10	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	0.97	0.16740	1.06281
11	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	0.92	-0.05376	1.18147
12	-1	-1	0	168	0.075	0.20	0.93	-0.00563	1.15620
13	0	-1	1	240	0.075	0.26	0.81	-0.78032	1.52416
14	1	0	1	312	0.150	0.26	0.69	-1.95000	2.10040
15	0	-1	-1	240	0.075	0.14	0.77	-1.16138	1.68663
16	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	0.92	-0.05376	1.18147
17	0	0	0	240	0.150	0.20	1.04	0.41348	0.92456
18	0	1	1	240	0.225	0.26	2.26	1.95000	0.19579

Fig. 1. CNC milling machine.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of surface roughness measurement (R_a) are presented in Table II. Table III presents some parameters obtained when analyzing the experimental results with Minitab 16 software, with a chosen significance level of 0.05 [1, 2]. From the results in this Table, it can be seen that the feed rate is a parameter that has a great influence on surface texture because the P -value of this quantity is much smaller than the significance level [1]. Similarly, the quantity f_z^2 also has a significant effect on the surface texture. Since the coefficient of the feed rate parameter is positive, it shows that increasing the feed rate increases the surface roughness. As the feed rate increases, the contact time between the work surface and the cutting-edge decreases, reducing the number of times the cutting edge hits the part surface, leading to an increase in surface roughness. On the other hand, when the feed increases, the surface roughness will increase, which is also consistent with the theoretical formula for calculating surface roughness as follows: $R_a = 1000 \times 0.0321 \times f_z^2 / r$, where f_z is the feed rate and r is the tip radius [19].

Cutting speed and depth of cut have little influence on surface texture, because the P -values of these two parameters are 0.335 and 0.662 respectively, which are larger than the significance level. However, the effect of cutting speed on surface roughness is greater than that of the depth of cut. Increasing cutting speed reduces surface roughness, while increasing cutting depth increases it. The magnitude of the surface undulation is inversely proportional to the cutting velocity and proportional to the depth of cut [18, 20].

From the data in Table III, the surface roughness model shown in (1) has been built.

$$R_{a(exp)} = 0.9667 - 0.0875 \cdot v_c + 0.4687 \cdot f_z + 0.0436 \cdot a_p - 0.2346 \cdot v_c^2 + 0.3779 \cdot f_z^2 + 0.1429 \cdot a_p^2 + 0.04 \cdot v_c \cdot f_z - 0.07 \cdot v_c \cdot a_p + 0.0275 \cdot f_z \cdot a_p \quad (1)$$

This model has coefficients R - Sq and R - $Sq(adj)$ equal to 0.8563 and 0.6945 respectively. The values of these parameters are as close to 1 as possible. The value of the coefficient R - Sq can be increased if (1) is supplemented with higher order quantities (larger exponents, for example v_c^3, f_z^3 , etc). However, doing so will increase the complexity of the model [1, 2]. Only 69.45% of the change in surface roughness is due to the change of input parameters. Thus, if model (1) is used to predict surface roughness, the accuracy will be limited. Therefore, we need to increase the values of R - Sq and R - $Sq(adj)$ in the regression model without making the model complicated (without using ternary, quaternary, etc.). Two metric transformations, Johnson and Box-Cox, will be used to solve this task. The condition to perform the data transformation according to these two transformations is that the data set must not be distributed according to the normal rules [1, 2]. The distribution rule of surface roughness values while testing is presented in Figure 2. This Figure is acquired in Minitab when determining the distribution rule of surface roughness. Each red dot represents the surface roughness value at an experiment. These red dots are located far from the middle line, there are even red dots lying on either side of the two curves on either side. At the same time, the P -value < 0.005 , which is much smaller than the significance level. This confirms that the surface roughness datasets are not normally distributed, that is, they are eligible to perform the Johnson and Box-Cox data transformations.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS

	Coefficients	Standard error	t stat	P-value
Intercept	0.9667	0.0985	9.816	0.000
v_c	- 0.0875	0.0853	- 1.026	0.335
f_z	0.4687	0.0853	5.496	0.001
a_p	0.0436	0.0853	0.513	0.622
v_c^2	- 0.2346	0.1155	- 2.031	0.077
f_z^2	0.3779	0.1155	3.273	0.011
a_p^2	0.1429	0.1155	1.238	0.251
$v_c \cdot f_z$	0.0400	0.1206	0.332	0.749
$v_c \cdot a_p$	- 0.0700	0.1206	- 0.580	0.578
$f_z \cdot a_p$	0.0275	0.1206	0.288	0.825
R - $Sq = 85.63\%$		R - $Sq(adj) = 69.45\%$		

Fig. 2. Probability plot of surface roughness (R_a).

Minitab is again used to convert data. Figure 3 shows the graph of the Johnson transformation. The upper left image section is the pre-conversion metric information discussed above. The data set after Johnson transformation has also been included in Table II. The lower left part of the figure shows the rule of the data set after the transformation. All the red dots have fit in between the two limiting curves, many of which are already very close to the line, and $P\text{-value} = 0.587$, which is much larger than the significance level. This confirms that the data set after the Johnson transformation has a normal distribution. Observing the upper right Figure also shows that the data set after transformation is distributed according to normal rules. The relationship between the data before and after the Johnson transformation is found in the lower right Figure (in Figure 3). So, a new model of surface roughness has been established as shown in (2). Transforming (2) we get the

surface roughness model as in (3). This model has coefficients $R\text{-}Sq$ and $R\text{-}Sq(adj)$ of 0.8669, 0.7172 respectively.

Figure 4 shows a graph of the Box-Cox transformation. The value of the dataset after Box-Cox transformation has also been included in Table II. The distribution rule of the dataset after Box-Cox transformation is shown in Figure 5. All red dots are located between the two limit curves. The $P\text{-value}$ is 0.655, which is much larger than the significance level. That shows that the data set after Box-Cox transformation is also distributed according to normal rules.

Since the lambda exponent of the transformation is equal to -2.00 (Figure 4), a new model of the surface roughness is established as shown in (4). This model coefficients $R\text{-}Sq$ and $R\text{-}Sq(adj)$ of 0.8787 and 0.7422 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -1.35178 + 0.941864 \cdot \text{Asinh}((R_{a(John.)} - 0.751544)/0.0906774) \\
 & = 0.1407 - 0.5826 \cdot v_c + 1.0869 \cdot f_z + 0.0794 \cdot a_p - 0.4662 \cdot v_c^2 + 0.6707 \cdot f_z^2 \\
 & \quad - 0.3464 \cdot a_p^2 + 0.2092 \cdot v_c \cdot f_z - 0.3299 \cdot v_c \cdot a_p - 0.0707 \cdot f_z \cdot a_p \\
 Ra & = 0.751544 + 0.0906774 \cdot \text{Sinh} \left(\begin{aligned} & 1.5846 - 0.6186 \cdot v_c + 1.1540 \cdot f_z + 0.0843 \cdot a_p \\ & -0.4950 \cdot v_c^2 + 0.7121 \cdot f_z^2 - 0.3678 \cdot a_p^2 \\ & +0.2221 \cdot v_c \cdot f_z - 0.3503 \cdot v_c \cdot a_p - 0.0751 \cdot f_z \cdot a_p \end{aligned} \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

Fig. 3. Johnson transformation for surface roughness (R_a).

$$R_{a(Box.)} = \left[\begin{aligned} & 1.0759 + 0.2828 \cdot v_c - 0.5466 \cdot f_z - 0.0351 \cdot a_p + 0.2091 \cdot v_c^2 \\ & - 0.3404 \cdot f_z^2 + 0.1722 \cdot a_p^2 - 0.1001 \cdot v_c \cdot f_z \\ & + 0.1837 \cdot v_c \cdot a_p + 0.0334 \cdot f_z \cdot a_p \end{aligned} \right]^{-1/2}
 \tag{4}$$

To compare the three established surface roughness models (1), (3), and (4), it is necessary to first use them to calculate the surface roughness and then compare them with the experimental results. Each model was used to calculate the

surface roughness with the values of the input parameters as shown in Table II. The results of the surface roughness determination for each experiment using the three models are included in Table IV. The surface roughness value when

calculated by the three models will be compared with the surface roughness obtained from the experiment. *PAE* is calculated according to (5). *MSE* is calculated according to (6). In these two equations, $R_{a(exp)}$ is the roughness value in the experiment; $R_{a(cal)}$ is the roughness value when calculating. N is the number of experiments.

$$PAE = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{R_{a(exp)} - R_{a(cal)}}{R_{a(exp)}} \right| \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (5)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N |R_{a(exp)} - R_{a(cal)}|^2 \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (6)$$

Table V presents some parameters of the 3 surface roughness models. From the data in this Table, the models using Johnson and Box-Cox transformations both have values of *R-Sq* and *R-Sq(adj)* larger than the model without a data transformation. The *PAE* and *MSE* of the 2 models using a data transformation are also smaller than those of the model not using any data transformation. Thus, the use of a data transformation has improved the accuracy of the model.

Fig. 4. Box-Cox transformation for surface roughness (*Ra*).

Fig. 5. Probability plot of surface roughness after Box-Cox transformation.

In Table V, both parameters *R-Sq* and *R-Sq(adj)* of the model using Box-Cox transformation are larger than those in the other two models. The *PAE* and *MSE* parameters of the model using the Box-Cox transformation are smaller than the other two models. Therefore, we can confirm that the surface texture model using the Box-Cox transformation has the highest accuracy. In contrast, the model that does not use the data transformation has the lowest accuracy. This result is in accordance with the conclusions in [10, 13]. Therefore, it can be said that the Box-Cox transformation is recommended to improve the accuracy of the surface model when milling.

TABLE IV. CALCULATED SURFACE ROUGHNESS

Trial	Measured	Without transformation	Johnson transformation	Box-Cox transformation
1	0.99	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
2	1.14	1.0761	1.0114	1.1142
3	0.75	0.8139	0.7858	0.7631
4	0.96	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
5	1.37	1.5312	1.3341	1.4010
6	0.92	0.8489	0.8454	0.9334
7	2.11	1.8851	1.7297	2.2010
8	0.81	0.5138	0.7339	1.3690
9	1.33	1.6262	2.0451	1.3220
10	0.97	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
11	0.92	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
12	0.93	0.7688	0.9422	1.0528
13	0.81	1.0349	0.8491	0.8282
14	0.69	0.7611	0.7367	0.7018
15	0.77	1.0027	0.8109	0.7615
16	0.92	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
17	1.04	0.9667	0.9634	1.0373
18	2.26	2.0273	1.7480	2.2624

TABLE V. PARAMETERS OF THE CALCULATED SURFACE ROUGHNESS MODELS

Surface roughness model	<i>R-Sq</i>	<i>R-Sq(adj)</i>	<i>PAE</i>	<i>MSE</i>
Without transformation (1)	0.8563	0.6945	12.20	2.59
Using Johnson transformation (3)	0.8669	0.7172	9.41	2.36
Using Box-Cox transformation (4)	0.8787	0.7422	8.88	2.10

IV. CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, some conclusions when milling 3x13 steel with TiAlN coated cutting pieces were drawn:

- Feed rate is a parameter that has a significant influence on surface roughness. As the feed rate increases, the surface roughness increases. The cutting speed and the depth of cut have no significant influence on the surface roughness.
- A data set that is not distributed according to the normal rules will be distributed according to the normal rules after performing a transformation using the Johnson or Box-Cox method.
- Using Johnson and Box-Cox transformations will increase the accuracy of the regression model. In the specific conditions of this study, using the Box-Cox transformation will build the regression model of the surface texture with the highest accuracy.

- The use of both transformations, Johnson and Box-Cox, to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model is not only successfully applied in this study as well as in several other published studies, but also it is a tool that improves the accuracy of the regression model in other cases.

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Flexural Strengthening of Prestressed Girders with Partially Damaged Strands Using Enhancement of Carbon Fiber Laminates by End Sheet Anchorages

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Abstract-This paper examines the impact of flexural strengthening on the percentage of damaged strands in internally unbonded tendons in partially prestressed concrete beams (0, 14.28%, and 28.57%) and the recovering conditions using CFRP composite longitudinal laminates at the soffit, and end anchorage U-wrap sheets to restore the original flexural capacity and mitigate the delamination of the soffit of longitudinal Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminates. The composition of the laminates and anchors affected the stress of the CFRP, the failure mode, and thus the behavior of the beam. The experimental results revealed that the usage of CFRP laminates has a considerable impact on strand strain, particularly when anchors are employed. The EB-CFRP laminates increased the flexural capacity by approximately 13%, which corresponds to strand damage of 14.28%, while flexural capacity increased by 9.3%, strand damage increased by 28.57% for members strengthened with laminates only, and around 21.58% and 16.85% for members reinforced with laminates and end anchorings. Quasi-experimental equations have been proposed to estimate the actual stress of untethered tendons considering the effect of CFRP laminates and final fixation winding.

Keywords-CFRP laminates; debonding; post-tensioned girder; strand damage; unbonded strand

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent destructive failures of pre-stressed (PS) concrete bridges have prompted a reassessment of the condition of several PS members [1], giving rise to new postings and, in some cases, emergency closure. Some of these failures are the result of terrorist attacks involving explosives [2], which damage PS bridge members or tendons [3]. The losing strands on the concrete member have a great effect on the design PS force which reflects a reduction of the nominal capacity and lack of serviceability [4]. One of the strengthening findings that will be investigated in this paper is the evaluation of the use of CFRP laminates with and without end anchorages for strengthening enhancement. CFRPs are increasingly being used to strengthen and repair Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures. The advantages of using Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP)

include the application's ease to use, the high ultimate strength, and corrosion resistance. The experimental results show that due to premature CFRP debonding from the concrete substrate, the maximum capacity of PS externally reinforced beams with CFRP sheets is not always completely realized. External FRP composites have emerged as a viable alternative to strengthening methods. FRP composites have been used for PS girder structures. It is not easy to determine strain and stress in unbonded tendons at ultimate flexural capacity due to the tendons' slip relatively to the surrounding concrete [5]. In practice, it is preferable to prevent the brittle failure mode by either eliminating it or shifting it to a more ductile mode. Anchoring the laminates to the concrete substrate with metallic or CFRP anchors may be a practical way to accomplish this [4]. CFRP U-wrapped anchors or other mechanical anchor systems have demonstrated high effectiveness in delaying the delamination process and increasing the strengthening efficiency. This study, along with [15], is a part of the ongoing investigating research regarding the efficiency of strengthening techniques that are conducted at Baghdad University (Civil Engineering Lab). The current paper focuses on the strengthening techniques using Externally Bonded CFRPs.

II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND METHODOLOGY

A. Design of the Tested Member

All tests were conducted in the laboratory of the College Faculty of Baghdad University under 4 points of loading as shown in Figures 1 and 4. Seven girders, as illustrated in Table II, have been used in this paper, spanning 3000mm and resting on simply supported ends of 2800mm apart. The specimens were reinforced with 2 ϕ 16mm at the bottom and 2 ϕ 10mm at the top whereas ϕ 10mm bars were used for stirrups. Two unbonded strands were used inside the 22.5mm PVC duct with end grips, and the strand extended by 0.45m from each side. CFRP laminates ($b_f=50$ mm and $t_f=1.2$ mm) were attached to the soffit to strengthen the specimen in addition to two CFRP sheets at the end for anchorage purposes with $t_f=0.167$ mm, set up on U wrapping shape as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Specimen and strand damage details.

Fig. 2. Strengthening types considered in this study.

B. Properties of the Tested Beams

The design of the concrete mixture consisted of: Portland cement C45 with densities of 412kg/m³ for cement, 1030kg/m³ for aggregates, 548kg/m³ for coarse sand, and 245kg/m³ for fine sand (*f_c*=44.60N/mm² and *f_t*=5.80N/mm²), while 5.46lt/m³ of superplasticizer were used. The yield, ultimate, strain, and area of steel bars are 518.20N/mm², 658.970N/mm², 12.20%, and 77.21mm² respectively for D10 bars and 577.30N/mm², 710.74N/mm², 13.40%, and 199.10mm² for D16 bars (*E_s*=200000MN/m²). Nominal area, ultimate strength, yield strength, and ultimate strain were 98.7mm², 1860.00MN/m², 1725.00MN/m², and 5.00% respectively for the 7 wires of Grade 270 unbonded tendons (*E_s*=197.5GPa). The manufacturer provided the carbon fiber fabrics' mechanical properties in addition to the resin, in which the nominal thickness, tensile strength, and ultimate elongation were 1.2mm, 3100MN/m², and 0.02 respectively for laminates (*E_f*=170GPa), and 0.167mm, 3500MN/m², 1.59% for unidirectional sheets (*E_f*=220GPa).

The first letter B in the specimens' designation in Table II stands for beam, and the numbers 1 and 2 after the second letter designate the 14.25% and 28.57% strands damage groups, respectively. The letter R corresponds to individual group references, S to CFRP laminate strengthening, and W to laminate and end anchorage wrapping strengthening.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES AND LOCATIONS OF STRAIN GAUGES

Usage	Type	Ω	Adhesive type	QTY, location
Steel	FLAB-6-11	118.5±0.5	CN	2 @ tension bars
Strand	YEFLAB-2-3	119.5±0.5	CN	3
Concrete	PL-60-11	120±0.5	CN-E	2 @ 5cm below the top
CFRP	BFLAB-5-3	119.5±0.5	CN	2

C. Recording Gauges and Setup

All members were tested using a unidirectional electrical resistance strain gauge attached at the middle span to measure strain in the strand, FRP, concrete, and steel (Table I).

D. Experimental Testing

The steel cages were instrumented with strain gages of electric type before being placed in wood forms for concrete casting, using ready-mixed concrete. In addition to the dial gauge for measuring camber, the strain gauge wires were linked to a data logger to capture the strain of the strands during the pre-stressing process, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Post-tensioning process.

Fig. 4. Test setup.

TABLE II. TESTED GIRDER DETAILS

Group	Girder ID	D (%)	Aps (mm ²)	Laminate (<i>L_f</i>)			Sheets (<i>S_f</i>)			<i>ρ_p</i>	<i>ρ_s</i>
				<i>t_{lf}</i>	<i>b_{lf}</i>	<i>L_{lf}</i>	<i>t_{sf}</i>	<i>b_{sf}</i>	<i>L_{sf}</i>		
(mm)											
(%)											
Ref.	B0	0	197.40	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.490	0.810
B1	B1R	14.28	169.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.385	
	B1S			1.2	50	2.7	-	-	-		
	B1SW			1.2	50	2.7	0.167	250	76		
B2	B2R	28.57	141.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.320	
	B2S			1.2	50	2.7	-	-	-		
	B2SW			1.2	50	2.7	0.167	250	76		

Two 1cm thick end steel plates were used at the ends of each specimen with the incision at one of the endplates to protect and guide the strain gauge's wires during the pre-stressing process. The 2 endplates were punched with 2.2cm diameter PS ducting. For anchorage at the unbonded strands, 2 pieces of split-wedge anchor grips (barrel-type) were used. The grips were attached to the ends of the strands, which were then marked using a permanent marker to determine the pre-strain level that was applied in each strand. ($\Delta_L=15.5$ cm as per the member design required). The first strand was pulled out to the requisite pre-stressing value in two stages: initial for starching the strand and final to the preferred pre-stressing value. Then the piston was released. The procedure was then repeated with the second strand, with pressure gauge readings from the hydraulic jack used in the post-tensioning procedure [6]. Two

dial gauges were attached to each end of the strand to find out the slipping of the strand slip during the loading process. Four LVDTs were used to measure the deflection of the 2 specimens near the support, one under the point load, and the other under the quarter point. All LVDTs were set up to zero strain at the start of testing as shown in Figure 4. To progressively raise the load, a 50-ton hydraulic jack was installed to a load cell with a maximum capacity of 50ton. Increments of 15kN were added until the cracking load was reached. The load was then applied in 30kN increments until failure occurred. Each beam took approximately 2 to 3 hours to complete the test. The load cell was used to monitor the applied load from the frame of the test and to collect the reading data. The applied cracks were signified for each load step after the appearance of the first crack. The fracture pattern on the 2 sides of the cross-section was captured on camera after the test. The modes and ultimate loads of failure were reported. During testing, the first crack and crack propagation were monitored as well as the load deflection.

III. RESULTS

The test girders' performance was measured in terms of maximum load-bearing capability. All the reference girders failed in the compression zone due to flexure tensile steel reinforcing yielding, whereas the strengthened beams failed by laminate debonding followed by sudden compression and tension of concrete and steel bars (Figure 6). The first flexural crack appeared in the midspan of sub-reference girders PC1R, and PC2R, with respective cracking loads approximately 94%, and 85% of the reference girder's cracking load. The cracking propagation is typically shown in Figure 5 at the end of the test members in the various test series.

Fig. 5. Representative beam crack patterns.

When the specimens were subjected to the externally applied load, the cracking patterns were quite similar and

typical of flexural members. During the initial cyclic loading between P_{min} and P_{max} , the first flexural cracks appeared within the constant moment zone. Table III shows the cracking loads P_{cr} for the various members before FRP application. As the applied load increased, the number of cracks increased as they began to form within the shear zone. The cracks tended to separate as the load increased and additional flexural cracks were formed. Table III contains a summary of the members' modes of failure. Unbonded PC specimens failed due to concrete crushing, CFRP ultimate strain (rupture), CFRP debonding, or combinations of these modes. The propagation of interface cracks in the concrete near the CFRP in a horizontal direction along with the embedded tension reinforcement until connecting with the vertical flexural cracks caused peeling off of the concrete cover, indicating FRP debonding failure. The control girder failed in a more brittle mode than the strengthened girders, which was evidenced by faster crack propagation and fewer cracks but with wider widths, whereas the control girder showed a more brittle mode [7]. That is explained by the propagation of fewer and faster cracks in wide widths. A large number of cracks with smaller widths occurred for girders strengthened by carbon fibers.

Fig. 6. Representative beam failure modes.

A. Flexural Capacity and Load Deflection

The tested members were investigated at 3 different load levels: cracking loads, post cracking elastic stage, and peak loads as shown in Figure 7. The CFRP laminates and tendons had almost no influence on the member behavior when the applied load did not reach the cracking load. The findings demonstrate that Group 1 and 2 exhibited more strength than the undamaged member. However, the strengthened members with laminates exhibited an increase in flexural capacity of 13-9% for groups 1 and 2 and 21-16% for laminates with anchors when compared to the undamaged girders of the same group as illustrated in Figure 7, indicating the effect of the end anchorage on strength and ductility. The stiffness of the reference girders decreases slightly and the strengthened girders did not significantly differ from the damaged reference girders of the same group. When the applied load exceeded the cracking load, the damaged members exhibited a relatively high rate of stiffness deterioration [8] due to the absence of a portion of the pre-stressing force, which increases the development rate of crack and displacement. Likewise, the flexural-strengthening CFRP EB of the laminates exhibited their ability to postpone the fracture formation and deterioration of the stiffness of the strengthened girders [9], and the girders strengthened with laminates and anchors were observed to be superior to the girders strengthened with laminates only. The deflection is at the same value as the applied load which is equal to 0.79 of the ultimate load. The serviceability limitation for deflection (span over 250) is considered and the corresponding value is used in this paper, as

per the result of control, the deflection at the serviceability limit is 1.12cm and this value is referred to as the permissible load which is about 79% of the ultimate load. The displacement of the strengthened girders was slightly reduced by 9–18% for B1S and B2S whereas almost the same amount (11-19%) of reduction occurred for B1SW and B2SW. It should be noted that in each case, the member with the end anchorage had a smaller drop in the value of the load, higher strength, and much more stiffness [10]. The CFRP girders strengthened with CFRP laminates and U-wrapping of CFRP sheets demonstrated

increased deflection at the maximum load due to the absence of a relatively gradually load drop after the initiation of partial debonding. The ability of the members with an anchor to preserve their ductile response was exhibited. The ultimate displacement increased significantly when the specimen strengthened with laminates only and laminates with end anchorage, and the increment reached 18.16% and 11.39% respectively for B1SW and B2SW in comparison with B1S and B2S.

TABLE III. SUMMARY OF SPECIMEN TESTING AND RESULTS

Girder ID	Cracking load (kN)	Cracking load concerning control (%)	Ultimate load (kN)	Mid-span deflection at ultimate load (mm)	P_{cr}/P_{ult} (%)	Change in flexural strength (%)		Failure mode
B0-control	55.03	-	166.240	26.9	33.10	-		SF, CC
B1R	52.05	94.5	157.250	25.5	33.10	5.410	R	SF, CC
B1S	62.79	14.06	187.990	24.1	33.40	13.080	I	SF, CC-DL
B1SW	66.78	25.9	202.120	28.5	33.00	21.580	I	SF, CC-CD
B2R	47.00	85.38	148.710	29.9	31.60	10.540	R	SF, CC
B2S	58.37	6.09	182.420	23.8	32.00	9.730	I	SF, CC-DL
B2SW	62.16	21.21	194.250	26.5	32.00	16.850	I	SF, CC-CD

SF, steel failure at tension zone, CC crushing of concrete, DL, delamination of CFRP laminate. CD covers delamination, a Negative sign is for reduction, and a positive sign is for increasing. R is for reduction, and I is for increase

Fig. 7. Load deflection curves.

B. Applied Load and Strain for the CFRP Laminates

The cracks in CFRP laminates before the cracking load are minimal and nearly equal (Figure 6). After the load reaches the cracking load, the strain clearly increases, and after the bonded steel reinforcement yields, the strain increment rate increases significantly. The increased rates of strain in the CFRP laminates, with and without the end anchors, were almost similar but the maximum strain of the strain increases in CFRP laminates end by anchors was much higher. At the serviceability load limit, the rise in a strain of strengthened members B1S and B2S was 0.265% and 0.346%, in comparison with the 13.25% and 17.3% of the ultimate strain of laminate capacity ($\epsilon_{fju} = 2\%$) with no significant change to the strengthened specimens with laminates and anchorage sheets, B1SW and B2SW. The strain increase at the ultimate

load was 0.830% and 0.90% corresponding to 41.5% and 45.1% of the ultimate strain of the fiber capacity of B1S and B2S. The B1SW and B2SW specimens achieved more strain at the ultimate load, which is about 1.0235% and 1.033% corresponding to the 51% of the laminate strain capacity. Furthermore, the use of FRP laminates with end U-wrapping anchorage sheets had a significant impact on the compressive concrete strain. The CFRP laminates, as previously mentioned, were able to stop the development of cracks in their path.

C. Applied Load and Effect on the Strands Strain

Because of the minor strain increases, the strand did not contribute to flexural strength before the first crack. The increase in the strand strain was calculated by subtracting the post-tensioning initial strain from the actual strain (Figure 8). During this loading stage, the strand exhibited the same behavior in all the tested members. The strain increases in the strand for the references groups 1 and 2 were greater than the control girder's, whereas the strand strain increases in the members strengthened with laminates was less than in the same group members without strengthening. At the serviceability load limits, the increase in the strand strain for B1R and B2R was $7500\mu\epsilon$ and $89501\mu\epsilon$, representing an increase of 8.5% and 29.5% from the control member. Similarly, the strain increases in the strands of the strengthened girders B1S and B2S were $6750\mu\epsilon$ and $7620\mu\epsilon$, with a reduction of 14.670% and 14.860%. The references' strand strain increments were much smaller in the loading stage after the load in the serviceability manner in the strengthened members B1S and B2S at the same loading level. The lessening of the tendon strain increases in the member strengthened with end anchors was 14.67% and 17.88% for B1SW and B2SW girders. The above results prove that the CFRP strengthened with laminates, including the end U-wrapped anchors, have a great influence on the behavior of the strands. As previously mentioned, the CFRP laminates were able to delay the cracks, prevent their development, and slow down the degradation of the member stiffness.

Fig. 8. CFRP and strands load-strain.

IV. EVALUATING THE NOMINAL MOMENT CAPACITY OF THE MEMBER

A. The Increased Strain in the Strands

Determining the increase in a strain of unbonded strands is a critical case in estimating the flexural strength of unbonded post-tension members strengthened with CFRP laminates. Regrettably, the design guidelines, such as [11] have only suggested one approach to evaluate the increase in the strain of bonded post-tendons and pre-tension members strengthened with EB-CFRP sheets, whereas the correlating approaches for unbonded strands in members strengthened with CFRP laminates were not included. Additionally, the result of the experimental work exhibited that CFRP laminates significantly influence the unbonded tendons' behavior [5]. The increase in the strain of the strand of the unbonded post-tension member strengthened with CFRP was evaluated using the equations for unbonded tendons in normal reinforced concrete members, as below [12]:

For members without end CFRP U-wrapped sheet anchors:

$$\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} = \psi \epsilon_c \left(\frac{d_p - c}{L_0} \right) \times \left(1 + 100 \frac{A_f E_f \epsilon_{fe}}{A_c E_c \epsilon_{fu}} \right)^{0.59} \quad (1)$$

For members with end CFRP U-wrapped sheet anchors:

$$\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} = \psi \epsilon_c \left(\frac{d_p - c}{L_0} \right) \times \left(1 + 100 \frac{A_f E_f \epsilon_{fe}}{A_c E_c \epsilon_{fu}} \right)^{1.35} \quad (2)$$

The overall strain of the unbonded strands $\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}}$ is calculated as:

$$\epsilon_{ps,CFRP} = \epsilon_{pe} + \Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{fe} is the initial strain of a strand not including strain losses = $F_p / (E_p A_p)$, F_p (N) is the actual tensile force in a strand, A_p (mm²) and E_p (MPa) are the cross-sectional area and elasticity modulus of a strand respectively, $\Delta_{\epsilon_{ps,CFRP}}$ is the increase in a strain of strands, ψ is "the length of the plastic zone divided by the height of the compressive concrete zone": $\psi = 10.50$ [13] for un-cracked, simply supported unbonded post-tensioned members, reinforced with CFRP laminates, and $\psi = 9.80$ [14] for pre-cracked unbonded post-tensioned members reinforced by EB-CFRP, ϵ_c is the maximum strain at the concrete compression fiber [11], d_p , (mm) is the distance between the compressive concrete fiber's furthest point and the centroid of the strands' cross-sectional area, c (mm) represents the compression zone height [6], L_0 (mm) represents the effective span of the member, and ϵ_{fe} represents the actual strain in CFRP laminates at the ultimate applied load.

B. Evaluation of the Proposed Formula

The suggested equations (2)–(4) were applied for the estimation of flexural strength of the 23 unbonded post tensioned members reinforced with CFRP laminates including the 7 simply supported members reinforced with EB-CFRP laminates investigated in this manuscript and the 16 slabs and beams of [7]. The theoretical (predicted) flexural strength, $M_{u,pred}$, was calculated as per [11] considering 1.0 as the factor of strength reduction, as below:

- Step # 1: Estimation of the compression concrete zone depth.

The depth of the neutral axis, c (mm), is initially assumed as depth/10 [11].

- Step # 2: Evaluate the strain in CFRP laminates, concrete, and strands.

The CFRP laminate strain, ϵ_{fe} , for failure detected by concrete crushing is:

$$\epsilon_{fe} = \epsilon_{cu} \left(\frac{d_f - c}{c} \right) - \epsilon_{bi} \leq \epsilon_{fd} \quad (4)$$

where d_f is the effective CFRP laminate depth, ϵ_{cu} is the concrete's ultimate compressive strength which is equal to 0.003, and ϵ_{bi} represents the initial strain in the substrate:

$$\epsilon_{bi} = \frac{-F_p}{E_c A_c} \left(1 + \frac{e y_b}{r^2} \right) + \frac{M_{DL} y_b}{I_c A_c} \quad (5)$$

where F_p is the initial prestressing force (N) after excluding the losses, e (mm) represents the prestressing force's eccentricity

concerning the concrete cross-centroid section, y_b (mm) represents the distance from the gross-centroidal section (ignoring steel rebars) to the farthest bottom fiber, r (mm) represents the radius gyration of the member section $= (I_c/A_c)^{0.5}$, I_c (mm⁴) represents the moment of inertia of concrete cross concerning the neutral axis, M_{DL} (N.mm) is the applied dead load's moment, and ϵ_{fd} is the strain's debonding, defined by:

$$\epsilon_{fd} = 0.41 * \sqrt{\frac{f'_c}{nE_c t_f}} \leq 0.9\epsilon_{ffu} \quad (6)$$

where f'_c is the concrete strength, ϵ_{ffu} , t_f , and E_f are the ultimate strain, thickness, and elasticity modulus of CFRP respectively, and n represents the CFRP layer's numbers.

The strain in CFRP laminate, ϵ_{fe} , for failure detected by the rupture of prestressing strands is:

$$\epsilon_{fe} = (\epsilon_{pu} - \epsilon_{pi}) \left(\frac{d_f - c}{c} \right) - \epsilon_{bi} \leq \epsilon_{fd} \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_{pu} is the strand rupture strain which is equal to 0.05 and ϵ_{pi} is the strand initial strain, which can be estimated as:

$$\epsilon_{pi} = \frac{F_p}{E_c A_c} + \frac{F_p}{E_c A_c} \left(1 + \frac{e^2}{r^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

- Step # 3: Estimation of the steel rebars strain, ϵ_s :

$$\epsilon_s = (\epsilon_{fe} + \epsilon_{pi}) \left(\frac{d - c}{d_f - c} \right) \quad (9)$$

- Step # 4: The depth of c must be recalculated, using the summation of forces equal to zero.

$$c = \frac{A_p f_{ps} + A_s f_s + A_f f_{fe}}{\alpha_1 f'_c \beta_1 b} \quad (10)$$

where f_{fe} (MPa) is the CFRP laminate stress $= E_f \times \epsilon_{fe}$, f_{ps} (MPa) is the strand's stress $= E_p \times \epsilon_{ps,CFRP} \leq f_{py}$, and f_s (MPa) is the tensile rebars' stress $= E_s \times \epsilon_s \leq f_y$.

- Step # 5: Checking the c for the depth of the compressive concrete zone.

Now, when the assumed value of c ($c_{assumed}$) and the calculated through the above equations ($c_{calculated}$) meet the presented criterion of convergence in (11), the appropriate value of c is obtained. If not, another $c_{assumed}$ value is calculated, and the process is iterated starting at the second step until convergence is achieved.

$$\text{criterion of convergence} = \frac{|c_{assu} - c_{cal}|}{c_{assu}} \leq 0.1\% \quad (11)$$

- Step # 6: Evaluating the flexural strength of EB-CFRP strengthened member.

The flexural strength of the EB-CFRP strengthened unbonded prestressed concrete member, $M_{u, pred}$ can be calculated as:

$$M_{u, pred} = A_p f_{ps} \left(d_p - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + A_f f_{fe} \left(d_f - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + A_s f_s \left(d - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + A'_s f'_s \left(\frac{\beta_1 c}{2} - d' \right) \quad (12)$$

Fig. 9. Flexural capacity predictions and experimental results comparison.

TABLE IV. THEORETICAL AND PREDICTED VALUE COMPARISON

Members from [7]				Members from this study			
Member	M_{u-P}	M_{u-E}	M_{u-P}/M_{u-E}	Member	M_{u-P}	M_{u-E}	M_{u-P}/M_{u-E}
UB1_H_F1	41.778	41.800	0.999	B0	90.706	91.43	0.99
UB1_H_F2	51.381	54.300	0.946	B1R	85.734	86.49	0.99
UB1_P_F1	34.749	41.400	0.839	B1S	103.774	103.39	1.00
UB1_P_F2	51.678	55.600	0.929	B1SW	104.61	111.17	0.94
UB2_H_F1	54.846	50.500	1.086	B2R	80.498	81.80	0.984
UB2_H_F2	63.855	65.500	0.975	B2S	100.0175	100.33	1.00
UB2_P_F1	50.787	58.500	0.868	B2SW	100.7985	106.84	0.94
UB2_P_F2	58.905	63.300	0.931	Average M			0.979
US1_H_F1	22.374	21.400	1.046	Standard deviation SD			0.026
US1_H_F2	27.324	26.900	1.016	COV			2.63%
US1_P_F1	19.701	21.600	0.912	Totals M 0.953 SD 0.063 COV 6.56% M_{u-P} is the theoretical (predicted) and M_{u-E} is the experimental value			
US1/P/F2	28.314	30.100	0.941				
US2_H_F1	25.443	26.600	0.957				
US2_H_F2	30.690	35.800	0.857				
US2_P_F1	27.423	29.800	0.920				
US2_P_F2	31.680	37.400	0.847				
Average M			0.942				
SD			0.071				
COV			7.5%				

The predicted-to-experimental flexural strength ratios are illustrated in Table IV and Figure 9. The mean value of 0.953 and the Coefficient of Variation (COV) of 6.56%, describe the precision of the theoretical flexural strength values and their applicability for predicting the flexural strength of the EB-CFRP reinforced unbonded prestressed concrete members with and without wrapped sheet anchorages.

V. CONCLUSION

- Beams outfitted with the proposed U-anchor had an about 15% higher debonding load, as well as companion beams with the anchor have a higher maximum load and corresponding deflection. Anchors experienced greater CFRP strain than their counterpart members without anchorages, and the maximum strain is much more than the theoretical strain-based [11] The anchorage was discovered to be effective in restricting the extent of debonding of the laminate, thus indirectly contributing to member flexural stiffness by restricting the crack width.
- For the same loading level, the flexural capacity of post-tensioned girders decreases as the strand damage ratio increases, whereas the displacement of girders increases the damaged strands ratio. The test results exhibited flexure capacity losses up to 5.4% for B1R and 10.54% for B2R at midspan for damaged strands, and for a strengthened member the flexural capacity gained back the lost strength due to the strand's damage and increased it by (13.08%, 26.47%, for B1S and B1SW, whereas for B2S and B2SW the enhancement was 9.73% and 25.25% respectively).
- Prestressed concrete element members with more than 20% damaged strands must meet the serviceability requirements before using enhancing procedures.
- The proposed equations for tendon strain in unbonded prestressed reinforced concrete members reinforced with EB-CFRP laminates, provide flexural capacity predictions with high precision and minimal variation with a mean equal to 0.95 and COV equal to 0.067.

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Design of a Low Power CMOS Inverter with the V_{BB} Stack Approach

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Abstract-Due to the exponential advancement in nanotechnology devices, low energy consumption has become a significant concern of researchers and VLSI designers. In this paper, the Variable body bias (V_{BB}) and the stack approach are used simultaneously to reduce the leakage power of a CMOS inverter in standby mode. This new technique is called the V_{BB} stack approach. The simulations have been conducted on the LT spice simulator. The power evaluation has been determined and compared between the conventional approach, the stack approach, and the V_{BB} stack approach. The results have demonstrated the performance of the V_{BB} stack approach. The power consumption in the V_{BB} stack approach has decreased by 23% compared to the conventional approach and by 10% compared to the stack approach.

Keywords-CMOS inverter; VLSI; power dissipation; leakage current; low power; V_{BB} stack approach

I. INTRODUCTION

The continuous demand for lightweight portable devices such as laptops, tablets, and smart phones has increased the need to reduce the processor size [1, 2]. VLSI designers have made possible to put millions of transistors on a single chip while maintaining good device performance [3]. The oxide thickness of transistor has been shrinking. The channel length has also become short, but produces increased leakage current in standby mode. With the continuous decreasing of technology size, the leakage power in standby mode is becoming the main contributor of total power consumption. The high power dissipation has become a major issue in digital circuit design with each new technology emergence [4]. The main effect of high leakage power is the increase in temperature, which in some cases leads to device breakdown [5]. Power optimization has become an important research field for VLSI designers.

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Many techniques have been proposed, each one delivering a new way to decrease power leakage, but the shortcomings of each push researchers to try to discover a better approach. In this work, the stack approach and the V_{BB} approach are used simultaneously to ensure the best power optimization of a CMOS inverter. The proposed technique is called the V_{BB} stack approach.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

At all levels of VLSI design steps, many approaches have been proposed to reduce power dissipation. Authors in [6] presented low power half adder, full adder, half subtractor, and full subtractor using the CMOS technology. Authors in [7] developed a full adder design using the modified GDI technique to reduce power consumption. Authors in [8] analyzed a MOS transistor to decrease leakage current in standby mode based on forward and reverse body biasing techniques. Authors in [9] used the substrate biasing technique to reduce the standby leakage power of a nanometer scale CMOS circuit. The substrate biasing V_{SB} of a CMOS transistor has a direct effect on the threshold voltage V_{th} , which can be controlled by varying the substrate potential. The equation that shows the impact of substrate biasing on threshold voltage is:

$$V_{th} = V_{th0} + \gamma(\sqrt{|2\phi_B - V_{SB}|} - \sqrt{|2\phi_B|}) \quad (1)$$

where ϕ_B is the flatband voltage, γ is the substrate effect coefficient, V_{th0} is the threshold voltage with zero body biasing, and V_{SB} is the source to substrate voltage.

The threshold voltage is directly proportional with the body potential V_{BB} (V_{SB}). Figure 1 illustrates the conventional CMOS connections and the V_{BB} connections.

Fig. 1. Body connections: (a), (b) conventional bias, (c), (d) V_{BB} technique.

Commonly, the body (substrate) of an NMOS transistor is connected to the ground and the body of the PMOS transistor is connected to V_{DD} [10]. With the V_{BB} technique, the body terminal of PMOS is connected to the positive voltage, and the body terminal of NMOS is connected to the negative voltage to increase the threshold voltage. Authors in [11] presented the stack technique as a method to reduce leakage power. This method is based on the principle that each transistor can be replaced by two half size transistors associated in series [11, 12].

Fig. 2. The stacking technique.

If only one transistor "N" is in standby mode, the potential in the source node is zero, hence there is not a self-reverse bias effect and the leakage current increases. When both transistors N1 and N2 are in standby mode, a low drain current occurs. A positive potential V_N appears. The gate to source voltage (V_{GS1}) of transistor N1 reduces because the sub-threshold current reduces which has as effect an increase to the threshold voltage. This effect is known as the stacking effect [13]. Authors in [11] used the sleepy stack approach to reduce the power consumption of a CMOS inverter. The sleepy stack approach consists of dividing each transistor into two half size transistors. A sleep transistor is placed in parallel to one of the transistors. During the standby mode, the sleep transistors are put off. The threshold voltage increases and the leakage current reduces. The increase of area is the major penalty of this approach. Authors in [14] used the MTCMOS technology to design of a low power XNOR gate. This method is based on adding two sleep high threshold voltage transistors to the principal circuit. While low threshold transistors are active to realize the principal function, the high threshold transistors are turned on. During the stand-by mode, the high threshold transistors are turned off, hence the subthreshold leakage current is cut off and the static power decreases. The MTCMOS technique reduces the leakage current but increases the propagation delay time.

Fig. 3. The sleepy stack approach.

Fig. 4. The MTCMOS technique.

Authors in [15] proposed the use of the LECTOR technique to cut down the leakage current of a NAND gate [17]. In this approach, two leakage control transistors LC1 and LC2 are introduced between the pull up and pull down network. The source of each leakage transistor controls the gate terminal of the other. The introduction of leakage control transistors increases the resistance between V_{dd} and Gnd, thus reducing the leakage current. The lector technique reduces the leakage current but increases the area and the propagation delay time.

III. LOW POWER INVERTER USING THE V_{BB} STACK APPROACH

The inverter is the basic design element of digital circuits. A good understanding of its behavior is necessary in order to build more complex circuits. It has one input and one output.

The output is always the complement of the input. Which means a logical 0 at the input produces a logical 1 at the output and vice versa [10, 11]. Generally, a CMOS logic circuit consists of a symmetrical and complementary pairs of PMOS blocks placed on the circuit as a pull up Network (PUN) and a NMOS block connected as a PULL- down network (PDN). The conventional CMOS inverter consists of two complementary transistors connected to the same input.

Fig. 5. The LECTOR technique.

Fig. 6. The conventional CMOS inverter.

In active mode, the transistors behavior is comparable to that of switches. When the input is at low logic level (0), the P-MOS transistor is conductive and acts like a closed switch, the Current flows from the V_{dd} supply to the output. When the inverter input is at high logic level (1), the PMOS transistor is cut off, disconnecting the output from the positive voltage V_{dd} and the N-MOS transistor is conductive and acts like a closed switch, pulling the output to low level (0). The power

dissipation in the CMOS inverter consists of two components, the dynamic and the static power. Dynamic power permits to charge and discharge the load during the active mode [12]:

$$P_{dyn} = C_L * V_{dd}^2 * f \quad (2)$$

where C_L is the load capacitance, V_{dd} is the supply voltage. Ideally a PMOS transistor must be in standby mode when $V_{gs} < V_{th}$ (static power), V_{gs} is the voltage from the gate to the source, and V_{th} is the threshold voltage.

Due to reduced transistor size, the gate oxide and the channel length become short which produces leakage power or static power. As reported by VLSI designers, static power may in the future dominate the total power consumed by CMOS devices as technology size continue to shrink [10, 16]

$$P_{static} = V_{dd} * I_{leakage} \quad (3)$$

where $I_{leakage}$ is the leakage current during the standby mode.

A major part of the leakage current is caused by the sub-threshold current [12].

$$I_{sub} = I_{sub0} e^{\frac{V_{gs}-V_{th}}{nV_T}} \left[1 - e^{\frac{-V_{ds}}{V_T}} \right] \quad (4)$$

where I_{sub0} is the zero bias electron mobility:

$$I_{sub0} = \mu_{eff} * C_{ox} \left(\frac{W}{L} \right) * V_T^2 \quad (5)$$

where V_T is the thermal voltage, V_{th} is the threshold voltage, η is the sub- threshold swing coefficient, V_{gs} is the transistor gate to source voltage, V_{ds} is the drain to source voltage, μ_{eff} is the electrons mobility, C_{ox} is the gate oxide capacitance per unit area, and W and L are the width and length of the channel respectively.

Fig. 7. Low power CMOS inverter (a) stack method, (b) V_{BB} method.

The sub- threshold current I_{sub} is inversely proportional to the threshold voltage V_{th} . Therefore, an improvement of the threshold voltage may resolve the problem of growing leakage power. The stack and V_{BB} techniques are frequently used to improve the threshold voltage in consequence decrease the leakage power in VLSI circuits and devices. Each method

increases the substrate potential in a different way which decreases the substrate leakage current. To take advantage of the stack and V_{BB} approaches, we have used them together in the same circuit. The new technique is called the V_{BB} stack approach. Each transistor in the conventional inverter is divided into two equal transistors. A positive potential is applied on the body terminal of PMOS transistors. A negative potential is applied on the body terminal of NMOS transistors. A self-reverse bias potential appears in all transistors, thus the threshold voltage increases and the leakage current decreases. The schematic circuit design and the simulation of the inverter with the V_{BB} stack approach have been done on the LT-Spice tool.

Fig. 8. Design of the inverter using the V_{BB} stack approach.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the performance of the proposed method, the inverter is simulated on the LT-Spice with supply voltage variation from 0.2V to 1V. Simulations have been carried out for the inverter in the conventional approach, the stack approach, and the V_{BB} stack approach. Power dissipation and delay have been calculated with variation in V_{dd} .

TABLE I. POWER DISSIPATION AND DELAY VARIATIONS AS FUNCTIONS OF THE SUPPLY VOLTAGE

Supply voltage (V)		0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
Conventional approach	Power dissipation (nW)	111	615	1604	3044	4897
	Delay (nS)	7.757	7.757	7.510	7.493	7.441
Stack approach	Power dissipation (nW)	82	443	1214	2460	4197
	Delay (nS)	7.645	7.561	7.544	7.510	7.491
V_{BB} stack approach	Power dissipation (nW)	71	368	997	2036	3535
	Delay (nS)	7.634	7.562	7.561	7.527	7.508

From the obtained results, it is observed that power dissipation increases simultaneously when the supply voltage increases. Power dissipation in the V_{BB} stack approach is

minimal in comparison with the other techniques, but the delay increases slightly due to the increase in the threshold voltage of the device. We can observe from Table I that by using the stack technique we can save 27% power as compared to the conventional method, but in this case the delay is increased slightly. By using the proposed V_{BB} stack technique, power dissipation is approximately 37% less than in the conventional method, but with a slight increase in delay of 2%. Figure 9 shows the power dissipation characteristics as functions of the supply voltage.

Fig. 9. Power dissipation characteristics.

The main achievement is the inverter with the proposed V_{BB} stack approach is that it shows much better performance in terms of consumed power as compared to the conventional and stack methods. Hence, the proposed V_{BB} stack approach technique is an optimum alternative method to realize low power devices with accepted performance in VLSI design.

V. CONCLUSION

The demand for low power VLSI circuits increases due to the continuous development of wireless technologies which require a limited source of power. Power dissipation is becoming a major issue in today's digital circuits. So, the main objective of VLSI designers is to reduce power consumption as much as possible. In this paper, the V_{BB} stack approach is presented as a solution to prevent the problem of leakage power. A comparative analysis of logic CMOS inverters that were designed with the conventional technique, the stack technique, and the V_{BB} stack technique was conducted in this paper. To evaluate the performance of the V_{BB} stack approach, all CMOS inverter designs have been simulated in LT-Spice, with supply voltage variation from 0.2V to 1V. From the experimental results, it is observed that power dissipation in the V_{BB} stack technique is much less than in the other techniques with a minor increase in delay.

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Regression Modeling and Process Analysis of Resistance Spot Welding on Dissimilar Steel Sheets

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Abstract-The resistance spot welding process is used to weld dissimilar materials. Dissimilar joining is formed by two 2mm thick sheet metals of 304L austenitic stainless steel and galvanized steel. This study investigates the effects of welding parameters such as welding current, welding time, and welding force. The welding time and the welding force were, respectively, in the range of 10-13 cycles and 7-8bar, while the welding current was in the range of 10–16kA. Tensile tests were applied to determine the resistance parameters of dissimilar joining. The experimental results showed that increasing the welding current increased the tensile shear stress of the weld coupon. Regression analysis was carried out to determine the significance of the process parameters by using the coupled of the full factorial experimental design with statistical and graphical analysis of the results. Furthermore, analysis of variance was used to determine the optimal parameters and combinations to achieve the highest strength level.

Keywords-resistance spot welding; dissimilar joining; stainless steel & galvanized steel; welding parameters; regression model; tensile shear stress

I. INTRODUCTION

Resistance Spot Welding (RSW) is the main welding process used in the manufacturing industry, especially in the manufacturing of automobile truck cabins, rail vehicles, motorcycles, and home appliances such as refrigerators. For example, there are 3000 to 12000 spot welds in a car [1, 2]. The majority of the research investigations in spot welding has been carried out on the joining of homogeneous materials [3-6]. Currently, research in different industries is directed towards the reduction of CO₂ emissions. The combination of heterogeneous materials is necessary to reduce the weight of the structures and CO₂ emissions [7-9]. Engineers are increasingly looking to join different material types ensuring

good mechanical strength, corrosion resistance, and sealing function [10, 11]. RSW of dissimilar materials was investigated in [10], finding that the lap shear strength depends on the strength and thickness of the non-stainless steels. A failure in dissimilar joining is called a plug failure.

The properties of RSW of dissimilar stainless steel lap joints were studied in [12], where the weld quality of dissimilar joints was linked to their tensile-shear strength. The welding current was the main governing factor that affected the tensile-shear strength of the RSW specimens. The current contribution of the weld was approximately 67% compared to weld time and applied load. As the weld current increases, the size of the weld nugget also increases. The mechanical performance of dissimilar stainless steel and carbon steel depends on the size of the fusion zone on the carbon steel side, where the pullout failure location of the carbon and stainless steel joint was in the Base Metal (BM) of the carbon steel side [11]. Tensile-shear properties and types of fracture of RSW joints were examined in [1], showing that increasing the weld time increased the tensile shear load-bearing capacity. Pullout and tearing failures are identified depending on the dissimilar joints (back hardening steel/304 stainless steel and back hardening steel/Interstitial steel). Pullout and interfacial failure modes were observed in several studies of homogeneous and inhomogeneous RSW of stainless steel and low carbon steel [11, 13-18]. The effects of welding current and welding process on residual stress distributions for dissimilar welded joints between stainless steel 316L and ferritic steel were investigated in [19], which have been used for lifetime assessment and failure mode predictions of the welded joints.

Several studies have been conducted to optimize the welding parameters [22-24]. Factorial analysis was applied to investigate the effect of feed water temperature, flow rate, and

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radiator dimension on the total heat transfer coefficient and entropy generation in the panel radiator [22]. The effect of welding parameters on the tensile strength of RSW of the 5052Al alloy using a factorial design was studied in [25]. The effects of RSW process parameters and their interactions were studied in [26] using a non-linear regression model.

This paper presents an experimental study on determining the effect of the RSW parameters on the tensile-shear strength of dissimilar joints of stainless steel 304L with galvanized steel Z275. Linear regression, variance analysis, and a mathematical model were applied to evaluate the effects of the RSW parameters and some combinations on tensile-shear stress.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

This study used 304L Stainless Steel (SS) and Z275 Galvanized Steel (GS), each having a thickness of 2mm. The chemical compositions of the steels are given in Table I. The dimensions of the tensile specimens were 85mm length and 30mm width, as shown in Figure 1. The total length of the RSW welded specimen was 140 mm.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE WELDING MATERIALS

Element	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni
SS 304L	0.03	1.0	2.0	0.045	0.015	0.1	0.03
GS Z275	0.12	0.50	0.60	0.10	0.045	/	/

Fig. 1. Dimensions of the tensile test specimens.

The samples were welded by a TECNA ART 8201N RSW machine. Welding was performed using a water-cooled electrode with a hemispherical active face. The electrode in the CuNi₂Be alloy had 6.0mm in contact surface according to:

$$D_{active} = 2e + 3 \quad (1)$$

where D is the active diameter and e is the sheet thickness in mm.

III. WELDING PARAMETERS DETERMINATION

The welding parameters were determined from previous research and the weldability of materials, depending on the nature of the base materials and thickness [20]. The welding current varied from 10kA to 16kA, the welding time increased from 10 to 13 cycles, and two values of the electrode force (7 and 8bar) were also applied. The distribution of the values of the three parameters was carried out with a factorial plan to ensure the union of all the values. Table II shows the combination of the welding parameters and the number of trials for each factor. The mechanical properties of joining SS 304L and GS Z275 materials are given in Table III.

TABLE II. FACTORS OF WELDING PARAMETERS

Factor	Levels	Values
I (kA)	5	10; 12; 14; 15; 16
T (cycles)	3	10; 11; 13
F (bar)	2	7; 8

TABLE III. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 304L SL AND Z275 GS

Materials	E (GPa)	σ_e (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	A%	HRB
SS 304 L	190	336	655	43.2	60
GS Z275	200	266	330	22.0	/

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A linear regression model was proposed to relate the tensile-shear strength of the RSW joints to welding current I , welding time T , and welding force F . Minitab 19 was used for regression analysis. As a result, a mathematical model was developed for the influence of the three welding parameters on tensile-shear stress, described as:

$$y = a + b1x1 + b2x2 + b3x3 + b11x1x1 + b23x2x3 \quad (2)$$

The regression equation between the welding parameters I , T , and F and tensile-shear strength was:

$$\text{Tensile Shear Stress (MPa)} = -343 + 33,2 I + 35,4 T + 47,4 F - 0,767 I^2 - 4,58 T * F \quad (3)$$

Table IV shows the results of tensile-shear stress with the parameters of each test.

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR TENSILE-SHEAR STRESS

Trial order	I (kA)	T (Cycles)	F (bar)	Tensile shear stress (MPa)
1	10	10	7	292.01
2	10	10	8	265.07
3	10	11	7	279.15
4	10	11	8	271.81
5	10	13	7	303.64
6	10	13	8	276.71
7	12	10	7	287.72
8	12	10	8	320.17
9	12	11	7	309.15
10	12	11	8	319.56
11	12	13	7	314.66
12	12	13	8	280.99
13	14	10	7	348.94
14	14	10	8	342.21
15	14	11	7	335.48
16	14	11	8	331.19
17	14	13	7	346.49
18	14	13	8	352.00
19	15	10	7	348.33
20	15	10	8	355.07
21	15	11	7	353.23
22	15	11	8	350.78
23	15	13	7	355.07
24	15	13	8	350.17
25	16	10	7	363.02
26	16	10	8	355.07
27	16	11	7	344.66
28	16	11	8	348.33
29	16	13	7	363.02
30	16	13	8	356.90

Table V illustrates the results of the analysis of variance with some interactions between the three welding parameters. The data show that the main effects of the welding current are relevant for the maximum load. Since the p-value of welding current is inferior to the significance level established at a 5% probability level ($p < 0.05$), the interaction between welding time and electrode force cannot be considered significant. This Table also shows other adequacy measures: $R^2=88.96\%$, adjusted $R^2=86.66\%$, and predicted $R^2=81.59\%$. Since they are all very close to 0.9, they indicate a suitable model.

TABLE V. ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

Source	DF	Adj. SS	Adj. MS	F.Value	P.Value
Regression	5	25237.7	5047.5	38.68	0.000
<i>I</i>	1	632.6	632.6	4.85	0.038
<i>T</i>	1	258.8	258.8	1.98	0.172
<i>F</i>	1	201.3	201.3	1.54	0.226
<i>I*J</i>	1	228.4	228.4	1.75	0.198
<i>T*F</i>	1	245.0	245.0	1.88	0.183
Error	24	3132.0	130.5		
Total	29	28369.7			

$R^2 = 88.96\%$
 Adjusted $R^2 = 86.66\%$
 Predicted $R^2 = 81.59\%$

It is necessary to compare the tensile shear stress values estimated by the model equations (2), (3) with the values obtained as a result of experimental calculations. The residuals consist of the difference between the data and the model data. A comparison of the estimated and experimental data for tensile shear stress is shown in Figure 2 [26, 27]. According to Figure 2, a good agreement was observed between the mathematical model obtained for the tensile-shear stress and the experimental data, and residuals fall relatively along a straight line. Consequently, the normal distribution assumption was considered satisfied.

Fig. 2. Normal probability plot of residuals.

Figure 3 is a residual versus observation order graph showing that all residual points are spread within the lower and upper bounds without evident patterns, confirming the assumption that the residuals have a regular variance. As a result, all diagnostic plots denote that all the necessary ANOVA assumptions are satisfied.

Fig. 3. Residuals versus observation order.

As shown in Figure 4, all residual points are dispersed within the lower and upper bounds, showing no pattern. This graph denotes that the independence assumption is also satisfied. The histogram shown in Figure 5 forms a normal curve equally distributed around zero, showing that the normality assumption is more than likely true.

Fig. 4. Residuals versus fits plots.

Fig. 5. Histogram of residuals.

As shown in Figure 6, a Pareto diagram provides statistical information on the effects of input variables, factors or welding parameters in this case, on tensile shear stress. It is observed that the welding current factor has a relevant impact on the

tensile-shear stress because it occurs outside the dotted line at 2.064. The other parameters and interactions have a meaningless or less impact relative to the welding current. It is important to know the effect levels of welding parameters on tensile-shear stress. Using this information, one could choose which parameter is more important for perfect welding joining [22, 28].

Fig. 6. Pareto chart of normalized effects.

These factors can be classified in decreasing order: welding time, welding time electrode force interaction, welding current, welding current interaction, and welding force. This result can be further supported by taking into account the main effects and interaction graphs, as shown in Figures 7 and 8 respectively. Figure 7 shows a graphical representation of the primary effects of the factors examined for the spot weld regarding tensile-shear stress. According to the graph, it can be concluded that the impact of a factor is directly linked to the slope and length of the line in the graphic. The greater the slope is, the higher the influence on the average maximum load increase will be when varying levels from low to high. According to Figure 7, the welding current has a significant impact on tensile-shear stress due to the higher slope, while welding time is less sensitive to the variability in tensile-shear stress compared to welding current. On the other hand, welding force has less effect on tensile shear stress.

Fig. 7. Main effects plot for tensile shear stress (MPa).

Figure 8 shows the main effect graph for tensile-shear stress. The three two-factor interaction graphs denote a powerful interaction between welding current and welding time, and welding current and welding force. Tensile-shear stress reaches its highest when welding current and welding time are kept at a high level, but welding force is at a low level, 16kA, 13cycles, and 7bar respectively. Similarly, tensile-shear stress reaches its minimum when welding current and welding time are both at low levels, but electrode force maintains a high level, i.e. 10kA, 10cycles, and 8bar respectively.

Fig. 8. Interaction plot for Tensile shear stress (MPa)

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a linear regression analysis used to investigate the effect of RSW parameters on the tensile-shear stress of dissimilar joints from experimental results. Based on this investigation, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The regression analysis showed that there is a linear relationship between welding parameters (welding current, welding time, and electrode force) and the tensile-shear strength of the RSW joints.
- According to the p-values and the Pareto chart, the welding current had the highest impact on tensile-shear stress compared to welding time, welding force, and other combinations.
- The welding process and the effects of parameters and interactions between them on tensile-shear strength can be analyzed based on regression models of the welding process on two heterogeneous sheets, stainless steel and galvanized steel, with a thickness of 2mm which can make it to be an assistant reference for the welding process.
- The optimal parameters that gave a higher tensile-shear strength were higher welding current (16kA) and welding time (13cycles) and lower welding force (7bar).

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Performance Assessment of the BLDC Motor in EV Drives using Nonlinear Model Predictive Control

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Abstract-In this paper, the Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) technique is proposed for the control of BrushLess Direct Current (BLDC) motors to address the problem of over-excitation, specifically in Electric Vehicle (EV) applications. This over-excitation increases the overall energy consumption of the machine and eventually reduces the vehicle's driving range. The developed NMPC incorporates a nonlinear model of the BLDC motor with EV load and obtains the optimal current through the optimal voltage applied to the machine to regulate the motor torque. The proposed NMPC is compared with three conventional control techniques, the Field-Oriented Control (FOC), the Direct Torque Control (DTC), and the hybrid (the combination of DTC and FOC) control. It is observed from the simulation results that the proposed NMPC controller is more energy efficient while maintaining performance. This paper also discusses the selection of the motor based on the specified vehicle requirements. This has been done by matching the vehicle speed-torque characteristic curve with the motor's one.

Keywords-BLDC motor; model predictive control; nonlinear systems; optimization; electric vehicle

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are a zero-emission solution for vehicular technology. They are the attractive alternative to the traditional Internal Combustion (IC) engines [1]. The, technology advancement in EV and energy management solutions are the top priority areas of the relative research. Traction motor, the main component of the power-train, consumes the most power from the batteries [1]. Several types of electric motors are used for the traction in EVs, such as Induction Motors (IMs), Permanent Magnet Motors (PMMs), Switched Reluctance Motors (SRMs), etc. In this work, a Brushless Direct Current (BLDC) motor, which is a type of PMM [2, 3], is considered. The driving range can be improved by the optimal usage of the available energy for the traction system. The application of control system engineering to control the BLDC motor has gained significant attention by ensuring the efficient and reliable operation of the motor [2-4]. Conventional control techniques have been utilized in the speed/torque control of BLDC motor for various applications. Its combination with fuzzy logic improves performance [5, 6].

The FOC is a vector control technique proposed mainly for the control of AC synchronous and IMs [7]. However, features like ripple reduction and better efficiency have been used in the BLDC motor control [8-10]. Due to these advantages, authors in [11, 12] tried the FOC principle to find the optimal current excitation component as an extension over the main controller. Another widely accepted control technique for the AC motors is the DTC [13, 14]. It has been primarily proposed for IMs and has been then utilized in BLDC motor control [15, 16]. In the DTC technique, the control actions (stator voltages and currents) are obtained from a switching table implemented with a Look-Up-Table (LUT). FOC and DTC have their own advantages and disadvantages. Recently, authors in [4] demonstrated the advantages of hybrid control (a combination of DTC and FOC) for the BLDC motor control in aerial drones. The experimental results show that the hybrid controller reduces the speed ripple in the steady state region compared to DTC and decreases the response time compared to FOC. Generalized Predictive Control (GPC) for a BLDC motor is presented in [17]. In GPC, the objective function needs to be computed for all possible switching states, which increases the controller's computational complexity [12, 18].

In this paper, the use of NMPC technique for the torque control with the BLDC prediction model is proposed. The objective function comprises of: (1) torque reference tracking, (2) current d-component minimization, which avoids the over-actuation of the motor, and (3) input regulation to minimize the required voltage in order to achieve the desired torque, while it also works as an integrator to reduce steady-state errors. Applicability of the NMPC in the BLDC motor control has been less addressed in the literature, but it has been successfully applied to Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) [11], where motor current excitation is always sinusoidal. In this paper, we improved the BLDC motor control performance using NMPC in various directions. The result was compared with 3 control techniques considering various key performance indices. All the control methods were validated through their speed-torque characteristics against the ideal characteristic of the EV, which is generated through the vehicle's effective weight, required acceleration, maximum grading, and speed range. All techniques were realized in

Matlab, and the proposed NMPC was realized in the CasADi [19] platform with a Matlab interface.

II. MODELING OF SYSTEM DYNAMICS

This section presents the nonlinear mathematical model of the BLDC motor and the EV coupled with the BLDC motor model.

A. BLDC Motor Model

The electrically modeled 3-phase BLDC motor is shown in Figure 1. For simplicity reasons, self and mutual inductance were considered constant. The mathematical model for the BLDC motor is expressed as:

$$v_a = Ri_a + L \frac{di_a}{dt} + E_a \quad (1)$$

where v_a is the phase voltage (V), i_a is the phase current (A), E_a, E_b , and E_c are the back-EMF phase in (V), R is the resistance per phase (Ω), L is the inductance per phase (H). Similar equations can be produced by replacing the suffix a with b and c to get the electrical equations of the other phases. This motor is supplied with 3 phase voltages which are in 120° phase shift from each other. The mechanical dynamics for the motor are:

$$T_e = k_f \omega_m + J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} + T_L \quad (2)$$

where T_e is the generated electrical torque to handle motor load (Nm), T_L is the mechanical load on the motor (Nm), J is rotor's inertia (kgm^2), k_f is the frictional constant (Nm/rad), and ω_m is the rotor speed (rad/sec). The BEMF in the stator is a function of rotor position (electrical angle θ_e) and it is trapezoidal in nature:

$$F(\theta_e) = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 \leq \theta_e \leq \frac{2\Pi}{3} \\ 1 - \frac{1}{\Pi}(\theta_e - \frac{2\Pi}{3}), & \frac{2\Pi}{3} \leq \theta_e \leq \Pi \\ -1, & \Pi \leq \theta_e \leq \frac{5\Pi}{3} \\ -1 + \frac{6}{\Pi}(\theta_e - \frac{5\Pi}{3}), & \frac{5\Pi}{3} \leq \theta_e \leq 2\Pi \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The phase-wise BEMF and the electric torque generated are given by:

$$E = \frac{k_e}{2} \omega_m F(\theta_e) \quad (4a)$$

$$T_e = \frac{k_t}{2} \left[F(\theta_e)_a i_a + F(\theta_e - \frac{2\Pi}{3}) i_b + F(\theta_e + \frac{2\Pi}{3}) i_c \right] \quad (4b)$$

B. D-Q Modeling of the Motor

The control aspect abc frame of reference is not suitable, as in the abc frame of reference, the motor voltage and current are oscillatory, even under constant speed and load. This makes it unsuitable to use in control law formulation. In the D-Q frame of reference, the voltage and currents are constant for constant

speed and torque. Therefore, using Clerk and Park transformation, the abc frame of reference will be converted into the D-Q frame of reference. In the D-Q domain the equations become:

$$v_d = Ri_d + L \frac{di_d}{dt} + \omega_r Li_q + E_d \quad (5a)$$

$$v_q = Ri_q + L \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_r Li_d + E_q \quad (5b)$$

where E_d, E_q are the BEMF functions of the electrical angle theta generated from the (4a).

C. Vehicle Model

All the effective forces are taken into account. Figure 1 represents the schematic of these forces [20], which are: the aerodynamic drag (F_w), the acceleration resistance (F_a), the rolling resistance (F_r), and the uphill resistance (F_g). The tractive force (F_t) required to drive the car is cumulative of all the above-mentioned forces [20]. It is represented as:

$$F_t = F_r + F_w + F_g + F_a \quad (6)$$

Substituting the respective equations for all forces we have:

$$F_t = \mu_r Mg \cos(\theta) + Mg \sin(\theta) + \frac{1}{2} \rho A_f C_d V_s^2 + \lambda M \frac{dV_s}{dt} \quad (7)$$

where λ is the rotational inertia constant and V_s is the vehicle velocity (m/sec). The details of the other variables are given in Table II.

The total tractive force F_t is nothing but the mechanical load on the motor in the form of linear force (N). The load torque applied to the BLDC motor is:

$$T_L = F_t \frac{r_w}{G} \quad (8)$$

where r_w is vehicle's wheel radius (m) and G is the gear ratio.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the vehicle showing the tractive forces acting on it.

The EV and BLDC motors are coupled, this modifies the torque equation (2), which becomes [21]:

$$T_e = k_f \omega_m + (J + M(\frac{r_w}{G})^2) \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} + \frac{r_w}{G} (F_r + F_w + F_g) \quad (9)$$

D. Motor Sizing and Driving Cycle

The vehicle requirements specified in Table I were considered to obtain the motor torque requirement. The vehicle parameters given in Table II are taken from [20].

TABLE I. THREE WHEELER EV OPERATING PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Unit
Maximum speed	50	Km/h
Maximum acceleration	2	m/s ²
Maximum grading	10	%

Using the vehicle model from Section II, we can get the different characteristic curves of the vehicle, by substituting the values for acceleration, speed, grading (road angle), etc. The speed-torque characteristic specified vehicle is generated and presented in Figure 3. T1 is the minimum torque required to maintain the respective speed, T2 is the minimum torque required to get an acceleration of 2m/s² for the respective speed, T3 is the minimum torque required to maintain the respective speed under 10% grading, and P1, P2, P3, P4 are constant power profiles of 1, 2, 3, and 4KW respectively. Out of these lines, the 3KW line fulfills the requirement with maximum speed of 60Kmph and can maintain constant speed of 26Kmph on maximum grading of 10%. Therefore, the 3KW motor is appropriate for the three-wheeler EV. Its specifications are given in Table II [21].

TABLE II. EV SPECIFICATIONS [21]

Parameter	Notation	Value	Unit
Mass	M	600	kg
Gravitational constant	g	9.81	m/s ²
Air density	ρ	1.225	Kg/m ³
Drag coefficient	C_d	0.5	-
Area	A_f	2.09	m ²
Rolling resistance coefficient	μ_{rr}	0.0015	-
Gear ratio	G	5	-
Wheel radius	r_w	0.19	m
Road angle	θ	1	rad

Taking reference from Figure 2, the torque and speed values are noted in Table III. This derives the gear ratio of 10 to match the vehicle and motor's torque and speed.

Fig. 2. Vehicle torque-speed characteristic curves. (a) vehicle characteristics with constant power profiles and constant acceleration lines, (b) minimum torque required for the desired speed with the 3KW powered vehicle.

TABLE III. GEAR RATIO DESIGN BASED ON VEHICLE REQUIREMENTS AND MOTOR SPECIFICATIONS

Object	Torque (Nm)	Speed (r/s)
Vehicle (maximum required)	378	81
Motor (rated)	80	367
Gear ratio	1:5	

Figure 3(b) shows the minimum requirements of speed and torque to match the vehicle requirements. The speed-torque curve of the controller should be above the shown curve in Figure 3(b).

III. CONTROL TECHNIQUES

This section presents the design and implementation of 4 control techniques (DTC, FOC, hybrid, and NMPC) under consideration for the assessment of BLDC motor with EV as the load.

A. Field Oriented Control

The fundamental idea behind the FOC technique is making torque and flux components distinct and then control them independently. The block diagram of FOC for the BLDC motor control is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the BLDC motor control in FOC technique.

Even though this method efficiently controls the machine, it is a parameter-dependent method, for example, the stator or rotor resistances are affected by temperature. Therefore, the FOC is not robust to parameter variations.

B. Direct Torque Control

DTC allows direct controls of the electromagnetic torque and stator flux through a suitable combination of control signals applied to inverter switches. As it directly controls the inverter switches, it is a simpler, but non-linear control structure with reduces computational complexity.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the BLDC motor control using DTC.

The schematic of DTC is shown in Figure 4. DTC has two control loops, (i) the external speed control and (ii) the internal torque and flux hysteresis loop. Two independent hysteresis controllers produce torque error and stator flux error, and based on those hysteresis controllers' output and stator flux angle, optimum switching logic selects one of the six voltage vectors and two zero voltage vectors from switching table.

C. Hybrid Controller

The principle of the hybrid controller is based on the switching between the two mentioned above techniques. DTC is used in the transient region and FOC in the steady-state region. The transient and steady-state regions are identified by calculating the error (e) between the current speed and the reference value of the speed ($e = \omega_r - \omega$). The control action of the hybrid controller is obtained as follows:

$$u = \begin{cases} DTC, & \text{if } e \leq \varepsilon \\ FOC, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where ε is the threshold valued of speed error to switch between transient and steady-state regions. Here, we consider $\varepsilon=0.1$.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of BLDC motor control using the hybrid technique.

The schematic of the hybrid controller is shown in Figure 5. The controller selection block selects the FOC and DTC with e value, and finally, the control signal, u is applied to the inverter.

D. Non-linear Model Predictive Controller

It is an optimal control method, where the control actions are obtained by solving a Constraint Finite-Time Optimal Control (CFTOC) (see Chapter 1 in [22]).

Figure 6 shows the idea of using centralized NMPC for the speed control of the BLDC motor. The NMPC algorithm is comprised of the nonlinear prediction model, integrator, user-defined constraints, and cost function, and a Non-Linear Programming (NLP) solver to solve the constructed Optimization Control Problem (OCP). We used a zero-order hold sampling for discretization and the Runge Kutta 4th order method for the approximation of the nonlinear function. The NMPC as a direct solution of the CFTOC problem for the reference track is represented as follows:

$$\min_u \sum_{k=1}^N (\| \omega_{m,k} - \omega_{m,k}^r \|_Q^2 + \| \Delta u_k \|_R^2 + \| I_{d,k} \|_P^2) \quad (13a)$$

Subject to:

$$x_{k+T_s} = f(x_k, u_k), \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13b)$$

$$\omega_{m,k} = g(x_k, u_k), \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13c)$$

$$\Delta u_k = u_k - u_{k-1}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13d)$$

$$-48 \leq u_k \leq 48, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13e)$$

$$u_{-1} = u(t - T_s), \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13f)$$

$$x_0 = x(t), \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (13g)$$

where, $x \in R^x$, $\omega_{m,k} \in R^{ny}$, and $u \in R^{nu}$ are the vectors of state, output, and input respectively. ω_m^r is the reference trajectory of speed reference and ω_m is the output or the measured speed. The function f in (13b) describes the nonlinear dynamics of the combined BLDC motor as given by (9), g in (13d) is the speed measurement function.

Fig. 6. Block diagram of the BLDC motor control using NMPC.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the controllers are tested for step-change response and EDC profile. Moreover, we present the numerical analysis of control techniques based on several Key Performance Indices (KPIs) and energy consumption. The current and voltage of phase C are shown as representatives, as all phases are having the same trend with a phase shift of 120°.

A. Speed Torque Characteristic

Speed torque characteristic gives information about the maximum possible torque delivered by a controller at each speed value. As per (4b), it is the product of BEMF and current, hence different current control techniques produce different torques and different speed-torque characteristics. It must be noted that the torque and speed plotted in the characteristic plot of Figure 7 are measured at the shaft of the motor. Along with controller's characteristics, Figure 7 also contains three reference profiles, which are designed as per the requirements from Table I, named as constant acceleration

(T1), constant energy (P4), and zero acceleration (T3) torque profiles. The T1 torque profile is nothing but the torque required to maintain an acceleration of 2m/s^2 at each speed value, the P4 torque profile indicates the torque at each speed value for constant energy of 3KW, and T3 torque profile indicates the torque required to cruise the vehicle at a constant speed.

Fig. 7. Controller's speed-torque characteristics against minimum speed-torque characteristics required for the considered EV.

In the case of the hybrid controller, the maximum torque delivered for the respective speed is decided by DTC. Therefore, the torque-speed characteristic curve of DTC and hybrid is the same. If we observe Figure 7 closely, all controllers except FOC are above reference lines T2 and P4. Therefore, DTC, hybrid, and NMPC guarantee the fulfillment of performance specifications. Due to this, FOC delivers less torque than the required and makes it sluggish. Even though FOC does not provide sufficient acceleration, it can maintain the current speed because its generated torque is greater than T3. This is the reason why the hybrid controller switches to FOC in steady-state. To get more insight into the above discussion, we will further analyze the step and EDC speed profile responses.

B. Step Response

All controllers are tested considering the reference step input of 15Kmph and speed, torque, current, and voltage of each one were monitored.

1) Field Oriented Control

Figure 8 shows the performance of the FOC in tracking the desired speed. Figure 8(a) depicts the speed response, Figure 8(b) the generated torque, Figure 8(c) the sinusoidal current excitation required to achieve the desired speed, and Figure 8(d) shows the input voltage applied by the FOC controller. The FOC achieves reference speed after 9.7s. This sluggish response is acquired because the generated torque is smaller than the required value.

2) Direct Torque Control

Figure 9 shows the performance of DTC for step response. The DTC technique tracks the reference speed sooner than FOC at the cost of higher current and torque ripples. Due to the higher current, DTC consumes more energy.

Fig. 8. FOC control with step change in reference input for BLDC motor control with EV load: (a) speed, (b) torque, (c) current, and (d) voltage.

Fig. 9. DTC control with step change in reference input for BLDC motor control with EV load: (a) speed, (b) torque, (c) current, and (d) voltage.

3) Hybrid Control

Figure 10 shows the step response of the hybrid control technique. The hybrid controller exhibits the combined effect of FOC and DTC with fast reference tracking like DTC (Figure 10(a)), reduced torque ripples (Figure 1(b)) due to the FOC, and reduced current and energy consumption due to the FOC (Figure 10(c)). Figure 10(a) also shows the controller selection mode, with zero as DTC during transients' region and 5 for FOC in steady state region.

Fig. 10. Hybrid control with step change in reference input for BLDC motor control with EV load: (a) speed, (b) torque, (c) current, and (d) voltage.

Fig. 11. NMPC control with step change in reference input for BLDC motor control with EV load: (a) speed, (b) torque, (c) current, and (d) voltage.

4) Nonlinear MPC

Figure 11 shows the step response of the NMPC technique. It can be seen that the NMPC achieves the desired speed much faster than other controllers (Figure 11(a)). But this faster response comes at the cost of more torque ripples and higher current and energy consumption during transients (Figure

11(b)-(d)). In steady-state, torque ripples, current, and voltage consumption are comparatively less. One more interesting observation is that as the motors speed approaches the set-point, the ripples are reducing.

TABLE IV. KPIS OF THE CONTROL TECHNIQUES FOR STEP KPIS IN REFERENCE OUTPUT

KPI	FOC	DTC	Hybrid	NMPC
Transient time	11.25	1.41	1.41	1.25
RMSE (%)	100	2.02	12.34	0.10
ME (%)	100	1.55	12.31	0.08
IAE (%)	100	2.01	12.34	0.10
ISE (%)	100	0.04	1.52	0.0001
ISCE (%)	99.82	99.54	100	99.0

5) Result Comparison

Table VI gives the summary of all the KPIs for the controllers and their performance regarding step response. From Table VI, it can be seen that the NMPC technique outperforms the other techniques, because the other techniques (DTC, FOC, and hybrid) are based on a fixed or finite combination of current excitation, whereas NMPC does optimal modulation in the current. This optimal modulation in the current reflects on the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) of the in-phase current. In the trapezoidal control (DTC), the THD is around 8%, in FOC it is 3% and for NMPC, as the optimal excitation varies, the THD varies between 4% and 7%. These ripples are required by considering the non-sinusoidal BEMF of the motor. In case of a sudden change in the set-point, the controller has to drive the motor with maximum torque, so NMPC tries to deliver maximum current without much caring about torque ripples, but as the motor approaches the set-point, the current approaches the minimum value with minimum ripples in current and torque.

C. Ramp Response

The hybrid controller selects either FOC or DTC based on the error threshold, but during the ramp type speed reference, if the controller selects the DTC, then the response cannot be energy efficient and if FOC is selected, then the controller cannot track the reference speed. In this view, a hybrid controller either toggles the two sub-controllers or selects only DTC without much caring about energy efficiency. This problem occurs only in the case of the hybrid controller. Therefore, in this section, this problem is addressed and the outcome is compared with NMPC.

1) Hybrid

To get efficient operation if the controller follows the toggling case, the results will be as shown in Figure 12. Due to the continuous switching between DTC and FOC there are ripples in speed and eventually this is reflected on voltage and current. This frequent switching can be avoided by using a hysteresis controller for DTC/FOC selection, but this controller will be either overexcited (DTC) or sluggish (FOC).

2) NMPC

Figure 13 depicts the NMPC response for ramp type speed reference. The NMPC shows better tracking with minimum error. This is due to the modulation in current excitation as per

the operating conditions. This modulation in current excitation helps making a smooth transition from transient region to steady-state region, with the desired performance.

Fig. 12. Enhanced view of motor speed tracking in ramp type reference.

Fig. 13. Ramp response of the NMPC for speed control of a BLDC driven EV.

D. European Driving Cycle

The hybrid controller combines the advantages of DTC and FOC. Therefore, in this section, we test the performance of hybrid control and NMPC techniques in real-life scenarios, which can be tested through the EDC. Both the controllers are tested for speed tracking as per torque given through EDC. Figure 14 depicts the response of both techniques. Figure 14(a) shows the speed and Figure 14(b) shows the desired and achieved torque. It can be seen that both controllers perform well regarding the tracking of the desired speed. However, the hybrid controller shows higher torque ripples and over-excitation of the motor with high oscillation in the current due to the higher voltage input during the DTC selection. As a consequence, the hybrid controller consumes more energy. Similar inference is generated by the different KPI's in Table V.

TABLE V. KPIS OF THE CONTROL TECHNIQUES FOR EDC

KPI	FOC	DTC	Hybrid	NMPC
RMSE (%)	100	4.38	0.29	0.02
ME (%)	100	3.46	0.29	0.026
IAE (%)	100	5.43	0.74	0.022
ISE (%)	100	0.192	0.025	0.0001
ISCE (%)	99.001	100	99.019	99.008
Energy (%)	53	100	50	47

According to Table V, FOC does not perform well. It shows higher RMSE and generates less torque. FOC can't compete, even in minimum energy consumption. Also, it is worth noting that the hybrid controller shows better RMSE and IAE, but consumes more energy. Overall, the proposed NMPC controller works smoothly and outperforms the other techniques. In summary, the drawbacks of the DTC and FOC techniques are removed by the hybrid controller by selecting

DTC and FOC as per requirements based on the speed error value. However, due to the sudden switching between DTC and FOC, a smooth transition is not possible for variable reference. This smooth transition requires an optimum modulation of excitation current waveform, which can produce the best solution to avoid over-excitation and torque ripples, and this has been achieved with the NMPC controller.

Fig. 14. Hybrid and NMPC controllers response over the european driving cycle profile: (a) speed and (b) torque.

Fig. 15. Current response of hybrid and NMPC controllers over the EDC profile: (a) phase A, (b) phase B, and (c) phase C.

V. IMPLEMENTATION ASPECTS

In real life, we need to implement motor control techniques on portable and resource-limited hardware like microcontrollers and/or FPGA. Below, we will discuss the implementation aspects of the NMPC technique.

- Prediction model: the success of NMPC depends on the accuracy of the system model. Therefore, it is important to have an accurate model of the motor to capture nonlinear dynamic behavior.
- Embedded implementation: In recent years, there have been several works on the embedded implementation of NMPC solvers, which allow deploying the whole algorithm on embedded devices [22, 24].
- Controller complexity: Due to the optimization, NMPC is a complex controller, and its complexity increases with the problem size (number of states, inputs, constraints, and prediction horizon). Several approaches have been presented to design low-complexity NMPC [22, 24].
- State and disturbance estimation: As an NMPC is a state-feedback control technique, it is important to obtain accurate values of the states. Furthermore, estimation methods can be used to estimate model parameters.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we showed the applicability of a nonlinear MPC to control the BLDC motor for a three-wheeler EV. The proposed NMPC technique improves the closed-loop control performance, reduces energy consumption and steady-state errors. The NMPC is designed with a nonlinear model of the BLDC motor with an electric three-wheeler load to obtain the optimal voltage for the regulation of motor torque. Another significant contribution of this paper is the performance assessment of the four considered control techniques. The proposed NMPC shows smooth operation and gives optimal control actions in the transients and steady-state regions. Therefore, in our assessment, it is concluded that the designed NMPC is best suited for the electric three-wheeler application, where abruptly changing set-points generates more transients. The future goal of this work is to implement the proposed NMPC-based control solution on embedded hardware and study its performance on the EV platform.

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Improved Optimization of the Charge Simulation Method for the Calculation of the Electric Field Around Overhead Transmission Lines Using Statistical Methods

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Abstract-In order to decide the appropriate arrangements of fictitious charges in the charge simulation method, the use of the Monte Carlo method is proposed for the estimation of the probability density function of two variables, the radius ratio, and the angle ratio. The scale and shape parameters of the Weibull's distribution are determined by the maximum likelihood estimator. The obtained results are used to calculate the electric field at arbitrary points in the neighborhood of high voltage transmission lines. The comparisons between the results computed by this method, the results calculated by the genetic algorithm, and those measured, confirm the effectiveness and accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords-charge simulation method; Monte Carlo method; optimization; genetic algorithm; high voltage transmission lines; electric field calculation

I. INTRODUCTION

Designing any high voltage device and analyzing discharge phenomena requires complete knowledge of electric and magnetic field distribution [1]. The potential surface gradient is a critical design parameter for planning and designing overhead lines (insulation or discharge) [2, 3]. The electric fields can be calculated using several analytical and numerical methods. The most used is the Charge Simulation Method (CSM) [4-9]. The CSM was introduced in 1969 [4]. Its basic concept is to replace the distributed charge of conductors and the polarization charges on the dielectric interfaces with a large number of fictitious discrete charges. The magnitudes of these charges have to be calculated so that their integrated effect satisfies the boundary conditions precisely at a selected number of points on

the boundary. The principle of this method is to simulate an actual field with a field formed by a finite number of simulation charges (point and line charges of infinite and semi-infinite length [11]) placed outside the region where the field is to be calculated. The values of the discrete charges are determined by satisfying the boundary conditions at a selected number of contour points:

$$[Qs] = [P]^{-1}[V_b] \quad (1)$$

where $[V_b]$ is the vector of contour point voltages, $[Qs]$ is the vector of unknown simulation charges, and $[P]$ is the matrix of potential coefficients calculated by contour points and simulation charges.

For overhead lines consisting of n parallel conductors placed above the ground, the elements of the matrix of potential coefficients are given by the following relation:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{1}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \ln \left(\frac{D_{ij}}{d_{ij}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_0 is the electric permittivity of vacuum $\approx 8.854 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m, D_{ij} , d_{ij} are respectively the distance between the j th point charge and the image of the i th point charge and the distance between the j th point charge and the i th point charge.

Based on the Laplace equation (3), the superposition theorem and image charge theory, the components at an arbitrary point in the plane y - z plane produced by n point charges $M(y,z)$ can be calculated by (4) and (5):

$$\Delta V = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

$$E_y(y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Q_i}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{y-y_i}{R_i^2} + \Gamma \frac{y-y_i}{R_i^2} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$E_z(y, z) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Q_i}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{z-z_i}{R_i^2} + \Gamma \frac{z+z_i}{R_i^2} \right) \quad (5)$$

where Γ is the reflection coefficient of soil's surface, R_i is the distance between the arbitrary point $M(y,z)$ and the i th point charge, y_i and z_i are the coordinates of the i th contour point, and Q_i is the i th fictitious charge. The reflection coefficient of the soil can be approximated as $\Gamma = -1$.

The current paper aims to optimize CSM parameters using stochastic optimization employing the Monte Carlo Method (MCM). This optimization is based on estimating the Probability Density Functions (PDFs) of the polar coordinates of the simulation charges where the relative mean square error of the voltage on the conductor surface is less than a threshold. To ensure the accuracy of this method, a comparison is made with the measured values of the electric field at arbitrary points near high voltage transmission lines with standard dimensions of the tower on the 40kV line SS Sarajevo 10 –SS Sarajevo 20 [10].

II. RELATED WORK

Since 1969, when the CSM was used for the first time [4], it has been applied and developed in many cases. Some of the main contributions, in chronological order, are:

Authors in [12] used CSM combined with the Rosenbloom's method to solve the potential distribution of the rod-plane. Authors in [13] calculated the field distribution for multi-phase AC sources or in configurations including volume resistance. Authors in [5] simulated the sheathed three cores belted power cable using the complex fictitious charges. Authors in [14] combined CSM with the Genetic Algorithm (GA) to optimize the CSM for a 2D electrode system with an asymmetrical structure. Authors in [15] used CSM-GA to calculate the electric field of a 35kV Vacuum Interrupter (VI). GA has been utilized to compute the electric field [16], to model the horizontal sphere gap [17], and to model the horizontal sphere gap above the ground plane [18]. Authors in [19] calculated the electric field around the head of a transmission tower and its composite insulators by coupling CSM with BEM. Authors in [20] used an optimization strategy to arrange the simulated charges in the thin electrode. Authors in [21] combined CSM with GA to solve the inverse problem in electric-fields of high voltage insulators. Authors in [22] combined CSM with Hashing integrated Adaptive GA (HAGA) to the contour design of support insulators. Authors in [23] used CSM combined with the gold section method to calculate the conductors' surface electrical field of ± 800 kV UHVDC transmission lines. Authors in [24] used CSM-GA to enhance the computation precision of electric fields associated with plate-type electrostatic separators. An adapting Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) combined with CSM was used for calculating the field distribution with non-axial symmetry resulting from a floating spherical conductor between the spheres in [25]. Authors in [26] improved the calculation accuracy of the electric fields associated with electrostatic plate

separators by using CSM-GA. For the optimization of high voltage electrode surfaces, authors in [27] used CSM combined with a Biogeography-based algorithm. Authors in [28] used CSM-PSO for sphere-plane gaps. 3D calculation of electric field intensity under transmission lines with CSM-PSO and CSM-GA was conducted in [29]. Authors in [30] made a comparison between the performance of PSO, GA, and Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) in 3D quasi-static modeling of the electric field produced by High Voltage (HV) overhead power lines. To optimize the ion flow field calculation, authors in [31] used CSM combined with the Flux Tracing Method (FTM).

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Introduction

The proposed algorithm is based on Stochastic Optimization (SO) methods. The SO methods generate and use random variables [32]. They are used in many areas, including aerospace, medicine, transportation, finance, electrical engineering, and many more science and engineering fields. SO can rely on sampling methods such as MCM [33], Latin hypercube sampling [34], or the Quasi-Monte Carlo Method (QMCM) [35]. The algorithm aims to optimize the location of fictitious charges by generating a bivariate distribution of $N \times N$ random variables $\langle C_r, C_a \rangle$ which are respectively the ratio between r_c and r_b , θ_c and θ_b according to (6)-(8). As shown in Figure 1, the contour points are arranged at equal distances on the perimeter of the conductor and are determined by their polar coordinates r_c and θ_c^k , according to (7)-(8). The simulation charges are also arranged at an equal distance on the perimeter of a virtual circle inside and are determined by their polar coordinates r_c and θ_c^k .

$$\theta_b^k = \frac{2\pi k}{N_c} (k-1), \quad k = 1 \text{ to } N_c \quad (6)$$

$$r_c = C_r r_b \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_c^k = \theta_b^k + C_a \cdot \frac{2\pi}{N_c} \quad (8)$$

where r_b is the radius of the conductor, θ_b^k the angle of the k^{th} contour point, N_c the number of contour points, r_c the radius of the virtual circle that contains simulation charges, θ_c^k the angle of the k^{th} fictitious charge, and C_r and C_a the radius and angle ratios ranging between 0 and 1.

Fig. 1. Arrangement of contour points, fictitious charges, and test point.

B. The Algorithm

For each iteration, we have a set of coordinates of fictitious charges, denoted by (C_r^i, C_a^i) such that:

The set of all coordinates is: $\mathcal{E} = \langle C_r, C_a \rangle$ and the set of acceptable coordinates is $\tilde{\mathcal{E}} = \langle \tilde{C}_r, \tilde{C}_a \rangle$. The work is carried out in two steps.

1) Step 1: Extraction of the Set of Solutions $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}$

Data: The electrical and geometric parameters of the line such as the potential of point contour V_b , the number of conductor n_c , the number of fictitious charges N_c , the objective function threshold $Fobj_{threshold}$, the number of iterations N which generate N random (C_r, C_a) pairs.

From $i=1$ to N

Do

Calculate $N_c * n_c$ coordinates of fictitious charges with (6) and (7).

Calculate the potential created by these fictitious charges with (2).

Calculate the fictitious charges with (1).

Calculate the potential created by these fictitious charges:

$$[V_t] = [P_t][Qs]$$

Calculate the objective function $Fobj$:

$$Fobj = \frac{1}{n} \sum (V_t - V_b)^2$$

Compare $Fobj$ with $Fobj_{threshold}$

If $Fobj > Fobj_{threshold}$ then (C_r, C_a) is rejected.

Else add (C_r, C_a) to the $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}$

2) Step 2: Statistical Study

The followed steps are:

1. Establish the histograms of C_r and C_a
2. Estimate the Weibull law parameters A and B with the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE).
3. Calculate the mean and standard deviation of C_r and C_a

The above algorithm is executed for a simple geometry problem (Figure 2) where $n_c=2$, $N_c=3$, $N=100$, $Fobj_{threshold}=4 \times 10^{-12}$, $h=11m$, $d=2m$, $r_b=7cm$, and $V=400kV$. After the iterations are completed, there are 26 accepted bivariates (C_r, C_a) and their histograms are shown in Figures 3 and 4. It is quite obvious that the greatest PDF is concentrated around 0.95 for C_r and 0.49 for C_a . From the obtained results, it should be noted that the shapes of the two histograms are asymmetrical. The obtained data of the first histogram are grouped near the upper limit and incline to the left towards the lower values. On the other hand, in the second histogram, the data are grouped towards the center, which leads to estimating the two parameters of the Weibull distribution as follows.

Fig. 2. Histogram geometry problem.

Fig. 3. Histogram of C_r .

Fig. 4. Histogram of C_a .

The Weibull distribution is used in reliability studies, for example, to study the voltage breakage of electric circuits [36]. The Weibull distribution has two parameters, denoted in the following equation:

$$f(x|A, B) = B \cdot A^{-B} x^{B-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{A}\right)^B} \quad (10)$$

where $A > 0$ is the scale parameter and $B > 0$ is the shape parameter of the distribution.

The Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) [37] estimates the Weibull parameters A and B . The results are given in Table I and the estimate distributions are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

TABLE I. ESTIMATED WEIBULL PARAMETERS

Data	A	B
C_r Relative radius	0.968882	31.02033
C_a Relative angle	0.507651	27.0408

Fig. 5. Estimate distribution of C_r .

Fig. 6. Estimate distribution of C_a .

The estimated distributions shown in Figures 6 and 7 agree with the histograms obtained in Figures 3 and 4. The estimated distributions have mean and variance $\mu_r=0.9519$, $\sigma_r=0.0015$ for the relative radii C_r , and $\mu_a=0.9519$, $\sigma_a=0.0015$, $\mu_a=0.4975$, $\sigma_a=5.2887 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for the relative angular distribution C_a . The optimum position of the coordinates of the fictitious charges obtained are $Cr \in [\mu_r - \sigma_r, \mu_r + \sigma_r]$ and $Ca \in [\mu_a - \sigma_a, \mu_a + \sigma_a]$ with respective mean [0.9505; 0.9534] and [0.4970; 0.4980]. For example, for $C_r=0.95$ and $C_a=0.49$ the optimum arrangement of the fictitious charges is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Optimum arrangement $C_r=0.95$ and $C_a=0.49$.

To verify this approach, an example of the electric field calculation around an overhead- transmission line, already treated in the literature [10] is examined below.

IV. RESULT COMPARISON

The considered example is a 400kV line with a horizontal conductor configuration, as shown in Figure 2. Measurements were taken at 1m height according to recommendations [38], and were performed in the middle of the range between the two adjacent transmission line towers. The electric field is calculated without considering the effect of conductor end, arc sag, and the influence of the tower. In addition, the electromagnetic fields caused by the overhead transmission lines can be approximated by quasi-static fields [39], where quasi-static field displacement current and changes in the magnetic flux are negligible, so the electric field has exactly the same characteristics as the static one. It is assumed that the component of the electric field vector in the x direction is equal to zero, and the electric field vector in an arbitrary point, caused by the n point charges, can be calculated using (7) and (8).

The application of CSM with a relative radius $C_r=0.95$ and relative angle $C_a=0.497$ normally leads to optimum results close to the measured results, but to ensure its effectiveness it must be compared with another method already used with CSM. The choice fell on the GA because it is the most used with CSM as shown above. Also, it has been widely used in the field of electrical engineering [40-43]. Figure 8 illustrates the graphs of the electric fields calculated by this method, by CSM-GA, and the measured values (the values are listed in Table II). It can be seen that the field calculated with the proposed method is closer to the measured field than the field calculated with CSM-GA.

Fig. 8. Distribution of the electric field.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF MEASURED AND CALCULATED RESULTS

Distance (m)	Measured (kV/m)	CSM-MCM	CSM-GA
0	4.13	17.69%	02.50%
5	4.45	02.50%	06.86%
10	5.93	01.44%	03.17%
10.8	6.09	01.11%	03.50%
15	5.81	03.20%	07.66%
20	3.84	01.75%	06.26%
25	2.30	00.99%	03.61%
30	1.39	04.69%	00.04%
35	0.81	16.11%	10.90%
Mean		04.38%	04.95%

V. CONCLUSION

A new approach for optimizing the charge simulation method using the MCM has been presented in this paper. The proposed algorithm aims to determine the PDFs of the classes of polar coordinates for which the error is minimal. The two PDFs follow Weibull's law. The PDF of relative radius (C_r) is asymmetric and concentrated near 1, while the PDF of the relative angle (C_a) is symmetric and is slightly centered at 0.49.

The proposed algorithm offers excellent flexibility and accuracy in determining the optimal locations of simulation charges. Accurate results are achieved for the electric field calculation around the overhead transmission lines. In addition, the solution is not a single element (C_a, C_r) like the results of other methods, but a range distributed according to the Weibull distribution whose parameters are calculated. This work aims at an optimal calculation of the electric field by CMS by arranging the fictitious charges so that they are very close to the edges of the conductor, and each imaginary charge mediates two consecutive contour points. The main contribution of this work is direct optimization without going through optimization methods.

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Energy Management of a Hybrid Electric Vehicle

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Abstract-Electric Vehicles (EVs) are becoming more popular and gaining attention due to a combination of factors such as falling prices and increasing environmental awareness. EVs fall into several categories related to energy production and storage. Standard developed, tested, and commercialized EV technologies include Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs), All Electric Vehicles (AEVs), also known as Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs), Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs), and Flexible Fuel Vehicles (FFVs). Still, the advantages of FCEVs are relatively small compared to other autonomous and refueling technologies. Considering the above aspects, this work presents a Matlab/Simulink model of an FCEV's behavior and opportunities.

Keywords-fuel cell; electric vehicle; EMS; solar energy; PEM; Matlab; dynamic-modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the gases emitted by fossil fuel-based vehicles are seriously threatening the environment and directly impact climate [1, 2]. Global warming and climate change are amplified by pollution due to the extensive burn of diesel by diesel-based vehicles [3, 4]. It has been reported that transportation is the origin of 24% of CO₂ emissions worldwide [5]. Even worse, in 2020, the European Environment Agency suggested that about 27% of CO₂ is emitted by the transport sector, while more than 70% of emissions are mainly caused by vehicles [5]. From the 1970s, fossil fuel combustion increased the emission of CO₂, CO, SO₂, and NO by 90% to reach 36.1Gt in 2014 [6]. For this reason the petroleum cars represent one of the most important sources of pollution to the environment [7]. Moreover, this type of car is witnessing an increasing demand from citizens. With this development, research and studies on clean energy have multiplied. These factors, aim to reduce pollution and encourage people to use Electric Vehicles (EVs) [8].

The standard EV utilizes one energy source, however it is not profitable in return. So, it has been upgraded by adding a second source with an Energy Management System (EMS). The complex setup and behavior of the multi-source hybrid power system puts additional requirements on the operation of the EMS. Regardless of the design of the power system, the EMS manages the power flow of the transducer in real time to achieve the control goal [9]. Therefore, the optimal control algorithm used in the driving cycle can be used as a representative research program for energy management technology.

EMS was selected as a potential research problem in industry and academia [10]. In the evaluation of the existing literature, there are many classifications of energy management methods. EMSs are classified into three types according to their optimization strategy: rule-based, local, and global. In [11], the authors outline the EMS of plug-in hybrid EVs. The classification of energy management is discussed, including rule-based and optimization-based control systems. In [12], the authors compare the advantages and disadvantages of each technique. Finally, many aspects of real-time implementation (for example, computational burden and optimization) are discussed. In [13], the authors examine and show various classifications of hybrid EVs that use hydraulic drive-classifying and internet-related technologies. With the advancement of ITS technology and machine learning methods (such as adaptability and real-time execution) [14], a new EMS is being created to meet the increasing performance requirements. However, a complete evaluation of EMSs is needed to better grasp the current technology and future research work. Unlike previous EMS studies, this one includes a complex ranking system.

There are two types of offline EMS: one based on global improvement and one based on regulations [15]. Instant improvement, predictive improvement, and learning-based

improvement are three types of online environmental management systems [16]. Since the proposed technology contains various methods for solution goals, optimization, and real-time implementation, a thorough review of the literature is conducted. The concepts, advantages and disadvantages of each technology are compared, and the design and operational characteristics of the proposed scheme are highlighted [17]. Finally, the development of a new EMS and recent literature highlight the important prospects for macromolecules. The hybrid part on a vehicle is the application of two energy sources. The Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) [18] is the best type for the EV due to its high efficiency and fast response rate with back up source (super-capacitor (SC)) [19]. The addition of photovoltaic (PV) energy will reduce the consumption of hydrogen up to 40% [20].

The current article describes a realistic environmental management system for the PVFCEV. The proposed method was developed in response to various constraints, including energy requirements and subsystems. Unlike previous papers, it avoids clustering (on/off) and global/local optimization, which may be deceptive due to algorithm modification and implementation assumptions. Instead, each algorithm is presented and reviewed individually, emphasizing its advantages and limitations, as well as alternative technologies to compensate for them.

II. THE SYSTEM DESCRIPTION OF THE PVFCEV

The PVFCEV consists of a PEMFC stack, hydrogen tank, a Super-Capacitor (SC), a PV array as a secondary power source, EMS, and an electric motor with driveline. The model description is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the PVFCEV.

The FC system is the principal energy source. The details of the FC used on the Simulink model are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. THE DETAILS OF THE FC

Parameter	Value
Number of cells	65
Nominal power	4.2 kW
Nominal voltage	45 V
Peak power	6 kW
Fuel supply pressure	1.5 bar

The SC has high power density and fast response. It gives power in the acceleration phase and is recharged by the excess energy generated by regenerative braking and the PV array. The main parameters of the SC source and the PV array are shown in Table II and III.

TABLE II. SUPER-CAPACITOR MAIN PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Rated capacitance	15.6 F
Rated voltage	291 V
Initial voltage	270 V
Number of series capacitors	105
Current prior open circuit	10 A
SOC start	80%

TABLE III. THE PARAMETERS OF THE PV ARRAY

Parameter	Value
Number of cells per module	72
Max power per module	250 W
Nominal voltage	50 V
Circuit current	6.3 A
Fuel supply pressure	1.5 bar
Number of series-connected module	2

The Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) was chosen thanks to its high operating efficiency and reliability. The EMS monitors the working status of the system, including PV array power, SC SOC, and the required power, to determine the power of the FC and the torque of the motor. The vehicle is subjected to several forces, where some of their vectors lead to the traction force (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The tractive forces on the vehicle.

The F_{Tr} traction force is needed to overcome the resistance to advance and accelerate the vehicle. It is written in the form of:

$$F_{tr} = F_{aero} + F_i + F_{arade} + F_{rr} \quad (1)$$

Thus, according to Newton's second law, the acceleration α can be expressed by.

$$\alpha = \frac{F_{tr} - (F_{aero} + F_{grade} + F_{rr})}{m_i} \quad (2)$$

F_{aero} is the aerodynamic force (N):

$$F_{aero} = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A_f V^2 \quad (3)$$

F_{rr} is the rolling force:

$$F_{rr} = mgC_{rr} \quad (4)$$

F_{grade} is the resistance force of hill climb:

$$F_{grade} = mg \sin(\theta) \quad (5)$$

Table IV shows the hybrid EV's parameters.

TABLE IV. PARAMETERS OF THE VEHICLE

Parameter	Value
Vehicle mass	1400 Kg
Gravity	9.8 m/s ²
Air density	1.18 kg/m ³
Road angle	0.5 degrees
Air drag	0.38

III. THE ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The EMS is based on the output of the SOC of the SC, the PV and the power demanded from the electric motor as shown in the figure 3.

Fig. 3. The scheme of the EMS: PV, FC, SC, and EV.

The position of the pedal determines the power needed from the motor. To determine the powers of the SC and the FC, the FC power is selected as the principal control variable of the controller. From Figure 3, the bus capacitive energy of EMS (E_{EMS}) is:

$$E_{EMS} = P_{FC} + P_{PV} + P_{SC} - P_{Ch} \quad (6)$$

The FC stack and the PV are generators (P_{Gen}):

$$P_{Gen} = P_{FC} + P_{PV} \quad (7)$$

By combination (6) and (7) we get:

$$E_{EMS} = P_{Gen} + P_{SC} - P_{Ch} \quad (8)$$

The generators' power is:

$$P_{Gen} = E_{EMS} - P_{SC} + P_{Ch} \quad (9)$$

General, the PV panel cannot be fast in terms of electricity production. For this case, the FC power compensates the lack of energy as given in (10):

$$P_{FC_ref} = P_{Gen} - P_{PV} \quad (10)$$

Moreover, we made a fuzzy algorithm with 3 inputs (*cycle*, P_{PV} , and P_{SC}) and the output is the P_{FC_ref} as shown in Figure 4. Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7) represent the input and the output of the fuzzy algorithm according to 45 rules.

Fig. 4. Input parameter PV.

Fig. 5. Input parameter SOC.

Fig. 6. Input parameter power demand.

Fig. 7. Output parameter FC.

The pedal determines the power demanded for a specific torque. The pedal represents the brake and the accelerator. The pressure ratio on the pedal is present in the testing model in the simulation. In the fuzzy system, the power is between 0 and 1. The fuzzy set for the PV are low, middle, and high to represent the intensity of the solar radiation. The fuzzy set for the SOC of SC are low, middle, and high to represent the ratio of the residual capacity. The power demand is split into five levels, from Very Small (VS) to Very Large (VL) after passing Small (S), Middle (Mid), and Large (L). Finally, the fuzzy set of the FC has 6 levels: Zero (ZE), VS, S, M, L, and VL. The rules of the fuzzy reasoning are presented in Table V. The algorithm was developed in Matlab.

The EM of the PV array is controlled by the Perturb and Observation (P&O) algorithm. Figure 8, presents the flowchart of the EMS algorithm for the PV. This method gives excellent results among different MPPT techniques.

TABLE V. FUZZY REASONING RULES

Inp SOC	Inp PV	Inp P _{Load}				
		VS	S	M	L	VL
Low	Low	VS	M	L	L	VL
Low	Middle	VS	S	M	L	VL
Low	High	VS	S	M	M	L
Middle	Low	ZE	VS	S	M	L
Middle	Middle	ZE	VS	S	M	M
Middle	High	ZE	ZE	VS	S	M
High	Low	ZE	ZE	VS	VS	S
High	Middle	ZE	ZE	ZE	VS	S
High	High	ZE	ZE	ZE	ZE	VS

Fig. 8. Flowchart of the P&O algorithm.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to validate the proposed EMS, the PVFCEV mode was simulated in Matlab/Simulink. We started testing the model with the following cycle of pedal positions:

- Time ∈ [0. . .2s] stop: The pedal is at 0%
- Time ∈ [3s. . .6s] acceleration: The pedal is at 80%
- Time ∈ [7s . . . 17s] stability: the pedal is at 70%
- Time ∈ [18s . . . 27s] apply the brakes: the pedal is at 75 %
- Time ∈ [28s . . . 30s] system shutdown

Figure 9 shows the results of model under the following conditions: 500W/m² solar radiance, 25⁰C temperature, and 80% SOC of the super-capacity. The SOC of the SC is high with medium radiation, the SC acts as the principal source on the [2s... 6s] period, according to the faster response of the SC compared to the FC. However, the SC is in the recharging mode during [0...2s] and when the vehicle stops. The power of

the SC during [0..2s] is negative and this action means that the PV array is charging the SC. The FC started to produce power at the 3rd second. When the FC power tries to become stable, the SC powers down and starts to recharge during [6...7s]. The period os [6s...7s] represents the change of acceleration from 80% to 70%.

Fig. 9. Simulation results of the vehicle for 500W/m² solar radiation.

The FC becomes the principal source in [8s...17s]. The FC power is the same as the motor power according to the stability of the system in that duration. After that, the FC power becomes zero and the power of the motor becomes negative due to the braking during [18s...27s]. At this time, the engine is trying as a primary source to recharge the SC. At the end, the vehicle stops and the power of the system is zero. The NEDC (New European Driving Cycle) is one of the cycles used to measure the degree of performance of the vehicle engines and energy economy. This cycle is divided in two parts: the first part is represented from 0s to 800s (urban driving cycle) and the second part from 800 s to 1200s (extra urban driving cycle) in Figure 10. The demand power (P_{Ch}) of the vehicle when the path traveled corresponds to the NEDC speed profile is given by Figure 11.

$$P_{Ch} = P_{FC} + P_{PV} + P_{SC} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 10. Profile of vehicle speed (NEDC).

Fig. 11. Demand power.

The power delivery of the vehicle (P_{ch}), the FC power, and the SC power are shown in Figure 12. We can see that the power profile of the FC depends on the fuzzy rules applied and the power profile requested. This allows meeting the demands of the vehicle while ensuring an energy exchange between the FC and SC during the traction phase, precisely, for the calls of low power and when the SOC of the SC has low values. In this case, the FC allows, at the same time, satisfying the demand of the vehicle and charging the pack of SCs. The gap between the power supplied by the FC and that required by the traction system is used to ensure the loading phase of the storage system. The SC load reached a high value during the FC stress period up to $t = 965$ s. This is explained by the use of the SC during the braking phases most of the time. Thereafter, the SOC value decreases during the interval up to $t=1170$ s when it is solicited from the FC. When the vehicle is in acceleration mode and the SC SOC is average, the SC shoulders the FC to provide the required power. The FC provides the power required charging the SC during the acceleration mode and when the SOC of the SC is low. In this case, the SC can easily recover from the braking energy.

Fig. 12. Power elements.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the technical results of PVFCEV via a mathematic model with a fuzzy algorithm designed for it. The EMS of the vehicle using the power of the PV, the demand power and the SOC of an SC as input parameters. The output of the EMS is the reference power of the FC. The use of the SC contributed to improving the vehicle's effectiveness in the acceleration phase, similar to previous research that remained in the use of the battery despite its poor efficacy. The EMS was validated by the simulation results. In order to get good results, the simulation started by the cycle of pedal position as a first step and the NEDC driving cycle was considered in the next phase. The proposed EMS operated efficiently and robustly under rapid changes in power demand, changes in solar power, and different levels of SC SOC.

In future work, we will focus on the design and implementation of experiments to validate the proposed PVFCEV and its EMS. The PVFCEV physical model in this work helps to facilitate the design of the experimental setup, as real physical component models are used.

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Comparison of Accident Databases and Analysis of Past Industrial Accidents in the Chemical Process Industry

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Abstract-Despite India being home to some of the worst chemical industry disasters, there is no proper accident reporting and analysis mechanism. The National Informatics Centre of the Ministry of Environment and Forest (MoEF) presented an online accident database called CAIRS to assist Past Accident Analysis (PAA). This paper compares CAIRS with major accident databases widely used by safety professionals. The parameters considered for comparison are scope, accessibility, method of data collection, quality, and the frequency of reporting. Past accident analysis showed that the total number of reported events is more or less steady and the number of major accidents is decreasing marginally in European countries, whereas in India only a few states report accidents using the CAIRS platform. The analysis raised serious concerns about the monitoring of reported information in the Indian database. At present, the information available in this database is not reliable and any conclusion based on this information can be misleading. Suggestions are offered to enhance the efficacy of the Indian accident database.

Keywords-Past Accident Analysis (PAA); chemical process industry; accident database; CAIRS; eMARS

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial accidents cause losses to human life, environment, and property. A critical examination of these events can bring valuable information on accident morphology, and lessons learned from past accidents can prevent similar events in the future [1, 2]. Accident investigation and follow-up of the results are vital in safety management systems. Learnings from past incidents can help us anticipate hazards and mitigate the associated risks by reducing the frequency and/or the consequences of the event. With the help of accident

investigation, the root cause of the accident can be identified and with corrective and preventive actions, associated risks can be mitigated and make the workspace safer. To anticipate, recognize, and control accidents in the industry we need to collect and review past incident information. It is well documented that the reasons for accidents in many cases are repeated [3, 4]. If we can find out reasons or patterns which are frequently repeating, such accidents can be avoided in the future, and this is the basic objective of Past Accident Analysis (PAA).

When processes are carried out at extreme temperatures and pressures, the probability of occurrence and the severity of any undesired event is higher. By properly analyzing the information obtained from past accidents, one can get to know the probable causes of failures and accidents in the chemical industry. Major accidents in the process industry are caused due to loss of containment due to process failures or due to natural events such as earthquakes, lightning, and floods, which are also called Natech events. Unlike process equipment failure accidents, Natech events can trigger accidents in the entire plant. Most of the time the response against these events is delayed due to the lack of communication or the non-availability of personnel leading to the escalation of the accidents [5, 6]. Although we can't completely safeguard against natural disasters, we can find the most vulnerable parts of the system and can add additional layers of protection for such installations. After identifying the vulnerable units/areas we can develop the system in such a way that it will have the least effect on such critical/vulnerable installations [6]. The repeated disruption in a process industry can be an indication of a major fault that can lead to an accident. If these disruptions

are more frequent, they raise questions about the safety controls in the organization. Authors in [7] analyzed industrial accidents from the FACTS database and concluded that repeated disruption can be considered a precursor to accidents, which indicates the failures in the control mechanism of the organization. By analyzing the past incident information it will become much easier to predict the common accident precursor in chemical process industries by looking at factors like the chemicals used, chemical release modes, etc. [8].

Unlike other branches of science and technology, where experimental and analytical data are used, in accident analysis, performing experiments to forecast an accident is a cumbersome task. The data we get from past accidents can be used to identify the root causes, which would help prevent similar accidents in the future. So, it is important to analyze past accidents and learn from them, so that the same situation will not be repeated [9-11]. PAA is possibly the most powerful and frequently utilized activity for gaining insight into the reasons accidents happen. PAA gives important "intelligence of knowing the past" and techniques to forecast hazardous events or mitigate the effects of incidents [3, 12-14]. Active research is being carried out in the field of accident analysis with the help of management tools and machine learning, incorporating data management tools such as Business Intelligence (BI) in past accident analysis, which can provide valuable insight to develop business strategy and tactics [15-18].

In the past, India has been home to several chemical industrial accidents including the world's worst industrial disaster, the Bhopal gas tragedy. To collate the accident data systematically, the National Informatics Centre of the Ministry of Environment and Forest introduced a web-based accident reporting platform called Chemical Accident Information Reporting System (CAIRS). This paper compares the functionality of this database with other well-known accident databases and its efficacy by performing PAA.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

Authors in [3] analyzed 3222 major accidents in chemical process industries reported between 1926 and 1997. Their study revealed that in process industries, 49% of accidents were caused by fire and explosions and 38% by toxic releases. Their study concluded that although the number of accidents per year decreased during the '80s, the losses per accident have an increasing trend. The fatalities per accident for fire/explosion and toxic release incidents are 3.27 and 2.49 respectively. In the chemical industry, accidents often involve cascading effects, also known as domino effects. Often devastating destructions are caused by accidents involving domino effects. Predicting and forecasting a standalone accident is much easier than forecasting a domino effect by risk assessment which also requires past accident data. That is one of the reasons very little work has been carried out on managing domino accidents in process industries. PAA can provide valuable information to predict and manage domino effects in process industries [9, 19]. Authors in [20] conducted statistical research on 207 major industrial accidents from 1969 to 1998. They identified that 39% of major accidents involve domino effects. The risk of domino accidents was determined to be dependent on the type of substance involved and gaseous hydrocarbons pose more

risk (58%) of causing domino accidents than liquid fuels (49%). Authors in [9] conducted another noteworthy study on this topic by analyzing 224 accidents involving domino effects from 1917 to 2019 and concluded that 80% of domino accidents occur in fixed installations and 20% during transportation. Domino effects are frequently associated with flammable substances, and Vapor Cloud Explosion/Fire (VCE/VCF) is the most common initiating cause of domino accidents. The analysis of reporting trends indicated that domino accidents are more rigorously reported in developed countries. Among developing countries, India reports the highest number of domino accidents (34%).

III. CHEMICAL PROCESS INDUSTRY ACCIDENT DATABASES

The main motive of accident investigation is to learn from the mistakes or lapses that led to an accident and identify remedial measures to prevent recurrences [21]. If information of multiple accidents is clubbed in a single source, the analysts will be able to gather pictures on a bigger canvas. Accident data clubbed under one unit consist an accident database. By analyzing this information we can identify the anatomy of accidents. Inferences from such analysis are being used for making or updating legal requirements and issuing safe work guidelines for similar processes and industries. As we know, even slight negligence can lead to a major problem in chemical industries, so it becomes important to find out the reasons of such accidents. After identification of the root causes, they could be mitigated. Public sharing of the accident investigation reports can help all stakeholders who deal with similar hazards. Accident databases are a vast source of such information, so by reviewing them, both the industry and the regulators can plan proactive measures to prevent the recurrence of accidents. Generally, the accident databases are used for the following reasons:

- To gain knowledge from past incidents: to perceive what has occurred, how has it occurred, what the outcomes were, and why it occurred. By this, the designers can avoid the mistakes which have caused accidents in the past.
- Where adequate information is accessible, it might be feasible to create frequencies or probabilities of incidents, which can support risk assessment studies [22].

There are many databases that maintain past accident data of the process industry. Some of the well-known accident databases include FACTS, eMARS, MHIDAS, CAIRS, and PUPAD. These databases have their advantages and limitations: some of them are not free to use, i.e they require some kind of subscription, and some of them do not have accurate data [12]. There are very few databases freely available for PAA and those which are available are having issues with data accuracy. So, the need occurs to have such a free database in order to provide a single platform to search past accidents and work on the learnings from them in order to create a workplace as safe as possible. The focus of this paper is to review the existing literature on PAA and by analyzing the existing databases to find out their problems and propose possible solutions. The major chemical process industry accident databases and advantages and disadvantages are briefly discussed below.

1) Major Hazard Incident Data Service (MHIDAS)

This database was launched in 1986 by Health and Safety Executive (UK), followed by the Canvey Island study, which highlighted the need for reliable data for quantitative risk assessment [22]. This database contains information on global accidents involving hazardous materials. Authors in [12] identified data discrepancies in this database. MHIDAS provides information on the incident type, origin, causes, fatalities, injuries, and losses in the UK and abroad, but it is no longer being updated.

- Advantages: Incidents can be analyzed based on activity, location and people affected. It is a huge inventory of past accidents, since it is one of the oldest databases.
- Disadvantages: A substantial fee is required to access it. It is no longer being updated.

2) eMARS- The Major Accident Reporting System

The Major Accident Reporting System, later known as eMARS was launched by the European commission in 1982, based on the recommendation of the Seveso directive [23]. This database contains information from the Major Accident Hazards Bureau (MAHB) supplied by the EU and affiliated countries and the information includes both accidents and near misses. Reporting of events categorized as major accidents by SEVESO directive III is mandatory for EU countries and voluntary for affiliated countries. In terms of categories of information, this is the most comprehensive accident database. The available information includes year-wise accidents, industry type, involvements of domino effects, Natech events, transboundary impacts, etc. [23].

- Advantages: EU member states have to report into eMARS compulsorily so most of the accidents do get reported here. Companies' names and locations are not provided in the database. Data are available in two forms i.e. short report and full report [24].
- Disadvantages: As it takes almost two to three years to complete a report after proper investigation, one has to wait up to three years to access the full report.

3) Failure and Accidents Technical information System (FACTS) Database

This is a global chemical process industry accident database launched by TNO Industrial and External Safety. Nowadays, it is maintained by the Unified Industrial & Harbour Fire Department in Rotterdam-Rozenburg. As of date, this is the largest repository of chemical industry accidents containing information on over 27500 industrial incidents. FACTS database gathers information from accident reports of companies and governmental agencies [25].

Advantages: Abstract containing all important information is available for every accident (3 levels of reports). It contains information from professional sources (CSB, ARIA, MARS, ZEMA, NRC, NTSB, reports by companies and publications) so data are considered to be reliable.

Disadvantages: Only accident tables are freely accessible. A fee is required to access detailed information.

4) Chemical Accident Information & Reporting System (CAIRS)

CAIRS is an Indian chemical industry accident database developed by the Environment & Forest Informatics Division of the National Informatics, Centre Govt. of India. Here, accidents are reported by companies and are updated in the database by authorities specified under the MSHIC Rule 1989 [26, 27]. The flowchart of updating the data is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Data updating process in CAIRS.

- Advantages: Includes reports and charts that can be freely accessed. Has reports from different authorities. Losses outside the premises are reported (fatality, injury, and missing).
- Disadvantages: The root causes of most of the accidents are not mentioned, not all accidents are reported, and there are data duplication and consistency issues.

5) Known Problems

The reported problems while performing PAA using accident databases are [12]:

- Improper accident reporting mechanism
- Record maintenance is not appropriate
- Hiding the actual cause of the accident
- The improper strategy of investigation.

Hence, it is important to consider the strengths and weaknesses of the databases before performing PAA.

IV. PAST ACCIDENT ANALYSIS

Comprehensive past accident analyses have been performed in [3, 9, 11, 28, 29]. The last well-known PAA was performed in 2011 [9]. Since then, significant PAA research was not performed for major accidents in the chemical process industry.

In this paper, PPA was performed based on the data available in eMARS and CAIRS. The selected period analysis was from 2010 to 2021.

TABLE I. DATABASE COMPARISON

Database	Country	Scope	Accessibility	Data updation process	No of records	Available information
MHIDAS	UK	Accidents involving hazardous materials from 1950 to 1990	Subscription required	No longer being updated. AEA technology was used to compile data from public domain sources.	8000+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date & location • Materials involved • No of people affected • General and special causes • Economic losses.
eMARS	EU	Major accidents and near-miss information	Free	Information provided by EU and affiliated countries under the Seveso directive.	1165	Comprehensive information, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accident, site, and installation descriptions and classification. • Cause description and classification. • Consequences description and classification. • Emergency response and legal actions. • Lessons learned.
FACTS	The Netherlands	Global accidents	Accident tables are freely accessible. Subscription required for detailed reports	Accident information from professional sources.	27500+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An accident table contains basic information about the year, country, activity, and causes of accidents. • The coded abstracts contain detailed information about location, operations, etc. • Detailed information about causes and consequences
CAIRS	India	Incidents reported by authorities in India	Free	Based on accident reports submitted to various governmental agencies.	100+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accidents' date and time • Company information • Chemicals involved and their type. • Causes • Number of people killed/injured within and outside the premises

1) Past Accident Analysis from eMARS database

During the studied period, 495 accidents were recorded in the eMARS database, and detailed reports are available for 378. The event-wise yearly trends of the reported events are illustrated in Figure 2. From the trends it can be inferred that the total number of reported events is more or less steady and the number of major accidents is decreasing marginally in Europe. This indicates that the trends identified by [9] are still prevailing in Europe. Out of these 495 accidents, 73% are major, 20% are near-miss incidents, and 7% are other events (Figure 3), meeting the criteria defined in the Seveso directive annexure [16].

Fig. 2. Year-wise accident reporting trends in eMARS.

Industry-wise recorded accident analysis can indicate the vulnerability of industries. The analysis, as shown in Figure 5, shows that 19% of accidents were reported in petrochemical/oil refineries followed by the general chemical manufacturing industry (10%), and the power generation, supply, and distribution (6%) industries. Interestingly, there is a drastic

reduction in the number of accidents reported in the general chemical industry during the analysis period compared to the previous decade (1998-2009), i.e. from 132 cases to 51, whereas the number of accidents in petrochemical/oil refineries increased from 84 to 93. eMARS also reports special circumstances involved with the recorded incidents such as Natch or domino events, transboundary effects, and involvement of contractors. Out of such 56 events, 54% of the cases involve contractors and 21% involve domino effects as illustrated in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Types of accidents reports in eMARS.

Fig. 4. Accidents involving special circumstances.

Fig. 5. Industry-wise accidents.

2) Indian Chemical Industry Accident Scenario

As illustrated in Figure 6, the analysis of chemical industry accidents reported to the various regulatory agencies in CAIRS, showed that out of 29 states, only 6 have reported accidents so far, pointing out the poor accident reporting culture in India. It was also found that there are duplicate data entries in CAIRS: Some of the accidents are reported multiple times, e.g. the accident in Accura Lab Pvt. Ltd, Telangana on 25th September 2013 is reported twice, one with the accident cause details and another without this information. Similarly, if an accident was involved with multiple chemicals it is reported multiple times.

Fig. 6. State-wise reporting of accidents.

The data collected from the CAIRS database were manually filtered to remove all duplicities, and 86 records were obtained, which were submitted to the chief inspector of factories. The year-wise reporting trends are depicted in Figure 7. As shown, there is no particular trend in the number of accidents reported in CAIRS. The maximum number of accidents was reported in 2016, while the minimum in 2014, whereas there are no available data after 2018. One of the major drawbacks of CAIRS is that the root cause of the accident is missing in most reports. Out of the 86 accidents analyzed, only 36 have their root cause mentioned, i.e. for around 58% of the accidents the root cause is not mentioned. This shows that the investigative findings of an accident are not recorded for most accidents. Figure 8 depicts the accidents with regard to their type/category. It was found that 57% of the reported cases are incidents. In some cases, accidents with fatalities are considered minor accidents or incidents, while accidents with fewer casualties may be considered as major. So, there is no

well-defined guideline or procedure to report an accident. This indicates a lack of monitoring of reported information in this database. At present, the information in this regard is not reliable and any conclusion based on this type of analysis can be misleading.

Fig. 7. Year-wise accidents reported in CAIRS.

Fig. 8. Accidents based on category.

The conclusion of the analysis based on the available information in these two databases is that the findings of accidents are better reported in eMARS, as the root cause, and the event sequence of every accident is mentioned in eMARS, but not in CAIRS. eMARS also provides more categories of information. The Indian database CAIRS needs urgent revisions to provide more reliable and useful data.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This work reviewed past accidents in the chemical process industry. A comprehensive analysis of past accidents enables us to identify the recent accident trends in the industry. Accident databases aid the analysis of past accidents. Global databases were compared and their advantages and disadvantages were listed. PAA of the accidents recorded in the European eMARS database and the Indian CAIRS database has

been performed. From the trends, it can be inferred that the total number of reported events is more or less steady and the number of major accidents is decreasing marginally in Europe. The analysis of the Indian chemical industry based on accidents reported in the CAIRS database can lead to inaccurate conclusions as accidents are not reported promptly in this database and an urgent revision to ensure data accuracy is required. Some suggestions on improving the existing databases are:

- Accident databases available in the public domain would encourage researchers to undertake active studies in this field and would also enable risk professionals and policymakers to make data-driven decisions.
- Before publishing the details in accident databases, the data entering officials need to rigorously verify all the entries, including the root causes of incidents.
- Additional information needs to be incorporated into the databases to meet the current risk assessment requirements.
- As most databases are country-specific, global collaborations are required to disseminate past accident information worldwide.

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The Taguchi Approach in Studying and Optimizing the Electro-Fenton Oxidation to Reduce Organic Contaminants in Refinery Wastewater Using Novel Electrodes

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Abstract-This study investigated the degradation of organic pollutants using an advanced electrochemical oxidation technique in a batch reactor cell consisting of a graphite anode, modified by electrodeposition of PbO_2 , and a graphene-modified carbon fiber cathode. The experiment was designed by the Taguchi design approach with an orthogonal array of L_{18} to study and optimize the degradation of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) by the electro-Fenton oxidation process. Four process parameters, Current Density (CD), Temperature, Fe^{2+} concentration, and time were measured at different levels. The impact of each factor was analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA). Furthermore, a linear model analysis was applied for the Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio and mean values, obtaining the optimal conditions. The most significant parameter of the COD removal efficiency was time, and the least one was temperature.

Keywords-organic pollutants; Taguchi; electro-Fenton; COD removal

I. INTRODUCTION

Wastewater from the oil industry is frequently produced and discharged into the main water bodies, causing severe environmental issues. The amount and characteristics of pollutants in oil refinery wastewater depend on the type of oil being processed, the plant configuration, the operation procedures, and the type of processing units [1]. Pollutants in refinery wastewater often consist of free hydrocarbons, suspended solids, and inorganic matter, with a high concentration of salts, sulfides, ammonia, organic carbon, phenol, benzene, heavy metals, nutrient grease, and chemical additives [2, 3]. Phenol is the most produced contaminant in the refinery industry, which pollutes surface and ground water and causes harmful effects on human health [4-7]. Phenol and its derivatives are highly soluble in water, so they can be present in a wide range of water concentrations, from a few milligrams to high concentrations that reach 7000mg/L, whereas refineries contribute approximately 6-500mg/L. Phenolic compounds persist in water or transform various reactions such as

chlorination and methylation into more harmful and toxic materials than phenol itself, such as chlorophenols and cresols [8]. Phenol is classified as one of the most harmful pollutants by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the European Agency (EA) and is toxic to humans and the environment [9]. Phenol can poison humans when ingested, inhaled, or in contact with the skin. Phenol vapors cause severe irritation to the eyes and mucous. Other severe symptoms caused by exposure to phenol include fatigue, headache, loss of consciousness, nausea, and vomiting. Exposure to phenol for a long time can change blood pressure and damage the liver, kidneys, and the nervous system [10, 11].

Phenol and phenolic compounds can be treated using several methods such as adsorption [12], biological treatments [13], coagulation/flocculation [14], chemical oxidation [15], ion exchange [16], and electrochemical oxidation processes [17]. Adsorption is limited by the adsorbers, as they cannot be easily renewable and need regeneration after a period of use, and the pollutant is not converted to less hazardous materials as it is concentrated and transferred to a vapor or an organic phase [18]. Biological treatment was related to many problems that concern the operating conditions, including providing a suitable environment for microorganisms, the low settle capacity of the sludge due to the low ratio of food to microorganisms, the formation of polymers consisting of lipids, proteins, and carbohydrates that negatively affect the settlement of the sludge, and the poisoning of microorganisms due to toxic compounds that require very long times for acclimatization and start-up [19, 20]. Coagulation requires the junction of non-reusable chemicals such as coagulants, flocculants, and aid chemicals and requires physical and chemical monitoring of the affluent. The volume of sludge generated increases, as well as the need for management and the cost of treated contaminates [14, 20-21]. Chemical oxidation, such as simple oxidation, ozonation, and hypochlorite treatment, requires completed physical and chemical treatments. Still, these

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processes require chemicals, thereby, production, transportation, and management of the necessary oxidants for the pre-treatment step. The type of oxidant directly affects the efficiency of the process. The creation of intermediates that may be more toxic than the treated substance has a limited effect on chemical oxygen demand, aromatic compounds, and volatile substances, especially when using hypochlorite, and the formation of sludge [15, 22]. Ion exchange technology needs a high initial cost of the selective resin, maintenance cost, time-consuming regeneration, and large equipment if there is a large volume of wastewater to be treated. Beads are easily fouled by organic matter that requires a physicochemical pre-treatment to remove these pollutants, which is not effective for organic target pollutants [16].

At this time, electrochemical treatment is one of the cleanest and most eco-friendly methods used as an alternative to other treatment processes for environmental protection. Electrochemical technology is a most promising one for the treatment of organic pollutants in refinery wastewater. It includes electrocoagulation-electroflotation, anodic oxidation, electrochemical reduction, and advanced electrochemical oxidation [23-24]. Electrochemical methods do not need to add a lot of chemical reagents because the leading reagent used is the electron, which is considered a clean reagent. These processes can also remove contaminants from even a massive quantity of different phases of polluted streams and require lower temperature and pressure than other non-electrochemical processes. Many electrochemical processes have high selectivity, which prevents the formation of unwanted byproducts because the applied potential can be controlled, which helps attacking specific bonds. The chemical substances added in electrochemical processes are small and safe. Electrochemical methods operate flexibly and their control processes, and equipment, are simple and inexpensive [17, 24-25]. Electrochemical oxidation processes are popular for treating organic pollutants in refinery wastewater and are classified into direct and indirect. Direct oxidation occurs on the surface of the anode electrode, and indirect oxidation uses an oxidizing mediator that forces organic matter to contribute to the oxidation reaction, such as hypochlorite [26], chlorine [27], and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) [28]. The electro-Fenton oxidation process is an indirect advanced oxidation process that uses the electrogenerated hydroxyl radical ($\bullet OH$) on the surface of electrodes, which has a high oxidation capacity in the oxidation of organic substances [29]. In the electro-Fenton oxidation process, ferrous ion (Fe^{2+}) is added externally, and H_2O_2 is generated electrochemically in-situ on specific electrodes that have appropriate cathodic potential by a two-electron reduction of oxygen [30]:

The electricity used in electro-Fenton oxidation processes is clean and contamination-free, so these processes are eco-friendly and do not generate secondary pollutants. $\bullet OH$ is generated in the solution by using Fe^{2+} as a catalyst which attacks the organic contaminants [30]:

The Fe^{3+} ion produced in (2) can transform to Fe^{2+} by a one-electron reduction reaction [30]:

The electrode material is an important factor that affects the performance of the electro-Fenton oxidation because it affects selectivity, efficiency, mechanism, and the products of the oxidation process [2, 31]. So, when choosing the electrode, material-specific properties must consider its electrical conductivity, selectivity, catalytic activity, cost, lifetime, and oxygen overvoltage [31]. The effect of the cathodic reaction on the efficiency of the overall oxidation process is also taken into account [31, 32]. Carbon electrodes are widely used as anodes and cathodes in electro-Fenton processes. They have high surface, high porosity, corrosion resistance, and offer low-pressure drops compared to other materials because they have a large space. Examples of these electrodes are graphite [33-35], reticulated vitreous carbon [36], activated carbon fibers [37], and carbon nanotubes [38]. This study uses the Taguchi approach to investigate the electro-Fenton oxidation process of organic pollutants in refinery wastewater. The process was carried out in a batch reactor cell consisting of a graphite anode modified by electrodeposition of a PbO_2 film on its surface and a carbon-fiber cathode modified by graphene. Different operating conditions were used in the oxidation process, and the effect of these parameters on the COD removal was also studied.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Taguchi Experimental Design

The Taguchi experimental design was used to examine the effect of several factors on the response characteristics with a minimum number of experiments using the orthogonal array technique. The studied parameters were three operating temperatures (15, 25, and 35°C), three current densities (2, 5, and 8 mA/cm²), three concentrations of Fe^{2+} (0.1, 0.2, and 0.4 mM), and 6h of electrolysis. Three levels were investigated for each current density, temperature, and Fe^{2+} concentration, and six levels of time, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. CONTROL PARAMETERS AND LEVELS

Control parameters	Levels
Temperature (°C)	15, 25, 35
Current density (mA/cm ²)	2, 5, 8
Fe^{2+} concentration (mM)	0.1, 0.2, 0.4
Time (h)	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6

Table II presents the orthogonal array layout of L_{18} ($3^3 \times 6^1$) used in this study. The notation 3^3 denotes 3 parameters studied on 3 different levels, and 6^1 represents one of the parameters investigated on 6 levels. Taguchi parameter design identifies the best-operating levels that lead to high COD removal. It was investigated which factors had the most and least significant effects on the efficiency of the process. A mathematical relation between the process parameters and the output was employed using regression analysis.

TABLE II. LAYOUT OF $L_{18}(3^3 \times 6^1)$ EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

No	Time (h)	CD (mA/cm ²)	T, (°C)	Fe ²⁺ (mM)
1	1	2	15	0.1
2	1	5	25	0.2
3	1	8	35	0.4
4	2	2	15	0.2
5	2	5	25	0.4
6	2	8	35	0.1
7	3	2	25	0.1
8	3	5	35	0.2
9	3	8	15	0.4
10	4	2	35	0.4
11	4	5	15	0.1
12	4	8	25	0.2
13	5	2	25	0.4
14	5	5	35	0.1
15	5	8	15	0.2
16	6	2	35	0.2
17	6	5	15	0.4
18	6	8	25	0.1

TABLE III. TED OF $L_{18}(3^3 \times 6^1)$ ORTHOGONAL ARRAY

No.	Time (h)	CD (mA/cm ²)	Temp. (°C)	Fe (mM)	COD removal (%)	S/N
1	1	2	15	0.1	33.52	30.51
2	1	5	25	0.2	43.62	32.79
3	1	8	35	0.4	51.78	34.28
4	2	2	15	0.2	48.32	33.68
5	2	5	25	0.4	57.32	35.17
6	2	8	35	0.1	52.34	34.38
7	3	2	25	0.1	50.87	34.13
8	3	5	35	0.2	67.81	36.63
9	3	8	15	0.4	68.75	36.75
10	4	2	35	0.4	73.64	37.34
11	4	5	15	0.1	60.87	35.69
12	4	8	25	0.2	69.78	36.87
13	5	2	25	0.4	75.41	37.55
14	5	5	35	0.1	73.65	37.34
15	5	8	15	0.2	79.36	38.00
16	6	2	35	0.2	82.32	38.31
17	6	5	15	0.4	82.89	38.37
18	6	8	25	0.1	84.72	38.56

B. Electro-Fenton Oxidation Process

The aqueous solution was prepared to simulate the organic pollutants of the al-Dora refinery wastewater (350ppm COD). The electro-Fenton oxidation process was used to treat the phenolic compound, carried out in an open undivided cell equipped with an anode and cathode having a distance of 3cm between them. The volume of the treated solution was 0.4L. The process used PbO₂ deposit on graphite as an anode and carbon fiber modified by graphene as a cathode. A rotation of 200rpm was achieved in the treated solution using a magnetic stirrer with a heating plate (LABINCO, model L-81). Compressed air was bubbled into the treated solution at 1L/min flow rate using an electromagnetic air pump (ACO-001). The electrolysis process for the treated solution was carried out at three different operating temperatures (15, 25, 35°C ± 1°C). The pH of the treated solution was adjusted to 3 by adding 1M H₂SO₄ to maximize H₂O₂ production. The experiments were carried out by applying different CD 2, 5, and 8mA/cm² using a DC power supply (KORAD KA3005D). FeSO₄·7H₂O was added externally as a catalyst with different concentrations of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.4mM. Sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄) was used as a supporting electrolyte with a concentration of 0.05M to improve the conductivity of the solution. Electrolysis was carried out for up to 6h, and samples were collected after each 1h to check the degradation efficiency by COD analysis. COD removal (%) was calculated with:

$$\text{COD removal, \%} = \frac{\text{COD}_0 - \text{COD}_t}{\text{COD}_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

COD₀ and COD_t were the initial and the COD concentration at time t in (mg/L) respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Taguchi Design Analysis for COD Removal

The effect of the most influencing parameters on the removal of organic pollutants was investigated by applying the Taguchi Experimental Design (TED). The process operating parameters of the $L_{18}(3^3 \times 6^1)$ orthogonal array were specified. The phenol and COD removal by the electro-Fenton oxidation process calculated from (5) are shown in Table III.

The experimental data were analyzed using MINITAB 19. The Taguchi method uses a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) to evaluate the optimum removal conditions and determine the response variation of the mean value that causes experimental noise. It uses it to recognize the levels of controlling factors that minimize the response variance from noise factors. The quantitative measure S/N refers to the mean of the output value (desired value) to the standard deviation of the output value (undesired value) [39-40]. S/N can be divided into three categories: Smaller The Better (STB), Nominal The Better (NTB), and Larger The Better (LTB). The type of S/N was chosen depending on the goal of the experimental process and the desired process quality characteristics. The LTB S/N was selected to maximize the phenol and COD removal efficiency. The LTB response can be evaluated by the standard formula for this type of characteristic [41- 44]:

$$\left(\frac{S}{N}\right)_i = -10 \log \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{Y_{ij}^2} \quad (2)$$

where i is trial number, Y_{ij} represents the response of the measured value for the i-th trial and the j-th run, and n is the number of replications for the experimental combination. In general, the highest S/N value is preferable.

Figure 1 shows a plot of S/N against CD, T, Fe²⁺, and t. Figure 2 shows the main effects graph for the means and represents the relationship between the operating parameter under study and the response obtained. The results plotted in Figures 1 and 2 are shown in Tables IV and V respectively, showing the effect of each operating parameter on COD removal. The ranks in these tables are based on delta statistics. The delta statistic equals to the difference between each factor's highest and lowest average. The highest delta value was assigned to Rank 1, followed by Rank 2 for the second-highest delta value, and so on [45]. The delta values in Tables IV and V indicate that the time of the experiment had the most significant effect on the COD removal. The second parameter that influenced COD removal was Fe²⁺ concentration, followed by current density, while temperature had the lowest impact on COD removal.

Fig. 1. Main effects plot for S/N.

Fig. 2. Main effects plot for means.

TABLE IV. RESPONSE OF S/N FOR COD REMOVAL

Level	Time (h)	CD (mA/cm ²)	Temp. (°C)	Fe (mM)
1	32.53	35.25	35.50	35.10
2	34.41	36.00	35.85	36.05
3	35.83	36.47	36.38	36.58
4	36.63	-	-	-
5	37.63	-	-	-
6	38.41	-	-	-
Delta	5.89	1.22	0.88	1.48
Rank	1	3	4	2

TABLE V. RESPONSE OF MEANS FOR COD REMOVAL

Level	Time (h)	CD (mA/cm ²)	Temp. (°C)	Fe (mM)
1	42.97	60.68	62.28	59.33
2	52.66	64.36	63.62	65.20
3	62.48	67.79	66.92	68.30
4	68.10	-	-	-
5	76.14	-	-	-
6	83.31	-	-	-
Delta	40.34	7.11	4.64	8.97
Rank	1	3	4	2

B. Analysis of Variance for Means and S/N Ratio

The orthogonal array in the Taguchi experiments contributes to each process parameter in the process response.

ANOVA is used to show which parameters have the most significant effect on the process and find the percentage contribution of each parameter to the change in the value of the dependent parameter [46]. The order of significance of the process variables can be easily identified by ANOVA because it is possible to calculate the source of the variation during the process [47]. The ANOVA table involves the degree of freedom (DF), the sequential sum of squares (Seq SS), the adjusted sum of squares (Adj MS), F-value, and p-value. These terms are defined in many handbooks as statistical expressions and are studied and analyzed with experimental designs. These factors showed the importance of each parameter on the process performance [48]. A small variation in any process variable with an excellent percent contribution will greatly influence the process performance. A portion of the total variance detected in the experiment for each effecting parameter is the percent contribution. So, the factor of the greater value of percentage contribution contributes more than other factors to the process's final results [49].

Tables VI and VII show that the highest sum of squares (SS) value went to time t, which had the most significant effect on COD removal. These tables also showed that the statistical significance of the mentioned factors is as follows: Fe²⁺, CD, and T based on p-values. Time is the most significant factor in phenol and COD removal, having 5 degrees of freedom. The least important factor in the processes is T, and the degree of freedom for the CD, T, and Fe²⁺ variables is 2. In general, when F is greater than 4, the change in the parameter studied significantly affects the process performance [40]. It is clear that all factors, time, current density, ferrous ion concentration, and temperature, significantly affect the removal of COD by the electro-Fenton oxidation process since the F values are greater than 4.

TABLE VI. ANOVA FOR S/N OF COD REMOVAL

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Time	5	70.3327	70.332	14.066	104.65	0.000
CD	2	4.5298	4.5298	2.2649	16.85	0.003
Temp	2	2.3735	2.3735	1.1868	8.83	0.016
Fe ²⁺	2	6.7040	6.7040	3.3520	24.94	0.001
Residual error	6	0.8065	0.8065	0.1344	---	---
Total	17	84.746	---	---	---	---

TABLE VII. ANOVA FOR MEANS OF COD

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Time	5	3328.85	3328.85	665.771	84.30	0.000
CD	2	151.65	151.65	75.824	9.60	0.013
Temp	2	68.42	68.42	34.208	4.33	0.069
Fe ²⁺	2	249.09	249.09	124.546	15.77	0.004
Residual error	6	47.38	47.38	7.897	---	---
Total	17	47.38	---	---	---	---

Moreover, the significance of process factors using a p-value indicates that when the p-value is less than 0.05, the process parameter significantly affects the quality characteristic [40]. Therefore, time is the most significant parameter, followed by Fe²⁺ concentration and current density, while the temperature is the least important parameter of COD removal. The adequacy of the model results can be evaluated using

random and normally distributed residual plots, such as histogram of residuals, normal probability, residual fit, and residual order. Figure 3 depicts the residual plots for COD removal. The following should be noted:

- Histograms showed that data have no outliers and are not skewed.
- Normal probability plots showed that data are distributed normally, factors employ the response, and there are no outliers.
- Residuals versus order showed that there are methodical influences in the data because of the time or the order of collection data.
- Residuals versus fitted data showed that there is constant variance and the relationships are nonlinear. In the ideal case, the data points should randomly drop around the zero line.

Fig. 3. Residual plots of COD removal.

C. Multiple Regression Model and Optimization

The equation that describes the multiple regression model for COD removal was:

$$\text{COD} = 11.08 + 7.936X_1 + 1.185X_2 + 0.2319X_3 - 144.2X_4^2 \quad (7)$$

where X_1 is the time of experiment (h), X_2 is CD (mA/cm^2), X_3 is Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and X_4 is Fe^{2+} (mM). The squared value of the correlation coefficient (R^2) for the predicted equation was 98.07%. All four factors affected the efficiency of COD removal. The most influential parameter was time, followed by Fe^{2+} concentration and current density, while the temperature was the least effective parameter. Table VIII shows the highest possible COD removal obtained from the optimization of (7). The optimal COD values ranged between 78.34-94.02%. The highest optimal value of COD removal agrees with the findings obtained from the S/N and means analysis results. The selected operating parameters to examine their effects were temperature = 35°C , $\text{Fe}^{2+} = 0.4\text{mM}$, $\text{CD} = 8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, and $t = 6\text{h}$. The regression equation (7) was utilized to observe the effect of the process variables on COD removal by the electro-Fenton oxidation process.

TABLE VIII. OPTIMAL COD REMOVAL AND OPERATING PARAMETERS

Time (h)	CD (mA/cm^2)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Fe^{2+} (mM)	COD removal (%)
5	8	15	0.2	78.34
6	8	25	0.1	82.72
6	2	35	0.2	83.80
6	5	15	0.4	85.81
6	8	35	0.4	94.02

D. The Impact of Operating Parameters on COD Removal

The effect of current density on COD removal from simulated wastewater was studied using the electro-Fenton oxidation process at 35°C temperature, 0.4mM Fe^{2+} concentration, supporting electrolyte consisting of 50mM sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_3), solution pH at 3, and applied CD ranging from 2 to $8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$.

1) The Effect of Current Density

Figure 4 shows the effect of Current Density (CD) on the removal of COD. The removal of COD was 86.9, 89.28, 91.65, and 94.02% at 2, 4, 6, and $8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ respectively, after 6h of electrolysis. Increasing CD from 2 to $8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ improved the rate of degradation of organic pollutants. Organic degradation increased with CD due to an increase in the amount of H_2O_2 generated electrochemically by electrolysis. When the amount of hydrogen peroxide increases, $\bullet\text{OH}$ increases enough to react with the organic pollutants that existed in the treated solution, minimizing COD values [50, 42]. The obtained results agree with other works that treated organic wastewater using the electro-Fenton oxidation process [2, 51-53].

Fig. 4. Effect of applied current density on COD removal from phenolic wastewater, Temperature= 35°C , $\text{Fe}^{2+}=0.4\text{mM}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3=50\text{mM}$, $\text{pH}=3$.

2) The Effect of Fe^{2+} Concentration

Fe^{2+} added to the system was externally considered an important parameter that influences the performance of the electro-Fenton oxidation process. The reaction rate increased with increasing concentration of Fe^{2+} up to a limiting value. Increasing the concentration above this value decreased organic

degradation due to scavenging reactions [53, 54]. Figure 5 shows that the removal of COD was 81.03, 85.05, 90.92, and 94.02% at 0.05, 0.1, 0.2 and 0.4mM Fe^{2+} respectively. Increasing Fe^{2+} leads to increased organic degradation because of the increased amount of produced $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals [55]. The results showed that ferrous ion concentration greatly affected the removal, especially on COD, which proved that the electro-Fenton oxidation process was largely influenced by the reaction conditions in the bulk solution between Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 , not by the electrochemical reactions on the electrode surface [56]. The results obtained agree with [56], who reached a COD removal efficiency of 95.9% using 0.7mM FeSO_4 concentration and $25\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ CD.

Fig. 5. Effect of Fe^{2+} concentration on COD removal from phenolic wastewater, temperature= 35°C , $\text{CD}=8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3=50\text{mM}$, $\text{pH}=3$.

3) The Effect of Temperature

Sometimes, a temperature increase would lead to an increase in the degradation performance. Choosing an optimum temperature is essential because a further increase in temperature is not needed and depends on the system. Figure 6 presents the effect of temperature on the removal of COD and shows that it was 89.38, 91.70, and 94.02% at 15, 25, and 35°C . Increasing the process temperature leads to a slight increase in the degradation of the organic pollutants by the electro-Fenton oxidation process because raising the temperature promotes the generation of Fe^{2+} [57]. The obtained results agree with the temperature behavior reported in [58, 59], who found that the increase in temperature affects relatively low the organic degradation of the electro-Fenton oxidation process compared to other factors. Furthermore, many studies noticed that the best range of operating temperature is $25\text{--}35^\circ\text{C}$ because lower or higher temperatures have a negative impact on removal efficiency. A lower temperature causes a slower initial kinetic process and reduces the degradation performance and reaction rate. Higher temperatures negatively influence the removal of organic contaminants because, at these temperatures, the electrogenerated H_2O_2 is dropped due to the decrease in the dissolved oxygen concentration. Furthermore, at high temperatures, H_2O_2 decays rapidly and decomposes into less reactive water and oxygen [58, 59].

Fig. 6. Effect of operating temperature on COD removal from phenolic wastewater, $\text{CD}=8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, $\text{Fe}^{2+}=0.4\text{mM}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3=50\text{mM}$, $\text{pH}=3$.

IV. CONCLUSION

A Taguchi experimental design was achieved using the L_{18} orthogonal array technique. The effect of the variable parameters on the removal of COD was studied by choosing four factors: CD, T, Fe^{2+} , and t. The optimum conditions were obtained from a linear model analysis for the S/N ratios and means. The optimum operating conditions for the removal of COD were temperature of 35°C , current density of $8\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, Fe^{2+} concentration of 0.4mM, and 6h electrolysis duration. The removal of COD under optimal operating conditions was 94.02%. The time of process variable had the most significant effect on COD reduction efficiency, and the temperature had the lowest impact. The electro-Fenton oxidation process of organic pollutants was influenced mainly by the bulk conditions like the Fe^{2+} concentration, as the electro-Fenton process occurs in bulk between Fe^{2+} and H_2O_2 , and not at the electrode surface. Increasing the operating temperature is crucial because it will improve Fe^{2+} generation, but a further increase is not essential.

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An Enhanced Z-Source Switched MLI Capacitor for Integrated Micro-Grid with Advanced Switching Pattern Scheme

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Abstract-In this paper, the Enhanced Z-Source Switched Capacitor Multi-Level Inverter (EZSC-MLI) is presented, which can generate a greater number of levels and magnitude in output. The proposed MLI has greater recognition due to its low harmonic profile, fewer switching components, compact size, low switch stress, isolated DC supply, high efficiency, and low cost. A high voltage boost factor is achieved by using the Z-Source. The Switched Capacitor module is used for charging all the capacitors to equal voltage magnitude based on a self-balanced scheme. The proposed topology for grid integration requires dual control loops, a primary voltage control loop, and a secondary current control loop. The performance of the proposed 7-level topology for grid integrated systems is verified with multi-carrier advanced modulation schemes and by simulations carried out in Matlab/Simulink.

Keywords-distributed energy resources; multi-carrier modulation techniques; multi-level inverter; impedance source; renewable energy sources; switched capacitor

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, sustainable and Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) like wind energy and photovoltaic (PV) stacks have been highly recognized as precious substitutions of fossil fuels due to their commercial merits and reliable operation. RESs integrated with power-conditioning systems play a vital role in satisfying the energy demands of a micro-grid system [1]. To improve the energy generation statistics, Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) are introduced. They have less size and easily interfacing methodology. DERs improve the overall system performance by reducing total loss, transformers, and

additional devices. Among the DERs, PV stacks are the most promising technology [2]. Generally, a high-voltage gain DC-DC boost converter is required to transform the low-voltage output of the PV to high voltage, which is integrated to the micro-grid by a DC-AC inverter [3]. The maximum duty ratio is restricted due to parasitic resistances and this decreases the overall system stability, causes grounding issues and high dv/dt on switches/diodes.

The above mentioned problems of the two-stage module are discarded by employing an X-shaped impedance circuit, which consists of two inductors and capacitors [4]. With the modish power semi-conductor device, several well-known inverter modules have been amalgamated into grid systems. MLIs are categorized as Diode Clamped (DC-MLI) [5], Flying Capacitor (FC-MLI) [6], and Cascaded H-bridge (CHB-MLI) [7].

The main reasons for producing a number of levels in voltage are: to increase the RMS quality, to decrease the dv/dt stress, and to eliminate large size filters. In MLIs, isolated multiple DC or virtual DC-links are obtained by using transformers or capacitors with the contribution of various switching components. Producing high voltage levels with a low number of isolated DC power supplies and fewer switching devices is the main challenge [8-10]. The suitable approach to limit the DC power supplies is to utilize the capacitors. Yet, additional charge balance strategy is used to intercept the discharging issues [11-13]. Generally, MLI topologies are governed by both fundamental and high switching frequency modulation schemes [14]. The topology with symmetrical and asymmetrical voltage sources is illustrated in [15]. Three phase

modular topologies are presented in [16-18] with reduced complexity and losses and improved performance. Balanced grid voltage was achieved using the LVRT (Low Voltage Ride Through) control approach in [19]. During a fault state, reactive power is given to ensure protection. The Shunt Var Compensator (SVC) controller was used, it was automatically engaged when a grid fault occurs.

This paper proposes the novel, simple, and efficient EZSC-MLI topology, which is validated by using advanced multi-carrier pulse-width modulation schemes. Dual control loop is used for controlling the voltage and current in the micro-grid system.

II. THE PROPOSED CONCEPT

The configuration of the proposed PV-based EZSC-MLI with grid integrated scheme is depicted in Figure 1. From left to right, the scheme consists of a PV cell, impedance network, Switched Capacitor (SC) module, and a 7-level MLI with dual loop control scheme. The PV supplies energy and feeds the impedance circuit, which transforms the low DC voltage to high DC-link voltage, maintained constant based on the active and shoot through states. The common DC-link voltage is powered by the respective capacitors in the SC module and the entire system is integrated to the micro-grid system through the 7-level inverter. The simplified MLI topology is controlled using advanced modulation schemes. The working and implementation of each unit are described below.

Fig. 1. Configuration of the proposed inverter.

A. PV Source

A PV cell relies on the photo-electric effect to generate electrical energy. A PV cell is similar to a natural diode. When the energy of sunlight is more than the semi-conductor energy gap, current travels via the external circuit system. Based on power level requirements, the PV cell is integrated in parallel and/or in series to attain high current and/or voltage.

$$I_{pv} = I_{sc} - (I_s \left[\exp q \frac{(V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv})}{NKT} \right] - 1) - \left[\frac{V_{pv} + R_s I_{pv}}{R_{sh}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where I_{pv} is the current flowing in PV cell (A), I_{sc} is the reverse saturated diode's current (A), K is Boltzmann's constant, N is Diode's ideality factor, Q is the charge of the electron, T is junction's temperature, R_{sh} and R_s are the shunt and series resistances of the PV cell (Ω), V_{pv} is the PV voltage at the output terminal (V).

B. Z-Source and Self Balancing Module

Generally, VSI accomplishes the buck conversion, which restricts its usage in several areas, such as DER. To amplify the PV input voltage, a two-stage boost conversion methodology is used, which requires additional switching devices, stage and control scheme. Using an impedance network in X-shape will reduce the complexity. High voltage gain is achieved at output terminals by furnishing shoot through state. This state is possible when the lower and upper switches in the same leg are conducted simultaneously and it is not possible while using a multi-level inverter. The Z network with single switch is proposed, since it reduces the complexity of control. The voltage across the traditional ZSI is:

$$V_{ZSI,trad} = 2 \times V_L - V_{pv} \quad (2)$$

Boost factor (B_f) and the peak AC voltage (V_o) are given by:

$$B_{f,trad} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2 \times T_{sh}}{T}} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{o,trad} = B_{f,trad} \times V_{pv} \quad (4)$$

where V_L and V_{pv} are the voltage across the Z source inductor and the input. Various methods are used to overcome the unbalanced voltage problems such as, feedback methods [20] or the regulated switching pattern scheme [21]. The SC balanced technique is very popular because it does not require a feedback method or continuous monitoring. The proposed switched capacitor module consists of two input capacitors C_{s1} , C_{s2} , three output capacitors C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and six switches S_{c1} to S_{c6} . The modes of operation are depicted in Figure 2.

In Mode-I (Figure 2(a)), all odd numbered switches will conduct. The capacitors C_{s1} , C_{s2} charge the C_1 and C_2 capacitors, thus the voltage across the C_1 (V_{c1}) is V_{c1} and the voltage of capacitor C_2 is V_{c2} . In Mode-II (Figure 2(b)), all even numbered switches will conduct. The capacitors C_{s1} , C_{s2} charge the C_2 and C_3 capacitors, thus $V_{c2} = V_{c2}$ and $V_{c3} = V_{c3}$. The voltages across C_{s1} , C_{s2} , C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are:

$$V_{cs1} = V_{cs2} = \left(\frac{V_{pv}}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$V_{c1} = V_{c2} = V_{c3} = \left(\frac{V_{in}}{2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where V_{dc} is the output voltage of the Z network. The maximum available output voltage across the inverter $V_{o,inv}$ is:

$$V_{o,inv} = V_{c1} + V_{c2} + V_{c3} \quad (7)$$

$$V_{o,inv} = \left(\frac{V_{dc}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{V_{dc}}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{V_{dc}}{2} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$V_{o,inv} = \left(\frac{3}{2} \right) \cdot V_{dc} \quad (9)$$

From (8) and (9), it is clear that voltage is balanced and boosted by 1.5 times. The capacitors C_{s1} , C_{s2} are powered by the ZSI module. The output of the Z network is given by the SC module. By considering the boost factor of 1.5, (4) and (5) can be rewritten to get the boost factor and the peak output of the enhanced Z network with the self-voltage balancing network.

$$B_{f,Enh} = \frac{1.5}{1 - \frac{2 \times T_{sh}}{T}} \quad (10)$$

$$V_{o,Enh} = B_{f,Enh} \times (V_{in}) \quad (11)$$

where T_{sh}/T represents the duty ratio of shoot through state, the peak output voltage of EZSC-MLI is 1.5 times greater than TZSI with and/or without shoot through state.

The graphical representation of Boost factor vs T_{sh}/T and peak voltage vs T_{sh}/T for TZSI and EZSI topologies are depicted in Figures 3 and 4. If the shoot through ratio lies in between 0 to 0.4, the design procedure for passive devices is the same for the two ZSI modules. For any given T_{sh}/T , the peak output voltage and the boost factor of EZSC-MLI are constantly 1.5 times higher than TZSI's, hence this network is named as an enhanced network [14]. If T_{sh}/T is 0.4, the boost factor of TZSI is 5 and EZSC-MLI is 7.5 and the corresponding peak output voltages are 500V and 750V (for input voltage of 100V). The proposed 7-level EZSC-MLI is integrated to a micro-grid.

Fig. 2. Operating modes of the SC circuit: (a) Odd number switching, (b) even number switching.

Fig. 3. Boost factor vs T_{sh}/T .

Fig. 4. Peak voltage vs T_{sh}/T .

C. Control Loops

In the proposed concept, dual control loops are utilized, i.e. the primary voltage control loop and the secondary current control loop. The aim of the primary loop is to regulate the

output voltage of the Z-source network, by changing the shoot through duty ratio as specified in (10). This maintains the MLI voltage constant and greater than the grid voltage. A reference voltage signal is obtained by comparing the PV voltage and the grid voltage. The outcome is compared with the triangular carrier signal to produce the shoot through state duty ratio. The aim of the current loop is the injection of the reference current to the grid within the harmonic standards of IEEE-519. Grid synchronization requires the inverter output voltage, frequency and phase should match with the grid. This is furnished by single-phase Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) circuitry.

The PLL circuit generates the required phase sequence and fundamental frequency as a current shape (I_{sin}) which is multiplied with the reference magnitude of current (I_{ref}) established as final reference current (I_{ref}^*). I_{ref}^* is compared with the actual grid current (I_{act}) and the outcome is imparted to the Hysteresis Current Controller (HCC) for the generation of the switching states to the H-bridge module [22] in the 7-level MLI. The ON/OFF states of the respective switches in the H-bridge module are highly demanded based on the reference grid current.

III. MODULATION SCHEME

The working principles of the 7-level MLI are level generation and polarity generation. The level generation module has three switches S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 , which convert the constant DC-link voltage to DC levels. The switching sequence for DC-level generation of the 7-level MLI is depicted in Table. I. On the other side, polarity generation has four switches, S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D , which convert the DC-level voltage to AC voltage and are controlled by the secondary current control loop. The switching sequence for polarity generation is depicted in Table II, where N represents the ON-state of the switch and F represents the OFF-state of the switch.

TABLE I. SWITCHING STATES OF DC-LEVEL GENERATION

V_o	S_1	S_2	S_3
V_{dc}	N	F	F
$2V_{dc}/3$	F	N	F
$V_{dc}/3$	F	F	N

TABLE II. SWITCHING STATES OF POLARITY GENERATION

V_o	S_A	S_B	S_C	S_D
0	F/N	N/F	F/N	N/F
Positive	N	N	F	F
Negative	F	F	N	N

The switches in the level generation scheme are controlled by advanced modulation schemes, such as the level-shifted multi-carrier modulation (LSPWM) scheme, the phase-angled (PAPWM) scheme, and the variable switching frequency (VSFPWM) scheme.

A. The Multi-Carrier Level-Shifted PWM (LSPWM) Scheme

In the well-known control action of LSPWM, all respective carriers are shifted by time. For n voltage levels, $n-1$ carriers are pre-requisite adjoining each other for the production of the switching pattern. The peak amplitude of triangular carrier wave-shape is differed and it is equivalent to the reference

sinusoidal voltage as a summation of all carrier-waves. High switching frequency is used. Generally it depends on multiplication factor and fundamental frequency. The frequency value of the carrier is measured by:

$$F_c = M_f \times F_f \quad (12)$$

where F_c denotes carrier frequency (Hz), M_f denotes the multiplication factor, with an odd value more than 11, and F_f denotes the fundamental frequency value (Hz). The modulation index of the pulse-width modulation scheme is:

$$MI_a = \frac{V_r}{V_c(m-1)} \quad (13)$$

where V_r , V_c denote the peak amplitudes of reference and carrier triangular wave-shapes. The production of switching states is done by relating the reference and carrier wave-shapes. When the reference wave is greater than the carrier wave, a particular switch is in the ON state and/or when it is less than the carrier wave, a particular switch is in the OFF state. The LSPWM schemes are: Phase Disposed (PD), Phase Opposed Disposed (POD), Alternate Phase Opposed Disposed (APOD). The PD based carrier waveform is depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. PD modulation scheme.

B. Multi-Carrier Phase-Angle Shifted PWM (PAPWM)

The PAPWM scheme shown in Figure 6 is the same with level-shifted modulation. All the carriers have equal switching frequencies and different peak amplitudes, which are vertically disposed by a certain phase-angle to vanquish the phase imbalance issues and unbalanced voltages [22]. The disposed phase-angle (ϕ_{ps}) is given by,

$$\phi_{ps} = \frac{360^\circ}{M_f(m-1)} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 6. PAPWM scheme.

C. Multi-Carrier Variable Switching Frequency (VSFPWM)

The VSFPWM scheme is the same with the level-shifted modulation scheme. All the carriers have different peak

amplitudes and unequal switching frequencies such as 5050Hz, 7050Hz, and 9050Hz. These frequencies are selected with respect to the multiplication factor. This modulation technique has better minimization of harmonic distortions and low switch stress and increased efficiency, while it requires low-rated filter units. The VSFPWM scheme is depicted in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. VSFPWM scheme.

D. Modified Modulation Scheme

A unique modulation scheme is introduced by utilizing PA and VSFPWM schemes for getting optimal switching states. All the carriers in the proposed modulation scheme have different peak amplitudes which are vertically disposed by the respective phase-angles and have unequal switching frequencies such as 5050Hz, 7050Hz, and 9050Hz with respect to the multiplication factor. The advanced modulation scheme is depicted in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Advanced PD modulation scheme.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The performance of the ZSI based 7-level SC-MLI fed grid-integrated system with several modulation schemes is validated in Matlab/Simulink and is developed with the help of the operating parameters shown in Table III. Figure 9(a) shows the complete Matlab model, Figure 9(b) shows the hysteresis controller, and Figure 9(c) shows the controller for generating shoot through pulses.

TABLE III. OPERATING PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
PV Source	$V_{pv}=100V$
Grid Voltage & frequency	$V_g=230V, F_g=50Hz$
Impedance source	$L_1=L_2= 10mH, C_1=C_2= 0.01F$
DC-link voltage	150V
Switching frequency	10KHz
DC-link capacitor	$C_{dk}= 0.01F$
Capacitors	$C_1=C_2= C_3= 0.01F$

Fig. 9. Matlab/Simulink model.

Fig. 10. Performance of the 7-level improved ZSI based SC-MLI using the proposed advanced modulation technique. (a) Voltage across the capacitors, (b) 7-level output Voltage, (c) output current, (d) output Voltage and current-in phase, and (e) THD of the output Voltage.

A. Performance Evaluation of the Proposed Topology with Advanced Modulation Techniques in a Standalone System

Figure 10 shows the simulation outcome of the 7-level ZSI based SC-MLI with advanced modulation scheme. From Figure 10(e), it is observed that the harmonic content in the output voltage is high at odd multiples of the fundamental frequency. The PV input voltage 100V is transformed into 150V DC-link voltage by the SC module. The DC-link capacitor voltages are maintained constant and balanced for achieving the significant 7-level output. The THD of the output voltage is 12.54%. The performance of the proposed 7-level SC-MLI is evaluated by classical and the proposed PWM schemes. It can be seen that the proposed advanced modulation scheme has better features. The THD analysis of the modulation schemes is depicted in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. THD analysis of the considered modulation schemes.

Fig. 12. Performance of the 7-Level ZSI integrated to the grid. (a) Grid Voltage and current, (b) in-phase grid voltage and current component, (c) grid active and reactive power, (d) THD of grid current.

B. Grid Integration Scheme

The proposed topology is integrated to a micro-grid with the advanced modulation technique. Figure 12 represents the simulation outcome of the 7-level EZSC-MLI with the advanced modulation scheme integrated to the grid with low-rated filter units. The attained grid voltage and current are pure-sinusoidal and maintained constant at the fundamental frequency. Both the components are in-phase representing a unity power factor. The THD of the grid current is 4.16%, well within IEEE-519 standards.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the enhanced Z-source SC-MLI topology with various modulation techniques is proposed. It is capable of operating with a high voltage gain factor. The proposed SC-MLI utilizes only a single PV source and 7 active switches for the production of 7 voltage levels. Effective modulation schemes are used for the generation of optimal switching states. They have better reduction of harmonic distortion over the classical schemes and attain favorable benefits. There is no need of additional balancing technique, a self-balancing technique is initiated which reduces the complex control circuitry. When using the proposed 7-level SC-MLI topology, the switching components are fewer over the classical MLI topologies. The proposed inverter topologies are more suitable for the DER fed grid by utilizing attractive voltage and current control loops. This system can be used for integrating different renewable energy sources.

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An Experimental Study on the Control of Slotless Self-Bearing Motor Using Nonlinear Control

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Abstract-This article presents a Slotless Self-Bearing Motor (SSBM) with a six-phase coil stator instead of an iron core. The rotor consists of a permanent magnet and an encased iron yoke. The magnetic forces caused by the interplay between the stator currents and the magnetic field govern the rotational speed and radial position of the rotor. An SSBM mathematical model and its control method are also included in this study. This motor is controlled by field-oriented control. Theoretical analysis of magnetic force and moment characteristics is performed, and a control approach is provided. Sliding-mode control is a control technique that is simple, and effective and is used to assist the control system in approaching the reference value. It is also widely utilized to control the position and speed of the motor. The findings were constructed and validated using experiment-confirmed analytical data to prove the proposed control strategy.

Keywords-FOC; Slotless Self-Bearing Motor; sliding mode control; PI; PID

I. INTRODUCTION

The quality of a powertrain depends on the engine. Creating a transmission system capable of smooth speed change with a wide adjustment range and high accuracy of the adjustment quantity in static mode is necessary to create a working area with negligible error. Working with any transition process must achieve increased stability, and the system must be able to respond quickly to adjustment requirements [1-3]. All these make more stringent the requirements on powertrains. Also, special needs for intelligent and fast control in synchronous motors will be significantly enhanced. Conventional motor structures have been greatly improved. However, there are still disadvantages of an engine with a steel core, such as the existence of pulsating torque and low operating frequency [3-5]. So, the steel coreless self-lifting motor is a significant invention that minimizes the frictional force between the rotating shaft in the machine part, helping the effortless

movement for better performance in motion applications of engineering disciplines [6-8]. Brushless motors have many advantages such as high speed, fast acceleration, and constant torque (Figure 1) and higher continuity, low noise, and less electromagnetic interference (Figure 2) [9-11].

Fig. 1. Comparison of the engine structure with and without steel core.

The cogging torque can be reduced by improving the stator grooves and the magnet pole exerts. A 6-phase coreless steel lifter motor comprises of a cylindrical two-pole magnet, a surrounding iron shell, a rotating shaft, and an aluminum base that connects the engine's components. The distance of the air gap between the magnet and the iron case remains constant to ensure a stable magnetic field of the magnet pole. As a result, the magnetic lines of force leaving the surface of interest tend to rotate towards the south pole. In other words, the magnetic lines of the staff will come out perpendicular to the tangent at that point, creating an even distribution of the magnetic field between the rotor and the stator. In addition, in this motor, the increase in the number of teeth on the stator makes for more interaction, and they create pairs of forces that cancel each other, thereby also reducing the cogging torque [11-13]. The SSBM in the experimental set motors is shown in Figure 3.

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Fig. 2. Torque comparison of two types of motors: (a) Motor with steel core, (b) motor without steel core.

Fig. 3. The SSBM in the experimental set motors.

This motor creates torque [14-16] and lift will be done by giving the supplied current. Thus, Lorentz force is generated. According to Newton's theorem, since the coil is at rest, the reaction forces acting on the motor rotor have opposite directions. This force consists of two components, one that generates lift and the other that creates rotor torque. When any current (positive or negative) is applied to a phase, a pair of forces is generated whose direction depends on its position relatively to the rotor. Thus, the torque and lift can be controlled by varying the amplitude and phase of the current in the stator. Consequently, the construction of the controller is required to improve system quality. A PI controller handles speed control, whereas a PID handles displacement position control [17-23]. The actual speed is close to the reference value and reacts effectively. When there is a load torque, the controller boosts or cuts the current to help minimize the divergence. The phase stator currents take on a sinusoidal

shape following the speed change. In addition, the actual speed is responsive and close to the reference value. The controller boosts or reduces the current to minimize divergence when a load torque is present. As a result, the phase stator currents take on a sinusoidal shape when the speed changes. On the other hand, the total rotor displacements jump from 0s to 0.1s. This signifies that the rotor is still centered in the stator. As a result, the controller promptly corrects the align deviation when applying external pressures. However, the rotor's speed and displacement overshoot during the transition point. Consequently, it has been reported that a Sliding Mode Control (SMC) system could be used to improve control quality. SMC is a control method that forces the system's trajectory onto the sliding surface using a high-speed switching control rule. Sliding-mode control is widely used in practical applications [24-27], because of its benefits, such as ease of implementation, finite-time convergence, excellent dynamic responsiveness, and robustness against parameter variations and disturbances. Furthermore, the stability of sliding-mode control may offer flawless tracking even when parameters or model errors are present, based on the design of a bearingless motor's SMC and dq axis current regulation [28-34]. Consequently, this SSBM outperforms the PID controller in position and speed control. Thus, the sliding-mode control will be chosen to design this motor's speed and position controller.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The stator currents are supplied as [17]:

$$\begin{cases} i_{a,d} = i_d \cos(\psi) + i_q \sin(\psi) \pm A_m \cos(\phi_m) \\ i_{b,e} = i_d \cos(\psi - 2\pi/3) + i_q \sin(\psi - 2\pi/3) \pm A_m \cos(\phi_m + \pi/3) \\ i_{c,f} = i_d \cos(\psi - 4\pi/3) + i_q \sin(\psi - 4\pi/3) \pm A_m \cos(\phi_m + 2\pi/3) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where i_d is the direct axis current, i_q is the quadrature axis current, ψ is the angular position of the rotor, A_m is the amplitude of the motor current, and ϕ_m is its phase.

We combine (1) with the stator winding properties to calculate the total force acting on the rotor and the generated torque. The rotating torque and bearing forces in case of turns are:

$$\begin{cases} \tau = k_{nm} k_m A_m \sin(\phi_m - \psi + \theta_0 + \pi/4) \\ f_x = -k_{nb} k_b \{i_d \sin(2\theta_0) - i_q \cos(2\theta_0)\} \\ f_y = k_{nb} k_b \{i_d \cos(2\theta_0) + i_q \sin(2\theta_0)\} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where τ is the rotating torque, f_x and f_y are bearing forces, B is the amplitude of the magnetic flux density, l_p is the length of the parallel part of the winding, l_s is the length of the serial part of the winding, n is the total number of turns, and θ_0 is the angular position of the +a-phase winding. It must be an odd number so that the wires do not overlap.

From (2), the mathematical model of the SSBM is completely constructed with force and torque equations. Next, the control system for the SSBM will be designed.

$$\begin{cases} k_m = -\left(3\sqrt{2}l_p + \frac{8(6-3\sqrt{2})}{\pi}l_t\right)rB \\ k_b = -\left(3l_p + \frac{12}{\pi}l_t\right)B \\ k_{nm} = 1 + 2\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3n}\right) + 2\cos\left(2\frac{\pi}{3n}\right) + \dots + 2\cos\left(\frac{(n-1)\pi}{3n}\right) \\ k_{nb} = 1 + 2\cos\left(2\frac{\pi}{3n}\right) + 2\cos\left(4\frac{\pi}{3n}\right) + \dots + 2\cos\left((n-1)\frac{\pi}{3n}\right) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

III. DESIGNING THE CONTROL SYSTEM

A. Control Structure

When the angular position of the rotor can be obtained, the stator current can be calculated by (1) and the force and torque by (2). The θ_0 is the angular position of the +a-phase winding so if the +a-phase coincides with the x-axis then $\theta_0=0$. φ_m is the phase of the torque current and depends on control strategy. To conduct the clear control algorithm, we can assume that

$\theta_0 = 0$ and $\phi_m = \psi + \frac{\pi}{4}$ or $\phi_m - \psi + \theta_0 + \frac{\pi}{4} = \frac{\pi}{2}$. Then, (2) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \tau = k_{nm}k_m A_m \\ F_x = k_{nb}k_b i_q \\ F_y = k_{nb}k_b i_d \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

It is easy to see that the rotating torque is produced by A_m and the bearing force is produced by i_d and i_q . Therefore, the rotating torque can be controlled by A_m and the bearing force by i_d and i_q . On the other hand, the two components, force and torque, are mathematically independent from each other, thus, the control structure is introduced as shown in Figure 3. The SMC is used for both the speed control and the displacement position control. SMC is a well-known powerful control scheme which has been successfully and widely applied for both linear and nonlinear systems. In this study, the linear sliding mode which uses the linear sliding surface has been used to design the speed and position controller.

Settings: $K_T = k_{nm}k_m$ and $K_{fx} = K_{fy} = k_{nb}k_b$, and (4) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \tau = K_T A_m \\ F_x = K_{fx} i_q \\ F_y = K_{fy} i_d \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The dynamic equation of the rotor is:

$$\tau - T_l = J \frac{d\omega}{dt} \quad (6)$$

$$F - F_l = Ma \quad (7)$$

where M is the weight of the rotor, a is the acceleration of the rotor, T_l is the load torque and F_l is the load force.

B. Designing the Position Controller

Assuming the effect of load torque and load force are the same as external disturbances, the mathematical model of the motor can be expressed as [17]:

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{x} = \frac{K_{fx}}{m} i_q \\ \ddot{y} = \frac{K_{fy}}{m} i_d \\ \dot{\omega} = \frac{K_T}{J} A_m \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The parameters of the two equations that generate the bearing force are the same. Thus, a sliding controller for both positions along the x and y axes is designed. The settings in the model in (8) are:

$$K_f = \frac{K_{fx}}{m} = \frac{K_{fy}}{m}, u_d = K_f i_d, u_q = K_f i_q \quad (9)$$

We suppose that the controlled object is only a double integral $1/s^2$, the SMC is used for calculating parameters u_d and u_q and then we return to calculate the current parameters i_d and i_q . The controlled object $1/s^2$ is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \begin{pmatrix} x_2 \\ u \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \underline{y} = x_1 \quad (10)$$

where $\underline{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix}$ is the state vector, \underline{y} is the output signal and $u = u_d = u_q$ is the control input. The most commonly used sliding surface is the linear sliding surface which is:

$$s_1(e) = a_0 e_1 + e_2 \text{ and } \frac{de_1}{dt} = e_2 \quad (11)$$

where e_1 is the position error and a_0 is a positive design parameter chosen such that the polynomial $P(s) = a_0 + s$ is a Hurwitz polynomial which has real parts of the roots smaller than zero.

To guarantee the stability of the system, the Lyapunov stability theory is used. The Lyapunov function has the form of:

$$V(s_1) = \frac{1}{2} s_1^2 \quad (12)$$

Then, the control design task becomes to make $\dot{V}(s_1) < 0$ in the neighborhood of the equilibrium. Thus, we have:

$$\frac{dV(s_1)}{dt} < 0 \Leftrightarrow s_1 \frac{ds_1}{dt} < 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{ds_1}{dt} \text{sgn}(s_1(e)) < 0 \quad (13)$$

On the other hand:

$$\frac{ds_1}{dt} = a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} + \frac{de_2}{dt} = a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} - u \quad (14)$$

Thus, (13) becomes:

$$(a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} - u) \operatorname{sgn}(s_1(e)) < 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} - u = \begin{cases} < 0 & \text{if } s_1(e) > 0 \\ > 0 & \text{if } s_1(e) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow u = \begin{cases} > a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} & \text{if } s_1(e) > 0 \\ < a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} & \text{if } s_1(e) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Choosing the control input u :

$$u = a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} + k_0 \operatorname{sgn}(s_1(e)) \quad \forall k_0 > 0 \quad (18)$$

From (9) and (18), the currents i_d and i_q are calculated as:

$$i_d = i_q = \frac{a_0 \frac{de_1}{dt} + k_0 \operatorname{sgn}(s_1(e))}{K_f} \quad (19)$$

$$\forall a_0, k_0 > 0 F - F_l = Ma$$

Thus, (19) is the SMC used for the position controller. Next, the speed controller is calculated correspondingly, but it has a difference from the reference signal.

C. Designing the Speed Controller

It is similar to the position controller, with settings [17]:

$$K_{T\omega} = \frac{K_T}{J} \quad \text{and} \quad u_\omega = K_{T\omega} A_m \quad (20)$$

The controlled object is still a double integral $1/s^2$, but the feedback signal is state variable, thus, the sliding surface is chosen as:

$$s_\omega(e) = b_0 e_{1\omega} + e_{2\omega} = b_0 e_{1\omega} + \frac{de_{1\omega}}{dt} \quad (21)$$

where $e_{2\omega}$ is the speed error and b_0 is a positive design parameter.

Similar to the position controller, we have:

$$s_\omega \frac{ds_\omega}{dt} < 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{ds_\omega}{dt} \operatorname{sgn}(s_\omega(e)) < 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow u_\omega = \begin{cases} > b_0 \frac{de_{1\omega}}{dt} & \text{if } s_\omega(e) > 0 \\ < b_0 \frac{de_{1\omega}}{dt} & \text{if } s_\omega(e) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Choosing the control input u_ω as:

$$u = b_0 \frac{de_{1\omega}}{dt} + C \operatorname{sgn}(s_\omega(e)), \quad \forall C > 0 \quad (24)$$

From (20) and (23), the current A_m is calculated as:

$$A_m = \frac{b_0 \frac{de_{1\omega}}{dt} + C \operatorname{sgn}(s_\omega(e))}{K_{T\omega}} \quad \forall b_0, C > 0 \quad (25)$$

Thus, (25) is the SMC which is used for the speed controller. The control system was designed from (19) and (24). However, to reduce the chattering due to the $\operatorname{sgn}(s)$ function, the sign function is replaced by the $\operatorname{sat}(s)$ function, which is defined as follows:

$$\operatorname{sat}(s) = \begin{cases} \operatorname{sgn}(s) & \text{if } |s| > \mathcal{E} \\ \frac{s}{\mathcal{E}} & \text{if } |s| \leq \mathcal{E} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where \mathcal{E} is the boundary layer thickness. However, although the sliding mode can be guaranteed outside the \mathcal{E} , it cannot be guaranteed inside it. This replacement can cause trajectory errors.

To reduce both chattered phenomenon and trajectory error, a saturation-integral relay function (SatPi) is proposed which is defined as:

$$\operatorname{SatPi}(s) = \begin{cases} \operatorname{sgn}(s) & \text{if } |s| > \mathcal{E} \\ \frac{s}{\mathcal{E}} + k_i \int_0^t s(t).dt & \text{if } |s| \leq \mathcal{E} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

where k_i is positive integral coefficient, t_0 is the time when the system state starts to reach \mathcal{E} .

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Setup

The entire experimental table is shown in Figure 4. Control Desk software was used to simulate models, build user interfaces, display process variables on screen, performing controller tuning, and monitoring objects. Table I presents the motors and the SMC controller parameters.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Motor parameters	Symbol	Value
Motor weight	m	0.4 Kg
Rotor radius	R	0.022 m
Stator radius	r	0.027 m
Flux maximum of the rotor	B	0.59 T
Length of the parallel part	l_p	0.008 m
Length of the serial part	l_s	0.006 m
The total number of turns	n	55
Controller parameters	Symbol	Value
Current-torque coefficient	k_m	-9.7×10^{-4}
Current-torque coefficient	k_{nm}	52.5
Current-force coefficient	k_b	-0.0277
Current-force coefficient	k_{nb}	45.49
Position controller parameter	a_0	150
Position controller parameter	k_0	100
Speed controller parameter	b_0	92
Speed controller parameter	C	56

Fig. 4. Images of the experimental version.

B. Results

The first tested controller was the position controller. The initial position of the rotor is $x = 0.5\text{mm}$, $y = 0.5\text{mm}$. At 0.8s the position controller was activated. The results are shown in Figure 5. At this point, the rotor position was brought back to the equilibrium position after only 0.12s, the currents i_d and i_q changed respectively and were limited from -1A to 1A.

After the position controller worked, the motor was brought to the balance position. Next, the rotor shaft was aligned with the origin, increasing the motor speed from 0 to 4500rpm. The results of the speed test response and change of rotor position are shown in Figure 6. The position response in the x and y axes has a slight fluctuation, but with minimal value. The most significant position deviation is only 0.1mm, thereby showing that the position controller works well even when the engine is running—motion at high speed.

Fig. 5. Experimental results of the position controller. (a) x, y axis position response (mm), (b) i_d, i_q current responses.

Fig. 6. Position response when speed changes. (a) x, y axis position response (mm), (b) speed change from 0 to 4500rpm. The line red is the reference response, and the black line is the real response.

Fig. 7. Response to position and speed in the presence of applied resistance.

To demonstrate that the position controller and speed controller work independently when the motor is operating at 4000rpm, a sufficient force is applied in both x and y axes of the engine. The actual speed response is close to the set speed response, without overturning, and the time it takes to set the speed is short ($t=2\text{s}$). At this point, the position error occurs, and immediately after that, the position controller suppresses the error and returns to 0rpm. The motor speed does not change, showing that speed and position controllers operate independently. Figure 8 shows the results of testing the rotor's trajectory at rotational speeds of 2000rpm and 4000rpm. Again, the maximum orbital deviation is approximately 0.12mm, and the engine operates stably. Figure 9 depicts the position deviation trajectory of the rotor along with the axis Ox (e_{1x}) and its derivative. Figure 9(a) shows the position error trajectory when the position controller starts to operate. At this time, the position error moves from 0.5mm to 0mm. Figure 9(b) shows that when the position controller is active, and the motor is stationary, the position error is approximately 0mm. Figure 9(c) shows the position deviation trajectory at 4000rpm. The maximum deviation amplitude is approximately 0.125mm. This value is relatively small, so we can say that the position controller is working correctly.

Fig. 8. Response to position and speed in the presence of applied resistance: (a) 2000rpm, (b) 4000rpm.

Fig. 9. The trajectory of the rotor position deviation along the x axis: (a) initial starting position of controller response, (b) position response when the motor is stationary, (c) position response at 4000rpm.

Fig. 10. Experimental results of the speed controller: (a) Speed response, (b) current response.

Finally, the response of the speed controller, with increasing and decreasing speed of the motor, is tested. At 1s, the motor speed increased from 0rpm to 2000rpm, and at 6s, it reversed to -2000rpm. The corresponding A_m current and the speed responses were checked (A_m current is limited from -1A to 1A). The motor speed increases from 0 to 2000rpm after 0.5s and reverses after about 1s. The experimental results in Figure 10 show that the system works stably, and that the position and speed controllers work well. However, there are still errors and incompleteness as in the simulation, but the deviation is not too much. They are enough for the controller to be used to control the motor and they verify that the motor model is almost as accurate as the experimental.

V. CONCLUSION

This article presents a detailed speed and position control design using SMC for SSBMs. The experimental results reliably verify the effectiveness of the proposed control method. In addition, it is shown that this motor is able to run stably at a considerable high-speed range with a small position error. Therefore, this research is a reasonable basis for controlling SSBMs with neural networks and fuzzy or artificial intelligence combined with state observers and tests in the future.

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Design and Implementation of a Medical Telemonitoring System based on IoT

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Abstract-With the advancement of technology, healthcare and monitoring systems face significant issues. Internet of Things (IoT) in healthcare enables real-time health monitoring at a low cost. This paper aims to provide a medical telemonitoring system based on IoT for healthcare applications for doctors and paramedical staff. The system is made up of many sensors that can capture electrocardiograms (ECGs) in real-time and measure the temperature of the human body. The designed circuit is implemented and the obtained results are analyzed and discussed.

Keywords-*e-health; Internet of Things; ECG*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of data and IT technology, healthcare monitoring systems are becoming of great concern [1, 2]. The modern human lifestyle among others, leads to many heart disorders such as arrhythmia, coronary occlusion, cardiac arrest, and heart inflammation. The early diagnosis of a heart disease may lead to minimization of deaths [3, 4]. Modern technologies such as the IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and robotics systems play a vital role in revolutionizing the health care system [5]. Smart health monitoring can be an effective solution to the above challenges as it may takes less time and is more accurate [6, 7]. Several solutions based on ECG measurement systems allow to record and process the cardiac signal by placing skin electrodes on chest and limbs [8].

Many researchers worked on developing and designing a hardware-based ECG acquisition system [3]. Authors in [9] provide a fascinating review of the existing technologies that

characterize commercial wireless ECG systems. The purpose of this study is to review the solutions described in the literature, besides commercially available devices and electronic components useful to setup laboratory prototypes. Authors in [10] proposed an IoT-based patient health monitoring system linked to the Cloud Talk platform. The proposed system streamlines the traditional workflow by providing all medical checkups, facilities, and tests in one location. Authors in [11] present an approach based on the Intel Galileo development board to gather and upload various data into a database for use by patients and doctors, making the traditional checkup process more convenient. Authors in [12] propose an automatic contactless thermometer to replace the traditional temperature measuring techniques and safeguard from human-to-human transmission diseases. The advantage of the proposed model is that it uses GPS coordinates and population density values towards identifying the most crowded areas. Authors in [13] proposed a system prototype for monitoring the heartbeat rate and body temperature of chronic patients using sensors. The monitored data are sent to a cloud database in real-time.

In this paper, we present an interactive virtual interface-based medical tele-monitoring system for doctors and paramedical staff, which is implemented using virtual interface-based software, LabVIEW, and IoT. The system aims to contact a Hospital Emergency Room for asking for first aids in case of positive diagnosis. Patient path estimation, ECG signal capture, human-body temperature, and hospital alarm management are the four main components of the system.

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II. THE ECG ACQUISITION SYSTEM

In this section, we explain the methodology followed to design and simulate the ECG acquisition system. The ECG is the most used non-invasive method for making a preliminary clinical diagnosis of cardiac diseases. It is a method of recording the electrical activity of the heart, which is generated by the heart's cells, during the cardiac cycle (both normal and abnormal) [14, 15]. The electrical activity of the heart is measured because every time the heart beats, an electrical signal flows through it. Electrodes are placed on the chest to record the signal. The architecture of the proposed system is shown in Figure 1. This System consists of sensors, which interface with an Arduino Uno R3 Module. The module transmits the sensor data to LabVIEW. The proposed approach is structured in two main phases:

- LabVIEW software was used to write the code of the application. The aim of the simulation is to evaluate the operation of the card, and know, beforehand, the quality of the results and develop design guidelines. Simulations were conducted on Win 10, NI Multisim Release 12.0.1, Arduino IDE Compiler 1.8.19 and NI LabVIEW14.
- Realization of the prototype and the physical implementation of the proposed system. In this step, we used the following tools to evaluate our algorithm: Electrodes to capture the signal from the human heart, passive components (resistor and capacitor), an Arduino board, a low frequency generator, an oscilloscope and a computer with I5 Processor and 8GB RAM.

Fig. 1. ECG data acquisition system.

Fig. 2. ECG amplifier, high-and low-pass filters.

There are three stages in the process of simulation, i.e. pre-amplification, filtering, and amplification. The Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) is a significant data converter system. It is one of the main building blocks of the ECG detection system and health care integrated circuits [16]. Figure 2 depicts the ECG amplifier, consisting of high-and low-pass filters. We used the Multisim software to generate the circuit simulation results. Multisim is an industry standard SPICE simulation and circuit design software for analog, digital, and power electronics in education and research [17]. Figure 3 describes the framework used to develop and implement the proposed approach. Figure 4 represents the simulation model of the proposed system circuit in NI Multisim before assembling on a Printed Circuit Board (PCB).

Fig. 3. Stages of the acquisition card.

Fig. 4. Circuit diagram of the system.

A. Pre-Amplification

The pre-amplification stage raises the amplitude of the sensed ECG signal from about 0.02mV to about 5mV. The first stage consists of pre-processing the signal using a low pass filter to reduce noise. The pre-amplifier plays an important role in the circuit design. It not only extracts the useful EEG signal, but also reduces the interference signals to the lowest level. Pre-amplification is done using the well-known AD620 amplifier. The AD620 is highly suited for medical applications, such as ECG and non-invasive blood pressure monitors, due to its low noise, low cost, low input bias current, and low power [18]. Three different sinusoidal signals are generated:

- A signal with 50mVpp amplitude and a frequency of 20Hz (main signal).
- A signal with variable amplitude and a frequency of 100Hz which is supposed as noise and reacts on the main signal.
- A signal with variable amplitude and a frequency of 150mHz, considered as noise.

The three signals were introduced to the AD620 through pin 3. Then, a balanced 9v supply was applied to the AD620. A resistance R1 of 470Ω was added to have a gain equal to 106 according to:

$$G_{ain} = \frac{49.4k\Omega}{R_g} + 1 \quad (1)$$

Figure 5 shows the circuit design. Figure 6 illustrates the pre-amplification block results, the results show an informative signal with a main frequency of 20Hz, to which noise signals of 100Hz and 150mHz is superimposed.

Fig. 5. Pre-amplification circuit.

Fig. 6. Pre-amplification block results.

ECG signals are frequently affected by various sources of noise, and baseline drifting is typical. Signal conditioning is unquestionably required to permit automated ECG analysis. A filtering approach is employed to provide baseline correction and noise suppression with minimal signal distortion.

B. Filtering

Generally, the ECG signal can be corrupted by different types of noise and artifacts that can occur within the frequency band of interest and have comparable properties to the ECG signal itself. We must process the raw ECG data in order to obtain valuable information from the noisy ECG signals. Filters are used to remove many forms of noise, including baseline wander, 60Hz power line interference, muscle noise, and motion artifacts. In this section, we use two filters to eliminate the frequencies considered as noise. Two passive filters are

placed in series, as shown in Figure 7. The cutoff frequency F_c of the filter is calculated according to:

$$F_c = \frac{1}{2\pi RC} \quad (2)$$

The two filters used for this block are:

- First, a low-pass filter around the cutoff frequency of $F_c=36\text{Hz}$ to eliminate the 50Hz noise.
- Second, a high-pass filter around the cutoff frequency $F_c=0.15\text{Hz}$.

We cannot eliminate frequencies higher than 1Hz since sometimes we find cases where the ECG frequency takes a value of 2 or 3Hz. So, it is not recommended to eliminate these frequencies since we risk losing information. Figure 8 describes the result obtained at the output of the filter. It can be seen that the noise has been largely attenuated by this filter, especially the ripples, which have frequencies of 100Hz and 150mHz.

Fig. 7. Pre-amplification and filters.

Fig. 8. Filtering result.

C. Amplification

This section is devoted to the design of an instrumentation amplifier of low frequency biomedical signals. An ECG signal is weak, with a magnitude of about 1mV, so a high gain amplifier is required to acquire this small signal. The amplification gain remains adjustable and also the reference value. Practically, to vary the gain and the reference voltage we use two 10kΩ potentiometers, one placed in pins 1 and 8 to adjust the gain and the other placed on reference pin 5. The block diagram and related voltage gains of the circuit for

different values of resistances are depicted in Figure 9. We obtain an amplified signal at 6.13Vpp and totally detached from the noise as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9. Diagram of ECG signal detecting, amplification, and filtering.

Fig. 10. Amplified and filtered output signal.

Fig. 11. Arduino hardware board.

D. Analog to Digital Conversion

An ADC is interfaced to an Arduino Uno via Serial Peripheral Interface. Figure 11 shows the breadboard allowing to convert signals sent from the ECG sensor to the Arduino through the ADC.

III. TEMPERATURE DETECTION SYSTEM

LM35 is a temperature measuring device having an analog output voltage proportional to the temperature. In general, normal body temperature is 36.1°C or above. Pin 1 of the LM35 is linked to the Voltage pin (VCC) of the Arduino Uno board in the circuit diagram to receive a 5V supply voltage. Both the pulse sensor and the Arduino board's Ground pin (GND) are interconnected. The Arduino's output pin (VOUT) is linked to the Analog Pin (A0) and gives a voltage output, which is then converted to temperature.

IV. LABVIEW INTERFACE

The ADC converts the analog output of the instrumentation amplifier to a digital signal. We propose a Graphical User Interface (GUI) in LabVIEW to display the ECG wave forms and to record the ECG data over a period of time. The ECG output from the circuit will be the input data in the LabVIEW interface where the data can be processed, stored, and displayed. Figure 12 shows the block diagram of the ECG system using system on chip.

Fig. 12. Block diagram made with the LabVIEW.

Figure 13 shows the result obtained by our card from a test on a teenager. It clearly shows that the ECG signal obtained is correct and totally detached from the noise source. It is noted that the treatment and diagnosis of this signal remains the work of specialist cardiologists.

Fig. 13. ECG signal after filtering.

In the patient table system, the collected data are saved and updated in real time. ECG signals are sent from the patient's mobile device to the hospital's remote database server. The following information appears on each patient's table:

- Patient ID
- Temperature

- ECG data acquisition
- Patient location
- Predicted states

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper presents the design and implementation of a medical telemonitoring system based on IoT and its integration with LabVIEW for recording the ECG data and measuring body temperature. LabVIEW was used to acquire the ECG signal samples from the data acquisition card, to save the data, and to display information about the patient health.

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Polarization Effect Assessment of Sub-6 GHz Frequencies on Adult and Child Four-Layered Head Models

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Abstract-Nowadays, with the extensive use of mobile phones, the Electromagnetic (EM) radiation penetration from Radio Frequencies (RFs), particularly into the human head, is an issue that needs resolving. Some serious biological hazards occur inside the human body due to RF radiation accumulation. The RF radiation can be minimized by embodying shielding and coating materials on the front side of the mobile handset. The novelty of the proposed work is the use of mathematical analysis in calculating the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) absorbed by planar four-layer adult and child head models when exposed to mobile smartphone RF radiation. The variation of SAR with the Angle of Incident (AoI) of the EM wave considers Transverse Electric (TE) and Transverse Magnetic (TM) Polarization. The SAR absorption alteration with the AoI of the EM wave is calculated with the help of the shielding effectiveness parameter of the external Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) shield coated with conductive copper (Cu) mesh, forming a laminated shield using the methodology of the transmission line method. Furthermore, the SAR variation with AoI for both human head models is calculated theoretically at Sub-6 GHz mobile frequencies of 4.5GHz and 3.6GHz. SAR of $7.41e-12$ W/kg and $4.41e-11$ W/kg is achieved theoretically for adult and child head models respectively, at 89° TE polarization at 4.5GHz.

Keywords- specific absorption rate; shielding effectiveness; transverse electric polarization; transverse magnetic polarization; four-layered head model

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile handsets [1-3] are used worldwide, but their introduction brought unforeseen adverse effects. These mobile handsets emit RF energy, a kind of non-ionizing electromagnetic radiation that severely affects human head tissues during their usage. More power in the form of biogenic magnetite crystals gets deposited in the human brain at higher frequencies. The brain is a target organ for EM radiation, and the different received dosage is categorized into ionizing and non-ionizing radiation [4]. The Fifth Generation (5G) technology features high cell density and higher data transmission rates. The frequency bands 5G mobile communication uses are below 6GHz, and known as the Sub-6 GHz band and FR-2 [5]. The amount of radiation emerging from a handset and entering the brain layer is estimated using the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) parameter [6-7]. The dependent parameters of SAR are the conductivity (σ), the mass density of human head tissues (ρ), and the tissue incident electric field (E). From the ICNIRP guidelines [8], the permissible SAR is around 2W/kg. Hence, any mobile handset causing SAR more than the allowable is unauthorized for usage.

Embodying a transparent shield material [9] with conductive coating helps reducing SAR. After incorporating a shield, the shield performance is estimated using a parameter called Shielding Effectiveness (SE). This parameter depends on the calculated Total Transmission Coefficient (TTC) using the

Transmission Line Method (TLM) for two planar four-layered head models representing humans of different age. The incoming EM radiation can be incident at any arbitrary angle. The calculation of SAR for the head models includes both TE and TM polarization of the incident EM wave. Mobile phone antenna performance and design are not examined in the current work. All SAR calculations are evaluated considering a planar four-layered head model. The planar head model in Figure 1 has four layers, namely skin, fat, bone, and brain. The considered parameters are electrical conductivity (σ), relative permittivity (ϵ_r) and relative permeability (μ_r).

Fig. 1. A 4-layered planar human (adult/child) head model with PET shield and Cu coating. (a) Parallel polarization, (b) perpendicular polarization of the EM wave incident on the shield surface transmitted through the head tissues.

Many researchers have worked on estimating and reducing the SAR absorbed by human adult and child head models at various mobile frequencies. Authors in [10] studied the mutual effect of interaction between mobile phones and the human head with the FDTD method to find the SAR distribution in the head near the hand-held receiver. The mobile frequencies used are 900MHz and 1800MHz. Maximum 1g and 10g averaged SAR using the FDTD method were calculated in adult and child scaled head models in [11] at GSM 900MHz and 1800MHz. The effect of a plane wave that is obliquely incident on a six-layered head structure at 900MHz and 1800MHz was analyzed mathematically by deriving the exact formula for the electric field. The SAR distribution concerning various distances between the source and head model is plotted and compared in [12]. Authors in [13] studied the SAR distributions and temperature elevation with FDTD modeling of mobile phones and WLAN networks when a plane wave is excited with an obliquely incident wave in a head model of six layers. SAR and temperature rise are calculated and studied for each head layer at 900MHz, 1800MHz, and 2400MHz at parallel and perpendicular polarization. Authors in [14] investigated the relationship between peak SAR and temperature elevation averaged over 10g of human head tissues in head models in the 1 to 300GHz range.

The novelty of the proposed work is the numerical and mathematical evaluation of SAR by utilizing the TLM taking shield parameters such as SE of different planar-aged human head models with no shield condition and with the mesh coated thin film as a laminated shield. The SAR estimation and reduction using the transparent mesh coated film is not

available in literature for mobile phone applications up to 5G frequencies. The novelty of the current work is the study of the theoretical analysis of SAR with the usage of a transparent metal mesh of minimum thickness with the TLM.

II. ANALYSIS OF SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF HUMAN HEAD

A. Shielding Material and Parameters of Mesh

A shield is required to control the radiation from the handset and its design should be able to control the SAR imposed on the planar four-layered human head. This can be achieved by designing a transparent laminated shield, i.e. coating a polymer film coated with a conductive film. In the current work, the considered polymer is Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), and the conductive coating is Copper (Cu). The combination forms a laminated mesh. The material parameters of thickness, conductivity, relative permittivity, and relative permeability are included, whereas the mesh parameters, as shown in Figure 2, are mesh spacing and width [15]. The mesh spacing and the mesh width are used to find the Cu-mesh impedance [16]. The parameters involved in the impedance equation are:

$$\eta_{Mesh} = r_{Cu-Mesh} + jx_{Cu-Mesh} \quad (1)$$

$$r_{Cu-Mesh} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{Cu}\delta(1-e^{-t/\delta})} * \frac{g}{2a} \quad (2)$$

$$x_{Cu-Mesh} = -\frac{g}{\lambda} \left[\ln \left(\sin \left(\frac{\pi a}{g} \right) \right) \right] * \eta_0 \quad (3)$$

Equations (1)-(3) are used in the impedance calculation of coating film used in the analysis of the TTC from which the shielding effectiveness is derived. The shield on which the coating film is embedded is the polymer PET and its properties are shown in Table I. The impedance of the PET shield can be calculated from [17]. Therefore, the impedances of the films are calculated from (1)-(3), which help in determining the TTC. It is also necessary to resolve the tissue impedance of the human models, as described.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE SHIELDING MATERIAL

Material	PET film	Cu mesh film
Thickness	100 μm	100 nm
Conductivity (S/m)	7.80E-13	5.96E+07
Relative permittivity	3.4	1
Relative permeability	1	1
Mesh spacing	Not applicable	300 μm
Mesh width	Not applicable	15 μm

B. Human Head Models and Tissue Parameters

In the current work, a planar four-layered head model of the adult/child human head is considered. The model properties differ significantly in their water content and tissue thickness. The tissues include the skin, fat, bone, and brain. These tissues vary in thicknesses, as shown in Table II. However, their properties vary with the operating frequency of the mobile phone device (f). The electrical conductivities (σ), relative permittivities (ϵ_r), and also the relative permeabilities (μ_r) of the tissues change with frequency. But since all the tissues are biological, all the relative permeabilities are equal to unity.

Also, the impedances of the tissues depend on the operating frequency. The tissue impedance is generally given by $\eta_{<k>}$ for Skin, Fat, and Bone with (4) as the corresponding equation for impedance calculation:

$$\eta_{<k>} = (1 + j) \sqrt{\frac{\pi \mu_{<k>} f}{\sigma_{<k>}}} \quad (4)$$

From (4), the corresponding tissue relative permeability and conductivity at the mobile phone operating frequency are found by substituting all tissue impedances.

Fig. 2. Mesh parameters of a copper coating film.

TABLE II. TISSUE THICKNESS OF HEAD MODELS [18-19]

Tissue	Tissue thickness (mm)	
	Adult head	Child head
Skin	1	1
Fat	2	0.5
Bone	7	6.5
Brain	70.5	62.3

TABLE III. ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND PERMITTIVITY OF TISSUES WITH FREQUENCY

Frequency (GHz)	Head tissue	Electrical conductivity (S/m)	Relative permittivity
3.6	Skin	2.085	36.92
	Fat	0.161	5.1641
	Bone	0.637	10.74
	Brain	2.724	47.159
4.5	Skin	2.687	36.18
	Fat	0.212	5.0766
	Bone	0.844	10.28
	Brain	3.58	45.862

C. Effect of Polarization on the Impedance of Shield Medium and Tissues

Electromagnetic radiation can be incident over a wide range of the angle (θ). In the case of a TE/TM polarized wave, the impedances of the shield or any medium or tissue are altered by a ratio of $\cos \theta$. The angle of incidence (θ) would range for all acute angles (0° to 90°)—the polarization effect results in different transmission coefficients than the ones considered without polarization. Therefore, a variation is introduced in the SE of the head, and the SAR is absorbed. The interpretation of SAR considering the AoI of EM wave for polarization and

head models is considered. Irrespective of medium or tissues, the impedance variation with polarization is:

$$Z_{<k>} = \frac{\eta_{<k>}}{\cos \theta} \text{ (for TE)} \quad (5)$$

$$Z_{<k>} = \eta_{<k>} * \cos \theta \text{ (for TM)} \quad (6)$$

D. SE and SAR Calculations using the Transmission Line Method

During the estimation of SAR, its relatively dependent parameter SE needs to be calculated. SE can be calculated by determining the corresponding TTC (T) of the wave radiated by the TLM. The reflection coefficients at the interfaces of the tissues are calculated by taking the impedances introduced by them under TE and TM polarization. Once the total transmission coefficient is calculated through the TLM, the SE can be determined [20-21].

$$SE(dB) = -20 \log_{10}(T) \quad (7)$$

$$T = p \prod_{k=Skin}^{Bone} [(1 - q_{<k>} e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}})] e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}} \quad (8)$$

$$T = p \prod_{k=PET}^{Bone} [(1 - q_{<k>} e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}})] e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}} \quad (9)$$

The step-by-step numerical procedure to evaluate the SAR absorbed into human head is:

Step 1: The mathematical finding of the transmission coefficient T without shield and with the PET/Cu coated laminated mesh as shield is obtained from (8) and (9). k ranges from PET shield and Cu mesh coat to brain layer. $q_{<k>}$ gives the reflection coefficient at the interface of the layered medium, $\gamma_{<k>}$ is the respective propagation constant of the layered medium, and $l_{<k>}$ is the thickness of each medium.

Step 2: The SE of any barrier in terms of electric field E is:

$$SE = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_i}{E_t} \right) \quad (10)$$

Step 3: The incident electric field (E_i) from (10) is obtained from the power density incident on the head from the guidelines issued by ICNIRP [8] which is $40W/m^2$ for frequency greater than 2GHz.

Step 4: The transmitted electric field (E_t) into the brain can be determined from the shielding effectiveness of the human head models without shield and with the PET and Cu laminated mesh.

Step 5: Equations (7) and (11) are necessary for SAR calculation, and thus, (8) and (9) give the variation of SAR with polarization for both head models.

$$SAR = \frac{\sigma E_t^2}{\rho} \quad (11)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From (8), the SE from the TLM varies according to the AoI range from 0° to 90° for both TE and TM polarizations. The results are obtained by simulations in Matlab. The variations with AoI are plotted and compared. The SE and SAR calculations with changing operating frequency are listed in Tables IV and VI.

TABLE IV. SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF HUMAN HEAD MODELS IN VARIATION WITH ANGLE OF INCIDENCE AT TWO SUB- 6 GHZ FREQUENCIES

Frequency (GHz)	AoI (degrees)	Shielding effectiveness (SE in dB)							
		4-layer adult head model				4-layer child head model			
		Without shield		With PET/Cu laminated shield		Without shield		With PET/Cu laminated shield	
		TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization
3.6	0	9.83	9.83	68.75	68.75	2.46	2.46	61.34	61.34
	30	9.62	10.08	70.26	67.28	2.21	2.74	62.80	59.92
	45	9.35	10.48	72.45	65.26	1.90	3.20	64.92	57.98
	60	9	11.33	76.41	61.96	1.48	4.16	68.76	54.78
	89	8.13	31.80	127.74	36.61	0.41	25.15	119.98	29.96
4.5	0	12.30	12.30	70.87	70.87	4.72	4.72	63.02	63.02
	30	12.12	12.51	72.49	69.29	4.52	4.95	64.59	61.49
	45	11.91	12.84	74.85	67.14	4.27	5.32	66.89	59.40
	60	11.61	13.56	79.14	63.63	3.93	6.12	71.08	56.00
	89	10.90	32.69	132.24	37.55	3.08	25.55	124.37	30.40

TABLE V. RESULT COMPARISON

Frequency range (Mhz)	SAR assessment technique	Obtained SAR absorption values (W/Kg)	Head model	Reference
900, 1800	Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD)	0.037	Adult	[11]
900, 1800	FDTD	0.42 at TE polarization, 0.83 at TM polarization	Adult	[12]
900, 1800, 2400	FDTD	1.8 at TE polarization, 2 at TM polarization	Adult	[13]
3600, 4500	TLM	1.51E-06 at TE and 5.38E-05 for TM polarizations for adult model with laminated shield and 9.42E-06 for TE and 3.03E-04 for TM polarizations for child model with laminated shield.	Adult and child	Current work

TABLE VI. SAR ABSORBED BY BRAIN IN BOTH HEAD MODELS IN TE AND TM POLARIZATION AT TWO SUB-6 GHZ FREQUENCIES

Frequency (GHz)	AoI (degrees)	SAR (W/kg)							
		4-layer adult head model				4-layer child head model			
		Without shield		With PET/Cu laminated shield		Without shield		With PET/Cu laminated shield	
		TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization	TE polarization	TM polarization
3.6	0	12.71	12.71	1.63E-05	1.63E-05	66.68	66.68	8.63E-05	8.63E-05
	30	13.34	12	1.15E-05	2.29E-05	70.63	62.52	6.17E-05	1.20E-05
	45	14.2	10.95	6.95E-06	3.64E-05	75.86	56.23	3.78E-05	1.87E-04
	60	15.39	9	2.79E-06	7.79E-05	83.56	45.08	1.56E-05	3.91E-04
	89	18.81	0.08	2.06E-11	0.027	106.91	0.36	1.18E-10	0.12
4.5	0	7.3	7.3	1.02E-05	1.02E-05	40.73	40.73	6.03E-05	6.03E-05
	30	7.61	6.97	7.00E-06	1.46E-05	42.69	38.64	4.20E-05	8.57E-05
	45	8	6.45	4.06E-06	2.40E-05	45.21	35.45	2.47E-05	1.38E-04
	60	8.56	5.46	1.51E-06	5.38E-05	48.86	29.53	9.42E-06	3.03E-04
	89	10.1	0.07	7.41E-12	2.18E-02	59.38	0.34	4.41E-11	1.10E-01

Fig. 3. SE plot of the head without shield and PET-Cu mesh Laminated Shield (LS) for AoI in the 4-layered adult head at 3.6GHz fixed-mobile frequency for TE and TM polarization.

In Figures 3 and 4, the comparison of the SE variation with the operating frequency for a four-layered adult head is made. It is observed that at 3.6GHz, the SE values for TE polarization appear to be constant. However, they decrease drastically without the shield. With the shield, the SE values increased sharply from 30° to 89°. In the case of TM polarization without a shield, the SE values increased symmetrically about TE polarized SE values from 72° to 89°. However, it can be seen that the SE values with shield at TM polarization abruptly decrease from 30° to 89°. At 4.5GHz, the phenomenon remains the same, but the difference is that at 4.5GHz, the SE values are higher than at 3.6GHz.

Figures 5 and 6 compare the SE variation with the operating frequency of the mobile phone for the four-layered child head. At 3.6GHz, the SE values for TE polarization appear constant, but they decreased drastically without the

shield, while they increased with the shield. In the case of TM polarization and without a shield, the SE values increased symmetrically about the TE polarized SE values. We see that the SE values with the shield are more significant than those without it. Moreover, the SE values in the model of the child head are always less than in the adult head model.

Fig. 4. SE plot of the head without shield and PET-Cu mesh LS for AoI in the 4-layered adult head at 4.5GHz fixed-mobile frequency for TE and TM polarization.

Fig. 5. SE plot of the head without shield and PET-Cu mesh LS vs angle of incidence in the 4-layered child head model at 3.6GHz fixed-mobile frequency for TE and TM Polarization.

Fig. 6. SE plot of the head without shield and with PET-Cu mesh LS vs angle of incidence in the 4-layered child head model at 4.5GHz fixed-mobile frequency for TE and TM polarization.

From Figures 3-6, for TE polarization with PET and Cu shield, the SE started to increase sharply at 35°, and for TM polarization, it abruptly decreased from 35° to 89°. The values of SE of head variation for particular angles of incidence of EM waves are listed in Table IV, and their corresponding SAR values in Table VI. It is observed from Table V that with an

increase in the SE of the four-layered adult/child head with frequency, the SAR absorbed by the brain consistently decreased to a negligible level much lesser than the prescribed SAR limit. The comparison of the results of the proposed method with the existing results is exhibited in Table V.

IV. CONCLUSION

The current paper compares the effect on human head models of the penetration of RF EM radiation for varying AoI from the sub-6 GHz operating frequency mobile phone. In TE and TM polarization, the SAR of the child model without a shield dominated over the adult model without a shield. When using a PET with a Cu laminated shield mounted on the front part of the mobile handset, the SAR is decreased in both models. Based on the operating mid-band 5G mobile smartphones and the incident angle polarization, the SAR variations are observed in both the head models without and with the laminated shield. In contrast, at the same operating frequency, for TE polarization, the SAR absorbed by the brain of the child model without a shield varied from 40.73 to 50.38W/kg for 0° to 89° angle of incidence variation. In contrast, the SAR decreased from 6E-05 to 4.41E-11W/kg with the PET and Cu lamination in TE polarization. For TM polarization and the same child head model, operating frequency, and AoI variation, the SAR decreased from 40.73 to 0.34W/kg, and with PET Cu mesh, it increased from 6.03E-05 to 0.11W/kg. Also, the minimum absorbed SAR was found at 4.5GHz for the adult head model in TE polarization at 89°, and the maximum absorbed SAR by the brain tissue was observed at 3.6GHz in the child head model in TE polarization at 89°. Therefore, the adult model absorbed more negligible radiation than the child head model with the PET/Cu mesh. However, compared to SAR without the laminated shield in a child's head, incorporating PET and Cu-based transparent film in the mobile handset has considerably decreased the SAR absorbed by the brain.

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Decoupling Control Applied to the Smart Grid Power Dispatching Problem

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Abstract-This paper presents controller designs of the decoupling issue dedicated to renewable decentralized generators or new generation grids known as smart grids. The control methods were based on a three-phase voltage source grid representation that integrated wind and photovoltaic generators. The utilized decoupling strategies (Boksenbom and Hood, Zilkind and Luyben, and inverted decoupling) allowed the optimization of energy transfers and costs through the routing grid distribution path. Simulations were conducted in Matlab/Simulink. The trustworthiness of the multivariable control system design in addition to the tuning method was established using three test batches, totally decoupled and stable from input dependencies.

Keywords-decoupling; smart grid; demand-response; power dispatching; controller design

I. INTRODUCTION

Methods presenting only one output controlled by a single deployed variable are classified as Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) systems. Several processes do not imitate such a simple control shape. Each unit operation needs to control no less than two variables, and consequently, there are frequently at least two control loops to deal with. Systems that involve more than one control loop are known as Multi-Input Multi-Output (MIMO) or multivariable systems. The electrical smart grid is essentially a massive MIMO system. Due to the interactions of the flow power offer and demand, it is not easy to design a robust controller for each path autonomously to lead an input x to an output y without affecting any other output. Many studies have focused on several loop control structures to diminish these interactions.

Decoupling methods are mostly used in industrial processes but are still applicable for many electrical system parameter-decoupling purposes. A simplified, ideal, and inverted decoupling comparative study was presented in [1], which was the base for many classic studies. Three decoupling methods were considered to deal with stability, robustness, and implementation aspects, while the complexity of the decoupler elements depended on the overall system size. An improvement of the two inverted decoupling methods was presented in [2] for the case of a stable linear multivariable class of processes,

through no minimum-phase zeros and multiple time delays. As some multivariable processes were still unable to be decoupled due to stability issues, alternative decoupling with a unity feedback structure was suggested. The PI/PID was designed using internal model control to decouple the processes. In the case of multiplicative input uncertainty, the low bounds of the control parameters were intended to guarantee the robust stability of the system. As the disturbances influence the way of the control synthesis of a MIMO system based on ideal decouplers and a PID regulator, single controller performance and robustness from the closed-loop could be prolonged to all loop systems [3]. An improved decoupling approach allowed more flexibility in the choice of transfer functions of the decoupled apparent process for general $n \times n$ processes, where the decoupler elements' complexity appeared independent of the system's size [4]. A decoupling internal model controller design method was proposed in [5] for industrial MIMO time-delay systems, based on a controlled model adjoint matrix. A decoupling compensator and an internal model controller, Butterworth low-pass filter, were designed for decoupling the generalized controlled object. The last filter aimed to improve the disturbance rejection aptitude. In [6], a method of finding the forced oscillation source was proposed. The relation between the observable outputs and the mechanical power problems in a unit was decoupled by sensibly designing a Luenberger observer using an aging structure task. A MIMO control system with multiple time delays and a model predictive control was presented in [7], describing a method to design MIMO filtered Smith predictors for $n \times n$ processes through multiple time delays based on the decentralized direct decoupling structure. This allowed simple tuning of the primary controller, making simpler the problem toward multiple single loops, if realizable, and it could also be used to eliminate the interactions among process variables.

The decoupling method is also applicable to electrical grid, microgrid, and smart grid annexed domains facing new intermittent and highly variable system challenges and expectations [8-17]. Modeling approaches were proposed in [8] using analytical tools for control design purposes of step-up grid-connected PV systems, such as voltage source

representation of the bulk capacitor interacting with the grid-connected inverter and considering the inverter of a double-stage PV system as a Norton equivalent. Furthermore, both ideal and real DC/DC converter models for the PV module were presented through four mathematical models, stated in state-space representation. A decoupled inverter connected to a grid was exposed in [9], using dynamic online grid impedance measurements in a micro grid application. The controller was implemented in a synchronous reference frame and PI controllers were used, while mutual coupling was introduced between the d and q control loops. The transformation into a synchronous reference was accurately decoupled using the dynamically measured grid impedance and feedforward control. Decoupling permits autonomous control of active and reactive powers following changes, and online real impedance measurement was proposed to make the decoupling more precise. In [10], a multivariable-droop synchronous current converter decoupling control strategy was proposed for the current management of weak grid/micro grid applications, offering a traditional forward design method that employs the loop determining technique. The controller mixes current regulation, management, and limitations that apply to weak and micro grids. The multivariable synchronous current converter allowed larger decoupling of d - and q -axis currents in weak and/or resistive grids, anywhere these control variables are highly coupled due to the converter's large load-angle operation.

In [11], the evolution allocation for the decoupling of the electrical network was studied using pure channel component transform, addressing issues such as robustness. Difficulties were efficiently overcome using singular values instead of proper decomposition. An algorithm was developed to show how the adopted transformation can be used for voltage stability analysis. In [12], a distributed generator strategy control was investigated to assist a conventional local grid by decoupling phase sequences, frequency domain unbalances, and harmonic compensation for grid-connected inverters through unbalanced loads. This strategy was considered sequential-asymmetric for unbalanced and harmonic voltage correction. Moreover, a Norton equivalent model in frequency-domain was used. This study showed that following a frequency-domain decoupled method, the fundamental positive, harmonic symmetrical, fundamental zero, and negative sequence components can be regulated independently.

In [13], a virtual synchronous generator control method was proposed for extensive renewable energies connected to a grid. A power decoupling control method based on linear active disturbance rejection control was developed to eliminate output power deviation. Using the coupling term estimates and disturbances from an extended state observer, the aforesaid matter triggered by power coupling can be lessened. Furthermore, the stability of the controller was analyzed. In [14], essential limitations were defined for the islanded mode of operation of micro grids which cannot be absorbed by conventional FP methods. Therefore, updates were designed for conservative approaches by including network frequency as a variable and avoiding the network soft bus. These particular aspects of the Newton-Raphson method modified the designs of the Jacobean matrix. Extended power factor equations were

decoupled by reformulating the Jacobean matrix based on the fact that lines are mostly resistive. Furthermore, two convergence improvement methods were also incorporated. Dual-buck inverters were examined in [15], reassessing volume, system weight, and power density of dual-buck single-phase grid-tied PV inverters. A new active power decoupling buffer and grid-tied photovoltaic inverter integration with single-inductor dual buck topology were proposed, using a single-loop direct input current ripple control method. Several concerns arise in the case of pulse width modulation using a high-voltage current source converter based on fully controlled devices, such as high switching losses, large DC voltage fluctuations, and thin power operation range [16]. To resolve these difficulties, a current source converter-based HVDC was proposed using fundamental frequency modulation presenting the topology, an independent control strategy, and a mathematical model. A synchronized control strategy was proposed to decouple active and reactive powers with an outer and inner current controller loop to lead to lower DC voltage fluctuations, lower switching losses, and a broader power operation range.

This study investigated a Two-Input Two-Output (TITO) grid system, as a MIMO system could be devised into several TITO subsystems. The main goal was to employ decoupling methods for grid part energy aggregation, aiming to decouple demand response paths based on statue and output feedback control methods.

II. CONTROLLER DESIGN AND METHODS

The control strategy of the phase grid-connected PV, wind, and storage system inverter is presented in Figure 1. The elements were taken from [17-24].

Fig. 1. Overall grid-connected system design.

The system can be described in the state representation by:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{X} = AX + BU \\ Y = CX + DU \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where A is the characteristic matrix, B is the order matrix, C is the output matrix, and D is the coupling matrix. A control law was defined by the output feedback as:

$$e = V - K \cdot y \quad (2)$$

where V is the new entries vector of the dimension $(m.l)$, K is the matrix of dimension $(m.l)$, m is the number of outputs, l is the number of entries, y is the output vector, and e is the input vector. K is calculated by solving:

$$|\lambda I - BKC| = 0 \quad (3)$$

The governing equations of the network filter defined in Figure 1 are:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{L_1 di_1}{dt} + R_1 I_1 + V_1 = y_1 \\ \frac{L_2 di_2}{dt} + R_2 I_2 + V_2 = y_2 \\ \frac{L_3 di_3}{dt} + R_3 I_3 + V_3 = y_3 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The fundamental principles of simplification of the equations of states, such as the Park model, can be used to either substitute or eliminate the effect of one or several equations, to implement and succeed in the decoupling methods by delimitating the effects of inputs on outputs. The relative Park equation model from the overall grid-connected system design is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{L_d di_d}{dt} + R_d I_d + V_d = y_d \\ \frac{L_q di_q}{dt} + R_q I_q + V_q = y_q \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Input and output voltages are linked by values belonging to R :

$$\begin{cases} V_d = \lambda_d y_d + \lambda_q y_q \\ V_q = \beta_d y_d + \beta_q y_q \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Using (5):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{L_d di_d}{dt} = -R_d I_d - V_d + y_d \\ \frac{L_q di_q}{dt} = -R_q I_q - V_q + y_q \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Substituting (6) in (7) gives:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{L_d di_d}{dt} = -R_d I_d - (\lambda_d y_d + \lambda_q y_q) + y_d \\ \frac{L_q di_q}{dt} = -R_q I_q - (\beta_d y_d + \beta_q y_q) + y_q \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -R_d & 0 \\ L_d & 0 \\ 0 & -R_q \\ L_q & 0 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} (1-\lambda_d) & -\lambda_q \\ L_d & L_d \\ -\beta_d & (1-\beta_q) \\ L_q & L_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, D = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The transfer function matrix $G(s)$ can be easily obtained from the state representation using:

$$G(s) = C(sI - A)^{-1}B + D \quad (10)$$

In the general case, the matrix D is null and the calculation of $G(p)$ is simplified as:

$$G(s) = C(sI - A)^{-1}B \quad (11)$$

$$G(s) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The used units are $L_1 = L_2 = 16.58.10^{-3}H$, and $r_1 = r_2 = 0.98\Omega$. The transfer matrix is obtained from the A , B , and C matrices:

$$G(s) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{0.096}{100s+0.96} & \frac{0.096}{100s+0.96} \\ \frac{-0.024}{100s+1.92} & \frac{0.072}{100s+1.92} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The grid inputs are two photovoltaic conversion chain outputs by two different steps:

A. Without Decoupling

After obtaining the coupled system block diagram and the transfer matrix $G(p)$ elements, the wiring was designed in Matlab/Simulink to visualize the evolution of its outputs as a function of time. The simultaneous excitation of $e1$ and $e2$ inputs is shown in Figure 2.

$$\begin{cases} y_1 = u_1 G_{11} + u_2 G_{12} \\ y_2 = u_1 G_{21} + u_2 G_{22} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$y = Gu \quad (15)$$

with:

$$y = [y_1, y_2]^T, u = [u_1, u_2]^T, G = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 2. Coupled system block Simulink diagram.

Fig. 3. Grid inputs.

At $t_0=0s$, a unit step is performed at each system input. Then the amplitude of $e1$ is reduced to 0.5 at $t=1500s$ without modifying the second input. After that, at $t=2500s$, the second input $e2$ decreases to 0.5, without modifying the first input $e1$. Figure 4 shows the evolution of each output $y1$ and $y2$.

Fig. 4. Grid outputs without decoupling

The evolution of outputs of the coupled system shows that the change in the first input could vary and affect the second output. The following subsection introduces some decoupling methods to obtain an overall system made of TITO subsystems varying in parallel to Figure 5. In particular, the input e1 should only affect the first output y1, and the input e2 should only affect y2. The chosen methods were Boksenbom and Hood [2, 10], Zalkind and Luyben [2], and a method based on inverted decoupling [2, 4].

Fig. 5. The TITO overall system.

B. Decoupling Using Boksenbom and Hood Method

Using (12), the decoupling matrix G_c^* can be given by:

$$G_c^* = \begin{bmatrix} G_{c,11}^* & G_{c,12}^* \\ G_{c,21}^* & G_{c,22}^* \end{bmatrix} \dots (16)$$

Reference signals are shown by $w=[w_1, w_2]$:

$$Gu = y, u = G_c^*[w - y]G_c^*[w - y] = y \quad (17)$$

$$y = [I + GG_c^*]^{-1}GG_c^*w \quad (18)$$

$$X = [I + GG_c^*]^{-1}GG_c^* = \text{diag}[x_1, x_2] \quad (19)$$

X is a diagonal matrix:

$$GG_c^* = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} G_{c,11}^* & G_{c,12}^* \\ G_{c,21}^* & G_{c,22}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} q_1 & 0 \\ 0 & q_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{cases} q_1 = G_{11}G_{c,11}^* + G_{12}G_{c,21}^* \\ 0 = G_{11}G_{c,12}^* + G_{12}G_{c,22}^* \\ 0 = G_{21}G_{c,11}^* + G_{22}G_{c,21}^* \\ q_2 = G_{21}G_{c,12}^* + G_{22}G_{c,22}^* \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$G_{c,12}^* = \frac{-G_{12}G_{c,22}^*}{G_{11}}, \quad G_{c,21}^* = \frac{-G_{21}G_{c,11}^*}{G_{22}} \quad (22)$$

As the decoupled matrix functions do not influence the evaluation of the diagonal matrix decoupling, according to this method principle, the PI/PID regulators must be chosen arbitrarily. The stability condition of the system has to be respected, as follows:

$$G_{c,11}^* = G_{c,22}^* = \frac{s+0.1}{s} \quad (23)$$

The Simulink transfer functions block wiring which characterizes this method are shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Boksenbom and Hood block Simulink diagram.

The same conditions were applied in this case. At $t_0=0s$, a unit step was performed for e1 and e2. Then, e1 was lowered to 0.5 at $t=1500s$ without changing e2. Next, as $t=2500s$, e2 declined to 0.5, without changing e1. The evolution of y1 and y2 outputs is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Boksenbom and Hood grid outputs.

The proposed control system is perceived as having good decoupling. Due to error approximation, the decoupling system interactions are thoughtful. Thus, a PI/PID must be implemented.

C. Decoupling Using Zlikind and Luyben Method

Using (11):

$$y = Gu^*, \quad u^* = G_c^*u, \quad u = G_c[w - y] \quad (24)$$

are chosen as follows:

$$y = GG_c^*u = GG_c^*G_c[w - y] \quad (25)$$

$$X = GG_c^* = \text{diag}[x_1, x_2] \quad (26)$$

$$G_c^*G^{-1}X, G^{-1} = \text{adj}(G)/\det(G)$$

where $\text{adj}(G)$ is the adjoint of the matrix of G , and $\det(G)$ is the determinant of the matrix G given by:

$$\det(G) = G_{11}G_{22} - G_{12}G_{21} \quad (27)$$

$$\text{adj}(G) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{22} & -G_{12} \\ -G_{21} & G_{11} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

$$G_c^* = G^{-1}X \begin{bmatrix} G_{22}x_1 & G_{12}x_2 \\ G_{21}x_1 & G_{11}x_2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\det(G)} \quad (29)$$

The chosen form is a unit diagonal given by:

$$G_{c,11}^* = G_{c,22}^* = 1 \quad (30)$$

therefore:

$$G_{c,12}^* = -\frac{G_{12}}{G_{11}}, \quad G_{c,21}^* = -\frac{G_{21}}{G_{22}} \quad (31)$$

G_{c1} and G_{c2} must be PI/PID regulators chosen as follows:

$$G_{c1} = G_{c2} = \frac{s+0.1}{s} \quad (32)$$

The Simulink transfer functions block wiring of this method is shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows the evolution of the outputs y_1 and y_2 applying the same conditions as in the other methods.

Fig. 8. Zlikind and Luyben Simulink block diagram.

Fig. 9. Zlikind and Luyben grid outputs.

D. Decoupling Using Inverted Decoupling Method

G_{c11} and G_{c22} are placed in the forward direction which can be PI or PID controller. Using (11) and (12), it is necessary that:

$$D_{12} = -\frac{G_{12}}{G_{11}}, D_{21} = -\frac{G_{21}}{G_{22}} \quad (33)$$

The Simulink transfer wiring function wedges describing this method are shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Inverted decoupling block Simulink diagram.

Fig. 11. Inverted decoupling grid outputs.

The inverted decoupling processes shown in Figure 11 does not contain bulk sums of transfer functions. Consequently, the diagonal controllers' fine-tuning becomes more accommodating in higher multivariable processes with solid cross-couplings, even if the system elements have simple changing aspects.

IV. RESULT COMPARISON AND DISCUSSION

The three methods obtained perfect decoupling, but the variation in the calculation of the terms that characterize each method and the simplicity of their use should be noted. In the Boksenbom and Hood method, the functions and the PI regulator were chosen in the decoupling block, but in the Zalkind and Luyben method they are taken equal to 1, which is simpler, and they do not appear based on a reduced decoupling block. The Zalkind and Luyben method requires the computation of the inverse $G(p)$, thus the determinant of G must be non-zero, which is not necessary for the two other

methods. The addition of a compensation block consisting of a PI controller in the direct chain for the Zalkind and Luyben decoupling method has the same effect as its addition in the decoupling block by the method based on the reduced decoupling block, so there is only a variation in the structure. Its absence in the Boksenbom and Hood method makes it lose flexibility in the implementation of the non-interactive control grouping, especially regarding the stability of the system. Using these criteria, the method based on a reduced decoupling block is the simplest because it requires fewer computations and has more flexibility via the PI controller.

A multivariable control system design employing a fine-tuning filter based on an inverted decoupler, using stator or output feedback control methods, was presented. The high closed-loop system enactment was attained for predefined robustness by eliminating unnecessary control exertion and introducing adequate filtration of the controlled variables. This was verified by the results which treat an extremely intermittent PV source and chain outputs. The proposed demand response path methods improved inverted decoupling. The disturbance response was minimized within a narrow range for the intermitting nature of renewable energy processes known for their instability.

V. CONCLUSION

The cogency of the proposed stator feedback multivariable control system design and tuning was confirmed using three methods. High closed-loop system performance was attained by avoiding unnecessary control exertion using the suitable controlled variables filtration. The three methods, Boksenbom and Hood, Zilkind and Luyben, and inverted decoupling, eliminated the opposing effects caused by non-minimum phase zeros and achieved dynamic decoupling.

The simulation results showed that the three proposed methods could establish a decent dynamic decoupling, solid robustness, and immunity against trouble. Results proved that they succeeded very effectively to limit the interactions of the inputs to the relative outputs, which opens the road to the generalization of these decoupling methods for the entire end-to-end chain of different energy sources to improve and optimize energy dispatching. Inverted decoupling gives more effective and precise results compared to Boksenbom and Hood and Zilkin and Luyben, given the additional regulation blocks G_{c11} and G_{c22} , which leads to maintaining the input magnitudes. Future work should assess more than two inputs and study a big-scale system matrix, rearranging it to a 2 by 2 matrix.

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Controller Design for the Pitch Control of an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

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Abstract-In recent years, the Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) has found its application in a large number of areas, especially in the ocean environment. But due to its highly non-linear nature with six degrees of freedom and the presence of hydrodynamic forces, the equations for AUV control become complex and difficult to design. Hence, in order to overcome this complexity and non-linearity, a reduced-order subsystem is derived for controlling the pitch. Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) and Fractional Order PID (FOPID) techniques have been applied for determining the controller for better performance of pitch control in the presence of disturbance.

Keywords-Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV); IMC-PID; LQR; FOPID

I. INTRODUCTION

An AUV is an automatic submersible vehicle that can function in the absence of real time controller, without any human interference [1]. The presence of nonlinearity in the vehicle dynamics makes difficult to apply linear controller to the AUVs and the complexity in the dynamics of AUVs makes the design of its controller difficult. Due to the presence of high non-linearity, time-varying characteristics, unpredictable hydraulic coefficients, and the interference caused by sea currents and waves, the dynamics of the AUV become quite complex. The design of a controller for AUV is a challenging task as the complexity in design basically lies in finding the hydrodynamic parameters and the non-linearity in the dynamics of the vehicle [2]. In order to control the pitch of AUV many methods have been proposed. The LQR-based controller has been designed for the derived divine plane model of AUV and the performance is analyzed with Matlab/Simulink in [3, 4].

The current paper, gives a detailed study of the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm used to optimize the

Fractional Order PID (FOPID) controller for obtaining a fast and robust response for the pitch control of an AUV [1, 5]. The parameters obtained using the PSO-based FOPID will be utilized for obtaining the response for pitch angle. The response of the PSO based FOPID controller is compared with the response of IMC-PID and LQR controllers. With the help of the response, Rise Time, Settling Time, Overshoot and Integral of Time Absolute Error (ITAE) can be computed. ITAE has been considered as the objective function [6, 7].

II. MODELING OF THE AUV

The mathematical modelling of an AUV requires the study of its kinematics and dynamics. The geometrical aspect describes the kinematics, while the dynamics of the vehicle describe and analyze the forces that cause motion [8]. To identify the location and direction of the AUV, the differential equation of the vehicle's 6-DOF (degrees of freedom) motion must be solved [9]. The positional and translational motion along x , y and z axes is represented using flow, amplitude, and heave [9] respectively, while the orientation and rotational motion are described with the help of roll, pitch, and yaw [1, 11, 12]

A. Vehicle Kinematics

A two-coordinate frame has been used to analyze a vehicle path with 6 DOFs [13]. Because it is attached to the vehicle, the moving reference frame is known as a body-fixed reference frame [13, 14]. An inertial frame is used to describe the trajectory of the body-fixed frame. With the body-fixed frame, we can characterize the vehicle's linear and angular velocities, whereas the inertial frame describes its position and orientation [1]. Six-DOF vehicle motion can be represented in a generic sense by the following vectors [14]:

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$$\eta = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_1 \\ \eta_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$v = \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_1 \\ \tau_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\eta_1 = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}$ is the position vector, $\eta_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \theta \\ \psi \end{bmatrix}$ the Euler

angle vector, $v_1 = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}$ the uniform speed vector [3], $v_2 = \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix}$

the rotational speed vector, $\tau_1 = \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix}$ represents the direction of

the forces, and $\tau_2 = \begin{bmatrix} K \\ M \\ N \end{bmatrix}$ is the moments vector.

TABLE I. MOTION OF THE AUV

DOFs	Motion	Forces and moments	Velocity [10]	Position and Euler angles [10]
1	Surge	X	u	x
2	Sway	Y	v	y
3	Heave	Z	w	z
4	Roll	K	P	φ
5	Pitch	M	q	θ
6	Yaw	N	r	ψ

The Euler angle transformation $\dot{\eta} = J(\eta_2)v$, where $J(\eta_2)$ is the Jacobian matrix, represents plotting among the two coordinate systems [14].

B. Vehicle Dynamics

The vehicle dynamics consist of translational as well as rotational motion [3, 8]. The equation for the translatory movement of the vehicle is:

$$m(v_0 + \omega * v_0 + \dot{\omega} * r_g + \omega * (\omega * r_g)) = f_0 \quad (4)$$

and the rotational movement of the vehicle is:

$$I_0 \dot{\omega} + \omega * (I_0 \omega) + m r_g * (v_0 + \omega * v_0) = m_0 \quad (5)$$

By employing Newton's and Euler's equations and ignoring surge, sway, heave, and yaw, the equation of pitch control can be expressed as [8, 15]:

$$\begin{aligned} I_x \dot{p} + (I_z - I_y)qr - (\dot{r} + pq)I_{xz} + (r^2 - q^2)I_{yz} \\ + (pr - \dot{q})I_{xy} \\ + m[y_g(\dot{w} - uq + vq) \\ - z_g(\dot{v} - wp + ur)] = K \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_y \dot{q} + (I_x - I_z)rp - (\dot{p} + qr)I_{xy} + (p^2 - r^2)I_{xz} \\ + (qp - \dot{r})I_{yz} \\ + m[z_g(\dot{u} - vr + wq) \\ - x_g(\dot{w} - uq + vp)] = M \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Assuming the velocity of the heave is very small and can be neglected, the state space equation of the system will be [16]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y - M_q & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{z} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -M_q & 0 & M_\theta \theta \\ 0 & 0 & u_1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ z \\ \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{fs} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The transfer function for the pitch control can be obtained from the matrix representation as:

$$G_\theta(s) = \frac{\theta(s)}{f_s(s)} = \frac{\frac{M_{fs}}{I_y - M_q}}{s^2 - \frac{M_{fs}}{I_y - M_q} s - \frac{M_\theta}{I_y - M_q}} \quad (9)$$

The transfer function for the AUV can be obtained considering the following data: Fin lift (M_{fs}) = -1575.9kg.m²/s, I_y = 469kg/m², added mass M_q = -458 kg.m², hydrostatic M_θ = 13719.6kg.m²/s², and takes the following form:

$$G_\theta(s) = \frac{-1.818}{0.0077s^2 + 0.507s + 1} \quad (11)$$

III. CONTROLLER DESIGN

In this section, we will go over the designs of various controllers that will be used to control the pitch of the AUV. It is necessary for the controller to be observable in all the states in order to be used effectively.

A. IMC-PID Controller

The Internal Model Controller (IMC) is composed of a constant controller $Q(s)$ and the plant model, where $G(s)$ is the model of the plant. It is equipped with an inbuilt filter controller $F(s)$. $Q(s)$ and $F(s)$ are corrected by increasing the robustness of the filter, which is achieved by selecting the filter parameter appropriately [2]. Figure 1 gives a representation of an IMC structure. The controller is given by:-

$$g_c(s) = \frac{q(s)}{1 - g_p(s)q(s)} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 1. IMC structure.

B. Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) Controller

The advantage of using LQR is that it provides practical feedback gain [3]. Conventional controllers have a drawback as they result in higher overshoot and due to the lack of proper tuning, often the controller is not optimal [17]. The state space model of the system is given by [3]:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \quad (13)$$

The LQR design method consists of designing the gain factor K , i.e. a state feedback. The objective function J is taken in such a way that its minimization makes the system stable [3]:

$$J = \int_0^\infty (x^T Q x + u^T R u) dt \quad (14)$$

Q and R represent symmetrical diagonal matrices that decide the weight factors [3]:

$$Q, R \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

The main aim of the LQR controller is to give optimal feedback gain as described below [3]:

$$u = -Kx \quad (16)$$

The feedback gain (K) can be calculated using the Matrix Algebraic Riccati Equation (MARE) [3] as follows:

$$u = -R^{-1} B^T P x \quad (17)$$

$$K = -R^{-1} B^T P \quad (18)$$

Fig. 2. LQR structure.

C. Fractional Order PID Controller [18]

Podlubny proposed the fractional order PID controller in 1997 [19], and since then, it has become widely used. It should be noted that the order of the integrator and differentiator in FOPID is different from the order of the integrator and differentiator in the typical PID controller. Both the integrator and the differentiator should be in the correct order [18, 20]. The transfer function of a PID controller of this type is:

$$G_{fo}(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s^\lambda} + K_d s^\mu \quad (19)$$

Fig. 3. FOPID structure.

Authors in [5] proposed the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) technique, in which a swarm is represented by m particles. These particles are described by two variables, x and v , representing the position and its corresponding velocity in the search space. The PSO algorithm is given in Figure 3. The algorithm starts with randomly initializing the particles and updating their position and velocity values until an optimized value is obtained [1]. The updated equation for position and velocity for the swarm in the search space is given by:

$$x_i(t + 1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t + 1) \quad (20)$$

$$v_i(t + 1) = \omega v_i(t) + C_1 \phi_1 [b_i(t) - x_i(t)] + C_2 \phi_2 [g(t) - x_i(t)] \quad (21)$$

ITAE has been considered as the objective function and is given by:

$$ITAE = \int_0^\infty t |e(t)| dt \quad (22)$$

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the PSO algorithm.

With the help of PSO, it is possible to optimize the parameters of the FOPID controller. The initial population is assumed to be 100 and the number of iterations is calculated to be 50.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Simulation of Pitch Control For AUV

The step response for the pitch control of the AUV using IMC-PID, LQR-PID, and FOPID is shown in Figure 5. The performance comparison of the three controllers is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. PARAMETER INDEX OF STEP FOR PITCH SUBSYSTEM

Method	Over-shoot (%)	T_r (s)	T_s (s)	T_p (s)	ITAE
IMC-PID	30.8	0.896	18.3	2.05	4.068
LQR	5.27	0.532	7.39	1.07	3.79
FOPID	3.55	0.0129	0.0558	0.031	2.867

B. Simulation of Pitch Control For AUV in the Presence of Disturbance

The response of the pitch subsystem using IMC-PID, LQR and FOPID in the presence of sinusoidal disturbance is illustrated in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Step response of the pitch subsystem via FOPID, OPTIMAL PID, and IMC-PID.

Fig. 6. Response of the pitch subsystem via FOPID, OPTIMAL PID, and IMC-PID in the presence of disturbance.

TABLE III. PARAMETER INDEX FOR THE RESPONSE OF THE PITCH SUBSYSTEM IN THE PRESENCE OF DISTURBANCE

Method	Over-shoot (%)	T_r (s)	T_s (s)	T_p (s)	ITAE
IMC-PID	32.33	2.236	36.66	4.579	11.642
LQR	5.96	1.601	10.96	1.015	10.978
FOPID	4.62	0.9720	0.0558	0.626	10.447

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a PID control technique for AUV pitch subsystems that is of fractional order. When compared to optimum PID and IMC-PID, this technique has significantly shorter settling time, rising time, peak time, and overshoot. It demonstrates an increase in the quickness of response in the presence of a disruption. It is obvious from the simulations that the performance of the proposed FOPID is superior to that of the optimum controller and the IMC.

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An Intelligent Fault Detection and Classification Scheme for Distribution Lines Using Machine Learning

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Abstract-The current paper focuses on the development and deployment of Machine Learning (ML) based algorithms for the classification and detection of different faults in the electrical distribution system. The methodology adapted using ML has higher computational accuracy than traditional computational algorithms. The parameters involved in developing ML for fault detection/classification are fundamental frequency, fault voltage, and current components at fault situations. During faults, the current and voltage waveforms consist of high-frequency transient signals. The Wavelet Decomposition (WD) technique is used to break down transient signals to obtain the required information. To investigate the performance of the ML-based algorithms, an IEEE 33 bus system is utilized, and a fault is generated in Matlab/Simulink environment. The methodologies used for fault detection and classification are K Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The performance of the designed algorithm is assessed by employing a confusion matrix, and the results demonstrated extraordinarily high accuracy.

Keywords-machine learning; wavelet decomposition; k nearest neighbor; decision tree; support vector machine

I. INTRODUCTION

The intricacy of power system networks presents many difficulties in distributing and preserving electricity. The primary aim of the protection system is safeguarding the overall system by identifying faults and preventing malfunctions to attain adequate power supply continuity [1]. Numerous domestic and commercial clients possess equipment that is susceptible to electrical interference [2]. A good protection system must ensure system stability by protecting against all types of failures at all network locations. A system built with the current technology must be trustworthy and dependable [3]. Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) can detect a variety of typical distribution system events, including load and equipment switching transients and short circuit faults [4, 5].

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are implemented in a variety of fields, including object recognition and language recognition. CNNs are getting increasingly popular, notably in power system management and control, due to their capacity and feasibility in identifying and classifying issues that arise in

power systems [6-11]. The authors of [12] employed Support Vector Regression (SVR) to enhance the effectiveness of short-term estimation techniques based on historical electricity demand information. Authors in [13] suggest fault categorization in a distribution network by implementing an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), and authors in [14] discuss rapid fault recognition and categorization in electrical distribution networks employing a hybrid of fuzzy logic and singular entropy theory. The application of ML is not restricted to limited fields. It is also applied to the agriculture sector in detecting plant diseases [15]. The necessity for a highly precise and resilient waveform deviation tracking system in high-voltage power systems makes research into its categorization and identification using deep learning techniques a popular subject [11, 16, 17]. In [18], a hybrid strategy of Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) with Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) involved features employed as inputs. Fault recognition and categorization in microgrid employing CNNs was proposed in [19]

Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), DWT, S-Transform (ST) and statistical techniques are some examples [20-23] of ML algorithms used for fault detection and classification in distribution lines and microgrids. Usually, the extraction of the feature components is specific to the system setup and might involve continued attempts, limiting generalization [24]. DWT is widely used in the feature extraction step [25]. However, the feature extraction section and functioning approaches are unique throughout respective deployments. For example, as a functional technique for defect identification, [26] employs DWT calculated singular entropy including a set of parameters. This approach works perfectly, however, the margin to greater fault impedance wasn't addressed. In [27], DWT is employed to collect features from current signals, while Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is used to select the best wavelet configuration. For fault categorization and diagnosis in a microgrid, authors in [10, 25] propose ML and in [18] propose deep learning-based methods. To categorize the problem, the wavelet transform is utilized to extract data from current signals, which are then classified using SVM [28] and DT [12].

Techniques such as ANFIS, Fuzzy Interference Systems (FIS), Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Feedforward Neural Networks (FNNs), CNNs, and conventional fault identification with relay systems are some efficient ML techniques. ML focuses on extracting knowledge from a large set of information and provides conventional ways for problem-solving. It really can deal with a wide range of information and be employed in various situations. Furthermore, by integrating more data for training, the accuracy of ML algorithms improves. Controllers like Fuzzy logic and FIS are straightforward and use "if-then" relationships to handle problems with uncertainty. They are a generally strong candidate even though they require huge training data sets. Incorporating ANFIS assists with tunable characteristics, decreases computational time, gives quick convergence and responsiveness, but the difficulty arises when large computation is expected, which is removed by adopting ML. The ANNs, FNNs, and CNNs help predict the specific fault type and are simple to apply. Their use is simple, involving

merely a few characteristics to be adjusted, and have many applications in real-world situations, but the training procedure is rather hard for high-dimension challenges. The gradient-based back propagation approach for non-linear discrete classification tasks provides a locally optimal solution. Slow convergence is provided by ANNs in the back propagation method. The convergence is determined by the initial value of weight restrictions linked to the system. Conventional relay systems use mechanical parts to detect a fault. These mechanical parts need periodical maintenance, otherwise their performance will be degraded and it should match the ratings of the transmission or distribution line.

Figure 1 depicts the flowchart of the suggested approach, where V_a , V_b , and V_c are the three-phase voltages, I_a , I_b , and I_c are the three-phase currents, V_{COFF} and I_{COFF} are Voltage and current coefficients, and the angles between V and I are considered as inputs. These inputs are fed to the developed ML detection and classification algorithm which continuously monitors the status of inputs until a fault occurs.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the proposed methodology.

II. FAULT DETECTION ANALYSIS

WD approach is considered to detect the fault and classify it. The WD method was also utilized in [29, 30] to extract the waveform but that's a 3-level decomposition, whereas this approach uses a 6-level WD as shown in Figure 2. The fault/disturbance signal is routed via Low Pass Filters (LPFs) and High Pass Filters (HPFs) until the necessary signal for analysis is achieved. The fault/disturbance signal is decomposed at 6 levels by passing via an LPF D and an HPF A. At level 1, the signal is decimated by 2 and D1 and A1 signals are obtained. D2 and A2 are obtained by passing the A1 signal through the second stage of LPF and HPF. Again, A2 passes through filters until level 6 and the final obtained signals are D6 and A6. As a result, significant information is derived from the initial signal which has to be evaluated.

III. PHASE LOCKED LOOP

A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is a regulatory technique which produces a signal as output with a phase-matched to that of an input signal. Its block diagram is illustrated in Figure 3. In order to keep the inlet and outlet phases locked, the input and output frequencies must be steady. Using the input voltage, V_{abc} , V_d , and V_q are obtained. V_d and V_q are voltage values near the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) in the d- and q- axes respectively. The output is an approximation of the voltage phase. The suggested PLL architecture for fault identification is depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Six level wavelet-decomposition.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the PLL.

In comparison to the block diagram in Figure 2, the error signal $e(t)$ relates to the waveform deviation, while the Proportional-Integral (PI) regulator and integrator correlate to the loop filter and Voltage Controlled Oscillator (VCO) respectively. The three-phase voltages (V_a , V_b , and V_c) that are sent into the PLL are first changed to $\alpha\beta$ quantities (V_α and V_β) using Clarke's transformation. A schematic of a PQ-PLL block is demonstrated in Figure 4. The quantities are then transferred into a reference frame. Considering the proximity of the $\alpha\beta$ quantities to the reference frame, an error signal is created. The error signal is sent into a PI regulator, which controls the error to zero. The input signals are in phase with the frame of reference once the error is zero. When the PLL's output angle is in phase with the current of phase A, the error is exactly zero. When there is a transient in the system, the error signal deviates from zero. The magnitude and frequency of the deviation will vary depending on the features of the transient.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the PQ-PLL.

IV. MACHINE LEARNING

As the name implies, ML is a phrase that is used to define the field of learning algorithms. An ML model will generally have three different phases: training, validation, and real-time implementation. During the training process, the system is fed through test data with known correlations so that it can detect patterns and create predictions within the same set accurately. The validation stage is intended to assess the overall system performance utilizing similar but disjoint data, as well as previously identified responses. In terms of model training methods, ML is typically classified into four major methodologies: supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforced learning. Models which are trained on a sample with knowing labelled outcomes are referred to as supervised learning. A list of classification algorithms that have been frequently used in the literature follows.

A. Support Vector Machine

During appropriate post-fault diagnosis, a knowledge-based approach that is based on SVMs is offered. SVMs are used as an intelligence tool to detect the faulty line originating first from the substation and to determine the distance from that. SVMs are compared to radial-based neural networks in datasets that depict diverse transmission system challenges.

B. Decision Tree

The DT's design is simple, and we can easily follow the tree structure to describe how to make a conclusion. The vast scope of power system DTs has lately been discovered to be extremely effective in applications such as online dynamic safety evaluation, stability to transients, and islanding identification.

C. K Nearest Neighbor

The KNN approach is a safe, supervised ML approach utilized to tackle classification and regression issues. Faults may be detected and recognized in distance protection using the KNN method.

D. Bayesian Learner

The Bayesian classifiers, also called Naïve Bayes are statistical classifiers that estimate the probability of class membership using supervised learning techniques.

E. Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO)

Training an SVM necessitates the solving of a large quadratic programming optimization problem. SMO divides this massive quadratic programming issue into a bunch of smaller quadratic programming problems.

F. Logistic Regression

If the dependent variable is binary, logistic regression is the best regression approach to use. Like other regression studies, it is a statistical approach. The dependent variable Y in logistic regression has values of 1 and 0 for the outcomes of interest.

G. Linear Regression

The relation between both the input variables (x) and output variables (y) for linear regression is generally stated as a linear equation of the form $y = a + bx$. As a result, the aim of linear regression would be to determine the values of coefficients a and b, where a is the interception and b is the line's slope.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Considered ML Techniques

To detect the fault and classify it in the distribution network, the testing data are evaluated using SVM and DT algorithms.

- If there are little training data (less than 1000), support vector methods are often good because they are highly regularized.
- SVMs have better production results than ANNs, while they avoid the problem of over-fitting. One can use the kernel function in the SVM to solve complex problems. They can effectively handle data with higher dimensions that are linear inseparable.

For data preprocessing, WD is employed. Matlab is used to obtain various operating and fault data. A total of 2746 input samples are considered, with 70% are used for training and 30% for testing the model's performance. The training data are used to train a model that can predict how to respond to incoming new data. Table I shows the accuracy rates of the tested algorithms. The cubic SVM algorithm yielded the best accuracy rate of 87.1%.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Classifier	Accuracy
Fine tree	82.20%
Medium tree	79.40%
Coarse tree	55.20%
Linear SVM	52.50%
Quadratic SVM	78.20%
Cubic SVM	87.10%
Fine Gaussian SVM	63.60%
Medium Gaussian SVM	67.20%
Coarse Gaussian SVM	51.80%

B. Case Study

The developed ML algorithms are tested on the IEEE 33 bus system (Figure 5). The suggested fault detection and classification technique was tested using the IEEE 33 radial distribution scheme.

A fault is developed to analyze the performance of the system. Figure 6 illustrates the occurrence of an L-G fault between 0.2s and 0.4s in a three-phase voltage waveform. WD is used to assess the fault voltage signal. Figure 7 depicts the L-G fault voltage signal of a multiresolution WD. The Db6 wavelet is used for producing a 6-step decomposition. At every frequency spectrum, the rebuilt variants of every element, along with the approximation and records of the unique signal, are represented.

Fig. 5. The IEEE 33 bus system.

Fig. 6. Three-phase voltage waveforms under L-G fault occurrence.

C. Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is the most often used method for evaluating the accuracy and correctness of a classification algorithm. It also helps identifying areas where the classifier has underperformed. It can also help understanding what the classification model is doing correctly and what sorts of errors it is producing. In Figure 8, the faulty classification confusion matrix is shown. It is evident that the suggested system can classify various faults, and the prediction rate is high. Figure 9 shows the True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Negative Rate (FNR) data and the TPR value is high, which says that the model can detect faults accurately.

Precision is a measure of how accurate a classifier is. A low accuracy might also be indicative of a massive amount of False Positives. Figure 10 shows the Positive Predictive Value (PPV)

and False Discovery Rate (FDR) values. It is clear that the PPV has higher value than FDR. The rows of the confusion matrix correspond to the anticipated class, while the columns are commensurate to the actual class. The diagonal cells are commensurate to suitably categorized observations. The off-diagonal cells are commensurate to observations that were wrongly categorized.

Fig. 7. WD analysis on LG fault.

True class	FAULTTYPE	1				
	LG		185	2	6	
	LL		2	186	7	
	LLG		8	5	182	
	LLL					25 40
	LLLG					22 43
	FAULTTYPE	LG	LL	LLG	LLL	LLLG

Fig. 8. Faulty classification confusion matrix.

True class	FAULTTYPE	100%				
	LG		96%	1%	3%	
	LL		1%	96%	4%	
	LLG		4%	3%	93%	
	LLL					38% 62%
	LLLG					34% 66%
	FAULTTYPE	LG	LL	LLG	LLL	LLLG

Fig. 9. TPR and FNR values of data.

True class	FAULTTYPE	100%				
	LG		95%	1%	3%	
	LL		1%	96%	4%	
	LLG		4%	3%	93%	
	LLL					53% 48%
	LLLG					47% 52%
	FAULTTYPE	LG	LL	LLG	LLL	LLLG

Fig. 10. PPV and FDR values of data.

VI. CONCLUSION

The utilization of ML algorithms for fault categorization and identification on a three-distribution network was extensively investigated in this study. The created systems used instantaneous current and voltage data as inputs for fault detection and categorization. This paper described a waveform-based fault classification method for electrical distribution systems. WD was employed for bringing out the features from recorded wave data. The massive volume of wave data processing activity was treated effectively by carefully spreading the computing burden. ML modules identified and classified the faults. The fault classification and detection results demonstrate the efficacy of ML in categorizing and identifying faults in less time than other traditional relaying systems. The systems make use of the natural capacity for pattern classification and identification. For distance protection, ML technology is strong, effective, reliable and precise.

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A Comparative Analysis of the Mechanical Properties of Annealed PLA

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Abstract—In order to obtain better performance, 3D printed parts can be the subject of post-processing operations like sanding, gap filling, polishing, annealing, epoxy coating, and metal plating. This paper takes into consideration the most commonly used material filament for FFF technology PLA and studies the mechanical characteristics through tensile and 3-point bending tests. The obtained results reveal significantly higher values of the mechanical properties after applying a 3-hour heat treatment at 75°C, for the following combinations of parameters: layer thickness of 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20mm and infill percentage of 50%, 75%, and 100%.

Keywords—3D printing; annealing; tensile test; 3 point bending test; flexural strength

I. INTRODUCTION

The need to achieve time and cost reduction of part fabrication allowed 3D printing technology to attract scientific interest. Although FFF is a commonly used method for obtaining parts, it has several disadvantages, like low cohesion between the fused layers, low tensile properties, and low resistance to humidity. In order to improve the mechanical characteristics and increase the percentage of crystallinity in the parts obtained by FFF annealing, a post-process heat treatment can be applied [1-3]. After a 3D printed filament is heated to be extruded through a nozzle, it is often relatively rapidly cooled. Uneven cooling may cause the shrinkage of the layers, which results as the effect of inadequate heat propagation in the structure of the printed part, especially in the extremities. Therefore this process causes the tensile and compressive stresses to accumulate in the structure of the polymer.

Annealing consists in gradually heating in the oven of the samples or parts, at a temperature between the glass transition and the melting temperatures. This treatment consists of

heating and cooling slowly in order to increase the bounding crystalline structures in the polymer and redistribute the stresses inside the printed part which will give higher crystallinity, mechanical resistance, and rigidity. Recrystallized PLA products also present a huge advantage compared to amorphous products: much higher Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT). While amorphous PLA products have an HDT of 50°C, semi-crystalline PLA products have an HDT of 130°C. Although PLA can be recrystallized after processing into a product, the products shrink and significant warpage occurs during recrystallization due to the increasing crystallinity. Distortion-free semi-crystallized PLA products can only be made during the process using nucleating agents [3-5].

The aim of this paper is to compare the influence of signaling factors, such as layer thickness and percentage of filling of PLA printed parts on the tensile and bending properties with annealed PLA printed parts in terms of various printing parameters.

II. MATERIALS, METHODS AND PROCEDURES

A. Set-up Process Parameters

Although 3D printing offers a wide range of applications, it still has certain limitations that may be improved through annealing. Because 3D printed materials have an amorphous molecular structure and no precise melting point, they gradually soften until they completely melt. This feature can be used as an advantage because in the event of annealing, the molecules in the material rearrange themselves, which can result in improved mechanical characteristics, i.e. making an object stronger. The specifications collected from filament producers of the PLA material used in this study are shown in Table I. In this experimental study, three infill percentages were used: 50%, 75%, and 100%, and in order to asset the

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mechanical characteristics, tensile and flexural tests were conducted on the annealed and unannealed samples and the results were compared. For the annealing heat treatment, the samples were kept for a period of 3h at a temperature of 60°C, with a very slow cooling. All samples were cooled together in an oven.

TABLE I. 3D PRINTED SAMPLE PARAMETERS

Parameters	Material specifications
	PLA
Nozzle diameter	0.40mm
Build orientation	Flat
Top solid layers	4 layers
Bottom solid layers	4 layers
Outline/perimeters shell	3 outlines
Internal fill pattern	Lines
External fill pattern	Rectilinear
Internal infill angle offsets	180°
Extruder temperature	210°C
Heated bed temperature	60°C
Default printing speed	70mm/s
Filament diameter	1.75mm
Filament density	1.24g/cm ³

B. Sample Preparation

The samples were printed with a Raise E2 3D printer with a volume capacity of 330×240×240mm. The design of the samples, later converted in STL format, was made in Autodesk Inventor and Idea Maker software was used to adjust process parameters such as internal structure pattern, infill percentage, and layer thickness. The printing speed was set to 80mm/s in X-Y deposition direction at a deposition temperature of 200°C.

Fig. 1. Tensile and flexural sample testing on the Lloyd LRX Plus Testing Machine.

The process parameters considered as variables were the thickness of the deposited layer (0.1, 0.15, and 0.20mm) and the infill percentage (50%, 75%, and 100%). A Lloyd LRX Plus Testing Machine (Figure 1) was used for both tensile and flexural tests.

C. Tensile Tests

In order to evaluate the mechanical behavior, in the first phase, tensile tests were performed [6]. Sets of 5 specimens were printed for each of the characteristics considered in the study, with standard dimensions of 165mm length, 5mm thickness, and 13mm width.

D. Flexural Tests

This method is used to study the bending behavior and to determine the flexural strength. The test speed was set at 1mm/min and the distance between the supports was determined to be 64mm ($L=16h$, where h is the height of the sample [7]). All tests were performed at 20°C and the samples were acclimatized for 24h. The geometrical features of the samples were made with standard dimensions of 10mm width, 4mm thickness, and 80mm length.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Tensile Tests

Due to the vast volume of content resulting from the testing of a large number of samples, instead of presenting the tables with the values of all 5 determinations, it was opted to do it only for layer thickness of 0.1 and only for the ultimate tensile strength. For 0.15 and 0.20 layer thicknesses, only the values of the averages of the determinations of linear specific deformation and Young's modulus are given. The average of the 5 determinations made for each sample, is also presented in graphical form for the better understanding of the differences between the samples with heat and without heat treatment.

TABLE II. ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH TEST VALUES OF UNANNEALED PLA FOR 0.1 LAYER THICKNESS

Infill %	Ultimate tensile strength, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	24.64	24.90	24.77	24.69	24.18	24.64
75%	25.90	25.92	26.54	27.04	26.36	26.35
100%	31.92	33.82	32.25	33.74	35.82	33.51

TABLE III. ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.1 LAYER THICKNESS

Infill %	Ultimate tensile strength, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	32.06	30.42	30.61	30.23	31.76	31.02
75%	35.44	34.99	34.90	37.10	37.10	35.90
100%	42.60	43.49	41.09	43.80	48.72	43.94

As can be seen in Tables II and III, the ultimate tensile strength values of all tested samples are higher, which reveals that annealing modifies the mechanical characteristics of the parts obtained by 3D printing in a positive way. They have been increased by enriching the material's crystallinity, which carried out higher values of ultimate tensile strength, as can be graphically seen in Figures 2-4. For each value of layer thickness studied, an ascending trend can be observed with increasing infill percentage.

TABLE IV. ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH TEST VALUES OF UNANNEALED PLA FOR 0.1 LAYER THICKNESS

Mechanical characteristics	Infill percentage					
	50%		75%		100%	
	WA	A	WA	A	WA	A
Ultimate tensile strength, MPa	24.64	31.00	26.35	35.90	33.51	43.91
Linear specific deformation, %	6.47	5.52	5.73	5.01	5.64	4.85
Young's modulus, MPa	2312	2120	2423	2146	2523	2224

As can be seen in Tables IV and V, a comparison was made between the average values of samples without annealing (WA) and of the annealed (A). An increasing trend of about 30% for the values of ultimate tensile strength can be observed, regardless of the infill percentage of the samples. The linear specific deformation and Young's modulus both have a decreasing tendency.

TABLE V. ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.15 LAYER THICKNESS

Mechanical properties	Infill percentage					
	50%		75%		100%	
	WA	A	WA	A	WA	A
Ultimate tensile strength, MPa	25.94	30.04	28.04	34.77	40.07	48.05
Linear specific deformation, %	3.54	3.01	4.19	3.90	4.72	4.08
Young's modulus, MPa	2124	1931	2266	2130	2607	2528

TABLE VI. ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.2 LAYER THICKNESS

Mechanical properties	Infill percentage					
	50%		75%		100%	
	WA	A	WA	A	WA	A
Ultimate tensile strength, MPa	23.80	27.49	26.96	31.95	35.58	41.63
Linear specific deformation, %	3.76	3.45	3.71	3.52	3.59	3.31
Young's modulus, MPa	1813	1586	2132	2076	2248	2187

Fig. 2. Ultimate tensile strength variation of 0.1 layer thickness for varying infill percentage.

Fig. 3. Ultimate tensile strength variation of 0.15 layer thickness for varying infill percentage.

Fig. 4. Ultimate tensile strength variation of 0.2 layer thickness for varying infill percentage.

The average of the determinations made for the values from Tables IV-VI, is being presented in graphical form in order to highlight the differences between the A and the WA samples.

B. Flexural Tests

As with the tensile tests, 5 test samples were performed for each of the 3 infill percentages of 50%, 75%, and 100%. As can be seen in the comparative graphical representations of Figures 5-7, the values of maximum flexural strength are clearly higher in the case of annealed samples. As in the tensile tests, there is a tendency for values to increase by about 15% for 0.1 and 0.15mm layer thickness [8]. The values obtained for 0.2mm layer thickness are lower, although here too there is an upward trend.

Fig. 5. Maximum flexural strength comparison between PLA and annealed PLA for 0.1mm layer thickness.

Fig. 6. Maximum flexural strength comparison between PLA and annealed PLA for 0.15mm layer thickness.

Fig. 7. Maximum flexural strength comparison between PLA and annealed PLA for 0.2mm layer thickness.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this paper was to highlight the variation of mechanical characteristics of annealed PLA 3D printed materials, with different parameters of the technological process.

When comparing the average values of samples with and without annealing, an increased trend of about 30% for the values of ultimate tensile strength can be observed, regardless of the infill percentage of the samples. Both linear specific deformation and Young's modulus have a decreasing tendency. Similar results have been obtained in other studies, for example a 30.25% increase in the ultimate strength compared to the as-printed samples was found in [9-11]. An annealing of 1h duration resulted in 24% increase in ultimate strength in [12].

Maximum flexural strength values are clearly higher in the case of annealed samples. There is a tendency for values to increase by about 15%, very similar to the 11%–17% obtained in [13].

Several signal factors such as deposition style and orientation and also raster gap and width can influence the values of the mechanical characteristics of the 3D printed samples without annealing. Also, soaking time and cooling rate can lead to different values for the heat treated parts. So, having taken into account all these aspects, the differences between the values in this article and the values from other studies [8, 10, 11, 14] can be explained. Future work will focus on the way the main factors of the annealing process influence the main mechanical properties of 3D printed parts.

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Overview of Green Roof Technology as a Prospective Energy Preservation Technique in Arid Regions

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Abstract-Concerns about climate change and rising energy demands have grown as a result of fast population rise and global industrialization. The construction industry has a huge impact on the energy and environmental sectors, accounting for about 40% of global energy consumption and a large portion of overall territorial emissions. There is a need for a shift in mindset when it comes to energy usage, as well as enhanced energy efficiency approaches and radical energy efficiency initiatives. As an energy-saving solution, the green roof, also known as the living roof has suitability and environmental benefits on many levels, while also strengthening aesthetic features and provoking structural innovation. Moreover, drought-prone areas, e.g. Saudi Arabia, have significant household energy demands. The Saudi building sector consumes more than 76% of the country's total electric power generation. As a result, the purpose of this study is to provide a general overview of living roof technology and its potential in Saudi Arabia as an energy-saving strategy. An overview of the building envelope, the impact of cladding design considerations on power usage, the benefits of a living roof, cost-benefit analysis, green policies, and examples from other countries are included in the paper. Other environmental benefits, besides the energy-saving potential of living roofs, were shown to boost the quantitative benefits of the living roof idea. A more detailed study is needed, among other things, to evaluate the energy-saving potential of living roofs based on the weather of various locations.

Keywords-sustainability; energy performance; living roof; energy saving potential; building insulation

I. INTRODUCTION

The world's growing economy has inevitably resulted in increased energy demands for corporate, industrial, residential, and transportation purposes [1], while concerns regarding the environmental impact of increased energy demands have surfaced. Some climate-related issues, such as zero-energy buildings, global warming, and greenhouse gas emissions, are gaining increasing attention [2-3] According to [4], energy consumption went up drastically from 4,674 Mton in 1971 to 8,918 Mton in 2011, with non-renewable fuels including oil, natural gas, and coal accounting for the majority of this increase [5]. According to statistics, the Middle East consumes

the most energy, with 33 of 4,674 million tons of oil equivalent (0.7%) in 1971 and 224 million tons of oil equivalent (4.8%) in 2011. Fossil fuels are the region's principal energy source. In 2015, almost 200 countries signed a climate deal in Paris under the auspices of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in a serious effort to phase out the use of fossil fuels. As a result, it is vital that the rapidly developing GCC countries invest what they have in order to develop energy sources that will be sufficient in the long-term. When it comes to overall development and economic size, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is the largest country in the Middle East, and its housing sector has seen an increase in energy demand from 2000 to 2014, that is estimated to be over 100%. According to [6], buildings that are used for residential purposes consume almost half of the total energy output. As a result, the construction industry has a significant demand for energy. To satisfy this rising need for energy, better ways must be developed to lower the amount of energy consumed by buildings, which can be accomplished by utilizing living roofs to improve energy efficiency [7]. Apart from the positive effects on the environment and its long-term viability, the usage of living roofs improves the architectural and aesthetic appeal of buildings. This approach of energy saving has been recognized internationally [8, 9].

The living roof offers the advantage of maintaining a balanced environment and temperature stability [10]. However, despite its benefits in terms of energy saving, it is not as extensively used in the high-energy-demanding Middle East as one might expect. This could be due to the lack of scholarship and high upkeep costs [11]. The living roof has received commercial interest because it offers answers to some of the most pressing issues regarding energy and the environment. Furthermore, an architectural model of a structure in the Middle East has not been developed with a clear plan on how to apply a living roof [5]. It is clear that the Middle East has not received adequate empirical research on this topic. As a result, a full study through research is required in order to investigate the possibilities of the living roof technology in relation to the hot Saudi weather in order to have a strong grasp of the living roof as a response to the topic of energy consumption.

II. METHODOLOGY

To achieve the purpose of this paper, extended literature review was conducted that looked into the use of living roof technology around the world and the long-term viability of its use in the desert climate of Saudi Arabia. The study would be of tremendous importance to the arid regions because it attempts to examine solutions to reduce high energy usage and its hazardous environmental consequences on structures.

An assessment is provided that contains a broad description of the building envelope system and the effects of envelope design considerations on the structure's energy consumption. The advantages of a living roof, the estimated costs, and the green regulations from sampled countries are provided. Finally, the article draws some conclusions and offers some recommendations regarding the arid regions.

III. THE BUILDING ENVELOPE

A. Overview

Buildings consume roughly one third of global energy and nearly 40% of all assets used [13, 14]. The bad and good ecological effects of the technology on buildings have been discussed. Authors in [11] indicated that the yearly direct and indirect ecological effects of the industry of building comprise 42% energy use, 40% emissions to the atmosphere, 30% unprocessed use of materials, and 25% water consumption. In addition, the energy supplied is less than the demanded energy due to population growth and globalization. Therefore, efforts are ongoing to conserve and maximize energy [15]. The reduction of the overall energy use in the course of buildings' life span through good use of the building envelope is one of the efforts employed [16]. A building envelope shields a building's interior environment from the outside hostile environment. Thermal comfort (temperature and humidity control), visual comfort (natural light regulation), and acoustic comfort (noise control to acceptable levels) are a few of the building envelope's tasks [3]. The building envelope's responses to heating, cooling, ventilation, and regular lighting requirements are critical in evaluating the envelope's efficiency in reducing energy usage. In this context, building envelope materials with high evapotranspiration and thermal emissivity are good passive cooling energy demand reduction solutions. The overall thermal gain to a building is governed by the U-value, which is controlled by the materials used and the design of various elements of the building envelope, and can range from 40 to 45% of the total heat load [17]. The primary goal is to reduce transmission of heat loads in order to save considerable amounts of energy. Authors in [16] looked into the impact of construction materials, thermal insulation, and envelope layer layout as solutions for lowering building energy usage. The heat resistance of a roof can be increased by $0.4\text{m}^2\text{K/W}$ for every 10cm increase in thickness when the substrate layer is made of clay [18]. In [19], the effects of different thicknesses of building insulation on thermal performance in hot, dry areas, were evaluated. When thermal shielding is installed on the exterior of the building envelope, the study found that significant energy savings can be achieved. In their investigations of level roof surfaces in the harsh weather of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, authors in [6] advised

the use of lighter surface colors for roofs. Authors in [20] assessed up to 6 distinct types of roof structures, in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. To improve heat efficiency, the insulating layer should be placed closer to the inside surface of the roof structure, according to this study.

B. Variables in Envelope Design and their Effect on Energy Consumption

1) Insulation

The most significant aspect in decreasing building energy use and ensuring acceptable indoor environmental quality is heat insulation [18]. Due to its thermal qualities, the exterior of the building envelope is vulnerable to the outside environment, posing a significant danger of heat gain or loss [21]. Thermal insulation reduces the need for heating and cooling and the risk of fire [22]. With walls and roofs forming practically a unitary portion of the building's envelope, the probability of absorbing or losing heat increases, thus, the envelope should have some heat insulation [5]. Thermal insulation prevents heat from moving through channels of conduction, convection, and/or radiation. Climate, environmental impact, Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), thermal conductivity of the components, economic implications, specific heat capacity, fire resistance, sound impacts, density, and other factors are all taken into account when selecting the appropriate insulating materials [23].

2) Thermal Mass

Thermal mass is essential for reducing building energy costs, which can be accomplished by making HVAC systems smaller. Thermal mass also reduces peak load shift conditions and total heat yield or loss, resulting in a smaller HVAC system and lower overall building energy expenditures [2]. The absorption and subsequent release of heat as needed is characterized by the thermal mass (also known as thermal lag). This is because the materials need time to absorb, store, and then release heat [24]. Thermal mass is best placed on the first floor for easy heat release and absorption since it absorbs and then releases heat effortlessly [25].

3) Lighting

Climate consideration in eco-friendly design has numerous advantages. Regarding lighting, orientation is important. The requirement for electric lighting can be considerably reduced by using proper building architecture and orientation while also boosting occupant satisfaction, which can be achieved by varying the direction of apertures [26]. The planned space use, the lighting equipment required, the occupants' living style, and window placement in relation to the sun's path, are all important considerations in lighting design. Energy-saving bulbs, smart technologies, dimmer switches, automation techniques, motion detectors, and Compact Fluorescent Lights (CFLs) can all help minimize lighting energy use [27].

4) Orientation

Orientation is an important consideration in building design, because it ensures the optimum use of solar energy depending on a site's geographical axes and the earth's axis. When the envelope's thermal performance needs to be improved, the conductive heat flow must be restricted. To do so, the building's form factor, also known as the building shape

[28], is taken into account. Because of the forms' intricacy, they may produce leaks by exposing a portion of the structure to the outside environment. As a result, compatibility must be established in order to reduce surface area and thus reduce the risk of heat absorption or loss. Corners should be avoided as much as possible by maintaining tight compactness [25]. The window-to-wall area ratio should be examined in order to create a window that is suited for a specific orientation. The floor-to-envelope area ratio should also be investigated in order to increase floor area relative to the envelope area. To fit the windows, the best elevation must be chosen. When compared to heights in the east and west, a rising window-to-wall area ratio can favor the southern elevation [6]. Outside, shading mechanisms should also be built to minimize solar gain during the summer and ensuring it during the winter when the sun is low [6]. To reduce solar energy acquisition in the summer, minimum window-to-wall area ratio could be situated on the eastern and western elevations. Because it is not exposed to direct sunlight, the north elevation is important for daylighting [29].

5) Occupants' Contribution

Depending on the type and intensity of occupant activities, vapor discharge has a significant impact on the energy usage of a residential building [30]. Occupant actions, according to a study conducted in the Netherlands, can result in a 4.2% increase in power use, whereas individual residents' behaviors may have a significant impact on overall energy usage [2].

IV. THE LIVING ROOF

A. Overview

According to [31, 32], living roofs are becoming more popular globally. The living roof is a construction made of composite materials [18]. Soil is transported onto a roof coated with a waterproofing layer [23]. The inner source (root) obstacles are above them, accompanied by a runoff cover (with adaptable profile element) that directs excess release to roof drains and provides water storage for planting during dry periods. A living roof can also be built by hoisting previously established plants with mechanical means. The growing medium has the benefit of being easily removed in the event of leaching or maintenance work due to its off-site prefabrication [33]. Living roofs have specific sections designed to keep the roof drainage system in good working order. Roots and natural materials must be kept out of the drainage pathway to ensure that it functions properly [34]. Living roof frameworks also improve the total insulating value of the roof system because they are used in conjunction with the basic material used in traditional roof systems. Living roofs have many advantages, including cost saving, energy conservation, and aesthetic appeal [11]. The substratum layer of the living roof plays a big role in this [35]. The plant layer, for example, has some aesthetic value and might also be used as a green product source [36]. Physical qualities of plants have an impact on their contribution to the environment [37]. A study of the ability of 5 plant species (sedum pachyphyllum, sedum clavatum, sedum spurium, disphyma crassifolium, and carpobrotus modestus) to withstand multiple dry period treatments (wet and non-wet) discovered that a living roof layer of diverse plant species was

more effective in terms of its capacity to withstand multiple dry period treatments (wet and non-wet) [38].

B. Advantages of the Living Roof Technology

1) Energy Saving Potential

Living roofs are designed to reduce the amount of direct and dispersed radiation striking the roof, saving large amounts of energy [23, 39]. Incorporating living roof technology into buildings resulted in a total energy decrease of 17%, according to a research conducted in Jordan [1]. Similarly, based on the soil density and thermal pressure, a study comparing the energy saving potential of living roofs with typical roof systems in Egypt's desert climate indicated that yearly power savings of 15-32% can be reached [40]. Energy savings of 48% for retrofitted/insulated roofs (U-value of $1.99\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) and 7% for moderated insulation (U-value of $0.8\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$) were discovered in an analysis conducted in Athens using TRNSYS software [41]. In schools and buildings with living roofs in Mediterranean climates, significant energy savings between 6 and 49% have been seen [42, 43].

2) Influence of Living Roofs on Indoor Environmental Quality

The energy savings from a living roof contribute directly to lower interior temperature maintenance cost [44]. According to a study in Germany that compared living roof technology to a common roofing structure, living roofs improve the internal climate of buildings [45]. It was found that living roofs reduce the temperature of the roof top and improve the inside environment of building structures.

3) Environmental Benefits of the Living Roof

Authors in [25] revealed that storm water management is one of the environmental advantages of living roofs. Rainwater runoff from vegetated roofs could be reduced by up to 40%. According to a study conducted in Singapore [5], living roof technology was able to lower the maximum flow by 65%, while saving overall runoff by 11.6% during peak strength rainfall (1mm/min). The study also found that living roofs can reduce surface heat by 7.3 degrees, extending the life of roof membranes. When factory and car emissions travel through the plant foliage/leaf index, air pollution is minimized, particularly for extensive living roof systems (trees and shrubs) [37]. Living roof technology may be used to enrich urban areas, giving a home for birds and insects while also maintaining indigenous species. Living roofs also have the benefit of reducing the heat island effect. On the temperature differential between position roofing and traditional roof surfaces, a medium of 20°C was recorded in [34]. Vegetated envelopes are more favorable in hot and sunny locations, according to [17], because the temperature of urban heat can be reduced.

4) Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

Without a cost-benefit analysis, the benefits of the proposed sustainable measures cannot be assured. A plan that has a higher cost than its benefit cannot be considered feasible. The cost-benefit analysis is a method for weighing the benefits of various solutions while accounting for the total cost of implementation. It is the basis for making decisions that benefit the economy [12]. The Net Present Value (NPV) is a common method for determining a system's current benefit after it has

been constructed and utilized for a period of time [46]. If the NPV of an investment is greater than zero, it could be realized. When making a comparison of various options, choose the one that has the largest NPV. The following equation is used to calculate the NPV [47, 48]:

$$NPV = -C_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{F_t}{(1+P)^t} \quad (1)$$

where t refers to the time period, which is commonly calculated annually, F_t is the net cash flow for year t , calculated using the formula $F_t = B_t - C_t$. The advantages or benefits accumulated for the year t are represented by B_t . The cost outflows for year t are represented by C_t . C_0 denotes the initial investment (including all funds spent on items as well as installations). The cost of capital is denoted by the letter P . The number n denotes the number of years for which a financial evaluation needs to be done.

5) Cost of Green Roof Installation

The value of a living roof system is determined by several elements, including the growing medium, material layer, seepage structure, barrier or palings use, and the quantity of plants. According to [49], the low-cost, largest living roof costs \$10 per square foot (0.09m²), whereas in-depth living roofs cost \$25 per square foot [50, 51]. In Germany, living roof prices range from \$8 to \$15 per m². Because of the manufacturers' business interests and experience, the cost in the United States may be higher [52]. Local sources in Saudi Arabia estimate the cost to be \$9 per square foot. As a result, it is possible to estimate that the prices will range from \$8 to \$25 per square foot.

6) Maintenance Cost

The maintenance cost makes up a major amount of the total cost of such a system. The type of vegetation utilized determines the cost of maintaining living roofs, which is higher in the first year of operation as the living roofs mature. These prices might range from \$0.75 to \$1.50 per square foot [48]. Local costs are expected to be roughly \$0.23 per square foot in Saudi Arabia.

7) Cost Due to Increased Property Value

Property and company owners gain from regular landscaping since their properties' market values rise, although no direct link has been shown between the presence of green rooftops and the property value. Anyhow, if a structure is located near a forest spread, its market value could be improved by 7.1% [53]. The purchase of trees/greenery could improve the overall value of properties by 15% to 25% [53].

8) Cost Due to Longevity Benefit

Green rooftops have an average lifespan of 40 to 55 years [12], while regular rooftops have an average lifespan of just approximately 20 years [25]. The cost of re-roofing a conventional roof is projected to be up to \$160 per m² [5]. Furthermore, the ability of diverse plants to convert oxygen to carbon dioxide varies. Previous studies have found that 1 hectare of living roofs may remove up to 72kg to 85kg of

pollutants [55]. The cost of reducing carbon emissions can be as high as \$20 per ton [54].

9) Reduced Cost as a Result of Better Air Quality Reducing the Effects of Urban Heat Islands

Green rooftops are viewed as both an air pollution remover and a source of innovation [55]. The quality of the air is defined by measuring dust, particles, and nitrates (NO₂), with a cost of \$3375/ton gained owing to NO_x gas losses in the atmosphere [56]. In addition, natural habitat creation and protection are critical in reducing the negative effects of urban environments [57]. Green rooftops use plants and soil to replace traditional rooftops, attracting insects such as butterflies, birds, bugs, and honey bees [58]. In the summer, the combination of dull surfaces and the lack of vegetation cause increase in urban air temperature [59]. Because of the use of HVAC systems, an increase in temperature causes an increase in energy demand [59]. Authors in [60] discovered that for every 1°C increase in temperature, power demand increases by 2% to 4% in 6 U.S. metropolitan areas. Heat island effect increases power consumption by up to 1GW - 1.5GW annually in the Los Angeles Basin [44].

10) Global Policies on Living Roofs (Case Studies)

Several cities give incentives in the form of grants to property owners who want to establish green spaces on their roofs, in order to encourage both commercial and residential owners to undertake arrangements for more green spaces on their roofs. Singapore, for example, has developed a thorough program to promote rooftop greening in order to fulfill a target of 50 hectares of new Skyrise Greenery Area by 2030. The creation of a roof floor incentive program, the allocation of city gardens, and technical consultation are all part of this [61]. The program also includes a monetary recompense for sustainable landscaping of current building structures in regions with a higher need for green spaces, and remuneration for new construction project designation of living roofs [49]. Portland, located in the northwest of the USA, favors living roof strategies due to the benefits of sustainably managing rainfall [11]. Germany discovered that light modifications of green rooftops can assist energy conservation. Green roofing is now used in many German cities. This strategy is backed up by accepted design standards and legal backing. As of 2005, Germany had planted 13.5 million m² of roof spaces [54, 62]. Munich, the Bavarian regional capital (Germany), is implementing a variety of living roof-related initiatives [63]. Such approaches include land use management rules, start-up grants for voluntary living roof construction, and a reduction in storm water levies [64]. Living roofs are particularly well-known in Munich. Thanks to a 14-year-old legislation requiring all appropriate roofs of any flat with a surface area greater than 100m² to be landscaped. Japan began with a light-hearted stimulus program that included free consultancy services. Following that, a subsidy program was implemented, resulting in the installation of 7000m² of living roofs. Worries about the environment's impact on buildings led the authorities to enact a regulation requiring construction works greater than 10,000 square feet or government buildings bigger than 25,000 square feet to landscape the 20% of the roof surface, or risk annual fines [24]. From these instances, it is clear that many cities are

employing a variety of hybrid strategies to promote living roofs, even though there are differences in nature and equipment, as well as institutional inequities. The ultimate purpose of city living roof initiatives is to maximize any positive impact by utilizing human and financial resources as efficiently as possible.

11) Building Energy Modeling Programs (BEMPs)

Computer simulation is a highly valuable and cost-effective technique for estimating and analyzing energy usage and overall building efficiency [65]. Since 1960, hundreds of Building Energy Modeling Programs (BEMPs) have been developed and implemented all over the world [66]. Well-known BEMPs include ESP-r, TAS, TRNSYS, BEopt, ECOTECT, IES Virtual Environment, eQUEST, and Design Builder [67, 68]. AED is becoming increasingly reliant on technologies that can answer particular queries during the design phase. Furthermore, AED can predict a building's thermal behavior before it is constructed [65]. It can model energy costs in new and old buildings in their existing state, determining the best way to use energy. A non-technical profession would benefit from an essay detailing how to use software interface. It should include enough depth to conduct research [69]. To take advantage of the benefits of other programs via data-sharing file formats, inter-software operability is also required [70]. It is vital for credibility to demonstrate conformance with criteria used in similar building performance studies. It is vital to utilize an appropriate instrument in performance analysis to ensure the functioning and capabilities of software [14]. There are a variety of software options available, each with its own set of features. The researcher's user choice condition suggests its capabilities to be toned down [68].

12) Software Package Comparison

Many simulation programs have been developed over the few previous decades. This is evident from the US Department of Energy's homepage dedicated to generating energy simulation software tools, which lists over 240 such programs. The tools on the site range from research-grade software to commercial versions. Many studies and comparative assessments were conducted to analyze the elements and capabilities of some of the instruments in this group. Authors in [71] proposed evidence-based validation, comparative study, and analytical verification as methods for ensuring the accuracy of construction energy devices. Following a series of testing and validations, Energy Plus was found to work with the DOE-2.1E, ESP-r, and BLAST simulation tools. Authors in [66] used Energy Plus to construct and test a VRV air conditioning system that is empirically connected to a new simulation unit. The monitored simulation data revealed a total energy cooling and utilization range of 25.19 to 28.3%. By comparing the building energy performance simulation program to other readily available building energy programs, a complete assessment of the program's capabilities may be established [72]. The comparison is based on general modeling descriptions, zone loads, building envelopes, HVAC systems, economic analysis, emissions, electrical systems, and electrical equipment. Some of the most commonly used comparison programs include Bsim, BLAST, DeST, Ener-Win, Energy –

10, EnergyPlus, eQuest, IDA ICE, ESP-r, IES VE>, TRACE, TRNSYS, Tas, SUNREL, HEED, PowerDomus, and HAP. Authors in [72] investigated 6 building performance simulation tools in order to provide early design support to architects. A set of criteria was used to evaluate the simplicity of use of numerous tools. Furthermore, none of the tools were deemed appropriate for use by architects. According to them, DesignBuilder stood out because it provides a graphical user interface for EnergyPlus, a well-known energy modeling program. Authors in [67] used an online poll to assess the usability of 10 distinct architectural tools. HEED, eQuest, IES /VE, GreenBuilding Studio, ECOTECT, Design Builder, Energy – 10, DOE 2.1E, Sketch up plug-ins, and EnergyPlus each had 249 valid results when these tools were considered. The program was evaluated on its usability, information management (UIM), and connection with the Intelligent Design Knowledge Base (IIBK). The study found that IIBK had a stronger preference for tool interfaces than UIM.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A description of living roof technology as a means of energy preservation is provided in this paper. The goal of the literature review is to emphasize the theoretical foundations for the subject as well as the potential benefits and economic implications of green roofing solutions. The literature review demonstrated that one of the most important benefits is determining the level of sustainability required by the construction industry in hot and arid climates. Furthermore, when alternative software was examined, it was found that DesignBuilder and Energy Plus have greater capability for analyzing various energy conservation measures, including the green roofing model. The proper paradigm for living roof implementation is in the design of buildings with decked roofs, as is the case in Saudi Arabia. Hot weather and energy cost may pose challenges for the implementation of sustainable techniques such as living roofs, but a gradual and steady shift is underway. According to Saudi Vision 2030, a recently created strategic policy framework, attempts are being made to eliminate more than 200 billion Saudi Riyals in energy subsidies by 2030. However, the advancement of living roof technology depends on a number of factors, one of which is the importance of living roof policies. Results and case studies from various cities around the world show that a lot of work was put into advocating ideas for adapting and modifying green roofing to meet local conditions.

Aside from the energy saving potential of living roofs, there are other, environmental advantages in their utilization, such as heat island abatement, habitat creation, increased property value, improved air quality, increased roof membrane longevity, and reduced carbon emissions.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following suggestions are provided to guide future research:

- Comprehensive investigation into the energy-saving possibilities based on meteorological data from diverse places will go a long way toward proving the claim of the prospective advantages this technology could provide.

- It is necessary to perform natural plant and horticultural studies on native species, as well as their ability to live in hot, humid situations. This will aid in determining the dependability of various plant species in terms of their ability to survive.
- The adoption of such sustainable techniques will be aided by establishing living roof design and construction guidelines for new buildings and retrofits.
- Policies should be developed to accelerate the adoption of such sustainable techniques, particularly for large-scale construction projects.

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CYANanobot: Miniaturized Boat-Assisted Data Acquisition for Automated Cyanide Monitoring in Wastewater Using Optical Nano-Sensors

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Abstract-Cyanide contamination in water and wastewater is ubiquitous, particularly in gold mining industries, where cyanide is commonly used to extract gold. It is constantly being monitored by collecting samples which are analyzed in the laboratory using traditional cyanide analysis, which requires complicated instrumentation, skilled analysts, and expensive equipment. Using the gold nanoparticle (AuNP)-decorated paper-based sensor employing Whatman Filter Paper (WFP) as a substrate, an automated process for cyanide monitoring with the aid of an assembled and improvised remotely controlled miniature boat was developed. The technology is equipped with a filtration system with automated water sample collection and preparation with an automatic paper sensor dispenser. Images of the collected wastewater samples are taken at different time intervals and are analyzed on their respective color spaces based on 8 mathematical models, each predicting the cyanide level of the water sample. The predictions are compared to the actual Ion-Selective Electrode (ISE) measurement, and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values were calculated. The predictions at 165s using the Hue, Saturation, Value (HSV) color space exhibited the highest R^2 of 0.85 and the lowest RMSE of 3.80 parts per million (ppm) with an average error of 3.40ppm. The predictions are sent to a database using Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM). The results suggest that the CYANanobot technology facilitates fast analysis time, circumvents the frequent instrument calibration, reduces operating costs, minimizes exposure to toxic

cyanide-containing samples, and reduces person-to-person interaction.

Keywords-cyanide; gold nanoparticle (AuNPs)-decorated paper-based sensor; remote-controlled boat; automated cyanide monitoring; image processing; GSM

I. INTRODUCTION

Issues of cyanide contamination in water and wastewater are ubiquitous, mainly in gold mining industries, where cyanide is commonly used to extract gold [1]. Typically, cyanide mining waste materials are contained in the tailings pond, where necessary treatment is done [2]. Monitoring the free cyanide concentration is conducted by collecting water samples and analyzing them in the laboratory using optical methods, electrochemical methods, mass spectrometry, gas chromatography, titrimetric methods, or amperometric procedures [3-5]. All these methods require skilled personnel to do the analysis on-site, however, restricted by the new normal brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, automation of this process in the mining industry is deemed necessary. Likewise, the conventional cyanide analysis, which requires additional sample preparation, apart from sample collection, needs to be revitalized using a sensitive, low-cost, and fast analysis using a paper-based nano-sensor [6].

Reliable cyanide detection was demonstrated by using the developed gold nanoparticle (AuNP)-decorated paper-based sensor using WFP. The sensor can give semi-quantitative detection as low as 0.05ppm, causing discoloration of the sensor from reddish-purple to white due to the formation of the water-soluble gold-cyano complex, which is known to be dependent on the amount of CN⁻ in the sample [7]. Smartphones to capture images and analyze the chemical concentration [8-11], a paper-based sensing chip [12] and electrochemical sensor [13] have been used to quantify the color changes of paper sensors.

This research seeks to automate cyanide monitoring of wastewater in a mining site using the developed Whatman Filter Paper- Gold Nanoparticles (WFP-AuNPs) sensor from on-site wastewater sample collection and preparation. Automated CN detection is conducted using the WFP-AuNPs sensor through digital image-based colorimetry, subsequent collection and analysis of data, and data storage. Console-operated software and computer vision algorithms were introduced to provide a qualitative, quantitative, and reproducible readout at a low cost for flexibility and an easy quantification system. Also, an Internet of Things (IoT)-based system was employed to transmit the acquired cyanide concentration data, other water parameters, and location, offering advantages over traditional methods [14-18]. The module was assembled in an improvised miniature boat that can be controlled remotely to traverse from one monitoring point to another within the sampling site. This remote access capability saves operating time and resources. The waterproof casing of the boat protects the assembly from external disturbances such as rain and winds. This study enables a more feasible and faster analysis, decreased human exposure and labor risk, and improves working efficiency.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Figure 1 indicates the system overview of the study. The system architecture shows the details of the system components and operation.

Fig. 1. System overview.

III. METHODOLOGY AND FLOWCHART

This section presents the workflow and procedures conducted in the study, as shown in Figure 2. Boat navigation and movement to predetermined sampling sites are conducted with a remote-control system. The user handles the transmitter, and the receiver is placed on the boat. When the boat arrives at

the site where the user wants to test, the user flips a switch that triggers the start of the sensor module. The location coordinates are also sent to the microprocessor. The sensor module is responsible for the automated cyanide level testing process. It uses a microprocessor that is serially connected to a microcontroller that controls water sampling, water preparation, water dispensing, triggering the analyzer module, data transmission, and water discharge, in that order, through a plurality of pumps and motors, a camera, and a GSM module. The sensor module and analyzer module comprise the sensing system.

Fig. 2. System architecture and flow.

IV. HARDWARE, SOFTWARE, AND SYSTEM INTEGRATION

A. Navigation System

The miniature boat was shaped into a monohull structure using 1-inch styrofoam frames, smoothed and coated with glazing putty, fiber cloth, and body filler. The mini-boat was tested for its buoyancy and its navigational control. The buoyancy test was conducted in a private beach resort by gradually adding loads to the boat. The navigation system used is an FS-16 2.4GHz 6-channel RC Transmitter as its controller bind with an FS-16 2.4GHz 6-Channel Receiver. The Receiver was connected to two 150A brushless waterproof Electronic Speed Controllers (ESCs) that control two brushless motors, each attached with motor thrusters at different channels. Another receiver channel was connected to the microcontroller of the sensor module to trigger the automated cyanide level testing at the chosen sample site.

B. Sensor Module

The sensor module was framed to maximize space while using local materials. Its layout is shown in Figure 3. When the microprocessor of the sensor module, a Raspberry Pi 4, receives the trigger signal from the navigation system, the microprocessor sends a trigger signal serially to the Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller. The microcontroller then starts the automated cyanide level testing process. A 3D printed built-in filtration module placed on the rear of the boat, fully submerged to the water source during testing, is connected to the water sampling system and contains a peristaltic pump and a beaker, through a silicon tube, as shown in Figure 4. After priming the tube, the pump then dispenses 50ml of water sample to the beaker.

Fig. 3. Layout of the sensor module.

Fig. 4. Front view of the sensor module.

The pH of the collected water sample is then measured. As the previous laboratory pH test result on the water sample indicated a pH level below 11 and the minimum pH level required for cyanide testing is 11, a consistent volume of 1.5ml of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) is added to the water sample. The solution was mixed with the water sample by pumping air using a diaphragm pump. The slider system in Figure 4 is a rack and pinion attached to a platform and a ball-bearing slider controlled by the stepper motor in Figure 2. Figure 5 shows the

slider system's positions at different stages in the testing process. First, the slider system retracts to the position shown in Figure 5(a), aligning the oblong-shaped hole in the platform to the paper sensor holder cartridge. The paper sensor holder cartridge contains two stacks of paper sensor holders, cylinders trimmed by a spherical cap, as shown in Figure 6, with circular AuNPs-integrated paper sensors in each holder. The paper sensor holders are 3D printed using black polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) to capture the edges of the paper sensors better as it turns white. These are stored in a cartridge with 3 segments, 2 are stacked with paper sensor holders, and the middle segment contains no paper sensor holders but has a hole in the base, as shown in Figure 7. The cartridge also has a servo motor attached with a semicircle wiper with a hole that can fit a paper sensor holder. As the wiper moves from left to right and vice versa, a single paper sensor holder falls into the hole and gets pushed into the hole on the base of the middle segment of the cartridge. The hole is aligned to the hole in the platform in a position demonstrated in Figure 5(a). With a paper sensor holder, the platform is positioned as illustrated in Figure 5(b). A silicon tube connected to the dispensing peristaltic dispenses 1ml of the prepared water sample to the paper sensor holder.

Fig. 5. The slider system positioned at different stages in testing. (a) Platform aligned cartridge, (b) platform at dispensing tube, (c) platform at imaging station, (d) platform at dispensing area.

Fig. 6. A paper sensor holder.

Fig. 7. Paper sensor holder cartridge.

The platform moves into the position shown in Figure 5(c). The image acquisition chamber in Figure 3 is spray-painted with black paint to block the ambient light that might affect the lighting during the data gathering from entering the box. Since the box was completely black and dark, a LED light strip with

a diffuser was installed inside the box to ensure consistent lighting during the data gathering process. These light sources are turned on before the platform arrives at the spot aligned to the camera. Temperature and humidity are also recorded and trigger the analyzer module. After receiving the predicted cyanide level, the light source is turned off and the data acquired from the process (cyanide level, pH, temperature, humidity, and location coordinates) are saved in the internal storage of the microprocessor and sent through SMS and to the IoT analytics platform Thingspeak. A line graph is shown for each parameter, with each point showing the value and the time the value was received.

The platform moves into a position described in Figure 5(d), where the paper sensor holders and water are dispensed. Another pump pumps the water from the discharging container back to the water source. The user then moves to the next sampling site. Before the 50ml water sample is collected at the second site, the tubes and beakers are rinsed by repeatedly intaking and discharging water from the water source 3 times. This is done by introducing the water from the second site to the sensor module.

C. Analyzer Module

An algorithm was designed to predict the cyanide level using images taken of the paper sensor at specific time intervals. Figure 8 shows the algorithm.

Fig. 8. Analyzer module algorithm.

Eight mathematical models were tested in this study. Each model has a specific time interval and color space. The model

names are 135sec_HSV, 165sec_HSV, 195sec_HSV, 240sec_HSV, 270sec_Lab, 315sec_HSV, 555sec_HSV, and 555sec_Lab.

A reference image was taken immediately as the paper sensor holder was pushed to the image acquisition chamber. This reference image was used for all models. At the time specified by the model name, an image will be taken and stored in the internal storage of the Raspberry Pi 4. A total of 8 images were captured, including the reference image, as the last two models use the same time interval. The stored images were used by a circle detection algorithm. This python script detects a paper sensor in the picture after applying a mask on the image using Circle Hough Transform. The circle was then cropped, and the Region Of Interest (ROI) was identified. An example is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Detection of paper sensors in the image. (a) Raw image, (b) binary mask, (c) the masked image.

Each paper sensor image's Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) was extracted in different color spaces. The extracted values for the images taken after the time duration in specific color space were then subtracted with the reference image's MPI in the same color space. The resulting value shows the change of MPI of the paper sensor after the time interval. The 8 MPI values were then fit to their corresponding mathematical model resulting in a prediction of the cyanide level of the water sample. The predictions were then sent to the microprocessor of the sensor module for storage and sending. The predicted cyanide level was also compared to the actual cyanide concentration measured using an Ion-Selective Electrode (ISE).

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Navigation System

The navigation system was tested in a pool near the campus. The boat's buoyancy was tested by gradually adding load while the boat was afloat. About 80kg can be safely carried by the boat.

Fig. 10. Buoyancy and stability test of the mini-boat.

The remote-control system was also tested in the private pool. The boat was smoothly navigated with the controls. The expected speed power from the motors was delivered. Overall, the remote-control testing has been successful, particularly the differential method.

For two consecutive weeks, the team conducted the actual testing in a mining tailing pond. The boat floated adequately with all the loads (batteries, sensor system, and other electronic devices.). The transmitter used was the FSi6 transmitter, a 2.4GHz radio system with 6 channels. CH 1 and 2 were dedicated to the two motors, while CH 6 was set for the toggle switch to trigger the sensing system. The remote control controlled the boat smoothly for a distance of 50m-100m.

Fig. 11. Navigation system actual testing in a mining tailing pond.

B. Sensing System

The CYANanoBot System was deployed for the actual testing. The system was tested many times in a day, repeatedly conducting water sample collection, water sample preparation, image capturing, paper sensor detection, color extraction, cyanide concentration prediction, water sample discharge, and data transmission. The 8 mathematical models were used to identify the time intervals that needed to be taken. After this, the paper sensor responses were detected and their color values were extracted. Then, using the image, the model, and the features needed in the model, the cyanide concentration was predicted using the model and the result was compared with the actual concentration measured with an ISE.

A total of 18 samples were collected on-site. Figure 12 shows the Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plots of the two best models and their respective R^2 . The predictions at 165s using the HSV color space exhibited the highest R^2 of 0.85 and the lowest RMSE of 3.80ppm with an average error of 3.40ppm. This model also showed the lowest prediction error, with the true value at 31.5ppm and its prediction at 31.4ppm. However, its maximum error is 5.9ppm. The model for 195s in HSV has the second-highest R^2 of 0.67 but its RMSE is 6.41ppm. The 240s model using the HSV color space exhibited the highest RMSE of 26.97ppm.

The current study has lower R^2 than the results of the reviewed literature, but the conducted tests concerned larger cyanide concentration values (12.6ppm to 41.1ppm) compared to studies that detected 0ppm to 1ppm with RMSE of 0.06ppm [10], 0 parts per billion (ppb) to 4ppb [11], and 0ppm to 20ppm [12]. Figure 13 shows the visualization of the transmitted data in Thingspeak.

Fig. 12. Q-Q Plot of two models during on-site testing.

Fig. 13. Data visualization in Thingspeak.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, a boat-assisted cyanide monitoring device focused on the use of AuNPs-integrated paper sensors through digital colorimetry was developed. The boat was successfully built, it is well-balanced and spacious. The remote-control system has been successfully installed in the system. Regarding the sensing system, it is effectively working with the automated procedures of intake, discharge, dispensing, imaging, detection, extraction, and sending of the acquired data. Based on the results of the models, the image taken at 165s in the HSV color space is the most promising in predicting the cyanide concentration of the water sample on-site as only one model

will be chosen for the final deployment. This time interval, 165s, against other model time intervals, such as 315 and 555s, is favorable as the image of the paper sensor can be taken at a lesser time reducing the risk of sample degradation and lessening the idle time of the bot in the sampling site. Instead of manually retrieving water samples and testing cyanide concentration using ISE, the bot can reduce person-to-person interaction, reduce testing time, avoid frequent calibration of the electrodes, and reduce operating costs as paper sensors are inexpensive. However, trained personnel are highly necessary for using and maintaining the system.

For future work, more tests for the model at a broader range of concentration are recommended along with other possible methods of acquiring color intensities of the paper sensors instead of a camera, consideration for confounding factors in the model, and implementing an autonomous navigation system.

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A Power-Aware Real-Time System for Multi-Video Treatment on FPGA with Dynamic Partial Reconfiguration and Voltage Scaling

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Abstract-As the energy consumption is an evaluating factor for System-On-Chip (SOC) design, this paper presents a power-aware architecture for a real-time multi-video system on FPGA. This architecture aims to optimize power consumption for a multi-video system on ARM-based architectures. The proposed architecture uses dynamic reconfiguration and voltage scaling to create a power-aware system for real-time multi-video processing with minimal power dissipation. Dynamic partial reconfiguration was used to optimize the utilization of resources and reduce dynamic power consumption. Voltage scaling was also used to optimize dynamic power consumption, by configuring the blocks to use the minimum necessary voltage for normal operating conditions. The proposed architecture focused on the Zynq platform. The results showed power savings of up to 70% concerning performance and real-time constraints.

Keywords-power consumption; Zynq; ARM A9; dynamic partial reconfiguration; voltage scaling

I. INTRODUCTION

Embedded real-time video applications are widely spread in many systems and have important applications in various domains such as segmentation [1, 2], object tracking [3], visual detection and matching [4], motion estimation [5], etc. These systems are generally executed in an embedded environment and are subjected to many constraints such as power consumption, time, and resources. As the market requires these systems to have high performance at a low cost, designers have to propose new architectures to meet different requirements. Many dedicated technologies and methods have been proposed to develop and implement high-quality real-time applications and optimized systems. The

proposed technologies range from specific processors like General Purpose Processors (GPPs), Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), and Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) to parallel architectures like Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) or even programmable logic devices (FPGAs). Today, FPGAs are being increasingly used to build complex video processing applications. They provide real-time performance that is difficult to achieve with GPP or DSP [6-8] while limiting the extensive design work required for ASICs. Furthermore, FPGAs provide the ability to implement highly parallel architectures due to the huge number of programmable logic available on the chip [9].

One of the major problems with FPGA implementations compared to ASIC solutions is power consumption, which is a limiting factor [10]. Therefore, more efforts are spent to propose a design with low-power dissipation. Since FPGAs are CMOS-transistors, power consumption can be divided into two main types: static power and dynamic power. Static power is dissipated when the circuit is in a quiescent state caused by leakage currents of the CMOS transistor. These currents are the sub-threshold leakage current, the gate leakage current, and the junction leakage current [11]. Dynamic power consumption is given by:

$$P_d = \alpha \cdot C \cdot V^2 \cdot f \quad (1)$$

where C is the capacitance, α is the charging rate depending on clock frequency, V is voltage supply, and f is the clock frequency. This power is highly related to technology and has become a concern with modern FPGAs implemented in 24nm [12-14]. To reduce power consumption, the principal causes of power dissipation have to be investigated during all steps of the design process, from the algorithmic level down to the

transistor level, considering the latest low-power technology methods at all the design levels.

This paper proposes a power-aware hardware architecture for real-time multi-video processing, using dynamic reconfiguration and voltage scaling to optimize the power consumption of a multi-video system. This method was applied to a high-performance video system of 1920×1080 pixels at 60fps.

II. FPGA POWER REDUCTION

Most modern FPGA boards are computing platforms that include programmable hardware elements, memory resources, configurable I/O, embedded processors, and even embedded operating systems. Hardware (HW) and software (SW) functionalities allow the combination of hardware's performance and software's flexibility. This combination of performance and flexibility comes at the cost of high power consumption, which is the main limit of FPGA platforms. To overcome this limit, new methods to optimize power consumption are investigated. The proposed methods explore all abstraction levels of the design process, from the system level to the circuit level and the technological level. Some works used HW/SW partitioning to propose optimal systems with low power consumption as power-aware decisions at a very early stage of the design process [15-17]. HW/SW partitioning is the problem of assigning application tasks to the existing computational cores under defined constraints such as area and power. It is formalized as an optimization problem aiming to minimize an objective function under defined constraints. In [15], an algorithm was proposed for HW/SW partitioning to find the best tradeoff between power and latency, modeling the application as a data flow graph and computing the latency and power consumption for every proposed partitioning. This algorithm performed a heuristic search for the best solution that respected the defined constraints. In [17], a data flow graph based on the Bee Colony Algorithm was proposed to solve the optimization problem of HW/SW partitioning under time and power constraints. The heuristic algorithm treated the optimization problem as NP-Hard, and the exact resolution may take a much longer time. To adjust the constraints according to the user's requirements, weighting coefficients were added to the constraints to specify which of the two conflicting terms is more important for the final partitioning result.

Other studies examined methods at the architecture level, like Dynamic Voltage Scaling (DVS) and Dynamic Frequency Scaling (DFS). DVS, DFS, or even Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) were first proposed to reduce the power consumption of microprocessors [18-20] and, as they were successful, they were generalized and used on FPGAs [21-22]. In [18], a method for static timing analysis in dynamic scheduling schemes was proposed. A safe timing analysis was proposed for systems with off-chip memories where memory latency did not scale with processor frequency. This method, called 'frequency-aware', replaced the Worst-Case Execution Time (WCET) [23] obtained by static-timing analysis. It expressed WCET bounds with frequency-sensitive parameters, where cycles were interpreted in terms of processor frequency and memory accesses were

expressed in terms of the memory latency overhead. The new proposed WCET was determined on-the-fly for a given frequency.

The problem of real-time systems with time-critical applications was addressed in [19]. A new algorithm was proposed for DFS, applied directly to the scheduler to modify task management. At first, a static frequency was assigned to every task, which was the lowest possible frequency that allowed the scheduler to meet the deadlines for a given task set. If a task was completed before the worst-case specification, the frequency was re-computed using the latest information. The new value was used until the release of the task for a future invocation. Therefore, the utilization was recomputed at every new scheduling time using the real computed time for accomplished tasks and the specified worst-case for the others. This method allowed a 20-40% power reduction. A DVFS technique for non-real-time applications was proposed in [20], where the main idea was to lower the CPU frequency when accessing off-chip peripherals. The temporal distribution of on- and off-chip workloads was computed with different scenarios to determine the CPU frequency during idle periods. The energy savings were up to 70%, with a variable performance penalty depending on the saving value.

Two methods for DVS on commercial FPGAs were presented in [21, 22]. In [21], a circuit was used to measure the logic delay, which would be used by the voltage controller block to dynamically adjust the supply voltage using a closed loop. The voltage controller was an external module implemented on a PC. Experimental results using a Xilinx Virtex XCV300E FPGA were presented, and power savings were 4-54%. Although the study noted that implementing the voltage controller as an internal module is a way for better resource utilization, giving results and statistics based on an external module is disputable since it may lack precision and can cause delay violations or more resource consumption.

III. REAL-TIME VIDEO PROCESSING AND ARCHITECTURE

A. Real-Time Video Processing

Real-time video processing plays a key role in industrial systems and is expanded to many fields. Real-time video processing systems process large amounts of image data in a short time. The purpose varies from a simple display to the extraction of useful information for intelligent scene analysis. Digital videos are data-intensive and resource-demanding multidimensional signals, as they need an important amount of resources for computations and memory operations. A typical video system consists of a video source, internal processing, and destination, as shown in Figure 1. The video processing module is traditionally classified into three levels: low, intermediate, and high. Each level differs from the others in input/output format and processing type. For example, the low-level takes an image and produces an output image, while the high-level takes image attributes as input and makes high-level interpretation to produce a knowledge-based control as output.

Fig. 1. Video processing system.

A common concern in real-time video processing systems is how to deal with large amounts of data. This pushes designers to search for a suitable architecture that guarantees the required performance with the worst-case latency to ensure no frame drops. This remains a challenging task, especially for embedded systems that have limited resources and power supply. The architecture has to allow parallel treatments, as it is hard to perform such a large data treatment serially. The best solution often comes with a combination of hardware and software approaches. The hardware offers high performance using parallelism, and the software guarantees flexibility. Fortunately, modern FPGA devices are characterized by sufficient logic resources and high operating frequencies for video processing.

B. Hardware and Software Architecture for Real-Time Multi-Video Processing

The design of a real-time system for multi-video processing is a demanding task. In addition to the constraints discussed above, constraints such as available resources and memory access management are added to the problem. The design of multi-video architecture needs to answer the following demands:

- Achieve the performance required by different parallel and communicating blocks. Blocks concerning video processing systems are subjected to timing constraints for high-bandwidth and data-intensive operations with the need to access the memory at the video rate.
- Extend it when needed. The extension is the ability to add new video processing chains or blocks or the limit of available resources.
- Obtain an optimal use of available resources. System partitioning between hard and soft resources allows getting the high performance of HW and the flexibility of SW.

In addition to the previous requirements, which are in direct relation to the system and platform, power consumption is another constraint that has to be considered, as battery life has become the main factor in the evaluation of embedded systems. The choice of the appropriate target platform is very essential for real-time systems. Of the existing FPGA platforms, many are appropriate for video processing with real-time constraints, as they can work at a frequency that can exceed 150MHz, and as a result, can support HD resolutions. In addition, FPGA vendors have incorporated various hardware and software IP cores that can be used for different functions needed in video processing, like timing generation and RGB conversions.

Fig. 2. General architecture for multi-video processing on FPGA.

Figure 2 shows the general architecture for multi-video processing using HW and SW available in the FPGA. The HW or Programmable Logic (PL) is used to implement video-related blocks like video-in, video processing sub-systems, and video-out. The SW or Processing System (PS) contains the Application Processing Unit (APU), which is responsible for system-level control registers, DMA controllers, and the Accelerator Coherency Port (ACP). The memory interface allows the PS and PL blocks to access the memory. The utilization of PS and PL to implement video processing modules is performed according to the available resources, performance constraints, power constraints, and other issues like flexibility and time to market.

This study used a Zynq ZC 702 based Xilinx evaluation kit as a target platform. This kit includes SW, HW, and IP components that facilitate the development of custom video applications. The APU contains two ARM Cortex-A9 processors sharing a 512KB L2 cache, which can be used for dual-core or single-core devices. Each processor is a low-power, high-performance core with a 32KB L1 cache for instruction and data. The AXI protocol [24] defines 3 types of interfaces: AXI4 for high-performance memory-mapped requirements, AXI4-Lite for low-throughput memory-mapped communications, and AXI4-Stream for high-speed streaming data. These application domains make the protocol indispensable for every real-time video system. The AXI interconnect, AXI3, and AXI Video DMA IP cores can form the basis of video systems capable of handling video frame buffers and giving access to a shared DDR3 SDRAM. This design utilized the AXI4, AXI3, AXI4-Lite, and AXI4-Stream interfaces. The Accelerator Coherency Port (ACP) is used to communicate the PL with the APU, as it is an AXI interface that allows the PL to implement an AXI master to access the L2 [25-27]. The AXI Video Direct Memory Access (VDMA) core implements a video-optimized direct memory access engine with a frame buffer. The AXI VDMA core transfers video data to and from memory under dynamic software control. Figure 3 shows the block diagram of the implemented design with the interface connection. The processor can access the PL using the AXI3 master General-Purpose (GP) 32-bit interfaces. The Zynq ZC702 has 4 AXI_HP interfaces, which allow PL to access DDR memory through high-bandwidth data path bus masters.

IV. DYNAMIC PARTIAL RECONFIGURATION FOR POWER REDUCTION

The Dynamic Partial Reconfiguration (DPR) offers a way to optimize the dynamic power consumption by enabling the usage of temporarily shared resources on the FPGA among different processing functions in a time-multiplexed manner. Hence, DPR enables better resource utilization and efficiency. The DPR results in a partial bitstream loaded onto the FPGA, targeting a fixed part of its area. Figure 3 shows the general architecture of multi-video processing. Fixed areas are predefined during HW design and are called the Reconfiguration Partition (RP).

Fig. 3. General DPR architecture for multi-video processing.

V. DYNAMIC PARTIAL RECONFIGURATION FOR REAL-TIME MULTI-VIDEO PROCESSING

Real-time multi-video processing is a demanding task in terms of performance, resource utilization, and power consumption. The target architecture was composed of the PS part, which allows communication with the DR, and the PL parts where the video-related blocks are implemented. A multi-video architecture is defined as a system with n video inputs, where n is limited by the resource constraints of the target platform. In this case, $n=4$ since the target Zynq platform has 4 HP ports that allow high performance communication with DDR, as shown in Figure 4.

A DPR-based architecture was proposed to optimize resources and power. DPR, also known as active partial reconfiguration, allows changing a part of the device while other blocks are running. While the FPGA is executing different blocks, the partial data will be sent to be configured. There are two ways for DPR [28], known as Difference Based Partial Reconfiguration (DBPR) and Module Based Partial Reconfiguration (MBPR). DBPR is used when a small change is made to the design. It is especially useful when changing Look-Up Table (LUT) equations or dedicated memory block content. MBPR uses modular design concepts to reconfigure large logic blocks. MBPR was used to implement the DPR on the target platform, defining two different parts: static modules and dynamic or Reconfigurable Modules (RMs). The static module is the part of the design that remains in operation during the PR process. The dynamic modules are the parts of the design that can be swapped in and out of the device on the fly, where multiple RMs can be defined for a specific region.

Fig. 4. Real-time multi-video processing.

Figure 5 shows the proposed architecture with both static and dynamic parts. PS and the multi-display present the static part while the dynamic part contains the PL.

Fig. 5. The proposed architecture with RDP.

VI. VOLTAGE SCALING

DVS is the process of varying the voltage of a target block at run-time. As voltage is directly related to power consumption [1], reducing it allows for a quadric reduction of power consumption. The following definitions must be considered to use DVS in a target FPGA [29]:

- The processing strength of a device is the ability and degree of variation in the attributes of the integrated transistors. There are three classes: weak, nominal, and strong. A weak device can operate with the lowest acceptable frequency at nominal voltages. Strong devices can run at faster frequencies than required at nominal voltages and can function at voltages lower than nominal at the minimum specified frequency.
- The voltage domain is defined as the group of modules sharing the same power supply voltage for the core logic of each device.

- The operating performance point is the voltage required for every device to operate at the desired processor clocking frequency. For example, for the processing system DDR I/O supply voltage, the minimum value is 1.14V and the maximum is 1.89V [30].
- The critical path of a system is defined as the longest path to achieve the execution of a program from the source to the sink of a data flow graph. This information is used to track the critical tasks when scaling voltage and frequency to ensure the performance of the system.

To implement DVS on a specific platform for a defined system, information about the operating voltage of each block must be accessible at runtime. This information can be obtained in two different ways:

- Dynamic analysis of the behavior of the system at runtime requires real-time access to the working blocks on the PL side. This can be done with additional modules implemented in PL or PS. This method requires extra resources to gather information at run-time.
- Static analysis of the system behavior using different test scenarios. The obtained test results can be used with the information provided by the manufacturer to make design decisions for frequency and voltage scaling.

This study followed the second method to perform DVS and DFS at runtime. Let V_{min_x} be the minimum voltage required for block x to operate in normal conditions and under which the system fails. These values are a characteristic of hardware blocks, fixed at the time of device manufacturing. Let V_{op_x} be the operating voltage of block x . The algorithm used to scale voltage is shown in Figure 6, where st is a float representing the step of incrementing and decrementing the voltage.

```

Inputs :  $V_{min_x}$ ,  $V_{op_x}$ ,  $st$ ;
Begin
Identify voltage bounds for the target block;
Do
   $V_{op} = V_{op} - st$ ;
  Test performance;
  if test failed
     $V_{op} = V_{op} + st$ ;
    Break;
  End if
While ( $V_{op} > V_{min_x}$ )
End

```

Fig. 6. Voltage scaling algorithm.

In the ZC702 board, power is supplied to the components through several independent rails using programmable power regulators (UCD9248) and a Power Management Bus (PMBus) compliant system controller from Texas Instruments. PMBus is an open standard protocol that defines communication with power converters and allows to write and read power, current, and voltage information. The processors can access the PMBus using a 1-to-8 I2C switch. Zynq-ZC7020 is divided into several power domains, as shown in Figure 7. These power domains are generated by 6 regulators that generate different voltages required by the Zynq and the onboard components. The supplied voltage and

currents are continuously measured and monitored by three UCD9248 power controllers available on the ZC702 board.

In this work, scaling the voltage of hard blocks was performed using the PMBus protocol, which simplifies communication with power converters as it allows the device's SW or HW to access a manageable power supply [31, 32]. Optimal operating voltages were calculated using the algorithm shown in Figure 6. Then, the system was configured only one time with these values at every start. The configuration and implementation of the proposed algorithm were carried out by the processor through soft code.

Fig. 7. Zynq power domains [31].

VII. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The proposed architecture was prototyped on the Zynq ZC702 evaluation board, which provides a hardware environment for developing and evaluating designs targeting the Zynq XC7Z020 device. ZC702 includes 1GB DDR3 component memory, 128MB Quad SPI flash memory, USB 2.0, Secure Digital (SD) connector, HDMI codec, I2C bus, 2 UART interfaces, and other features. This section provides experimental results and shows the benefits of the proposed design in power reduction. A performance comparison is also held to verify the performance of the whole system.

A. Hardware and Software Architecture

The target system was designed using the Vivado Design Suite. This design suite can accelerate design implementation with place and route tools that analytically optimize for multiple and concurrent design metrics, such as timing and power. Vivado gives the ability to analyze the design at each design stage, allowing for modifications in the design process. It also provides timing and power estimations after synthesis, placement, or routing. The following blocks were used to implement the hardware architecture:

- The processing system was used to initialize blocks and master memory access. The frequency and voltage scaling modules were also implemented in the processing system.
- The AXI interconnects were responsible for handling information to and from the processing system.
- The AXI performance monitor was used for different statistics with the AXI protocol interfaces. It was used for transactions, external system events, and performance measurement for AXI4, AXI3, AXI4-Stream, and AXI4-Lite interfaces and captured real-time performance metrics

for throughput and latency. The performance monitor IP was used to perform real-time profiling using the SDK.

- The video pipeline contains Video Direct Memory Access (VDMA), which is a soft IP core that provides high bandwidth for direct access to the memory using AXI4-Stream video peripherals. The AXI4-Lite slave interface was used to perform initialization, registers, and status.
- The video-related blocks are standard blocks used in a video chain to transfer the video stream after the necessary conversions. The RGB to YCrCb module converts the design pixels from the RGB encoding used by the AXI4-Stream to the 16-bit YUV 4:4:4 signal format. The Chroma Resampler block had the output of the RGB to YCrCb as input. Its role was to convert the input signals to YUV 4:2:2 required by the HDMI output.

The software part running on the PS was built using the Xilinx Software Development Kit (SDK). The software part running on the ARM processor with a standalone operating system had the role of hardware control.

B. Partial Dynamic Reconfiguration Results

Figure 8 shows the resource results without (a) and with PDR (b). Figure 9 shows the occupation of the resources on the target platform without (a) and with DPR (b). The figures show an improvement in the used resources, which lowered power consumption.

Fig. 8. Resource utilization.

C. Voltage Scaling Results

The voltage scaling method was implemented as software code running on the processor. Communication with the voltage rails was performed using the I2C bus. To avoid unnecessary additional resources, the optimal values were computed using excessive test scenarios. This analysis defined the optimal values that would be used by the system without the need to collect them at run-time using additional

resources. The DVS method requires knowledge of the voltage limits of different blocks. Table II shows the maximum and minimum recommended operating voltage values for some blocks of the ZC702 device [30].

Fig. 9. Resource occupation.

TABLE I. VOLTAGE RECOMMENDED VALUES FOR SOME BLOCKS OF THE TARGET ZYNQ ZC702 DEVICE

Blocks	Description	Minimum operating voltage (V)	Typical operating voltage (V)	Maximum operating voltage (V)
vccpint	PS internal supply voltage	0.95	1	1.05
vccint	PL internal supply voltage	0.95	1	1.05
vccpaux	PS auxiliary supply voltage	1.71	1.80	1.89
vccaux	PL auxiliary supply voltage	1.71	1.80	1.89
vccbram	PL block RAM supply voltage	0.95	1.00	1.05

Although voltage can reach more inferior values than those indicated in the safety bounds, for example, Vccpint minimal value can reach 0.5V [30], the safe functioning of the device outside the indicated bounds is not tested. It is indicated that exposure to maximum values for extended periods could affect the device's reliability [30]. Figure 10 shows the voltage scaling results of some Vcc rails. Every figure shows the power margin for every chosen value. For example, for the Vccint rail, when the minimum operating value is chosen (0.95), the power consumption of this block varies between 22 and 31mW.

Fig. 10. Voltage scaling results on different rails.

Figure 11 shows the time needed by the rail to reach the target voltage value. This figure shows the case of two rails with different typical voltage values. For both rails, the typical functioning voltage was attended after 5ms.

Fig. 11. Voltage configuration time.

D. Frequency Scaling and Design Performance

Frequency scaling is the concept of varying the operating frequencies of blocks at run-time according to the target architecture. There are two frequencies: the frequency of the PL blocks and the frequency of the PS. An analysis of the functioning of the system was performed to study the possibility of applying frequency scaling, using the System Performance Analysis (SPA) toolbox. This toolbox was used to explore the performance of HW and SW at an early stage in the target system. Observing system performance in critical stages helped make the right optimization decisions and refine system performance without degradation. The SPA software metrics included CPU utilization, instructions per cycle, L1 data cache access, miss rate, write and read stall cycles per instruction, and other metrics. The hardware metrics were available using the AXI performance monitor core, designed to measure the real-time performance of the connected AXI interfaces, including AXI read and write transactions, throughput, bandwidth, and others. This work used CPU utilization and AXI read latency and throughput metrics.

Figure 12 shows the CPU utilization rate of the proposed real-time architecture. Only one core was used. The graph shows that the utilization ranged between 91% and 100%. These results show that applying DFS on one processor executing a real-time video system does not allow a noticeable optimization, as the CPU utilization is usually at its maximum level.

Fig. 12. CPU utilization.

Figure 13 shows the read transactions and latency cycles of the ports HP0 (Slot 0) and GP0 (Slot 1).

Fig. 13. Performance metrics at runtime.

E. Comparison with Other Works

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to bring together DPR and voltage scaling. This section limits the discussion and comparison with works that used frequency and voltage scaling, as these two methods allow the reduction of the biggest part of power consumption (60%). Voltage and frequency scaling of commercial FPGAs was implemented in several studies using different methods. The proposed method was compared with two existing main methods that focused on the frequency and voltage of commercial 28nm FPGAs. The first study used voltage and frequency scaling [34], while in [35], voltage, frequency, and logic scaling were used to optimize power consumption. The voltage scaling unit was identical to the one used in [34]. The frequency-scaling unit used a ROM containing the configuration parameters used by the MMCM to generate the clock for the user logic. The frequency decreased continually at run-time and stopped when a value was detected that could cause timing violations. Compared to those studies, this study used voltage scaling in addition to the DPR. Authors in [34, 35] collected information like frequency and voltage of functioning blocks at run-time and scaled them accordingly. Collecting information at run-time results in extra resources and additional complexity. These works applied the proposed

methods to Power Consuming and Speed Testing Modules (PCASTMs). These PCASTMs were proposed with different numbers of modules occupying different percentages of the device. For voltage scaling, the voltage values were tested under the recommended values in the datasheet. Testing with values below the recommended minimum can give more power savings of up to 60% [36], but with doubtful safety for long-term function with real-time constraints.

This study exploited the fact that since the different execution scenarios are known in advance, the collection of information was performed at the design level using tests and

timing analysis to determine the optimal operating points. Implementing the proposed method requires only an I2C IP core and is of low complexity. Additionally, scaling the voltage many times at runtime is not useful as it results in power and heat dissipation while accessing the power rails. It is more efficient to configure the device blocks with the optimal voltage at the start. Table III shows a comparison between [34, 35] and this study. According to the results obtained, the proposed method presents up to 70% power savings with an improvement of 5% compared to the other studies.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH OTHER WORKS

	Additional resources	Frequency scaling method	Voltage scaling method	Test method	Power achievements
[34]	Microblaze, Picoblaze, I2C, IP core, Dual-port RAM	I2C communication with Si570 oscillator	I2C communication with PMBus	Random functions with different sizes	Up to 64.98%, (using voltage and frequency scaling)
[35]	Microblaze, I2C, IP core Dual-port RAM ROM	Configuration of MMCM, ROM	I2C communication with PMBus	Random functions with different sizes	Up to 60% (using frequency, voltage, and logic scaling)
This study	I2C IP core	none	Soft configuration of PMBus	Real-time video application with real-time constraints	Up to 70% (voltage scaling and PDR)

VIII. CONCLUSION

The design of an optimized system is very challenging due to the complexity of a SOC design. Power consumption has become a struggle with the increasing consumers' demands and the saturation due to Moore's law. Designers have to find new solutions to reduce power consumption. This study proposed a design method that brings together partial reconfiguration and voltage scaling. These methods were used to design a real-time multi-video processing system, implemented on a Zynq ZC702 board with an ARM 9 target processor. The proposed method is general and can be applied to other real-time systems. Compared to existing works, the proposed design allowed up to 70% power savings with minimal additional resources. Future work should examine the application of other methods like clock gating and their integration in the design of real-time video systems.

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Assessing the Effect of Underground Void on Strip Footing Sitting on a Reinforced Sand Slope with Numerical Modeling

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Abstract-This paper presents the results of the numerical analysis undertaken to investigate the effect of the underground void on the load-bearing capacity of a strip footing placed on an unreinforced and geogrid-reinforced sand slope with a void inside. The failure mechanism of the soil was also investigated. The numerical model was obtained using 2D plane-strain FEM analysis (in Plaxis software), in which the nonlinear Mohr-Coulomb model was utilized. The effects of various parameters such as the number of geogrid layers (N), the vertical distance ratio between the top of the cavity from the base of footing (H/B), the horizontal distance of void centerline to the footing center (X/B), on the behavior of footing are studied in this research. The results indicate that there is a critical zone under the footing in which the existence of void has no influence on the bearing capacity and stability of the footing. In addition, the use of geogrid reinforcement reduces the settlement and enhances bearing capacity. Finally, the bearing capacity factor and failure mechanism increase with increasing horizontal and vertical void distances ratios (X/B and H/B) and reinforcement layers.

Keywords-cavity; slope; strip footing; geogrid-reinforced; sand, finite element analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In civil engineering, sometimes buildings and other engineering structures may sit on underground voids. Underground cavities that traverse the subsoil can be classified into two types: the ones of artificial origin due to human activity (e.g. installation tunneling, exploitation of underground quarries and mines, gas and water networks creation, etc.) or natural cavities formed by the action of water, which dissolves limestone or gypsum found in subsoil. Generally, the existence

of underground voids on a foundation can cause large-scale disorders in the constructions, inducing the collapse of structures and the settlement of foundations.

There is a vast literature analysis of the carrying capacity and failure mechanisms of foundations resting on unreinforced soil with void through three principal methods: experimental investigations, numerical studies, and theoretical studies [1-5]. The numerical observation of [6] reported that the failure zone has developed considerably toward the void closest to the foundation and does not usually extend other voids. Theoretical methods [7] and centrifuge tests [8] have been performed to examine the stability of the void. Authors in [9] used a Finite Element Method (FEM) to investigate the bearing capacity and the failure mechanism of a strip footing built on double-voids. Their results indicate that the mode of failure depends on the size and location of the voids. Authors in [10] applied the procedure DLO to analyze the stability of footing situated on cohesive-frictional soil with single and dual square voids. The results implied that the presence of voids has a greater impact on $c-\phi$ soil compared to that on non-drained soil. The failure mechanism is related to several soil properties, the placement of voids, and the linear distance between two voids. Authors in [11] carried out a series of laboratory loading tests and numerical modeling simulations to investigate the impact of an underground void on the load-settlement behavior of a strip footing. They demonstrated that the FEM results are in good agreement with the experimental load-settlement curve. Also, the presence of subterranean voids can lead to stress concentrations within the soil, which can cause failure. Authors in [12] adopted FEM to study the collapse of strip foundations

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on the sand with single and twin continuous voids. The obtained results are in accordance with the theoretical and numerical solutions available.

For over 40 years, due to its relatively ease of use, and small cost, geogrid reinforced soil has been used in a variety of fields of geotechnical engineering [13, 14]. When a foundation is found above the void, one of the possible remedial measures to improve the bearing capacity and reduce the settlement and the performance of footing would be to reinforce the foundation soil with layers of geogrid. With this in mind, some researchers have also studied the behavior of a foundation built on reinforced soil containing the void [15-21]. Authors in [22, 23] presented an analytical solution for designing a planar geosynthetic reinforced soil system on a cavity. Authors in [24] conducted full-scale model tests on a shallow circular footing placed on geocell-reinforced sand bed overlying a clay bed having a circular void. They found that a substantial improvement of the bearing capacity of the footing can be achieved by providing an adequately sized geocell mattress, over the clay subgrade with the void. They also observed that, in order to have a great impact, the geocell mattress must extend beyond the void at a distance greater than the diameter of the void. Authors in [25] developed a laboratory-scale model with the intention of studying the effects of varied parameters on the performance of the strip footing supported by geogrid-reinforced sand over a void. The investigated parameters included void embedment depths, the number of reinforcement layers, and relative densities. They reported that loading pressure and footing settlement improved significantly with increasing void anchorage depth, number of geogrid layers, and relative soil density. Authors in [26] used numerical analysis to investigate the behavior of single and two adjacent strip footings placed on unreinforced/reinforced granular bed overlying clay containing voids. Their results show that the proving geogrid reinforcement increases the load carrying capacity of the footing in both cases. The influence of a single void on the bearing capacity is negligible when the void is situated at a critical depth greater than 5B and at a horizontal distance greater than 3B from the center of the footing.

The majority of the above mentioned studies focused on foundations resting on a horizontal ground, however, many of these structures are placed above or near slopes. There are some investigations that have been conducted to calculate the ultimate load carrying capacity of strip footings subjected to central loading near reinforced slopes without voids [27-31]. In contrast, strip footings adjacent to reinforced slopes with voids have received little experimental and theoretical/numerical research. Therefore, in the present paper, a series of finite element studies were conducted to analyze the bearing capacity behavior of footing on a reinforced sand slope with a single circular void subject to static vertical loading. Additionally, the benefits of geogrid-reinforcement application to stabilize strip footing and failure mechanisms of the sand slope were examined under different conditions of the void. To achieve this objective, a total of 80 numerical model tests were conducted with different depth ratios (H/B), horizontal spacing ratios (X/B) and reinforcement layers (N).

II. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The finite element software PLAXIS was used to simulate the footing-void system in both condition unreinforced and geogrid reinforced sand slope. The sand surrounding the void is supposed to follow perfect and elastoplastic behavior law, where the rupture criterion is considered as Mohr-Coulomb in conjunction with non-associated flow rule, i.e. $\psi \neq \phi$. The Mohr-Coulomb model was chosen for its simplicity and the availability of the necessary parameters. The adopted parameters of the analysis are summarized in Table I. The foundation was treated as an elastic beam element based on Mindlin's beam theory with significant flexural rigidity (EI) equal to 32,000MPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.2, and normal stiffness (EA) equal to 25KN/m³. The void was considered to be circular in form and of diameter equal to the width of the footing. In addition, the void is simulated as a tunnel without a lining.

TABLE I. SOIL PARAMETERS

Parameters	Name	Unit	sand
Model type	Model	-	Mohr-Coulomb
Dry density	γ_{unsat}	KN/m ³	16.7
Wet density	γ_{sat}	KN/m ³	19.3
Young's modulus	Eref	KPa	1.2 104
Poisson's ratio	ν	KPa	0.30
Cohesion	c	KN/m ³	1
Angle of friction	ϕ	(°)	38
Angle of dilation	ψ	(°)	6

Reinforcement geogrid, which is usually used to increase load bearing capacity, has only one tensile stiffness (EA=30KN). The reinforcement layers were simulated using the elastic geogrid element of Plaxis. The interaction between the soil and the geogrid is modeled on both sides through interface elements. The boundary conditions for all the models were chosen such that the vertical boundary is constrained horizontally and free vertically, while the bottom of the numerical model is fully fixed. During the generation of the mesh, 15 triangular plane strain elements were selected to model the soil, while the geogrid was modeled with 5 node elastic elements. The refined mesh option was adopted to guarantee a better representation of the stress field under the base of the foundation, near the crest of the slope, geogrid layers, and the void. The model slope geometry, generated mesh, and boundary conditions are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The numerical model.

The calculation is performed in three phases: The first relates to the formation of the initial stress condition, the second stage deals with building the sand layers by placing the

reinforcement elements and creating the void, and the last one is to load the strip footing. It is worth noting that for each analysis, a prescribed footing load was applied in increments, followed by iterative analysis, until failure. In all numerical models, the failure load is determined by the pronounced peaks in the load-displacement curves.

III. VALIDATION OF THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

In order to confirm the numerical model, the slope surface was replaced by a horizontal ground surface. The bearing capacity factor N_γ values obtained by the finite element approach were compared with those given in the literature. Table II presents the numerical results for N_γ values associated with various friction angles (ϕ) obtained by different researchers. It is clear that the magnitude of N_γ increases with increasing ϕ . As shown in Table II, the computed values of N_γ are significantly lower than the solutions reported in [32], however, they are in good agreement with those reported in [33, 34], with a difference less than 6%. This good agreement can be considered as a validation of the numerical model obtained from this study.

TABLE II. BEARING CAPACITY FACTOR N_γ

ϕ°	Current study	[32]	[33]	[34]	[35]	[36]
25	7.24	9.7	6.76	6.76	10.88	6.74
30	15.47	19.7	15.07	15.67	22.4	15.24
35	31.03	37.5	33.92	37.15	48.03	35.65

IV. TEST PROGRAM

Four series of tests were conducted to analyze the inclusion effect of the geogrid layers on the bearing capacity of shallow foundations supported by sand containing a void near a slope. Figure 2 illustrates the different tests conducted in this study with parameter details. In previous studies, several values of μ/B , h/B and L/B were proposed for foundations on geogrid-reinforced sand, where “ μ ” is the distance between the footing bottom and the first geogrid layer (L) the length of the geogrid, (h) is the distance between two geogrid layers, and B is the footing width.

Fig. 2. Geometry parameters.

In order to study the best arrangement of geogrid layer inclusions, authors in [37, 38] reported that there are critical values for μ/B , and h/B ranging from 0.3-0.35, beyond which the reinforcement has no effect on the bearing capacity. On the other hand, the optimal value of L/B was 0.35, as determined in [25]. Based on these results, the values of $\mu/B=0.35$, $h/B=0.35$, and $L/B=4$ were adopted in the current study in order to

achieve maximum bearing capacity and reduce the settlement of the footing. Each series of tests analyzed the effect of one parameter while the other parameters were held constant. The variable parameters included the number of reinforcement layers (N), the depth between the foundation base and the crest of the cavity (H/D), and the horizontal distance of the void from the foundation centerline (X/B). Table III presents the different numerical programs and their fixed and variable parameters.

TABLE III. NUMERICAL PROGRAMS AND PARAMETERS

Test series	Type of reinforcement	Variable parameters			Fixed parameters
		N	X/B	H/B	
1	Unreinforced (without void)	0	-	-	$\mu/B=0.35$ $h/B=0.35$ $L/B=4$ $T_g(\beta)=2/3$
2	Unreinforced (with void)	0	0	0.5	
			1	1	
			2	1.5	
			3	2	
2	Reinforced (without void)	1 - 2 - 3	-	-	
4	Reinforced (with void)	1 - 2 - 3	0	1.5	
			1	2	
			2	2.5	
			3	3	

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 80 model tests in 4 series were conducted on a strip footing constructed on a reinforced sand slope with a void to account for the influence of all the variable parameters. Two dimensionless factors are introduced to quantify the influence of the void and reinforcing layers on the bearing capacity in order to establish accurate comparisons between the numerical tests, knowing that authors in [4, 6, 26] also assessed the impact of void and reinforcement soil in terms of reduction factors, not in terms of ultimate bearing capacity. The first parameter is the bearing capacity ratio (i_h), which can be given in the form shown in (1). This factor is defined as the ratio of load-bearing capacity of the footing on the unreinforced sand with a void and without void respectively.

$$i_h = \frac{q_{uv}(\text{with a void})}{q_u(\text{with out void})} \quad (1)$$

The second parameter is used to assess the combined effect of reinforcement layers and the existence of the void on bearing capacity. This parameter is defined as i_{hr} , i.e. the ratio between the load-bearing capacity of the strip footing on the reinforced soil with a void to that of unreinforced soil without one:

$$i_{hr} = \frac{q_{uvr}(\text{with a void})}{q_u(\text{without void})} \quad (2)$$

A. Effect of Geogrid Layer

To examine the effect of geogrid-reinforcement, the strip footing was placed on the reinforced sand slope with 3 layers of reinforcement ($N = 1, 2$, and 3). Figure 3 represents the variation of the reduction factor i_{hr} with different void embedment depths ratios ($H/D = 1.5, 2, 2.5$, and 3), when the void is assumed to be located directly below the centerline of

the foundation ($X/B = 0$). It can be observed that the bearing capacity increases due to the provision of the reinforcement layers. In addition, the bearing capacity of the foundation was increased along with the number of layers of geogrid reinforcement. Additionally, as the mass of the sand layer above the void increases (increasing H/D), the shear resistance increases.

Fig. 3. Variation of reduction factor i_{hr} at different H/B .

Therefore, significant stability of the void had been observed. Also, the i_{hr} increases, regardless of the number of geogrid-reinforcement layers. Figure 3 displays that in the case of reinforced sand when $N = 1$ and H/D attained a value of 3, the bearing capacity values of the strip footing tended toward the bearing capacity of the strip footing on unreinforced sand without a void. However, with up to two layers of reinforcement, the bearing capacity of strip footing on reinforced sand with a void, is greater than the unreinforced sand's without a void. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the reinforcement layers in improving the ultimate bearing capacity of strip footings resting on a sand slope with a void.

B. Effect of Void Depth

The embedment depth of the void from the soil surface is one of the main parameters of soils with a void. Figure 4 reveals the variation of reduction factor i_h versus depth ratios (H/B) varying from 0.50 to 3.50 with an increment of 0.5. Interestingly, it is observed that the value of i_h increases continuously with increase in the value of depth ratios H/B up to a reach a limit value at $H/B = 3.5$, beyond which the reduction factor becomes constant. This limit value is called the critical depth, H_{cr} . At this specified depth, the footing behavior converges to that without void. A similar result was reported in [25]. A significant reduction in the bearing capacity value was observed when the void was located at $H/B = 0.5$ and 1. This happened because the soil layer above the void was thin and the failure surface gets smaller than the one without a void. Therefore, low pressure is necessary for the failure surface to achieve the slope, causing a decrease in bearing capacity.

Fig. 4. Variation of reduction factor i_h versus different depth ratios for $X/B=0$.

C. Effect of Horizontal Distance

Figure 5 reveals the variation of reduction factors i_h and i_{hr} , versus depth ratios (H/B), for different horizontal distance ratios ($X/B = 0, 1, 2, \text{ and } 3$) and reinforcement layers $N=0, 1, 2, 3$.

Fig. 5. Variation of i_h and i_{hr} versus different depth ratios H/B for varying X/B .

Fig. 6. Failure surface for unreinforced sand slope.

As shown in Figure 5(A), the reduction factor is affected by the position of the void (X and H). Furthermore, the value of bearing capacity increases with increasing depth distance ratios (H/B , X/B) and number of reinforcement layers. It is observed from Figure 5 that the maximum reduction on the ihr is noted when $X/B = 0$ and $H/B < 3$. For unreinforced sand, if the depth ratio H/B or X/B is greater than 3.5 and 3.0 times the width of the footing respectively, the bearing capacity of the footing does not affect by the presence of the void, while ihr is greater than 0.8. For the case of reinforced sand as shown in Figure 5(B) when $N=3$ for different X/B ratios, ihr remains constant and the corresponding value approaches 1.0. In this case, the

bearing capacity of the footing is similar to the case without void, while the influence of void becomes insignificant. As reported in [39, 40], this behavior occurs because the maximum extend of the failure zone in cohesionless soil is $3B$ below the footing and $2.5B$ on both sides. Therefore, the void is located out of the soil shear zone.

VI. FAILURE MECHANISM

Figure 6 shows the failure surfaces for the strip footing close to the unreinforced sand slope with or without a void. Various horizontal spacings between void and footing $X/B = 0, 1.0, 2.0,$ and 3.0 and different embedment depths of void H/B were considered. As shown in Figure 6, the failure mechanism depends significantly on the location of the void. When the foundation is situated on an unreinforced sand slope without void, a triangular zone formed under the foundation. The failure surface occurs at the footing side and extends laterally towards the slope, as illustrated in Figure 6(A). For the unreinforced sand case with a void, and with depth ratios $X/B = 0$ and $H/B < 3$, as can be seen in Figure 6(B), the failure surface doesn't form the triangular wedge and the void is located in the shear zone of the failure mechanism. However, the slip surface extends vertically connecting both the edges of the foundation to the upside of the void crest and is appearing smaller than the one in the case without void. On the other hand, if X/B or H/B are above 3 and 3.5 respectively, the void is located out of the rupture zone. In addition, the behavior and failure mechanism are similar to the strip footing on unreinforced sand without a void (see Figure 6(C)-(D)). This proves that the void does not affect the load-bearing capacity of strip foundations.

VII. CONCLUSION

The current numerical study analyzed the effect of underground void on the bearing capacity behavior of strip footing sitting on the crest of unreinforced and geogrid-reinforced sand slope. The main conclusions of the study are:

- It was found that the ultimate bearing capacity depends on the location of the underground void (X/B and H/B) and the number of reinforcement layers.
- The presence of voids always reduces the load carrying capacity of the footing in both unreinforced and reinforced cases.
- The ultimate bearing capacity increases with distance (X and H).
- Using geogrid reinforcement increases bearing capacity and reduces the settlement of the strip footing.
- The load-bearing capacity of a strip footing increases with increasing number of reinforcing layers.
- There is a critical distance ($X_{cr} = 3$ and $H_{cr} = 3.5$) beyond which the influence of the underground void on the footing stability is considered to be negligible.
- The depth and width of the failure surface increase with increasing vertical and horizontal distance (X and H).

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Human Emotion Detection with Electroencephalography Signals and Accuracy Analysis Using Feature Fusion Techniques and a Multimodal Approach for Multiclass Classification

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Abstract-Biological brain signals may be used to identify emotions in a variety of ways, with accuracy depended on the methods used for signal processing, feature extraction, feature selection, and classification. The major goal of the current work was to use an adaptive channel selection and classification strategy to improve the effectiveness of emotion detection utilizing brain signals. Using different features picked by feature fusion approaches, the accuracy of existing classification models' emotion detection is assessed. Statistical modeling is used to determine time-domain and frequency-domain properties. Multiclass classification accuracy is examined using Neural Networks (NNs), Lasso regression, k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF). After performing hyperparameter tuning, a remarkable increase in accuracy is achieved using Lasso regression, while RF performed well for all the feature sets. 78.02% and 76.77% accuracy were achieved for a small and noisy 24 feature dataset by Lasso regression and RF respectively whereas 76.54% accuracy is achieved by Lasso regression with the backward elimination wrapper method.

Keywords-feature fusion; DNN; Lasso regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotion detection is a part of artificial intelligence. It is a multidisciplinary area where the major fields involved are medical signal processing, artificial intelligence, machine learning, and brain-computer interfacing. It presents a collection of emotion recognition study scenarios in the following domains: software engineering, website personalization, education, gaming, and medicine. Efforts have been made in recent decades to create new methodologies and techniques for emotion identification. Researchers are increasingly interested in detecting human emotions via biological brain signals [1]. Researchers have been interested in inventing apps that would allow two individuals to communicate without really interacting. Electroencephalography (EEG) headsets are accessible on the

market and are inexpensive, allowing the study in this field without having to use complicated brain interfaces. EEG is a reliable and affordable way to measure brain activity. To achieve the criteria of a Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), emotion recognition using EEG data requires a sequence of operations to be performed, e.g. removing artifacts from the EEG data, extracting temporal or spectral information from the time or frequency domain of the EEG signal, and finally developing a multi-class classification strategy [2]. The main problem is that the extracted characteristics are calculated using the entire recorded EEG signal sample, which frequently contains incorrect information. As a result, supplementary procedures like choosing electrodes that show a big shift in brain activity during emotional states to accurately identify emotional states and conspicuous feature selection for a more precise conclusion are becoming increasingly critical. Experiments demonstrate that including these procedures expands the number of possibilities for testing the system's correctness. In the current study, a multimodal technique is employed to assess system accuracy. Techniques such as feature selection and feature fusion are employed [3].

II. RELATED WORK

Earlier research focused on either building feature extraction techniques or evaluating multiple classification models for reliable emotion detection on databases such as DEAP and SEED [1]. It is used to extract characteristics that are constant across all participants from a collection of EEG channels. NNs and SVM models are extensively used for classification and prediction. KNN is the most popular algorithm for testing emotional signals. In the studies mentioned below, work has been done on existing databases. These databases record emotional signals in a controlled environment for a predetermined length of time. It is, however, impossible to record all of the signals in a set time frame. The brain's functioning is complicated and varies from person to person as well as from one emotional state to another. Each

participant has a varied excitation time interval for each emotion. Hence the real study of emotional signals acquired in the natural world is envisaged, with a primary focus on large applications [3]. In Table I the reviewed related work is summarized.

Work on self-created databases is required in the current context. In applications such as BCI for mentally challenged persons and paralyzed people who can't convey their emotions

through words, signals must be collected in the real world rather than in a controlled setting. As a result, research on self-created databases including signals acquired in the natural world is expected. A self-created database is employed in this research investigation. The following part discusses the database construction process. To increase accuracy, the feature fusion approach is applied. For accuracy testing, a multimodal approach for multiclass classification is adopted.

TABLE I. RELATED WORK SUMMARY

Reference	No. of channels	Feature extraction algorithm	Classification models	Accuracy(%)
[4]	10	DWT, Principle component analysis	SVM	91.1
[5]	32	Minimum Redundancy Maximum Elevance (mRMR)	SVM & RF	60
[6]	5	Time-frequency domain features	DST	81.64
[7]	32	Entropy, time and frequency domain features	ANN	93.75
[8]	3	Probability distribution for wavelet packet coefficients	SVM	70.5
[9]	32	Spectral features	DBN	79.2
[10]	32	Fusing of 6 statistical features	SVM	81.87
[11]	14	Gabor function and wavelet transform	ANN	64.87
[11]	10	WT- wavelet transform	KNN	84: arousal, 86:valence
[12]	Adaptive	Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test	SVM	80.4: arousal, 71.16: valence
[13]	Adaptive	Feature Fusion- statistical, wavelet energy, wavelet entropy	SVM, KNN, QDA	83.8
[1]	Adaptive	ZTWBES	RNN	89.33

ANN: Artificial Neural Network, DWT: Discrete Wavelet Transform, RF: Random Forest, QDA: Quadratic Discriminant Analysis, ZTWBES: Zero-Time Windowing Based Epoch Estimation

III. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Emotive Epoc 14 channel headset was utilized for data collection. The experiment used a 120-emotion-signal database that was self-created, with 30 signals from each of the four considered classes (Angry, Calm, Happy, and Sad). With proper coverage and electrode configuration, it is possible to rebuild a source model of all-important brain regions and understand how they interact. The sensors are made up of saline-soaked felt pads. In Figure 1 the proposed system is shown. The first step is signal acquisition and database creation.

Fig. 1. The proposed system.

A. Database Creation

Healthy individuals were chosen based on their willingness to participate, whereas intellectually disabled subjects were

picked with their parent's permission. The Emotive Epoc 14 channel EEG headset is simple to use and comfortable to wear. The training data collection included 22 healthy volunteers (15 females, 7 males) ranging in age from 12 to 70 years old (mean = 35.55, SD = 16.97). Prior to their participation, each subject signed an informed consent form. One of the participants suffers from mild autism. She can communicate and convey basic emotions. A total of 120 emotional signals were recorded. Each emotion class has 30 emotion signals, which were stored in the Emotive cloud and could be used at a later time. Participants were given auditory stimuli to choose from in order to generate a calm feeling. Anger is elicited by the use of a visual stimulus. Self-thoughts are also used to evoke emotion in subjects. Some of our former events are strongly embedded in our minds, and revisiting them might elicit the same sort of powerful feeling. Thoughts have been found to be a very effective sort of stimulus for producing emotions. A single ADC technique and sequential sampling were employed. The rate of sampling was 2048 internal down sampled to 128 fs. The dimension of each recorded file is $41 \times \text{Number of samples} \times 60$ s. The files were edited and only the 14 electrode data were saved in .csv format. The dimension of the database is $120 \times [128 \times 60] \times [14]$. The dataset comprised of 120 files and 30 emotion signals of each emotion type (Angry, Calm, Happy, and Sad). $[128 \times 60]_{\text{rows}}$ signals were recorded for 1min at 128 fs, $[14]_{\text{col}}$ represents the electrodes. The signals were pre-processed using filtering. ICA is a technique for separating data artifacts (since they are usually independent of each other) [3]. Statistical modeling [5] was used to extract 24 characteristics from the database. The feature set's dimensions are 120×24 . Variance, Mean, Standard Deviation Kurtosis, IEEG, Skewness EEG synchronization MAV (Mean Absolute Value), Modified MAV type 1, Modified MAV type 2, Simple Square Integral (SSI), EEG-VEEG Variance Root Mean Square (RMS), absolute standard deviation difference mean2 (DASTD), PXX with autoregression, Waveform Length (WL), Band Power,

Max Pow, Max Pow Index, Harmonic Distortion, Hilbert Parameter, Power Spectral Density (PSD) [14] characteristics were considered. Figure 1 depicts the followed multimodal method.

B. Feature Fusion for Feature Selection

Classification models were utilized to assess the accuracy of emotion recognition, with feature selection and feature

fusion strategies discussed. 14 * samples wrtr captured in 1 minute and (128*60) feature set file is used. Feature selection is done by using filter method, wrapper method, and the embedded method. Feature fusion is used on the reduced feature set and tested for RF, KNN, SVM, DNN, and Lasso regression models [15]. For feature selection, filter and wrapper methods were used. As a result, these methods generate a reduced feature set.

Fig. 2. Correlation matrix.

1) Filter Method

This approach filters unnecessary features and selects only a subset of important features. After choosing the characteristics, the model is produced. Filtering is done with the Pearson correlation matrix. The reduced notable feature set is created using the steps described below.

Step 1: Create a heatmap with Pearson correlations for all 24 features.

Step 2: Examine the relationship between the independent variables and the output variable label.

Step 3: Choose characteristics that have a 0.4 or higher correlation with the output variable. The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to +1. DASTD and WL characteristics have Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.46 and 0.54 respectively.

2) Wrapper Method

It is a repeated procedure. It requires one machine learning method, which is used as an estimation criterion. Based on performance, features might be added or eliminated. This approach is more computationally expensive than the filter method, but it is more accurate. Recursive feature elimination and backward elimination are utilized.

3) Backward Elimination

The model is fed with all the potential characteristics. The model is tested every time it is used. Worst-performing features are deleted one by one until the model's overall performance is within a reasonable range. By verifying the pvalue, the features are eliminated. If the calculated pvalue is more than 0.05, the feature is excluded from consideration. For linear regression,

an OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) model is utilized. The selected features are: 'Mean', 'VAR', 'Skew', 'MAV', 'VEEG', 'DASTD', 'HA', 'HC', 'Bandpower'].

4) Recursive Feature Elimination

It ranks the features using an accuracy feature ranking approach. The model is created using all 24 characteristics. With 24 features, the Linear Regression model is utilized. It ranks all the variables from most important to the least. True represents a relevant feature and false represents an irrelevant aspect in the output. The model's accuracy is computed repeatedly for each feature. The optimum amount of characteristics with the best accuracy is chosen. It is done by looping through all the features from 1 to 24, and then selecting the one with the best accuracy.

a) Feature Ranking

- Optimum number of features: 10
- Score with 9 features: 0.54
- Index (['STDDEV', 'VAR', 'MAV', 'VEEG', 'RMS', 'DASTD', 'HA', 'Band power', 'Hilbert', 'PSD'])

b) Feature Fusion

The output of the feature selection step is a reduced feature set. In this step, 3 reduced feature sets are created and used to test system performance. The system is trained using a reduced feature set and then accuracy is tested for different classification models [4].

C. Multimodal Approach

The classification algorithms used for testing the accuracy of the feature set [7] are: KNN, SVM, RF, Lasso Regression, and multiclass classification using neural networks (DNN) [1].

1) KNN

KNN is a supervised machine learning algorithm, also known as the lazy learner or non-parametric learning method. It uses feature similarity to forecast the values of new data points, which means a new data point will be assigned a value based on how closely it resembles the points in the training set [4]. It is great for nonlinear data since it makes no assumptions about the data, and it is also great for small datasets [16].

2) SVM

The purpose of the SVM is to find a hyperplane that differentiates data points in an N-dimensional space. The number of features determines the hyperplane's size. It works well when there is a clear demarcation between the dimensions and when the number of samples is larger than the number of dimensions [9]. When the data set contains additional noise, such as overlapping target classes, it performs poorly [17].

3) RF

It creates decision trees from several samples, using the majority vote for classification and the average for regression. This method employs a meta-approach and is based on ensemble learning. It aims to improve forecast accuracy by merging predictions from various models. It associates decision tree predictions and chooses the best prediction among them.

4) Lasso Regression

It is based on the concepts of shrinkage and L1 regularization, and it employs a procedure in which data values are reduced toward the central tendency and a penalty proportional to the absolute size of coefficients is applied. This regularization results in sparse models with a few coefficients. Lasso regression helps feature selection by reducing the magnitude of λ to zero if required. The output depends on the value of λ . The followed algorithmic steps are described below:

- Importing data set
- Preprocessing:
- Making a distinction between dependent and target variables.
- Fitting the model
- Model predictions
- Check the initial score of R Square and perform hyperparameter tuning if necessary. After performing hyperparameter tuning, a remarkable increase in accuracy is observed. The hyper parameters are: param = {'alpha': [.00001,0.0001,0.001,0.01,0.1], 'fit_intercept': [True,False], 'normalize': [True,False], 'positive': [True,False], 'selection': ['cyclic','random']}. The best found hyperparameters are: {'alpha': 0.01, 'fit_intercept': True, 'normalize': False, 'positive': False, 'selection': 'random'}. After adjusting the alpha parameter and using the best parameters, the accuracy of the model increased remarkably to 78.02, which is the highest among all the models.

D. DNN: Multiclass Classification Using Neural Networks

a) Encode the Variable Output

There are 4 alternative numerical values in the output variable. When implementing NNs to represent multi-class classification issues, the output attribute must be reshaped from a vector of values for each class. Each class's value will be represented in the matrix as a Boolean type. This is referred to as "one-hot encoding." It is the process of converting category variables into dummy variables [18].

b) Create the Neural Network Model

Wrapper classes are used to define NNs. A rectifier activation function was used in the hidden layer. The output layer must produce 4 output values, 1 for each class, using one-hot encoding. The highest output value is used to determine the class. Table II summarizes the network structure of this simple one-layer NN. The softmax activation function is employed in the output layer. The output values are between 0 and 1 and may be used to calculate the expected probability. Categorical cross-entropy [10] and Adam gradient descent optimization with a logarithmic loss function [19] were used. Multi-class cross-entropy loss and Leibler Kullback divergence loss are used in multi-class classification problems. The default loss function is cross-entropy. In this, each class is given a distinct integer value, which is the preferred loss function under the maximum likelihood inference paradigm. The loss function should be estimated initially and adjusted if necessary.

TABLE II. NEURAL NETWORK TOPOLOGY

Feature Set	Feature extraction method	Topology of layers in DNN
24 feature set	Actual feature set	24 total inputs → [48 hidden nodes] → 4 outputs
Accurate24_RF_FM.csv	Extracted features after filter method	2 total inputs → [4 hidden nodes] → 4 outputs
Accurate24RF_WM_BEL.csv	Extracted features after wrapper method backward elimination	10 total inputs → [20 hidden nodes] → 4 outputs
Accurate24_RF_RFE.csv	Extracted features after wrapper method recursive feature elimination	10 total inputs → [20 hidden nodes] → 4 outputs

The average difference between the actual and the anticipated probability distributions is calculated via cross-entropy for all classes [20]. A measure of how dissimilar one probability distribution is from another is the Leibler Kullback divergence. It determines the wasted data (in bits) when the

anticipated probability distribution is used to approach the desired target probability distribution. In the training phase, the number of epochs passed was 200, and the batch size was 5 [10]. Using the 10-fold cross-technique, the model was evaluated on the dataset, a process that takes around 10s to be concluded, and it provided an object that specifies the assessment of the 10 built models for each of the dataset splits.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, features are produced using the feature fusion approach, and multiple classification models are used after parameters are adjusted to attain maximum accuracy. The goal of this research is to get the maximum accuracy possible for the multiclass classification issue with tiny and noisy data sets. For this sort of database, the Lasso regression and RF algorithms appear to perform better.

TABLE III. ACCURACY COMPARISON

Feature selection method	Feature fusion	DNN	Lasso regression	KNN	SVM	RF
24 feature set	'Mean', 'STD', 'VAR', 'SKEW', 'Kurtosis', 'IEEG', 'MAV', 'MAV10', 'MAV20', 'SSI', 'VEEG', 'RMS', 'DASTD', 'AREG_PXX', 'HA', 'HM', 'HC', 'WL', 'BANDPOWER', 'PERODOGRAM1 (MaxPow)', 'PERODOGRAM2 (max Pow index)', 'ENVELOPE (Harmonic Dis)', 'Hilbert', 'PSD' [3]	29.17	78.02	33.33	44	72.66
Filter method	WL, DASTD	31.67	51.19	63	19.4	66.6
	WL	31.67	51.89	63	0	68.44
Wrapper method: Backward elimination	'Mean', 'VAR', 'Skew', 'MAV', 'VEEG', 'DASTD', 'HA', 'HC', 'Bandpower', 'PSD'	30.83	76.54	36	25	64.58
Wrapper method: RFE	'STDDEV', 'VAR', 'MAV', 'VEEG', 'RMS', 'DASTD', 'HA', 'Bandpower', 'Hilbert', 'PSD'	15.83	63.46	36	19.4	67.47

Fig. 3. The accuracy plot.

In Table III, the comparison of the accuracy using feature fusion and the multimodal approaches for multiclass classification is presented. In this research study, 24 features

are extracted from the database. Three feature sets are constructed using the feature fusion approach, which are then utilized to assess the classification accuracy using KNN, SVM,

NNs, RF, and Lasso regression classification models. Four feature sets were used to evaluate the performance of the KNN method. For the 24 feature set, the greatest accuracy produced by KNN was 33.33% for most of the K values and 36% for the feature set generated using the wrapper technique, which is extremely low due to the high dimensional database. It is calculated in a significant way for the feature set produced using the feature selection filter approach. For this small and noisy database, SVM and DNN –models did not perform well. RF performed better because it is less prone to overfitting, it is typically resistant to outliers, and can deal with them on its own. After changing the hyperparameters to match the model, Lasso regression works well for the 24 feature set and the feature set produced using the wrapper technique. It is quite difficult to acquire high accuracy for a self-created database of signals gathered in natural settings.

V. CONCLUSION

After changing the hyperparameters for the 24 feature set, Lasso regression was found to have the greatest accuracy of 78.02%. The best hyperparameters were adjusted as mentioned above, with the trial and error method. Backward elimination of the wrapper approach achieved 76.64% accuracy. For all the feature sets, the RF algorithm worked admirably. When compared to other classification models, the DNN algorithm's accuracy is quite low, and the database's limited size might be the cause. Also the SVM model did not perform well, because the limits of target classes overlap. The experimental findings show that on small and noisy datasets, Lasso regression and RF employing feature selection and feature fusion techniques perform better.

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD STATEMENT

This research study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. This research study is not at all being conducted for diagnosis or treatment of any disease. This research study is purely used for research applications and personal use.

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Wear and Indentation Resistance of Polyethylene Nanocomposites at High Temperatures

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Abstract—The presence of nanofillers in the polyethylene matrix can play an important role in changing their behavior during mechanical testing. Moreover, high ambient temperature can seriously affect the properties of polyethylene and cause softening, which leads to a decrease in stiffness, strength, hardness, and wear resistance. In the current work, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanoclays with 0.5wt.% are embedded into polyethylene blend matrix to enhance its mechanical properties, mainly wear and indentation resistance at different ambient temperatures. The results show that the processing method used resulted in homogenous distribution and good dispersion of nanofillers. The addition of 0.5 wt.% CNT or nanoclays increased the indentation and wear resistance at both room and high temperatures. At high temperatures, the presence of nanofillers caused an increase in wear resistance by 32.2% at maximum depth.

Keywords—polyethylene; wear; indentation; temperature; nanotube; mechanical properties

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanoindentation testing is an alternative method that can be used to assess the near-surface properties of polymeric materials like wear and penetration resistance [1]. This type of near-surface property testing has been widely applied for polymeric materials loaded with nanoparticles to investigate the correlation between properties and volume of fraction of nanoparticles [2-8]. However, up to date, most nanoindentation experiments are limited to evaluating near-surface properties of polymeric materials at room temperature, whereas, elevated temperatures have remarkable effects on the properties of polymeric materials within their operating environments. Therefore, instrumented indentation techniques have been developed to perform testing under various environmental conditions including high temperatures and moisture to meet the commercial requirements [9-15]. Polyethylene-based nanocomposites are attractive to researchers due to their wide range of applications and types [16-18]. Moreover, they have ease machinability, competitive cost, and various processing methods in addition to good properties like corrosion resistance, flexibility, ductility, and impact resistance. However, it is known that temperature has severe effects on the

properties of polymeric materials, which cause softening and lower their properties.

This work is carried out to evaluate the effects of nanoparticle addition on the penetration and wear resistance of polyethylene at different temperatures (22.8 and 40°C). A low volume of fractions of carbon nanotubes and nanoclays (0.5wt.%) were embedded separately into the blend of polymeric materials to improve their mechanical properties, mainly wear and penetration resistance.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Materials

Nanoclay and CNTs were added separately to blended polymers of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene and high-density polyethylene. The ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene powder has an average molecular weight of 3×10^6 g/mol, and was provided by SABIC Company, Saudi Arabia. The high-density polyethylene pellets were purchased from ExxonMobil Chemical Europe, Belgium. Nanoclay was provided by Elementis specialties, USA and Multi-wall Nanotubes (MWNT) with an average diameter of 25nm were purchased from Nanocyl, Belgium.

B. Processing

A twin-screw extruder was used to blend 75wt.% of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene with 25wt.% of high-density polyethylene. Then, two types of nanoparticles were embedded separately into the polymeric matrix using similar conditions. These types are CNTs and nanoclay with a constant volume fraction of 0.5wt.% to form polyethylene nanocomposites. The mini twin-screw extruder consists of five controlled zones from the feeding port to the die. The processing parameters used in this work are shown in Table I. The extruder produces small pellets which are then compressed using a hot press with 190°C to form a square mould (100×100×1.65mm). Various moulding pressure and holding times were applied to find the optimal one which was 309MPa moulding pressure and 15min holding time. Then, water was used to cool the mould to room temperature.

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TABLE I. PROCESSING METHOD PARAMETERS

Extruder speed (rpm)	Processing temperature (°C)					Cooling
	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Die	
400	180	190	200	210	220	water

C. Material Testing and Characterization

Various characterization techniques were applied to evaluate the dispersion and distribution of nanoparticles in the matrix of polyethylene nanocomposites. They were investigated using two experimental techniques, which are Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). A NanoTest Machine 600 from Micro Materials Ltd (Wrexham, UK) was used to perform the wear test on the specimens using a controlled chamber at temperatures of 22.8 and 40°C. A diamond Rockwell tip, with a 200µm radius, 2mN load, 10µm/s speed, and 10 scratches was applied. The surface morphology of the polymer nanocomposite was investigated using a sharp tip (in the range of 5-10nm) of an Atomic Force Microscope manufactured by Veeco Instruments Inc. (Cambridge, UK). Then, the Nanoscope software was used to analyze the data. An instrumented indentation machine with a controlled chamber Micro Materials Ltd (Wrexham, UK) was used to perform the experiments under temperatures of 22.8 and 40°C. At least 10 indents were made using a Berkovich indenter, with a face angle of 65.3° with 10mN maximum load, 600s dwell period, and 2mN/s loading and unloading rates. Oliver and Pharr method [19] was applied to analyze the results. In this method, the initial portion of the unloading curve is described by the power law relation:

$$P = \alpha (h - hr)m \quad (1)$$

where P is the load, α and m are constants determined by curve fitting, h is penetration depth and hr is the depth of the residual impression. The contact stiffness (S) can be obtained by:

$$S = \frac{dP}{dh}(h = h_{max}) = m \propto (h_{max} - h_r)^{m-1} \quad (2)$$

The contact depth (h_c) at maximum load (P_{max}) can be estimated using:

$$h_c = h_{max} - \varepsilon \frac{P_{max}}{S} \quad (3)$$

where ε is a constant related to the geometry of the indenter, which is 0.75 for the Berkovich indenter and h_{max} is the maximum penetration depth. Thus, the projected contact area (A_c) is determined from h_c by the following relation:

$$A_c \approx 24.5 h_c^2 \quad (4)$$

and hence the indentation hardness (H) is:

$$H = \frac{P_{max}}{A_c} = \frac{P_{max}}{24.5 h_c^2} \quad (5)$$

The reduced modulus can be calculated from stiffness (S) using the relation:

$$S = \frac{dP}{dh} = \beta \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} E_r \sqrt{A} \quad (6)$$

where $A=24.5 h_p^2$, E_r is the reduced modulus, and β is a correction factor that depends on the type of indenter (1.034 for

Berkovich indenter). Consequently, the elastic modulus (E_s) for the specimen can be calculated using the equation:

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{(1-\nu_s)^2}{E_s} + \frac{(1-\nu_i)^2}{E_i} \quad (7)$$

where E_s , ν_s and E_i , ν_i are the elastic modulus and the Poisson's ratios of the specimen and the indenter respectively, ($E_i = 1141 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_i = 0.07$).

A dwell period of 600s was applied at maximum load to minimize the effect of viscoelastic behavior (nose).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Nanoparticle Dispersion and Distribution

Dispersion and distribution of nanoparticles into the matrix are very important factors that significantly affect the mechanical properties of the processed polymer-based nanocomposite. Figures 1 and 2 show that CNTs and nanoclays were dispersed very well into the polyethylene blend. Figure 3 shows the surface morphology of the three materials investigated in the current paper. Figure 3(a) shows the blend without any additions, whereas Figures 3(b)-(c) indicate the presence of nanoclays and CNTs on the surface of the tested materials. Moreover, it can be seen that the nanoparticles are distributed homogeneously on the surface of polyethylene nanocomposite, which indicates the effectiveness of the applied processing technique.

Fig. 1. SEM images showing the dispersion of nanoparticles into the blend matrix: (a) blend, (b) blend with 0.5wt.% clay, and (c) blend with 0.5wt.% CNT.

Fig. 2. TEM images showing the presence of nanoparticles in the blend: (a) blend with 0.5wt.% clay and (b) blend with 0.5wt.% CNT.

Fig. 3. AFM images showing the surface morphology of: (a) blend, (b) blend with 0.5wt.% clay, and (c) blend with 0.5wt.% CNT.

Fig. 4. Indentation behavior of polyethylene nanocomposites at different ambient temperatures: (a) 22.8°C, (b) 40°C.

B. Nanoindentation Behavior

Figure 4 shows the indentation behavior of the blend and its nanocomposites. It is clear that the addition of 0.5wt.% nanoclays enhanced the indentation resistance of the blend at both room and high temperatures. More enhancement in indentation resistance is achieved by the embedding of CNT into the blend's matrix at similar conditions. This can be attributed to the difference in geometry between CNT (one-dimensional shape) and clay (two-dimensional shape).

Moreover, the interaction between nanoparticles and the matrix is another important factor that depends on the bond strength between the two materials and the interface thickness and properties.

C. Wear Resistance

The incorporation of nanofillers into polymeric matrix can significantly affect the tribological performance of polymer nanocomposites [20]. This is achieved by improving the load bearing capacity and reducing the crack initiation in the surface. However, it is known that nanofiller geometry has a great influence on the mechanical behavior and the mobility of polymer chains. Therefore, investigating the effect of two types of nanofillers with different geometry on the wear resistance of polyethylene nanocomposites at different ambient temperatures is a novel work. It can be seen in Figure 5 that the addition of CNT and nanoclays has significant influence on the wear resistance of polyethylene-based nanocomposites.

Fig. 5. Wear resistance of polyethylene nanocomposites at different ambient temperatures: (a) 22.8°C, (b) 40°C.

The addition of a low volume fraction of nanofillers resulted in a 25% increase in wear resistance and maximum depth at room temperature. At high temperatures, the presence of these nanofillers caused an increase in wear resistance by

32.2% at maximum depth. These results indicate that nanocomposites have higher wear resistance at different ambient temperatures. This can be attributed to the presence of nanofillers, which disrupted the movement of polymeric chains. Moreover, the application of high temperature on the blended material caused a reduction in wear resistance by 15%. On the other hand, only a 5% reduction in wear resistance is observed for nanocomposites at high temperatures. This indicated that the use of polymer-based nanocomposites increases wear resistance of blends at various ambient temperatures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, homogeneous distribution and good dispersion of nanofillers were achieved using an in-house processing method. The addition of a low volume fraction of nanofillers caused an increase in indentation resistance of polymer-based nanocomposites at various ambient temperatures. Moreover, the presence of CNTs and nanoclays in the polymeric materials resulted in a significant improvement in wear resistance at both room and high temperatures, due to the chain movement mechanisms of the nanofillers, which work as obstacles for chain movements during the application of the load.

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The Fisher Component-based Feature Selection Method

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Abstract-A feature selection technique is proposed in this paper, which combines the computational ease of filters and the performance superiority of wrappers. The technique sequentially combines Fisher-score-based ranking and logistic regression-based wrapping. On synthetically generated data, the 5-fold cross-validation performances of the proposed technique were compatible with the performances achieved through Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO). The binary classification performances in terms of F1 score and Geometric Mean (GM) were evaluated over a varying imbalance ratio of 0.1:0.9 – 0.5:0.5, a number of informative features of 1 – 30, and a fixed sample size of 5000.

Keywords-feature selection; regularization; dimensionality reduction; class imbalance

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of low-cost electronics, the dimensions and complexity of datasets, e.g. the Internet of Things (IoT), text classification, and medical imaging, are constantly increasing. High dimensional datasets, compared to their low dimensional counterparts, require more processing time and more space complexity, which is known as the curse of dimensionality. Besides, the presence of irrelevant and/or redundant features leads to less-interpretable and over-fitted learning models. The issue becomes more severe when the number of features is more than the number of instances/samples like gene selection in microarray data, where typically the data examples are fewer than 100 and the number of raw features ranges from 6,000 to 60,000 [1]. In such a situation, a trained model may become useless as it would result in infinitely high variance [2]. Furthermore, the covariance/correlation-based methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Fisher Discriminant Analysis (FDA), and linear regression become ill-posed problems. A common way to address the issue is to select the informative and non-redundant features from a known feature set, which results in lower dimension datasets. The use of such datasets improves the generalized accuracy of a trained model, reduces computational time, and improves model interpretability.

Three categories of feature selection, i.e. filter, wrapper, and embedded methods, are widely been used. The filters

measure the relevance (e.g., Fisher score, mutual information, correlation [3-5]) of a feature with the target. Filters are computationally fast, simple, easy to scale, and generally don't require a learning model [6]. A filter, however, generally ignores feature dependencies and does not consider combined discriminatory power, and consequently, can result in suboptimal feature selection [7]. Wrappers evaluate the usefulness of features' subsets by training and testing a model on them, and generally use a cross-validation method. Forward feature selection, backward elimination, and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) are the most common used wrapper methods. The optimal feature combination that maximizes the overall performance is determined by adding and/or removing features. Wrapper methods are, however, computationally expensive. Greedy (best subset) selection requires 2^p , whereas, both forward and backward feature selection techniques require at least $\frac{p(p+1)}{2}$ models/iterations [2]. Embedded (also known as shrinkage) methods intrinsically maximize the overall performance during the training/learning of a model, like a Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) or l_1 regularization [4]. However, not all the models such as k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), and decision tree incorporate l_1 regularization during their training.

Contrary to feature selection techniques, dimensionality reduction techniques project the original input data into a lower-dimensional feature space and don't require learning/training. PCA is a classical data analysis and dimensionality reduction technique, which captures the maximum variability in data. PCA transforms the feature space into a new (meta) orthogonal feature space of the same dimension. Its effectiveness is, however, limited to unsupervised problems. FDA on the other hand is a traditional supervised dimensionality reduction technique, which respectively maximizes and minimizes the between-class distance and within-class mean distance. Contrary to PCA, the dimension of the FDA-transformed data is one less than the number of classes (i.e. $C - 1$) [8, 9].

Authors in [4] ranked the features per the sum of absolute values of the coefficients of the first two principal components. The ranked features were then evaluated with a wrapper. They

compared the results with the ones from analysis of variance (ANOVA), absolute correlation, and classifier-based ranking, and achieved higher performance. Since PCA is unsupervised, their method may underperform in real datasets when the classification-related information is different from the direction of the maximum variance. Several feature selection techniques have been published and implemented in well-known machine learning libraries like Python's sklearn, and Matlab. These techniques, however, uniquely behave with varying datasets, like different models select different features in standard wrapper feature selection techniques. For class imbalanced datasets, most of the classification models [10] and, subsequently, the wrapper and embedded feature selection techniques, perform poorly, i.e. may not accurately determine all informative features. The identification of the most suitable features with varying class imbalance ratios is therefore of much importance and requires a solid solution.

In this paper, a feature selection technique is proposed, that combines the computational ease of filters and the performance superiority of wrappers. The technique sequentially combines Fisher-score-based ranking and logistic regression-based wrapping. In doing so, the proposed technique requires the training of a maximum of p models. On synthetically generated data, the proposed technique gave a very compatible mean of 5-fold cross-validation F1-scores and Geometric Means (GM) to LASSO. The binary classification performances were evaluated over a variable imbalance ratio of 0.1:0.9 – 0.5:0.5.

II. METHODS AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A simulation study was conducted to examine the effect of informative and non-informative features on feature selection techniques. Like [4], synthetic data of 30 features with varying imbalance rates and noise (i.e. non-informative features), were generated using the "make_classification" library in python's scikit-learn.datasets. Each of the binary classes was a single cluster. The informative features were drawn independently from the normal (0,1) distribution for each class and then combined as random linear combinations within each cluster to add covariance [11]. The non-informative features were represented by random noise. The datasets were generated with varying number of informative features from 1 – 30, and with a step of 2. The imbalance rates were changed from 0.1:0.9 – 0.5:0.5, and the sample size was fixed to 5000 samples. The model was validated using 5-fold cross-validation.

A. Feature Ranking

Feature ranking is to place the features in an order per their importance in order to identify the most important features. For this purpose, FDA was used. For binary classification, FDA results in one component. The features were ranked according to the absolute values of their respective coefficients in the FDA component. Eigenvalues and eigenvectors respectively indicate the explained variance of an FDA component and the linear combination of the original features, i.e. $FC = w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + \dots + w_px_p$, where x_j is j^{th} feature and w_j is corresponding weight of j^{th} feature. Eigenvalues and eigenvectors are computed from $S_W^{-1}S_B$, where S_W and S_B are respectively the within-class and between-class scatter matrix, defined as:

$$S_B = \sum_{j=1}^c n_j (\mu_j - \mu) (\mu_j - \mu)^T \quad (1)$$

$$S_W = \sum_{x \in D_j} (x - \mu_j) (x - \mu_j)^T \quad (2)$$

where μ_j , n_j , and c are the mean vector, the number of instances (observations) for class j , and the total number of classes respectively.

B. Feature Selection

The ranked features were further sequentially evaluated using the logistic regression-based wrapper, shown in Figure 1. The top-ranked feature was first fed to the classifier and the classification performance due to class imbalance rate was recorded in terms of F1 score. Then iteratively, the next consecutively ranked feature was added. At each iteration, a feature was added to the subset if its combined mean 5-fold cross-validation classification performance was higher than the previous iteration. The feature was otherwise discarded. The value of C was kept high (i.e. 1×10^9) to avoid inherent LASSO or ridge regularization by the classifier.

C. LASSO

LASSO, defined as $\|\beta\|_1 = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|$, is a practical strategy to perform feature selection and classification simultaneously. $\|\cdot\|_1$ and $\lambda > 0$ are the l_1 -norm and regularization parameter respectively. LASSO selects the features by generating a sparse weight vector (few non-zero coefficients). Consequently, LASSO reduces the variance and the intricacy of the model, and therefore, is an alternative feature selection technique [12]. Non-zero coefficients indicate the importance of the respective features, whereas, zero coefficients indicate irrelevant and redundant features. The number of non-zero coefficients are roughly controlled via λ . Larger the λ , sparser is the weight vector and vice versa. The optimal value of $C = \frac{1}{\lambda}$ was therefore selected from a range 10^{-3} - 10^3 with a step of 10, using 5-fold cross-validation via grid search method.

Fig. 1. The proposed feature selection technique. $X^{n \times p}$ is the training feature set, where n is the number of examples/instances and p is the number of features. $y^{n \times 1}$ shows n binary training labels. C_p represents p coefficients/weights of the Fisher component.

D. Classification

A commonly used logistic regression classifier [13] was used to validate the efficacy of the proposed feature selection technique under varying imbalance rates and number of irrelevant features. Let a feature vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ with n rows, and an associate class labels/target $y \in \{0, 1\}$ be the training data for logistic regression classifier defined as:

$$p(y/X) = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta x)}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta x)} \quad (3)$$

where $p(y/x)$ is the conditional probability of a target given a feature \mathbf{x} , and β shows the classifier's parameters.

Class imbalance is generally handled by sampling the data or modifying the classifier. Standard classification algorithms generally use a default threshold of 0.5 to assign class membership. Any adjustments to such threshold change the class membership referred to as cost-sensitive learning. Simulation studies have shown that cost-sensitive learning can increase the sensitivity and decrease the specificity and vice versa. However, the accuracy more or less remains the same. The synthetically generated datasets were skewed or class-imbalanced. The cost-sensitive learning was therefore employed by assigning equal prior probabilities (0.5) to both classes to account for the class imbalance ratio in the training datasets. A generalized classification system was attained using stratified 5-fold cross-validation.

E. Evaluation of the Feature Selection Techniques

As the datasets were synthetically generated, we have the prior knowledge of informative and non-informative features. Each row of the matrix shown in Table I was used to describe the performances of the proposed and LASSO feature selection methods. Both feature selection techniques were evaluated using true positive rate, i.e. $TPR = \frac{CS}{IF}$, false positive rate, i.e. $FPR = \frac{IS}{IF}$, and true selected positive rate, i.e. $TSPR = \frac{CS}{TS}$. CS , IS , and TS are the number of correctly, incorrectly, and total selected features respectively. IF is the number of informative features used in the datasets. The performances of the proposed method and LASSO at selecting features were the average of 5-fold cross-validation with balanced datasets and varying number of informative features.

F. Evaluation of the Overall Classification Performance

For a binary-class problem, multiple confusion matrix-based performance metrics like sensitivity, specificity, and precision are commonly used. These metrics, however, by themselves are incomplete. Practically, combinations of these metrics are used to summarize the entire performance. For class imbalance datasets, F1 score $\left(\frac{(1+\beta^2)sensitivity \times precision}{\beta^2 \times sensitivity + precision}\right)$ and geometric mean (GM) $(\sqrt{sensitivity \times specificity})$ have been the widely used measures of performance. The overall performances of the system under varying class imbalance ratios were therefore measured in F1 score and GM. The coefficient β shows the relative preference of sensitivity against precision [14]. In this study, both sensitivity and precision were given the same weight, and therefore, $\beta = 1$.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I shows the mean 5-fold cross-validation feature selection performances of LASSO and the proposed method with varying number of informative features out of a total of 30 features. With balanced datasets, and irrespective of the number of informative features, LASSO compared to the proposed method had higher TPR but at the cost of higher FPR. This indicates that LASSO correctly selected more features than the total number of informative features, and can therefore result in an over-complex model. Besides computational requirements, such models are hard to interpret. Conversely, the proposed method, compared to LASSO, gave lower FPR and selected fewer features, and subsequently, can result in a simpler model.

TABLE I. MEAN 5-FOLD FEATURE SELECTION PERFORMANCES OF THE PROPOSED AND LASSO FEATURE SELECTION METHODS

IF (out of 30)	LASSO			Proposed		
	CS	IS	TS	CS	IS	TS
10	8	17	25	5	7	12
15	11	11	22	8	6	14
20	17	9	26	12	7	19
25	24	5	29	16	3	19

Figure 2 indicates the mean 5-fold performances of the proposed method and LASSO with logistic regression classifier and with the balanced datasets. The number of informative features out of the total 30 features varied from 1 to 30 features with a step of 2 features. The remaining features (i.e. total features – informative features) were the irrelevant features consisting of noise. On average, both LASSO and the proposed method gave similar results. Irrespective of the number of informative features and the feature selection technique, both GM and F1 score exhibited similar trends, indicating a balanced dataset. The fluctuations in both the performance measures are due to the number of informative features. Higher performances indicate that both feature selection techniques have correctly selected the informative features, whereas, lower performances indicate that some of the irrelevant features have also been selected, and informative features have been rejected by both methods as shown in Table I.

Figure 3 shows the mean 5-fold cross-validation performance of the proposed method and LASSO on the datasets with 20 informative and 10 irrelevant features. The class imbalance ratio varied from 0.1:0.9 to 0.5:0.5. Both LASSO and the proposed method gave similar results. However, the F1 score linearly increased with the decrease in the imbalance rates, and subsequently, the maximum values were achieved with the balanced datasets, whereas, the imbalance rate did not demonstrate much of its effect on the GM because it involves specificity and sensitivity, and does not tell about the number of false positives.

The proposed method, compared to LASSO, resulted in simpler models with comparable classification performance (see Table I, Figures 2-3).

Fig. 2. Effect of number of informative features on classification performances on synthetically generated class-balanced dataset.

Fig. 3. Effect of imbalance ratio 0.1:0.9 – 0.5:0.5 on the classification performance using 20 informative and 10 irrelevant features.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an alternative feature selection technique is presented that uses the simplicity of a filter and the performance superiority of a wrapper. The proposed technique requires fewer models than its counterparts, i.e. forward and backward feature selection methods. Unlike regularization, the proposed method can easily be used with any classifier. Furthermore, the overall classification performance of the proposed method was comparable to the one of LASSO (a regularization technique), in terms of F1 score and GM.

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The Effect of Geometric Parameters on the Strength of Stone Columns

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Abstract-Many geotechnical sites are unsuitable for construction due to their low bearing capacity. In the present study, stone column technique has been analyzed for the ground improvement of soft clayey soil. The change in bearing capacity of stone columns with variation in static parameters has been estimated using Indian Standard Code 15284 (IS Code) - 2003, Bouassida's method (1994), and Afshar's and Ghazavi's method (2014). From the analytical solution of the expression by the IS Code method for bearing capacity of the stone column, it is found that with the increase in diameter of the column, the bearing capacity of the stone column increases. Comparison of the results from the three methods has been conducted and it was found that values obtained from IS Code are very close to those obtained by the other two analytical methods. Also, the critical interpretation of the results shows that the IS Code gives safer design values for a wide range of the static parameters. The results of the IS Code were compared with the experimental findings to evaluate the ability of the method to design the actual load carrying capacity of the stone column.

Keywords-ground improvement; clay; bearing capacity; reinforced soil

I. INTRODUCTION

The stone column is one of the most important techniques used for improving ground quality. The construction technique for stone column comes under vibro - replacement. It increases the bearing capacity of the ground to remarkable extent and also reduces the post construction settlement of weak soils [1-11]. The first use of stone columns was done in Europe in 1834 [12]. Stone columns act as reinforcement and vertical drains for the soft clayey soils. They increase the bearing capacity of the ground by enhancing the horizontal component of effective stress [13-14]. Drainage function of stone columns is very useful in the mitigation of damages due to liquefaction. Stone columns are constructed by filling cylindrical cavities in soil stratum with granular material that increases the rate of consolidation. Consolidation is highly affected by the compressibility in the smear zone for smaller diameter to spacing (S/D) ratio of the stone columns [15, 16]. The techniques used for installing stone columns in Indian subcontinent are explained in [17]. The authors concluded that stone columns can be installed by both displacement and non-

displacement methods. Due to the reinforcement of soil by highly compacted granular material, the settlement of the soil also decreases [18, 19]. Greater stiffness of stone columns compared to that of the surrounding soil causes a large portion of the vertical load to be transferred to the columns. Therefore, the entire soil below the foundation behaves as a reinforced soil with higher load carrying capacity. A group of stone columns gives better stability than a single stone column of huge diameter [20, 21]. Spacing and diameter of the stone columns are two critical parameters that affect their bearing capacity. Several researchers have studied the deformation pattern of groups of stone columns keeping in view factors like depth and spacing [22, 23].

A lower bound solution for the estimation of the bearing capacity of a foundation resting on reinforced soil using rigorous analytical results of the yield design theory was proposed in [24]. Coulomb's lateral earth pressure theory was used to predict the stone column ultimate bearing capacity in [27]. Researchers regarded an imaginary retaining wall to develop a simple analytical solution for estimating the bearing capacity. They analyzed the effect of parameters such as column diameter, friction angle of the column material, and column spacing on the ultimate bearing capacity of the stone column [24-29]. The present study deals in finding the optimum spacing of the stone columns when they are provided in group to achieve maximum bearing capacity. For different values of diameter and spacing of the columns, bearing capacity has been calculated using IS 15284 Part-I [30], by varying the angle of internal friction of granular column material. The estimated values of bearing capacities of the reinforced soil from IS Code method have been compared with the bearing capacity values obtained in [24] and [27] and finally conclusions have been drawn regarding the effect of these parameters on the ultimate bearing capacity of a stone column.

II. METHODOLOGY

The major materials used in the analysis of stone columns are clay (soft soil) and aggregates (stones). The range of physical parameters used in this study for the prediction of the bearing capacity of the stone columns are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS USED IN THE ANALYSIS

Parameter	Range	Reference
Diameter, D	0.5m – 1.5m	[16]
Spacing, S	$2D - 3D$	[2]
Angle of internal friction, ϕ	$35^\circ - 45^\circ$	[20]
Critical length	$3D - 5D$	[15]
	$2D$	[24]

A. Bearing Capacity Using the IS Code Method

IS:15284 Part I [30] is a simple analytical method for calculating the ultimate bearing capacity of a stone column which uses Coulomb's lateral earth pressure theory.

1) Capacity Based on the Bulging of the Column

Considering that the foundation soil is at failure when stressed horizontally due to the bulging of the stone column, the limiting (yield) axial stress in the column is given by the sum of the following:

$$\sigma_v = \sigma_{rl} K_{pcol}$$

$$\sigma_v = (\sigma_{ro} + 4C_u) K_{pcol} \quad (1)$$

where σ_v is the limiting axial stress in the column when it approaches shear failure due to bulging, σ_{rl} is the limiting radial stress, which is equal to $\sigma_{ro} + 4C_u$, C_u is the undisturbed undrained shear strength of the clay surrounding the column, and σ_{ro} is the initial effective radial stress = $K_o \sigma_{vo}$, where K_o is the average coefficient of lateral earth pressure for clays equal to 0.6, K_o is the average initial effective vertical stress considering an average bulge depth twice as the diameter, i.e. $\sigma_{vo} = \gamma (2D)$, γ is the effective unit weight of soil within the influence zone, and $K_{pcol} = \tan^2(45^\circ + \frac{\phi}{2})$, where ϕ_c is the angle of internal friction of the granular column material. The safe load on column alone is given by:

$$Q_1 = \frac{\sigma_v \times \frac{\pi D^2}{4}}{2} \quad (2)$$

where $A_c = \frac{\pi}{4} D^2$ is the cross-sectional area of stone column and 2 is the factor of safety.

2) Surcharge Effect

Initially, the surcharge load is carried completely by the rigid column. As the column dilates, some load is shared by the intervening soil. Consolidation of soil under this load results in an increase in its strength which provides additional lateral resistance against bulging. The increase in capacity of the column due to surcharge may be computed in terms of increase in mean radial stress of the soil as follows:

$$\Delta\sigma_{ro} = \frac{q_{safe}}{3} (1 + 2K_o) \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{ro}$ is the increase in mean radial stress due to surcharge and q_{safe} is the safe bearing pressure of soil with a factor of safety of 2.5:

$$q_{safe} = \frac{C_u N_c}{2.5}$$

So, the increase in the safe load of column, Q_2 is given by:

$$Q_2 = \frac{K_{pcol} \Delta\sigma_{ro} A_s}{2} \quad (4)$$

3) Bearing Support Provided by the Intervening Soil

This component consists of the intrinsic capacity of the virgin soil to support a vertical load which may be computed as follows:

The effective area of stone column including the intervening soil for triangular pattern is equal to $0.866S^2$. The area of intervening soil for each column, A_g is given by:

$$A_g = 0.866S^2 - \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \quad (5)$$

The safe load taken by the intervening soil is:

$$Q_3 = q_{safe} A_g \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the overall safe load on each column and its tributary soil is:

$$Q_{safe} = Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3 \quad (7)$$

B. Bearing Capacity by Bouassida's [24] Method

The Bouassida's formula [24] for the estimation of bearing capacity is:

$$\frac{Q_{cc}}{A} = 4C + 2\eta [C(K_p - 2) + C\sqrt{K_p}] \quad (8)$$

where Q_{cc} is the lower-bound estimate for the foundation bearing capacity, C is the cohesion of the reinforcing material, η the proportion of reinforcement, K_p is the coefficient of passive stress of the reinforcing material.

C. Bearing Capacity by Afshar's and Ghazavi's [27] Design Method

To calculate the ultimate bearing capacity of stone columns, an imaginary retaining wall is assumed that extends from the edge of the columns in the vertical direction. The center to center spacing of the columns is S and the entire system is analyzed using plane strain condition by converting the stone columns into equal sized vertical strip walls. The lateral distance between the walls is estimated to be 0.866 times S . The width W of the continuous strip wall is related to spacing as: $W = \frac{A_s}{S}$, where A_s is the cross section area of the stone column (in the horizontal direction). The ultimate bearing pressure is given by:

$$q_{ult} = C_c \left(\frac{2 \cos \frac{\phi_c}{2} \sqrt{K_{pc}}}{\cos \frac{\phi_s}{2} K_{as}} \right) + \bar{q} \left(\frac{K_{pc} \cos \frac{\phi_c}{2}}{K_{as} \cos \frac{\phi_s}{2}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} W \gamma_c \left(\frac{K_{pc} \cos \frac{\phi_c}{2}}{K_{as} \cos \frac{\phi_s}{2}} - \frac{\gamma_s}{\gamma_c} \right) \tan \eta_a$$

where C_c is the cohesion of the soil, ϕ_c is the angle of internal friction, K_{pc} is the lateral passive earth pressure coefficient, K_{as} is the lateral active earth pressure coefficient, \bar{q} is the surcharge pressure on passive region surface, γ_c is the unit weight of the column material, γ_s is the unit weight of the soil material, and η_a is the angle of active wedge with horizontal direction.

III. RESULTS

A. Parametric Study Using the IS Code Method

The results of IS Code method [30] have been obtained for soft clays of different area ratios. The ratio of center to center spacing between the columns and the diameter of the column are taken as $S/D = 1.5$, $S/D = 2$ and $S/D = 3$. The effect of the angle of internal friction of the stone column material (ϕ), unit weight (γ), and soil cohesion (C_u) on the bearing capacity of stone column is studied. The bearing capacity obtained by varying the above-mentioned parameters is presented in Figures 1-6. To study the effect of variation of ϕ on the bearing capacity of the stone columns, the value of bearing capacity is calculated for S/D ratio equal to 2, 3, and 1.5 for 2 sets with diameters: $D = 0.5$ and $D = 1.5$. It was observed that bearing capacity increases with decrease in S/D ratio and diameter of the stone column plays an important role in its bearing capacity. When the friction angle varied from 35° to 45° , there has been continuous increase in the value of bearing capacity. Also, the percentage change in bearing capacity is 44.80% for $S = 1.5 D$, 34.57% for $S = 2D$, and approximately, 21% for $S = 3D$ for $D = 0.5$ m. Similarly, for $D = 1.5$ m, when friction angle varied from 35° to 45° , the percentage change in bearing capacity is 46.42% for $S = 1.5 D$, 36.88% for $S = 2D$ and 23.23% for $S = 3D$. Figures 1 and 2 show the variation of bearing capacity (q) with the angle of internal friction (ϕ), at $D = 0.5$ m and 1.5 m respectively. It is observed that, bearing capacity shows direct relation with angle of internal friction.

Fig. 1. Variation of bearing capacity with angle of internal friction ϕ ($D=0.5$ m).

Fig. 2. Variation of bearing capacity with angle of internal friction ϕ ($D=1.5$ m).

Fig. 3. Variation of bearing capacity q with diameter D .

The second geometric parameter responsible for affecting the bearing capacity of the stone column is the column diameter. To study the effect of diameter (D) on the bearing capacity (q) of the stone column, the diameter was varied from 0.5 to 1.5m for 6 sets of S/D ratios = 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4 and 5. It can be clearly seen from Figure 3 that as the S/D ratio increases, the bearing capacity of the stone column decreases. When the diameter increases from 0.5 to 1.5m, the percentage change in bearing capacity is 15.26% for $S = 1D$, 12.01% for $S = 1.5D$, 9.27% for $S = 2D$, 5.54% for $S = 3D$, 3.55% for $S = 4D$, and 2.42% for $S = 5D$. It is observed that when spacing is less than two times the diameter of the column, there is higher increase in values of bearing capacity.

The third parameter whose effect is studied on the bearing capacity of stone columns is the unit weight of the soil (γ). The change in bearing capacity with different values of γ is studied with two sets of diameter, $D = 0.5$ and 1.5 m at center to center spacing, $S = 1.5D$, $2D$, and $3D$. Cohesion (C_u) of the soft soil and the angle of internal friction of the column material (ϕ) are taken as 20kN/m^2 and 38° respectively. When the values of unit weight vary from 14 to 19kN/m^3 at $D = 0.5$ m, the percentage change in bearing capacity is 1.95% for $S = 1.5D$, 1.53% for $S = 2D$, and 0.94% for $S = 3D$. Similarly, when the values of unit weight increase from 14 to 19kN/m^3 at $D = 1.5$ m, the percentage change in bearing capacity is 5.27% for $S = 1.5D$, 4.23% for $S = 2D$, and 2.71% for $S = 3D$. Therefore, the conclusion is that while designing the stone column, the unit weight of the native soil has very less significance.

B. Comparison between the IS Code and Bouassida's Method

The IS Code method basically depends upon diameter, angle of internal friction of column material, and the unit density of the native soil. The range of these parameters for the study is taken as 0.5m to 1.5m, 35° to 45° , 14kN/m^3 to 19kN/m^3 respectively. A comparison between the predictions made by the IS Code method and Bouassida's method [24] follows.

The IS Code uses the shear strength parameter of stone column and native soil materials for the prediction of bearing capacity, whereas the important parameter in [24] is area replacement ratio. From Figure 5, it can be stated that at spacing $\geq 2D$, the IS Code method gives conservative values of

bearing capacity in comparison with Bouassida’s method [24]. The difference in bearing capacity values by IS Code method and Bouassida’s method increases as the spacing of the columns increases. It was found that the bearing capacity value by IS Code method is higher than the value obtained through Bouassida's method for $S = 1.5D$ (Figure 5).

The percentage deviation in the values of bearing capacity by using IS Code method and Bouassida’s method was calculated for every 10% increment in design parameters. Figure 4 shows that for $S = 2D$ and $S = 3D$, the IS Code method gives lower value of bearing capacity for every 10% increase in the design parameters, i.e. D , ϕ , and γ .

Fig. 4. Comparison of the bearing capacity by IS Code and Bouassida’s method.

Fig. 5. Comparison of bearing capacity vs ϕ by IS Code and Bouassida’s method.

C. Comparison between IS Code Method and Afshar's and Ghazavi's Design Method [27]

The analytical solution given by Afshar and Ghazavi [27] was used for the same soil conditions as used in the IS Code method and the bearing capacity has been calculated for $\phi = 35^\circ$, $\gamma = 14\text{kN/m}^3$, and $D = 0.5\text{m}$. The values of bearing capacity were calculated for two sets of spacing and diameter ratio, i.e. $S/D = 2$ and 3 . Figure 6 shows the graph comparing bearing capacity obtained by the IS Code method [30] and the

Afshar – Ghazavi method. It is clearly visible that for $S = 2D$ and $S = 3D$, the IS Code method gives lower values of bearing capacity than the Afshar -Ghazavi method.

Fig. 6. Comparison of bearing capacity by the IS Code method Afshar - Ghazavi method.

D. Result Comparison of the IS Code Method and Experimental Findings

The ultimate bearing capacity of stone columns calculated analytically is compared with the experimental results observed from model tests by [31, 19].

The bearing capacity of soft clay reinforced with a single stone column was investigated using small-scale physical model test in [31]. The test tank used in their experiment had 650mm diameter. A stone column having a diameter of 25mm and a length of 225mm was constructed at the center of the clay bed. The undrained shear strength of the clay was 20kN/m^2 and the internal friction angle (ϕ) of the stone column material was 38° . The ultimate load of the single load column was found to be 450N. Implementing the soil parameters in IS Code method, the ultimate load calculated from analytical method was about 420N, which is quite close to the result obtained in [31].

A large-scale test on stone columns was conducted in [20]. The stone columns were installed in triangular pattern with $S = 4\text{m}$, $D = 0.9\text{m}$, and length $L = 6.6\text{m}$. The ultimate bearing capacity of native soil was 34kN/m^2 and field load tests were carried out on stone columns using real Reinforced Concrete (RC) footing. Considering the average cohesion of the soft soil, $C_u = 12\text{kN/m}^2$, Maurya’s model test [20] gave an ultimate load of about 800kN. For the same soil and load conditions the IS Code method gave stone column ultimate bearing capacity $q = 36\text{kN/m}^2$ and ultimate load of about 770kN, therefore, both results are close to each other.

IV. DISCUSSION

After the analysis of the stone columns from the three considered analytical methods of stone column design, it has been found that the friction angle ϕ of the stone column material increases the interlocking between particles, thus affecting the strength of columns. It was observed that bearing capacity increases with decrease in S/D ratio and the diameter of the stone column plays an important role in its bearing capacity. IS Code Method [30] gives conservative values of bearing capacity compared to Bouassida’s method [24],

whereas the Afsar - Ghazavi method [27] gives the highest values.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The bearing capacity of a stone column mainly depends on the angle of internal friction of column material (ϕ), the diameter of the stone column (D), the length of the stone column (L), the spacing between the stone columns (S), the unit density of the surrounding soil (γ), and the undrained cohesion (C_u) of the surrounding soft soil.
- Upon varying the first geometrical parameter, i.e the spacing of stone column, it was seen that stone column capacity decreases by increasing the center to center spacing to $3D$. Beyond this value, the decrease of the stone column capacity is negligible. If the spacing between the stone columns is less than twice the diameter, then the design of the stone column is not feasible from the construction point of view. Therefore, spacing greater than $2D$ is suggested.
- The analytical result suggests that the bearing capacity of the stone column increases with the increase in the friction angle of the stone material and the diameter of the column due to the high interlocking between the stone particles.
- It was found that the variation of bearing capacity with respect to diameter is more with smaller values of S/D ratio.
- The variation of stone column bearing capacity with the unit weight of the soil shows a nearly constant graph, which means that the stone column bearing capacity remains almost the same with variation in unit weight.
- The IS Code method gives conservative results for bearing capacity when compared to Bouassida's design method for $S/D = 2$ and above. Likewise, it is found that for $S = 2D$ and $3D$, the IS Code method gives lower values of bearing capacity than Afshar's and Ghazavi's method [31].
- The study shows that among the 3 design methods, lower bearing capacity values are obtained from the IS Code method, intermediate values are obtained from Bouassida's method, and the highest values are obtained from Afshar's and Ghazavi's method.
- The values of ultimate bearing capacity of the soil and stone column capacity observed from the model tests in [20, 31] are close to the values obtained from the IS Code method [30].

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Drought Analysis Using the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) at Different Time Scales in an Arid Region

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Abstract-Drought causes insufficient soil moisture and crop water balance damage. One of the most commonly used indicators in drought monitoring is the Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI). In this study, the performance of the SPEI at 1-, 3-, 6-, 9-, and 12-month timescales was compared and analyzed from temporal and spatial variations at 12 meteorological stations in the Barmer arid region from 1979 to 2013. To determine the significance of drought characteristic trends, the modified Mann-Kendall (M-K) test is used. The results revealed that as the timescale increased, the temporal variations in the SPEI became more consistent. The M-K test revealed that the SPEI showed decreasing trends at 1 and 3 months, but increasing trends at 6, 9, and 12 months. The findings of this study are instructive and practical for drought assessment, risk management, and decision-making.

Keywords-drought; SPEI; Mann-Kendall; arid region; meteorology

I. INTRODUCTION

Drought has had devastating effects on the ecology in a global scale during the recent decades. Severe drought, particularly in arid and semiarid areas, poses a long-term danger to human livelihoods. Climate change, on the other hand, will become more common in the twenty-first century [1-2]. The severity of drought is determined by its duration, frequency, intensity, and the geographical distribution of rainfall, as well as the water requirements of humans, animals, crops, and the vegetative cover of the region. Drought features are difficult to define and analyze because of their complexity and intensity [3-5]. Drought is divided into four categories based on its impact: meteorological drought, agricultural drought, hydrological drought, and socioeconomic drought [6-8]. Drought can reduce crop production and threaten the socioeconomic sustainability of communities [9]. Furthermore, dry weather during a drought can cause forest fires, which are another major environmental issue [10]. Since India is an agrarian society and agriculture engages 68% of the population, analysis and forecasting of agricultural drought are more important than for other types of drought. The arid region of

western India is threatened by severe droughts due to water scarcity, irregular rainfall, and severe climatic conditions [11]. Drought cannot be avoided, but it can be mitigated with forethought and planning. As a result, many studies have been conducted to provide an objective and quantitative assessment of drought severity. Drought indices are widely used to measure drought impacts [12]. They are proxies based on climate data that are assumed to adequately describe the degree of drought hazard. Over 150 drought indices have been developed and are widely used in drought assessment, monitoring, and forecasting [13]. The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) developed in [14] is a precipitation-based drought index that, unlike other indices, requires precipitation as an input. It is widely used due to its data minimalism. The SPEI [13], is a modified form of SPI that involves monthly climatic water balance (difference between precipitation and potential evapotranspiration) as input parameters.

The objective of this paper is to show the spatial and temporal variation of meteorological drought using SPEI at different time scales over the Barmer district from 1979 to 2013. The modified M-K test is used to determine the significance of drought characteristic trends.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. The Study Area

The study area is the Barmer district in western Rajasthan, India. This district covers an area of 28,387km². The district of Barmer is the third largest in Rajasthan and the fifth largest in India, and is known for its vegetation. It lies between 24°58' and 26°32'N and 70°05' and 72°52'E. The district is located in the western part of the state and is part of the Thar Desert. Because of the arid Thar Desert and the sandy soil, temperature varies greatly throughout the year. During summer the temperature rises to 46-51°C, whereas, during winter, it drops to 0°C. The Barmer district is primarily a desert, with an annual rainfall of 277mm. The district experiences frequent drought. Because of rapid urbanization and poor management, the

district is also dealing with recent flood problems. With agriculture and cattle rearing being the only means of livelihood of the residents, persistent drought forces them to migrate to other parts of the state.

B. Data Collection

Daily and monthly weather data for the Barmer district were downloaded from global weather data [15] for 12 weather stations in western Rajasthan from 1979 to 2013.

C. Standardized Recipitation Evapotranspiration Index

SPEI [13], is derived from SPI and calculates the monthly climatic water balance using precipitation and potential evapotranspiration (*PET*) as input parameters.

$$D = P - PET \quad (1)$$

where *D* is a simple aggregation of water shortages or excesses over time, *P* is precipitation in mm, and *PET* is the potential evapotranspiration in mm. *PET* is calculated using the Penman-Monteith (PM) equation [16].

TABLE I. SPEI DROUGHT CATEGORY CLASSIFICATION

Drought class	SPEI
No-drought	Greater than -0.5
Mild	-0.5 to -0.99
Moderate	-1 to -1.49
Severe	-1.50 to -1.99
Extreme	Less than -2

On various time scales, the *D* values can be summarized:

$$D_n^k = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (P_{n-i} - PET_{n-1}), \quad n \geq k \quad (2)$$

where *k* is the monthly time scale and *n* is the number of calculations.

The difference in water balance is normalized as a log-logistic probability distribution to estimate the value of SPEI. The probability density function is expressed by:

$$f(x) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]^{-2} \quad (3)$$

where *α*, *β*, and *γ* are scale, shape, and origin parameters respectively. As a result, the probability distribution function can be written as:

$$F(x) = \left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{x-\gamma}\right)^\beta\right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

SPEI can be calculated using the standardized values of *F(x)* given in [17]:

$$SPEI = W - \frac{C_0 + C_1W + C_2W^2}{1 + d_1W + d_2W^2 + d_3W^3} \quad (5)$$

where $W = \sqrt{-2 \ln P}$ for $P \leq 0.5$. *P* is the probability of exceeding a determined *D* value, $P = 1 - F(x)$. If $P > 0.5$, then *P* is replaced by 1 - *P* and the sign of the resultant SPEI is reversed. The constants are $C_0 = 2.515517$, $C_1 = 0.802853$, $C_2 = 0.010328$, $d_1 = 1.432788$, $d_2 = 0.189269$, and $d_3 = 0.001308$.

SPEI can be classified mainly in 5 classes [14], as shown in Table I.

D. The Modified Mann–Kendall Test

To auto-correlate data, the modified M-K trend test is used [17-19], which is recommended by the World Meteorological Organization for analysing meteorological and hydrological variables. Under the no trend null hypothesis, the original M-K statistic value *Z* has a standard normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a variance of 1. After introducing a correcting factor n_1^s in *Z*, the modified M-K statistic *Z** can be estimated by the following equations:

$$Z^* = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{n_1^s}} \quad (6)$$

$$n_1^s = \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{2}{n_1} \sum_{jj=1}^{n_1-1} (n_1 - 1) jj & \text{for } jj > 1 \\ 1 + 2 \frac{r_1^{n_1+1} - n_1 r_1^2 + (n_1-1) r_1^2}{n_1 (r_1-1)^2} & \text{for } jj = 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where r_{jj} is a sample's self-correlation coefficient, and *jj* is lag. Significant change is observed, if $|Z|$ or $|Z^*| \geq 1.96$ and *β* (confidence) value 0.05. The significant change is increasing in magnitude, if *Z* or *Z** are positive, else the magnitude is decreasing if *Z* or *Z** is negative.

The SPEI drought indices at various time scales are used to assess drought in arid regions. The main advantage of using SPEI over the commonly used SPI in determining drought is that SPEI takes into account both precipitation and *PET*. As a result, in comparison to the SPI, the SPEI captures the primary impact of rising temperatures on water demand. The M-K statistical test is used to determine whether a set of data values is increasing or decreasing over time, and whether the trend in either direction is statistically significant.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the temporal variation in monthly precipitation from 1979 to 2013. The monthly variation shows that the wet period lasts from July to September, and the dry period from November to January. In Barmer, the monthly precipitation ranges from 0 to 330mm. The variation of monthly *PET* is shown in Figure 2. *PET* value varies from 80 to 270mm.

Fig. 1. Temporal variation of precipitation from 1979 to 2013.

A. Temporal Variation of SPEI

The monthly SPEI is calculated at 5 time scales (1, 3, 6, 9, and 12 months) from 1979 to 2013 (Figure 3). There are

significant differences in the sensitivity of SPEI values at different time scales, with the smaller time scale indicating more obvious wet and dry changes. SPEI and SPI can produce better results with a time lag of more than one month and a minimum of 30 years of data. The intensity of the drought increased as the timescale increased. It has also been observed that a continuous mild drought leads to a severe drought. At 1 and 3 months, the SPEI value generally indicates meteorological drought, while at 6 and 9 months, it indicates agricultural drought. Droughts of severe intensity occurred in 1986, 1987, 2002, 2004, 2006, and 2009.

Fig. 2. Temporal variation of PET from 1979 to 2013.

Fig. 3. SPEI at (a) 1-, (b) 3-, (c) 6-, (d) 9-, (e) 12-month time scale.

B. Trends of Drought Characteristics

The trends of SPEI at various time lags, obtained using the modified M-K method, and the Sen's slopes for the years 1979–2013 are shown in Table II. SPEI showed decreasing trends at

1 and 3 months, but increasing trends at 6, 9, and 12 month time scales. Only the SPEI at 12 months found significant trends, while the SPEI at other time scales showed insignificant trends. SPEI has a low Sen's slope (-0.01) at 1 month, indicating a clear downward trend, and zero at the other time scales.

TABLE II. M-K TEST FOR SPEI

Parameters	Z	Trends and significance	Sen's slope
SPEI1	-1.46	Insignificant decrease	-0.01
SPEI3	-1.1	Insignificant decrease	0
SPEI6	0.47	Insignificant increase	0
SPEI9	1.59	Insignificant increase	0
SPEI12	2.29	Significant increase	0

C. Spatial Variations in SPEI

For the spatial interpolation of drought characteristics, the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation method has been used. A severe drought was observed in 2002, followed by a period of good precipitation in 2003. As a result, we analyse the spatial distribution of drought in 2002 and 2003. The spatial distribution of the SPEI at 6-month time scale in Barmer for the drought (2002) and wet (2003) year is shown in Figure 4 during the wet months of the year (July to September). Throughout the region, high drought intensity was observed during the drought year and reflected in very poor vegetative conditions. During the wet year, wetness is observed in the starting of the monsoon and as monsoon passes, the degree of wetness decreases rapidly due to the high temperature variation and Thar Desert. As long as the SPEI values are high during the wet year of 2003, they improve plant conditions.

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of drought indices for the drought year 2002 and the wet year 2003.

D. Comparison of SPEI Drought with the Observed Drought

The SPEI drought classification on a 12-month time scale is compared to the observed drought data from 1979 to 2005. The observed data are taken from the Central Arid Zone Research Institute, Jodhpur. The predicted by SPEI and observed number of drought years is shown in Figure 5. The drought year 1991 predicted by SPEI as moderate drought while observed showed it was severe drought year.

The SPEI drought index is one of most recently developed drought indices. Drought in the arid district of western Rajasthan is assessed using the SPEI drought indices at various time scales. Because the district has experienced frequent

droughts due to climate change, it has become necessary to assess the droughts over time in order to reduce their impact. Crop yield loss occurs during drought years. Drought assessment helps in reducing the impact of agricultural droughts by effectively managing available water resources. Drought knowledge, both spatial and temporal, reduces risks, so the IDW interpolation method was used to show its spatial variation, which indicated that whenever there is a drought, the western region of Barmer is adversely affected.

Fig. 5. Comparison of predicted and observed drought.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, SPEI was used at different time scales to calculate the drought in Rajasthan's arid Barmer district, from 1979 to 2013. The index fluctuated the most on the shortest timescale. The fluctuations in the SPEI tended to be gradual over the longest timescale. As a result, the SPEI-reflected drought may be consistent over long timescales. Throughout the region, the spatial distribution showed a high level of drought intensity during the drought year. SPEI showed decreasing trends at 1 and 3 months, but increasing trends at 6, 9, and 12 month time scales. From 1979 to 2005, the annual SPEI showed 17 drought years out of the 19 totally observed drought years. SPEI can be used to estimate drought in arid regions at different time scales.

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A New Miniature Micro-Strip Two-Layer Band-Pass Filter Using Aperture-Coupled Hairpin Resonators

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Abstract-The goal of this project was to provide novel band-pass filter design techniques for mobile communications, which allow a significant reduction in the size of the filters produced. The novelty comes from the transformation of the single layer technique into a double layer technique by inserting coupling slots in a common mass plane. Because of their tiny size, these filters are suitable candidates for integration into mobile communication systems. Indeed, when compared to the dimensions of a single-layer planar filter, the multilayer construction allowed us to reduce the size of the filter by more than 40%. Five U-shaped hairpin resonators were placed on two micro-strip layers in the planned filter. Two apertures etched on a common ground plane positioned between the two layers allow varied couplings between the upper and bottom layer resonators. A five-pole hairpin band-pass filter was created as a result.

Keywords-micro-strip filters; miniature circuits; hairpin resonator; multilayer structure; apertures; resonator filters

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of wireless communications is continuously expanding and improving. Indeed, since the introduction of cellular systems, particularly 4G systems [1, 2], downsizing of RF components in general, and filters in particular, has piqued interest and has become a critical requirement. Filtering at 4G operating frequencies is considered a challenge itself: waveguides and, more broadly, three-dimensional (3D) approaches, which are widely used in mobile communications, are not available in 4G cellular networks, whereas planar filters, which are generally not used in 4G systems due to their relatively high losses, tuning difficulties, and low operating powers, become more appealing. Several strategies have been presented to address this demand. Micro-strip line filters are particularly appealing for mobile radio applications due to their efficiency and repeatability [3]. The latest generation of cellular systems is characterized by a constant reduction in cell

size. This tendency, on the one hand, increases the market volume of base stations, while, on the other hand, reduces the power supply demand for wireless communication networks [4, 5]. Special attention must be paid in this context to the types and qualities of employed equipment, such as weight and size, which are becoming an increasingly strong limitation for the realization of current cellular telephone circuits [3, 4, 6, 7].

Planar technology has sparked interest in the design of microwave circuits in this context, due to the multiple benefits of these structures, which include low cost, small size, light weight, ease of design, and reproducibility. Filters are also the first, out of all the components, of the microwave block circuit to be explored in planar technology [3].

The current work proposes and investigates a unique five-pole micro-strip band-pass filter with a two-layer structure and aperture-coupled hairpin resonators operating at 2.45GHz [9]. The suggested filter architecture consists of five hairpin resonators etched on two stacked layer substrates, with two slots in the common ground plane providing coupling between the upper and bottom layer resonators [8-10].

II. DESIGN APPROACH

To demonstrate our approach, a five-pole U-shaped band pass filter with hairpin resonators was designed with the specifications listed in Table I. The proposed filter is designed to have a 5% Fractional Bandwidth (FBW) and a median frequency f_0 of 2.45GHz [12-14]. A five-pole Chebyshev low-pass filter prototype with a bandwidth ripple of 0.1dB was chosen. A five-pin resonator on two stacked micro-strip layers was used to meet these requirements. The coupling between the resonators on the upper and lower layers is accomplished by etching two coupling apertures on a common ground plane between the two layers. The proposed stacked five-pole band-pass filter of aperture-coupled hairpin resonators on the outer

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surfaces of the two dielectrics is shown in exploded view in Figure 1. The substrate thickness is h , and the aperture dimensions on the common ground plane are dx and dy .

TABLE I. THE PROPOSED BANDPASS FILTER SPECIFICATIONS

Center frequency (f_0)	2.45GHz
FBW	5%
Insertion loss	3dB maximum
Bandwidth (at -3dB)	120MHz
Stopband rejection (dB)	< -30dB

To design this filter, numerical simulations were performed using the full-wave simulator Advanced Design System (ADS) for HP-Agilent [9, 15] to simulate the frequency responses of these fundamental couplings, and thus to acquire the varied spacing between resonators and coupling aperture dimensions. The typical resonant responses between the second and third or third and fourth coupled resonators are shown in Figure 2(a). The typical resonant responses between the first and second resonators, or between the fourth and fifth resonators, are shown in Figure 3(b). The coupling coefficient can be then extracted by using the following relation [8]:

$$K_{ij} = \mp \frac{f_e^2 - f_m^2}{f_e^2 + f_m^2} \quad (1)$$

where f_e and f_m are the two split resonant frequencies.

Fig. 1. Structure of the proposed filter.

The proposed Band-pass filter uses U-shape hairpin resonators [15]. To produce necessary coupling between adjacent resonators, these resonators were placed near each other in a specified space S [16].

Fig. 2. Typical resonant responses: (a) horizontal coupling, (b) aperture coupling.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the proposed approach, the proposed five pole band-pass filter [17] using identical miniaturized hairpin resonators is designed in the ISM band with center frequency f_0 at 2.45GHz, band-pass bandwidth of 150MHz (FBW= 5%), and stop-band rejection of 20dB at +70MHz from the center frequency [18]. The circuit was designed and optimized using a substrate with relative dielectric of $\epsilon_r = 6.15$, loss tangent of 0.0027, and thickness 50mil (1.27mm). The filter can be synthesized using the method reported in [10, 19] from which the lumped-element values of low pass prototype filter were determined as:

$$g_0 = g_6 = 1, g_1 = g_5 = 1.1468, g_2 = g_4 = 1.3712, g_3 = 1.975$$

The coupling coefficients and Q_{ext} can be calculated as follows:

$$Q_{ext} = \frac{g_0 g_1}{FBW} \quad (2)$$

$$M_{1,2} = M_{4,5} = \frac{FBW}{\sqrt{g_1 g_2}} \quad (3)$$

$$M_{2,3} = M_{3,4} = \frac{FBW}{\sqrt{g_2 g_3}} \quad (4)$$

The coupling coefficient $M_{1,2}$ and $M_{4,5}$ values are used to determine the dimensions of the apertures (dx, dy), between the resonators 1 and 2 and 4 and 5 respectively. The coupling coefficient $M_{2,3} = M_{3,4}$ is used to find the spacing between the resonators 2 and 3. The Input/output loads are achieved via tapped feed lines. Figure 3 shows the coupling coefficients of different spacings.

Fig. 3. Coupling coefficients of different couplings.

Fig. 4. Bandwidth versus resonator spacing S.

As depicted in Figure 5, it should be noted that the suggested filter's bandwidth varies inversely with the separation between resonators. A five-pole U-shape hairpin resonator band-pass filter prototype with two layers was manufactured utilizing the design technique. Experiments were carried out utilizing an HP8722 network analyzer to evaluate the suggested filter's performance. Filter responses that have been measured are provided and compared to simulation results. Figures 5 and 6 show the simulated and measured S parameters of the proposed filter. From these curves, it can be observed that good agreement is achieved between simulation and experimental results. The band-pass insertion loss fluctuates around 1.65dB, the return loss is less than -11dB, which are higher than the simulated results (0.8dB, 15dB).

Fig. 5. Simulated S parameters S11 and S21 of the filter.

Fig. 6. Measured S parameters S11 and S21 of the filter.

These small differences are mainly due to the effect of input/output SMA connectors, the dielectric conductance, and the resistance of the conductor which were neglected in the simulations [14]. Also, a fractional bandwidth of 4.75% at 2.5GHz is achieved. With such features, the proposed miniaturized filter is suitable for wireless communication systems. It can be seen that the bandwidth of the proposed band-pass filter is slightly wider than that of the conventional filter. Moreover, a slight frequency shift between the two responses can be observed, which should be attributed to the accuracy of the dimensions of the opening, and leads to a stronger coupling. From these responses, two desirable transmission zeros can be observed, and a symmetrical characteristic of the frequency responses is obtained [19]. The proposed filter has a size of 21.8mm×21.6mm. This structure provides 40% reduction in size compared to the single layer filter structure.

IV. CONCLUSION

The goal of this project was to provide a novel band-pass filter design technique for mobile communications. The design procedure allows a significant reduction in the size of the produced filters. The approach's novelty comes from the

transformation of a single layer technique into a double layer technique by inserting coupling slots in a common mass plane. Because of their tiny size, these filters are suitable candidates for integration in mobile communications systems. Indeed, when compared to the dimensions of a single layer planar filter, the multilayer construction allowed us to reduce the size of the filter by more than 40%.

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Transmitting Side Power Control for Dynamic Wireless Charging System of Electric Vehicles

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Abstract-This paper proposes a new power control method in dynamic wireless charging systems for electric vehicles. A dual-loop controller is proposed to control charging power while the electric vehicle is moving without communication between the transmitting and receiving sides. The output power is estimated through the coupling coefficient estimation. However, the coupling coefficient varies with the position of the vehicle. Therefore, this paper also presents an easy-to-do practical estimation method from the transmitting side, in which the coupling coefficient value is continuously updated according to the vehicle's position. As a result, the output power is controlled according to the required level with an error of less than 5%.

Keywords-electric vehicle; dynamic wireless charging; coupling coefficient estimation; LCC compensation; power control

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of Electric Vehicles (EVs) to reduce air pollution is globally rising. Much research on EVs is performed to make their use more convenient and safer [1-3]. One of the issues of interest to researchers is wireless charging technology for EVs [4, 5]. Wireless charging eliminates all charging cables, making charging safer and more flexible. Currently, Dynamic Wireless Charging (DWC) systems are preferred because EVs can be used on the road while charging [6, 7]. Therefore, the EVs can travel longer distances, the size and weight of the battery can be smaller, and the transportation efficiency is improved [8, 9]. In the DWC systems, output power pulses occur because coupling coefficients vary as the EVs move along the transmission lane. Moreover, output power sharply drops when the EV moves with lateral misalignment [10, 11]. This problem affects battery life. Many studies have been done to reduce the pulse of the output power by coil design [12, 13]. This solution may not be consistent for real EVs that have different sizes of receiver coil. In addition, these researches have not addressed the problem of EVs moving in lateral misalignment. Also, in a DWC system, many EVs of different types move and interact with the transmission lane and each EV type requires different levels of charging power [14]. Therefore, advanced control methods need to be applied in DWC systems to control the output power. Some studies perform power control for EVs in a wireless charging system [15]. In these studies, the output power is controlled using DC/DC converters on the receiving

side. This solution increases the converters' number as well as increases the loss in the system.

This paper proposes a new power control method on the transmitting side without additional DC/DC converters. However, to be able to perform control only at the transmitting side, it is necessary to know the output power on the receiving side. The output power can be known by using the wireless communication network [16]. This solution is not suitable for the DWC system where the EVs are always moving in a hard environment. In [17], the transmitting-side inverter is also used to control the output power in DWC systems. This study uses auxiliary coils to detect the position of the EV and determines lateral misalignment to control the output power. This system takes up a lot of space and is expensive. In [18], parameters are estimated based on high-frequency voltage, current, and phase angle measurements. However, the method of measuring these parameters at high frequency is a challenge in practice. In [19], a quadrature transformation algorithm is used to estimate power. This method requires a complex measuring circuit and signal conversion. To solve the above difficulties, the current paper proposes an easy-to-do practical power estimation method based on measuring the resonant current RMS value on transmitter coils and inverter input DC power. This new power control method provides stable output power to any EV position and provides multi-level output power for different EV types in the DWC system.

II. THE POWER CONTROL PROBLEM

A. Structure of the Proposed System

The structure of the designed system is shown in Figure 1. On the transmitting side, transmitters are designed modular. Each module includes a full-bridge inverter that provides power to three transmitting coils through LCC compensation circuits. At the receiving side, the induced AC voltage on the receiving coil is also fed through the LCC compensation circuit to the impedance matching circuit, the battery management converter, and the battery. The transmitting coils are placed under the roadway to form a DWC lane for the EVs. In Figure 1, at the transmitting side: $S_1 \sim S_4$ is the SiC MOSFET; U_{DC}, U_{AB} are input and output voltages of the inverter

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respectively, $L_{fi}, L_{fr}, C_{fi}, C_{fr}, C_i, C_r$ are the inductances, lower branch capacitors, and upper branch capacitors of double LCC compensation circuit respectively, I_i, I_{Li} are the input current to LCC compensation circuits and the resonant current on the transmitting coils ($i=1,2,3$) respectively, I_{Lr}, I_r, u_{ab} are the

resonant current on the receiving coil, the output current/voltage of the compensation circuit, and L_r, L_r are the coil inductances. The issue of switching between modules has not been considered in this paper.

Fig. 1. The structure of the proposed DWC system.

B. Characteristics of the Coupling Coefficient According to the EV's Position

Figure 2 shows the FEA simulation model of a design system's magnetic coupler. The design of the transmitter and receiver is described in [20]. It is assumed that during dynamic charging, the transfer distance is always 150mm. Receiver's positions in the x and y directions are defined as dx and dy respectively. When the receiver is centered with the first transmitter (T_1), dx is zero and dy is zero. Figure 3 shows the FEA simulation result of the total coupling coefficient. This result is obtained in case dx increases from 0 to 800mm and dy increases from 0 to ± 60 mm, where the total coupling coefficient of the receiver with the transmitters is performed as follows:

$$k_r = \sum_{i=1}^3 k_{ir} \quad (1)$$

where k_{ir} is the coupling coefficient of the i th transmitting coil (T_i) with the receiving coil (R). The results show that the coupling coefficient k_{ir} is the greatest when the receiving coil is centered with the transmitting coils.

The FEA simulation result in Figure 3 (solid lines) shows that when dy is 0mm (case 1-red line), the average value of the total coupling coefficient is 0.143. When dy is 40mm (case 2-blue line), the average value of the total coupling coefficient is 0.111. In case 3 (black line), the dy is 60mm and the average value of the total coupling coefficient is 0.078. These show that during dynamic charging, the total coupling coefficient is varied and is significantly reduced when lateral misalignment increases.

Fig. 2. The FEA model of the proposed magnetic coupler.

Fig. 3. FEA simulation/estimation coupling coefficients result.

C. Analysis of Power Control Capability

The fundamental harmonic approximation method was used to give an equivalent circuit as shown in Figure 4. U_{AB} is

approximated as a sinusoidal source. For simplicity in circuit analysis, the losses on the compensation circuit and inverter are ignored. R_r, R_r are the resistances of the transmitting and receiving coils respectively, R_L is the equivalent load impedance seen from the impedance matching circuit input to the load, $L_1 = L_2 = L_3 = L_t$ are the transmitting coils which are designed the same, M_i is the total mutual inductance of transmitting coil (L_i) with other transmitting coils ($M_i = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^3 M_{ij}$), and M_{ir} is the mutual inductance of the transmitting coil (L_i) with the receiving coil (R).

Fig. 4. Equivalent resonant circuit.

Fig. 5. The PWM signals for S1, S2, S3, S4, and voltage waveform.

The relationship of compensation circuit parameters is shown in (2) [20]:

$$\begin{cases} C_{fi} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 L_{fi}} \\ C_i = \frac{1}{\omega^2 (L_i - L_{fi} + M_i)} \\ C_{fr} = \frac{1}{\omega^2 L_{fr}} \\ C_r = \frac{1}{\omega^2 [L_r - L_{fr}]} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$\omega = 2\pi f_{sw}$

The resonant current in transmitting coils is the same and is expressed as [20]:

$$I_{L1} = I_{L2} = I_{L3} = I_{Li} = -j\omega C_{fi} U_{AB} \quad (3)$$

Analyzing the circuit of Figure 4 and combining it with (2)-(3) the output power can be expressed as:

$$P_{out} = \frac{R_L L_t L_r}{\left(\frac{R_r R_L}{\omega^2 L_{fr}} + L_{fr} \right)^2} k_r^2 I_{Li}^2 \quad (4)$$

In designed DWC systems, the resonant frequency is usually kept constant, and the designed parameters of coils and compensation circuits are constant. It is assumed that at the receiving side the equivalent load impedance value is maintained constant and equal to the optimal load value for maximum transfer efficiency. Equation (4) shows that if the coupling coefficient (k_r) is estimated, then the output power could be controlled by regulating the resonant current of transmitting coils (I_{Li}). Further, (3) shows that this resonant current can be controlled by controlling the inverter output voltage value (U_{AB}). The output voltage of the inverters is adjusted by the phase-shift method. The signals for S1~S4 and the inverter output voltage waveform are shown in Figure 5. The RMS of the inverter's output voltage can be expressed as [21]:

$$U_{AB} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} U_{DC} \cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (5)$$

From (3), (4), and (5) it is shown that the output power can be adjusted by adjusting the phase-shift angle α .

D. Estimated Output Power

Given the circuit of Figure 4 at resonant point, the derivatives of the equations are shown below. The equivalent reflected impedance of transmitting coils to each other is:

$$Z_{Mi} = \frac{j\omega M_i I_{Li}}{I_{Li}} = j\omega M_i ; \text{ with } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (6)$$

The receiving side impedance (Z_s) can be represented by the ratio between the coupled voltage $j\omega M_r I_{Li}$ and the receiver resonant current I_{Lr} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_s &= \frac{j\omega M_{1r} I_{L1} + j\omega M_{2r} I_{L2} + j\omega M_{3r} I_{L3}}{I_{Lr}} \\ &= \frac{j\omega \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 M_{ir} \right) I_{Li}}{I_{Lr}} = \frac{j\omega M_r I_{Li}}{I_{Lr}} = R_r + \frac{\omega^2 L_{fr}^2}{R_L} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The equivalent reflected impedance of the receiving coil to each transmitting coil can be expressed as:

$$Z_{pi} = \frac{j\omega M_{ir} I_{Lr}}{I_{Li}} = \frac{\omega^2 M_{ir} M_r}{Z_s} \quad (8)$$

The equivalent impedance of each transmitting coil is calculated as:

$$Z_{Li} = R_i + Z_{pi} + j\omega L_i + j\omega M_i \quad (9)$$

At the resonance condition, the reflected impedance Z_{pi} can be calculated as:

$$Z_{pi} = Re\{Z_{Li}\} - R_i = \frac{P_{Li}}{I_{Li,RMS}^2} - R_i \quad (10)$$

Approximately, ignoring the power loss on the inverter, the total impedance reflected from the secondary to the transmitting side is shown in (11):

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 Z_{pi} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 P_{Li}}{I_{Li,RMS}^2} - 3R_i = \frac{P_{DC}}{I_{Li,RMS}^2} - 3R_i \quad (11)$$

where P_{DC} is the input power of the inverter. From (8) and (11), the coupling coefficient is given by:

$$k_r = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L_i L_r} \left[\frac{R_r}{\omega^2} + \frac{L_{fr}^2}{R_L} \right] \left[\frac{P_{DC}}{I_{Li,RMS}^2} - 3R_i \right]} \quad (12)$$

When the DWC system is designed, the system parameters, such as coils, compensator, and resonant angular frequency are assumed to be constant. When P_{DC} and $P_{Li,RMS}$ are measured by sensors, the equivalent load impedance (R_L) is maintained constant and k_r is estimated according to (12). Therefore, the output power is estimated according to (4).

E. The Proposed Power Controller

The block diagram of the proposed power controller is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Power control block diagram.

The inner loop is the current loop which is important for the estimated results to have high accuracy. The outer loop is a power control loop according to the load. At the transmitting side, the RMS value of resonant current (I_{Li}) and the value of the inverter input voltage/current (U_{DC} / I_{DC}) are measured. Then, (12) is used to estimate the coupling coefficient, and (4) is used to estimate the output power. The reference output power ($P_{out.ref}$) is compared with the estimated output power

($P_{out.est}$), then the error is taken to the power controller to determine the referent current value (I_{Li}^*). The error between the referent and the measured current is passed to the current controller. The current controller determines the phase shift angle to control the inverter.

III. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A simulation model was built on PSIM simulation software to verify the proposed method. The system parameters are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE DWC SYSTEM

Parameter	Values	Parameter	Values
P_{out}	1.5kW	L_{fi}	52.6μH
U_{DC}	310V	C_{fi}	66.5nF
U_{ab}	400V	C_1	93.7nF
k_r	0.14	C_2	123.2nF
f_{sw}	85kHz	C_3	95nF
L_i	102μH	L_{fr}	28.9μH
R_i	0.13Ω	C_{fr}	120.9nF
L_r	120μH	C_r	38.5nF
R_r	0.115Ω		

Fig. 7. Simulation characteristic of the output power according to the reference power.

Fig. 8. The experimental DWC system setup.

The total coupling coefficient estimation results are shown in Figure 3(b) (dot lines). In case 1, d_y is 0mm and the average value of the estimated total coupling coefficient ($K_{r,est}$) is equal to 0.138. In case 2, d_y is 40mm and $K_{r,est}$ is equal to 0.108. In case 3, d_y is 60mm and $K_{r,est}$ is equal to 0.074. The estimation error is less than 5.3%.

Figure 7 shows the simulation result of power control when the reference power changes from 0.8kW to 1.2kW. It shows that the value of the estimated power ($P_{out,est}$) and the load power ($P_{out,load}$) grip to the reference value ($P_{out,ref}$) with a response time of 1.1ms and an error of 0.5%. Figure 8 shows the experimental model of the proposed DWC system. PE40 ferrite bars were used to increase magnetic conductivity. Polypropylene film capacitors were used for their small loss and high ability to withstand high currents at high frequencies. MOSFETs SiC (C3M0280090D) was used for the inverter. Stranded wire was used in building the coils. The impedance matching circuit and battery were replaced by an equivalent load.

The experimental waveforms when the receiver position dx and d_y are zero and $U_{DC} = 310V$ are presented in Figure 9. The results show that the resonant frequency is 85kHz and the ZVS condition for SiC is achieved in both cases of phase shift angle (α) equal to 0 and 60° . Figure 9(a) shows the resonant current $I_{Li} = 10.6A$, output power equal to 1.32kW, and the system efficiency reaching 89.6% in the case of $\alpha = 0^\circ$. Figure 9(b) shows that when $\alpha = 60^\circ$, $I_{Li} = 9.2A$, the output power is equal to 1.2kW and the system efficiency reaches 89.2%.

Fig. 9. Experimental waveforms: inverter output voltage/current and resonant currents.

The following tests were performed to demonstrate the operation of the dual-loop controller in two cases. The DC voltage (U_{DC}) was set to 250V and the equivalent load R_L to 53.3Ω. In case 1, when the position of the receiver is $dx = 0mm$ to 800mm and $d_y = 0mm$, the required output power changes from 600W to 400W. The experimental results of the reference/ estimation/measured output power, phase shift angle α , the inverter output voltage waveform (u_{AB} - red color), and resonant current (I_{Li} - blue color) are presented in Figure 10.

The results show that the angle α increased from 41.6° to 51.4° , $I_{Li,RMS}$ decreased from 6.34A to 5.21A, and the output power responds to the preset value. In case 2, when the position of the receiver is a lateral misalignment in the y-direction from 0mm to 40mm, the reference output power is 400W. The experimental results are presented in Figure 11. In this case, the coupling coefficient reduces, the phase shift angle α decreased from 52.6° to 36.7° , the r.m.s value of I_{Li} increased from 5.18A to 6.9A, and the output power was constant.

Fig. 10. Experimental results when the reference output power changes from 600W to 400W.

Fig. 11. Experimental results when the reference output power is 400W.

These results show that the proposed control method could control the output power with a response time of 0.01s and an error less than 5%. The output power estimation method could continuously estimate the output power. The proposed system responds well when the vehicle speed is below 40km/h. Figure 12 shows the system's efficiency experimental result when the

receiver moves along the transmission lane without any lateral misalignment. The average system efficiency is 80.7%.

Fig. 12. Experimental efficiency characteristics.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a new method of controlling the output power in the DWC system for EVs. The transmitting side inverter has been used to control power without using an additional boost/buck inverter. The parameter estimation method has been made simple by measuring the r.m.s. value of the sinusoidal current and the DC input power of the inverter. These solutions can lower the cost of the system. Furthermore, the proposed method can control the output power according to the required level of different EVs. The average system efficiency reaches 80.7%. The output power is controlled in the DWC with an error less than 5%.

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A Low-Profile Wearable Textile Antenna Using AMC for WBAN Applications at 5.8GHz

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Abstract-This paper presents a low-profile, wearable textile antenna, designed for Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) applications operating in the 5.8GHz band for Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) applications. An Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC) structure was used to improve antenna performance and protect the human body from back-radiation. The antenna with the integrated AMC achieved a measured gain of 8.92dBi, an efficiency of 80%, a wide impedance bandwidth of 1.4GHz (24.1%), and SAR values of 0.00103 and 0.00034W/Kg for 10g and 1g tissues respectively. The proposed antenna was studied in a worn-on-body scenario using a multilayer numerical model of the human body. The influence of the thickness of each tissue layer of the human body was investigated. The results showed that the antenna maintained its performance, a stable gain was obtained, and the SAR values were also below the IEEE guidelines that guarantee the safety of the wearer.

Keywords-Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC); ISM; Specific Absorption Rate (SAR); textile antenna; WBAN applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Wearable antennas have been intensively studied, as they are widely used in WBAN applications such as health monitoring, emergency services, identification systems, enterprise, space, military rescue activities, and physical training [1]. The use of body-worn electronic devices, such as smart glasses, watches, and textiles, has grown rapidly as a result of the increasing need for wireless communication. The main interests in the implementation of these systems are well-being, health, and lifestyle [2]. As a result, Wireless Body Area Networks (WBANs) have attracted considerable attention [3]. Antenna design for WBAN systems is challenging compared to conventional systems because the human body is a dispersive

medium due to its high permittivity and conductivity [3]. Many researchers studied different types of antennas to improve their performance near the human body. For example, in [3-5], monopoles with an Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC), a circular ring slot antenna with a SIW cavity back, and a Planar Inverted F Antenna (PIFA) were presented as wearable textile antennas that provide stable performance near the human body.

These antennas use rigid substrates, which can be uncomfortable for the human body, so different bending conditions must be considered [1]. Body antennas are best made from flexible textiles and wearable materials that naturally conform to the body surface [6]. Due to the recent rapid growth of electronic textile technology, several researchers focused on the application of flexible textile materials in antennas [7]. Since the textile antenna is bent on the human body, the effects of deformation need to be studied. Therefore, to obtain an optimal antenna design for WBAN systems, insensitivity to body effects and realization of practical wearable environments should be considered simultaneously [3]. In addition, a low-profile antenna is highly desirable to ensure comfort for the wearer. Furthermore, the Specific Absorption Ratio (SAR) must be below the normal criteria and not exceed the critical values of 1.6W/kg for 1g of tissue or 2W/kg for 10g of tissue, according to the guidelines of IEEE C95.1-1999 [8]. Furthermore, one of the challenges of using a wearable antenna is the variation in tissue thickness, especially in the fat and muscle layers. This thickness is not the same for all individuals [9]. Therefore, the effects of different thicknesses of body models on antenna performance need to be investigated. To overcome these problems, this study investigated a low-profile textile monopole antenna for WBAN applications at 5.8GHz. A 50Ω Coplanar Waveguide (CPW)

was used for the feed because it offers wider bandwidth and higher gain and needs to be metalized only on the one side. However, since the antenna must be placed near the human body, there is no ground plane to protect it from the generated back radiation. Therefore, an AMC is needed to improve antenna performance and protect the body from the effects of back radiation [6]. This study proposed a low-profile textile antenna loaded by an AMC structure with high gain, high efficiency, and good isolation while achieving low SAR level. Moreover, the influence of the thickness of each tissue layer of a human body on the proposed antenna performance was studied for the first time to ensure that the antenna adapts to all individuals while maintaining performance stability. To ensure that the proposed antenna fits different human bodies, three different body models with different tissue thicknesses and compositions were considered to study the effect of human tissue thickness on antenna performance in terms of gain and SAR.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN AND DISCUSSION

A. Antenna Geometry

The monopole antenna configuration was designed based on the design proposed in [5] and optimized for operation in the ISM 5.8GHz band. Figure 1 shows the dimensions and the fabricated prototype. The wearable antenna has a simple structure to avoid manufacturing complexities with overall dimensions of 14x22x0.58mm. The antenna was printed on a flexible polyester textile substrate with a dielectric constant $\epsilon_r=2.22$, loss tangent $\tan\delta=0.004$, and a thin thickness of 0.5mm. The conductive layer was made of a 0.08mm thick pure electro-textile copper taffeta from less EMF [5, 10] with a conductivity of 2.5×10^5 S/m. It was smooth, soft, lightweight, pliable, and easy to cut and sew. A 50Ω CPW was chosen to feed the antenna. Design and simulations were carried out using CST Microwave Studio [11, 12]. The antenna was fabricated with the optimized dimensions listed in Table I.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the proposed antenna: (a) front view, (b) photograph of the manufactured prototype.

TABLE I. OPTIMIZED DIMENSIONS OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA

Parameter	W	L	L1	a	b	c	d	e	f
Value	32	22	11	5.1	5	3	0.2	4.5	5

B. Parametric Study

Figure 2(a) shows the evolution steps of the proposed antenna design. The design process was divided into three

stages (Ant 0, Ant 1, and Ant 2) to achieve the final design. The method used was to cut out both sides of the patch and insert a slot to achieve the desired resonant frequency by controlling the reflection coefficient parameters. Figure 2(b) shows the reflection coefficients S_{11} of the three stages. The first antenna (Ant 0) is a simple CPW antenna structure, which had a good impedance matching characteristic with a wide impedance bandwidth. The two sides of the patch were truncated in Ant 1, resulting in better impedance matching, but caused a shift in the resonant frequency from 5.94GHz to 6.25GHz. In the final step, a slot was added to the patch to achieve the desired frequency. This variation also resulted in a good impedance match ($S_{11}=-58$ dB) and a wide bandwidth of 2.18GHz (4.69-6.87GHz).

Fig. 2. (a) Evolution steps of the design of the proposed antenna, (b) corresponding S_{11} reflection coefficients.

The effect of parameter X and the width of slot C on the antenna's impedance matching was examined. The antenna performance was examined for a variable length of X from 4 to 1.5mm, as shown in Figure 3(a). As the length of X decreased, better impedance matching was achieved, and the center frequency of the reflection coefficient shifted to higher frequencies. Figure 3(b) shows that varying C from 2 to 6mm resulted in a significant increase in impedance matching with an improvement in impedance bandwidth of about 600MHz.

Figure 4 shows the simulated and measured reflection coefficients of the antenna with optimal dimensions. Good agreement was found in terms of bandwidth between simulation and measurement at the resonant frequency. The simulated -10dB impedance bandwidth was 2.18GHz (4.69-

6.872GHz), while the measured bandwidth was 2.27GHz (4.55-6.82GHz), which largely covers the desired band. However, the measured S_{11} was 26 dB lower than the simulated value due to imperfections during the manufacturing process.

Fig. 3. Influence of parameters on the S_{11} performance of the proposed antenna: (a) effect of truncation width X , (b) slot width C .

Fig. 4. Simulated and measured S_{11} of the antenna.

III. AMC-BACKED ANTENNA DESIGN AND RESULTS

A. AMC Unit Cell Design

The AMC structure is a good candidate for a reflective plane of the radiated wave in wearable antenna applications, as

it reduces the radiation absorbed by the human body and improves performance [1, 4]. Since the CPW antenna does not have a reflective plane and emits back-radiation, it should be isolated from the human body. Several studies used various basic classical geometric shapes (square, triangle, circle, and cross) to form a wide and two-band AMC surface [5, 8, 13-15]. This study focused on a hexagonal structure on textile because of its advantages in terms of size and bandwidth [13]. Figure 5 shows the extended dimensions of the AMC unit cell. The unit cell structure was developed on a felt substrate with a relative dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 1.22, a loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) of 0.016, and a thickness of 2mm. The conductive material was copper taffeta. During the design of the AMC structure and the simulation phase, the AMC network was extended by one row and one column at a time until optimal performance in terms of gain and Forward-to-Backward Ratio (FBR) was achieved. A good impedance match was achieved within 5.8GHz. The dimensions of the different structures were adjusted to achieve a 0° phase around 5.8GHz. The frequency bands were determined by variations of $\pm 90^\circ$ around the 0° phase values, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Structure and simulated reflection coefficient phase of the AMC unit cell.

B. Integration of the Textile Antenna and AMC Surface

Figure 6(c) shows the manufactured prototype AMC antenna. The monopole antenna was built on an AMC layer with 2×2 units $\alpha \delta$ total dimensions of 34.8×39 mm. A gap of 1mm thickness separated the antenna from the AMC to minimize mismatch and electrical contact and avoid short circuits [8]. A foam-like Rohacell substrate was placed in this space without changing the properties of the AMC antenna structure. The expected impedance matching and radiation characteristics of the AMC antenna at 5.8GHz WBAN applications were achieved by optimizing the geometric dimensions of the monopole antenna and the AMC unit cell.

C. Measurement Results and Discussion

Figure 7 shows the measured reflection coefficient S_{11} of the AMC antenna and the simulated results. It is noted that the simulated bandwidth is larger from 5.70 to 7.10GHz (24.1%) than the measured one, which ranges from 5.71 to 6.75GHz

(17.9%). This small deviation may be due to uncertainty in the properties of the textile support and mechanical inaccuracies. Note that all results can cover the ISM band of 5.8GHz, which ensures that the proposed antenna can meet the requirements for 5.8GHz WBAN applications.

and *H* planes at 5.8GHz of the antenna with and without AMC. The results show that the AMC antenna has stronger forward radiation, while the backward radiation was reduced by 20dB by the AMC reflector plane. Thus, it was possible to reduce the backward scattering wave toward the human body.

Fig. 6. AMC antenna: (a) configuration of antenna on AMC, (b) bottom view, (c) manufactured prototype, (d) measuring reflection coefficient S11.

Fig. 7. Simulated and measured reflection coefficient of the AMC antenna.

Figure 8 shows the radiation pattern measurements performed in the anechoic chamber of Orange Labs in the *E*

Fig. 8. Measured radiation patterns of the antenna with and without AMC at 5.8GHz: (a) Measured performances of the AMC antenna in the anechoic chamber, (b) E-plane, and (c) H-plane.

Figure 9 shows the measured gain and efficiency of the antenna with and without AMC. The measured gains of the antenna with and without AMC are 8.92 and 2.5dBi respectively. Due to the hexagonal shape of the AMC surface, the achieved gain is higher than the existing antennas'. The

maximum measured efficiency of the antenna without AMC was 60%, while the measured efficiency of the antenna with AMC was almost 79.96% at 5.8GHz. These values show that the proposed AMC textile antenna is very efficient.

Fig. 9. Simulated and measured gain and efficiency of the textile antenna with and without AMC.

IV. ANTENNA ON THE HUMAN BODY

A. Antenna Performance in Bending Configuration

In mobile systems, a wearable antenna is often bent as a result of the movement of the human body. To study the performance of the AMC textile antenna in a dynamic body environment and under deformation, it was bent over a cylinder with a radius R of 60mm, representing the middle arm, in two planes (E and H). Figure 10 shows the simulated S_{11} of the proposed AMC antenna in flat and bent conditions in the E - and H -plane. This figure shows that the bandwidth remained stable in both bending conditions and covered the 5.8GHz band.

Fig. 10. Simulated reflection coefficient of the AMC-antenna in bending conditions in both E and H planes.

It is necessary to validate the performance and study the effects of human body loading on the proposed antenna. To reduce the simulation time, a 3D numerical model was studied.

This model consisted of three layers representing skin, fat, and muscle tissue from the outside to the inside. The properties of the dispersive human tissue layers were taken from [16-18] and are shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Modeling the 5.8GHz antenna with and without AMC on the human body model.

Figure 12 shows that after removing the AMC surface the resonant frequency shifted toward the lower band due to the high dielectric properties of human tissue [19]. This removal also affected the attenuation of the reflection coefficient and the detuning of the resonant frequency. On the other hand, the required operating bands of the AMC antenna were achieved due to the high isolation provided by the AMC. It can be noted that the reduction of the distance d between the antenna and the human body model leads to a mismatch of the reflection coefficient S_{11} . Therefore, protection from electromagnetic radiation was provided by a distance of 4mm between the AMC antenna and the tissues of the multilayer models.

Fig. 12. Reflection coefficient of the proposed antenna with and without AMC, according to distance from the human body model (0-4mm).

The antenna was placed directly on the skin of the arm, as shown in Figure 13, and the reflection coefficient antenna was also plotted when placed on the body. The two results are close to each other. The differences compared to free space are negligible and cover the frequency band.

Fig. 13. Measured reflection coefficient.

B. SAR Validation

SAR was used to examine the health risks posed by portable antennas on the human body. According to the guidelines of the IEEE standards C95.1-1999 [20] and C95.1-2005 [21], the RF energy absorbed by human tissue should not exceed the critical values of 1.6W/kg for 1g of tissue or 2W/kg for 10g of tissue. SAR is given by a temporal derivative of the incremental energy (dW) scattered in an incremental mass (dm) contained in a volumetric element (dV) with a data density (ρ) [22], calculated by:

$$SAR = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dW}{dm} \right) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dW}{\rho dV} \right) \text{ (W/Kg)} \quad (1)$$

$$SAR \text{ (W/Kg)} = \frac{\sigma E^2}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

where σ represents the conductivity in (S/m), ρ designates the mass density in (Kg/m^3), and E represents the electric field in (V/m). SAR is related to the internal E -field by:

$$E = \left(\frac{\rho}{\sigma} SAR \right)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$J = (\sigma \rho SAR)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

A numerical assessment of SAR can be performed in case of a lack of equipment and the high cost of experimentally determined SAR values. This work examined various numerical SAR studies based on mass-averaged methods using the IEEE C95.1 standard included in the CST MWS software. The simulated 1g and 10g average SAR at 5.8GHz for the antenna with and without AMC on humans are shown in Table II. The obtained results show that the presence of the AMC surface reduces SAR and provides better protection to the human body. In both cases, the SAR values of the AMC antenna were lower than the SAR limits, which guarantees its safe use.

TABLE II. SIMULATED SAR OF ANTENNA WITH AND WITHOUT AMC

SAR (W/Kg)	1g tissue	10g tissue
Antenna without AMC	0.038	0.14
Antenna with AMC	0.000103	0.000349

C. Effects of Tissue Thickness on the AMC Antenna

The thickness of the tissue layers, especially fat and muscle, varies from person to person. Therefore, keeping the skin thickness constant at the average standard measurement of 3.6mm [5], different combinations of thickness values for fat and muscle layers can be studied for imaging multiple individuals [9]. Table III shows the parameters of three proposed models with different combinations, to examine how SAR can be affected by the different thicknesses of human tissue layers. The thickness of the fat and muscle layers changed, while the thickness of the skin layer remained unchanged. In the first case, the thickness of the fat layer ranged from 7 to 27mm, whereas in the second, the thickness of the muscle layer varied from 23 to 63mm, while the third had simultaneous changes in the fat and muscle layers. Furthermore, many thickness combinations of the fat and muscle layers with a total thickness of 60mm were considered.

TABLE III. THREE EXAMPLES OF DIFFERENT HUMAN MUSCLE AND FAT LAYERS THICKNESS

Case	Tissues	Thickness (mm)				
		a	b	c	d	e
1	Skin, S	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Fat, F	7	12	17	22	27
	Muscle, M	50	50	50	50	50
2	Skin, S	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Fat, F	7	7	7	7	7
	Muscle, M	23	33	43	53	63
3	Skin, S	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Fat, F	7	12	17	22	27
	Muscle, M	53	48	43	38	33

Table IV shows the 1g and 10g SAR, as well as the gain distribution for the AMC antenna in different types of the human body at 5.8GHz. In the first case, where the fat layer increased while the size of the muscle and skin layers remained constant, a decrease in both SAR values was observed. In model 2, where the muscle layer increased, the SAR values were almost stable. In case 3, where the thickness of the fat and muscle layers was changed simultaneously, a small increase in SAR values was observed, but it is noteworthy that all these values were below the normal SAR criteria. In summary, the gain and SAR values remained almost unchanged in all cases when the thickness of the different layers was varied, ensuring that the proposed AMC antenna is a strong candidate for WBAN applications for different wearers.

TABLE IV. 1G AND 10G SAR FOR THE AMC ANTENNA IN VARIOUS PROTOTYPES OF THE HUMAN BODY AT 5.8GHZ

Case	a	b	c	d	e	
1	SAR (W/Kg)/ 1g	0.46	0.45	0.43	0.42	0.42
	SAR (W/Kg)/ 10 g	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.16
	Gain (dBi)	8.29	8.32	8.32	8.38	8.26
2	SAR (W/Kg)/ 1g	0.25	0.25	0.26	0.25	0.25
	SAR (W/Kg)/ 10 g	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10
	Gain (dBi)	8.24	8.23	8.24	8.24	8.23
3	SAR (W/Kg)/ 1g	0.41	0.47	0.42	0.43	0.45
	SAR (W/Kg)/ 10g	0.16	0.181	0.164	0.169	0.17
	Gain (dBi)	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29

TABLE V. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED AMC ANTENNA TO OTHER STUDIES

Ref	Freq. (GHz)	Dim (mm) / Reflector type	BW (GHz)		Gain (dBi)		SAR (W/kg)		Radiation efficiency (%)
			FS	HBM	FS	HBM	1g	10g	
[3]	5.8	75x42x1 / Ground plane	5.65-5.88 (3.96%)	5.62-5.97 (6.10)	-	3.12	-	-	37.7
[5]	5.8	102x68x3.6 / AMC	4.30-5.90 (27.5%)	-	6.12	-	0.61	1.49	-
[23]	5.5	46x36x2 / Ground plane	5.05-6.04 (18%)	5.13-5.93 (14.54)	5.9	5	0.9307	0.4016	74.1
[24]	5.5	42x28x4 / Meta surface	4.96-5.90 (17%)	4.96-5.90 (17%)	6.7	-	0.3699	0.2170	77
This work	5.8	34.8x39x4.58/ AMC	5.70-7.10 (24.1%)	5.8-7.23 (24.65%)	8.92	8.29	0.00103	0.000349	79.96

D. Comparative Study

Table V shows the performance comparison of the proposed wearable textile antenna with WBAN antennas proposed in other studies. It can be noted that the proposed antenna not only has the advantage of conformability and flexibility when worn on the human body due to the textile substrate but also has several advantages in terms of size and performance, such as high gain, low SAR, bandwidth that is not affected when worn, and is still sufficient for the application.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a textile antenna for wearable applications operating in the 5.8GHz ISM band. A flexible textile AMC structure was used to protect the human body from back radiation and improve performance in terms of gain and efficiency. The antenna design had reduced dimensions of 34.8x39mm and 4.58mm thickness. The wearable AMC antenna was examined in free space and on the human body. To ensure that the proposed antenna fits different human bodies, a study on the effects of the thickness of each tissue layer of a human body model on the antenna was conducted, which showed good and stable performance. These characteristics make the proposed wearable antenna a good candidate for WBAN applications.

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The Performance of Spectral Clustering Algorithms on Water Distribution Networks: Further Evidence

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Abstract-The aim of the current paper is to revisit the performance of spectral clustering algorithms for water distribution networks. In the literature, there have been attempts to introduce improved algorithms based on graph theory. We focus on a class of these algorithms that applies the concepts of the spectral clustering approach. We assess the performance of spectral clustering algorithms on a wider range of water network types (i.e. large, medium, and small sized networks) using a wider range of clustering methods (both partitioning and hierarchical) and performance indicators. Our findings suggest that partitioning methods, such as k-means are not consistently efficient in all types of networks. Nonetheless, the Partitioning Around Medoids (PAM) algorithm shows a relatively good performance according to modularity, while the internal indices of k-means and hierarchical clustering algorithms are more efficient. Stability indices show that PAM and CLARA algorithms are more efficient.

Keywords-sectorization; clustering methods; spectral clustering algorithms

I. INTRODUCTION

Water Distribution Networks (WDNs) are large and complex networks designed and built to serve the water supply needs of an urban area. Proper and efficient control and management of WDNs is one of the key aspects in the operational practices of water supply networks and a major challenge [1, 2]. This is particularly true for large urban areas and cities, where the network becomes larger and more complex. In order to manage and monitor unusual demands - caused generally by leaks - the common practice involves using District Metered Areas (DMAs) [3, 4], which allow water

network systems to monitor water inflows and outflows to reduce water and revenue losses. Thus, an optimal and efficient approach to optimally partition the water network into DMAs is of crucial importance. Although WDN is an efficient approach for the partitioning of the DMAs [5], achieving optimal partitioning remains challenging, due to the existence of many parameters that need to be accounted for, such as hundreds of valves, tanks, pipelines, and pumps [6-8].

Although many methods have been proposed, the literature does not offer a conclusive result on the best performing approach to cluster DMAs. For example, authors in [9] developed an algorithm based on graph theory, which divides the water distribution system into clusters according to the direction of the flow in the pipes. This algorithm is general enough to be applied for various purposes including the enhancement of water security by assigning sensors to clusters, and/ or the efficient isolation of a containment intrusion. Authors in [10] propose the use of pressure sensitivity matrix analysis combined with clustering techniques to optimally characterize and determine a sensor configuration that maximizes the degree of locatability subject to the budget constraint of sensor configuration. Furthermore, they show that their proposed method is successfully implemented to identify the optimal set of pressure sensors that need to be installed in a DMA in the Barcelona WDN. Authors in [36] propose a multistage approach that involves the simultaneous application of sectorization of a large WDN - into DMAs - and optimization of rehabilitation of the network with new components such as pipes, valves and tanks. Finally, authors in [34] conduct a comparative analysis of three commonly used

methods to create DMAs, Fast Greedy, Random Walk, and Metis. The performance of these methods is evaluated on two cases of a large and complex WDN EXNET with unweighted and weighted edges. They conclude that Fast Greedy has an overall better performance and was found to be more effective in weighted graph partitioning. In this context, water network partitioning has become one of the most popular methods and strategies adopted to improve the optimal WDN control and management, within which spectral graph theory is central tool for developing clustering algorithms. In particular, authors in [11] propose a holistic analysis framework to support water utilities for an efficient supply management. The proposed approach is based on graph spectral methods that employ the properties of eigenvalues and eigenvectors of matrices associated with graphs. The approach aims to reduce the challenges urban water supply may face in an increasingly complex city-based environment, which is characterized by various heterogeneous and interconnected infrastructures often affect the process of supplying households with safe water. The approach is tested on two WDNs, C-Town and an operational network. As a result, they show that their proposed approach is useful and optimal to efficiently manage WDNs.

Despite the attractive features of this holistic approach, the extent to which this approach is robust is not known. For example, the authors in [11] offer limited evidence that spectral based algorithms are useful and lack robustness checks. Thus, the main aim of this paper is to extend the analysis offered by [11] by testing the sensitivity and robustness of the graph spectral methods in two ways. First, we test these methods on three different types of WDNs: A complex and large network (EXNET), a medium-sized network (C-Town), and a small-sized operational network (OUED EL MA). These networks represent different types of water networks in terms of structure and size. Second, we assess the performance of the spectral based algorithms using the PAM, CLARA, and DIANA clustering methods. We apply these algorithms on the three types of networks described above. Then, the performance of each algorithm is assessed based on three criteria, namely modularity, internal indices, and stability indices. Our findings suggest that the performance of algorithms differs depending on the performance criterion and the type of network. In this context, according to modularity, the PAM algorithm is found to perform better. K-Means and hierarchical clustering are found to be the most efficient according to the internal indices, while PAM, hierarchical clustering, and CLARA have better stability index. Thus, one cannot generalize the approach of [11] as a generic method applicable to all types of networks.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Spectral Clustering

A water network can be represented as a graph whose edges and nodes represent network pipes and pipe junctions, respectively [12, 13]. This graphical structure makes the spectral clustering approach suitable for solving water network problems. The spectral clustering approach has many attractive features. It is simple to implement and can be solved efficiently by standard linear algebra software [14-17]. In addition, it outperforms standard clustering techniques such as k-means [14]. This method is implemented in three steps, namely: (i)

computing a similarity graph, (ii) projecting data onto a low-dimensional space, and (iii) identifying clusters. Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of the spectral clustering algorithm highlighting further the computations involved throughout all the steps. This includes associating both adjacency and Laplacian matrices to graphs. Next, their eigenvalues are computed, which are then related to the structural properties of graphs [18, 19].

Fig. 1. Spectral clustering algorithm.

Finally, spectral k-means clustering algorithm is applied to extract the final clusters from the eigenvectors' matrix when all clusters are assumed to have equal size and homoscedastic. In most of the cases this assumption is not satisfied. Clusters will differ in their size, density, and variance [20]. Violating this assumption does not necessarily rule out the use of k-means algorithm. It simply implies one needs to correct the algorithm for the times this assumption is violated. In addition, and given the recent advances in computer processing power, using other alternative algorithms that relax the assumption of clusters' size and variance constancy is necessary to achieve robust results. Thus, in this paper, we conduct a comparative exercise using different clustering algorithms. This includes the following: Clustering Large Applications (CLARA), Partitioning Around Medoids (PAM), Agglomerative, Divisive Analysis (DIANA), and k-means. This setting will allow us to extract the best partitioning scheme according to internal quality and stability indices available in the literature.

B. Clustering Methods

There are two broader classes of clustering methods: (i) partitioning and (ii) hierarchical clustering methods. While partitioning methods divide the data into mutually exclusive partitions (i.e. clusters), hierarchical methods classify the data into multi-levels or a hierarchy of clusters. In general, these methods have key differences. Partitioning clustering methods are faster. They require, however, stronger assumptions such as

initial parameters and number of clusters. In contrast, hierarchical clustering methods require only a similarity measure and not initial parameters such as the number of clusters. Figure 2 illustrates the different methods used under each clustering class. In this paper, we discuss two types in each clustering method. This includes the k-means and k-medoids under partitioning methods and agglomerative and divisive under hierarchical.

Fig. 2. Most popular clustering methods.

1) Partitioning Clustering

k-means algorithm is one of the oldest and most commonly used clustering algorithms. It attempts to partition the dataset into k predefined clusters where each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean. Authors in [21] used k-means on large-scale networks to determine clusters in order to minimize the sum of squared distance error between nodes for developing DMAs configuration.

PAM is a variant of k-means in which instead of using the mean point as the center of a cluster. It uses an actual point in the cluster to represent it. Authors in [22, 23] combined PAM partitioning method with spectral clustering to introduce a greedy heuristic that reassigns the nodes belonging to minor connected components to major connected components of an electric power network.

CLARA is an extension to k-medoids (PAM). It is used to deal with data containing a large number of objects. Authors in [24] highlighted the advantages of using spectral clustering over CLARA and showed that spectral clustering has better performance to analytically localize leaks in a WDN. In addition, authors in [25] compared PSO algorithm to partitioning clustering performed by other algorithms that work with various attribute types (such as PAM and CLARA). The findings obtained by these algorithms were consistently similar. Authors in [25], however, show that PSO is more efficient.

2) Hierarchical Clustering

Agglomerative algorithms are based on graph theory concepts. They iteratively merge the nodes to build a bottom-up hierarchy. Authors in [26] presented an algorithm that uses a computationally efficient spectral and hierarchical clustering algorithm to reveal the internal connectivity structure of a network representing a power grid, subject to any choice of

electrical parameter associated to the transmission. Hierarchical spectral clustering has revealed a static internal structure of the network.

DIANA is a technique that constructs the hierarchy in the inverse order [27]. First, all the data points are considered as a single cluster. Then, using iterations, the dataset is divided into clusters until reaching the optimal n clusters in the last iteration.

3) Quality Measures of Graph Clustering

For robustness purposes, we apply various measures of quality. This includes the following:

Modularity (M): This measure is the most common quality measure for graph clustering [28]. It captures the trade-off between the number of edges bridging clusters and a measure accounting for the number and the similarity among each other [29]. Modularity can be defined as:

$$M = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij} - \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \right] \delta(c_i, c_j) \quad (1)$$

where A_{ij} is the value of the adjacency matrix between vertices i and j , k_i is the sum of the weights of the edges adjacent to i , m is the number of edges in the graph, and δ is the Kronecker delta which takes value of 1 if its arguments are equal and 0 otherwise. Authors in [29] presented the classical modularity index and tailored and modified it for WDNs in order to optimize the framework based on the maximization of the WDN-oriented modularity-based index versus the minimization of the cost of newly installed devices to obtain network segments.

4) Internal Measures

Connectivity: It uses vertex distances to measure cohesion and separation of clusters. It is formally defined as [30, 31]:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^L \sum x_{i,nn_{i(j)}} \quad (2)$$

where L is a parameter that determines the number of neighbors that contribute to the connectivity measure, $nn_{i(j)}$ as the j is the nearest neighbor of observation i , $x_{i,nn_{i(j)}}$ is 0 if i and $nn_{i(j)}$ are in the same cluster and 1 otherwise. The connectivity value should be minimized.

Dunn (D): Dunn's index [32] shows the distance between objects in a cluster and its intercluster separation. It uses the minimum pairwise distance that each cluster has to reach to be compact. To calculate the Dunn index, we adopt [31]:

$$D = \frac{\min_{C_k, C_l \in C, C_k \neq C_l} (\min_{i \in C_k, j \in C_l} \text{dist}(i, j))}{\max_{C_m \in C} \text{diam}(C_m)} \quad (3)$$

where $\text{diam}(C_m)$ is the maximum distance between observations in cluster C_m . The Dunn index has a value between zero and 1 and should be maximized.

Silhouette (S): The silhouette value measures the degree of confidence in the clustering assignment of a particular

observation, with well-clustered observations having values near 1 and poorly clustered observations having values near 0 [31]. For observation i , S is formally defined as:

$$S(i) = \frac{b_i - a_i}{\max(b_i, a_i)} \quad (4)$$

where a_i is the average distance between i and all the other observations in the same cluster, and b_i is the average distance between I and the observation in the nearest neighboring cluster.

5) Stability Measures

Clustering is considered stable if the corresponding partitioning remains unchanged with its minimum change [33]. As a sub-category of internal indices, there are many stability measures that help validate cluster solutions available: Average Proportion of No overlap (APN), Average Distance (AD), Average Distance between Means (ADM), and Figure of Merit (FOM) [31].

III. WATER DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

For robustness purposes, we assess the performance of spectral clustering algorithms on three different types of water networks. This is in contrast to [11] as it presents conclusions limited to medium sized networks. In this context, we consider 3 types of water networks, chosen according to their type (looped or mixed) as well as their size based on the number of nodes and edges (i.e. small, medium, and large).

Fig. 3. WDNs: (a) EXNET, (b) C-Town, (c) Oued El Ma.

The first network is EXNET (Figure 3(a)), which is large-sized and complex. It serves a population of approximately 400,000 inhabitants. The network system consists of 2416 pipes and 1891 nodes. Elevated reservoirs provide the energy to the entire system [34]. The second network is the medium-sized and operational Oued El Ma WDN, as illustrated in Figure 3(c), which is located in an Algerian medium-sized city with a population of 14000. The water network consists of 621 nodes and 630 edges. C-Town network– as depicted in Figure 3(b) – is a small-sized WDN. C-Town is a benchmark water network model employed in the field of water distribution system analysis with 444 pipes and 396 nodes [35].

IV. CRITICAL DISCUSSION

Authors in [11] focused on the sectorization of the C-Town network for 5 sectors using the k-means algorithm. In this section, we assess the performance of the algorithm proposed in [11] and compare it to alternative algorithms including PAM, CLARA, hierarchical clustering, and DIANA using the same experimental settings. In other words, we use the same conditions including C-Town network with 5 sectors. Figure 4 illustrates the sectorization using the k-means and our proposed alternative clustering methods. In general, our replication is successful and consistent with the original work [11].

Fig. 4. Clusters of C-Town.

Fig. 5. C-Town network sectorized: (a) k-means (a), (b) PAM, (c) CLARA, (d) hierarchical, (e) DIANA.

Figure 5 reports the internal, stability, and modularity indices for the 5 algorithms on a C-Town WDN with 5 sectors. According to the findings, k-means clustering algorithm is reported to be stable by only 1 criterion (AD). It performs, however, better based on modularity and internal criteria including Connectivity and Dunn. Our findings suggest, that hierarchical clustering performs relatively well in terms of stability and internal criteria.

However, our evidence show that the k-means performs better only in a very special setting, i.e. for small-sized WDNs with a small number of sectors. For larger number of sectors and medium to large-sized networks k-means performs poorly compared to PAM and hierarchical clustering in general.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we report and discuss the findings of our simulations. In this context, spectral partitioning was carried out for the three considered WDNs using the techniques discussed above. For each WDN, we report the identified clusters using the k-means, PAM, CLARA, general hierarchical clustering, and DIANA. Furthermore, for each network, the performances of clustering methods are evaluated on different number of clusters. Our experimental setting allows 6 different partitions of clusters as follows:

- Large water network allowing 10, 20, 25, 30, 40, and 50 partitions.
- Medium sized network allowing for 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 partitions.
- Small-sized network: allowing for 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, and 10 partitions.

A. Large and Complex Network (EXNET)

Figure 6 illustrates the performance of clustering algorithms across 6 different partition combinations.

Fig. 6. EXNET WDN spectral clustering.

The number of clusters across these partitions ranges between 10 and 50. There are 8 performance criteria reported for each of the 5 clustering algorithms. According to these criteria, PAM has been found to perform consistently well across all 6 combinations of partitions. In particular, PAM is dominant as the number of clusters increases to 40 and 50. Hierarchical is found to perform relatively well, especially

when the number of clusters is lower than 40. Furthermore, the performance of hierarchical clustering methods is as good as that of PAM when the number of clusters is 10, 25 and 30. Based on the overall performance, PAM seems to meet all the criteria when the number of clusters is 50. In other words, PAM is found to be better in terms of internal, stability, and modularity performance.

B. Oued El Ma Water Distribution Network

Figure 7 reports the performance of the algorithms for a medium-sized WDN. According to the findings, the hierarchical clustering algorithms perform better when the number of clusters is smaller (3 to 6). In contrast, the overall performance of partitioning methods is better when the number of clusters increases as shown in the cases of 8, 10, and 12 clusters.

Fig. 7. Oued El Ma WDN spectral clustering.

C. C-Town Water Distribution Network

Figure 8 reports the performance of clustering algorithms across the 6 different partition combinations for a small-sized WDN. Similar to the medium-sized network, the findings suggest that partitioning-based clustering algorithms perform better than the hierarchical based methods when the number of clusters increases. For example, when the number of clusters is 10, PAM performs better than any other algorithm in terms stability and modularity performance criteria. Hierarchical based methods, however, perform, better when the number of clusters is 3 and 5 in terms of stability and internal performance.

Fig. 8. C-town WDN spectral clustering.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Improving the management of WDNs can be achieved by dividing the network into sectors (DMAs). Among the most used methods for network partitioning is spectral partitioning, which consists of generating a spectral space from the eigenvectors of the Laplacian matrix associated with the network. The final phase of this partitioning is often done by the k-means algorithm, which is not always adequate. It is, therefore, useful to consider the performance of other existing algorithms in order to highlight the most efficient in terms of clustering quality indices such as modularity, internal indices (Connectivity, Silhouette, and DUNN) as well as stability indices such as APN, AD, ADM, and FOM.

A simulation exercise was conducted to assess and evaluate the performance of 5 clustering algorithms on 3 types of WDNs. The studied networks were chosen according to their type and size. Our findings show that k-means is not consistently effective either in terms of type of network or number of sectors. Our critical study of [11], shows further that k-means performs well only under special conditions including small-sized networks with a very limited number of sectors. Thus, one cannot confirm the validity of using k-means as a tool to sectorize DMAs in larger and medium-sized networks.

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Pressure Drop in Horizontal Two-Phase Flow

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Abstract-In an artificial environment, the most important key in the process equipment design is determining gas-liquid two-phase flow frictional pressure drop of pipes. To achieve this, an experimental investigation was carried out in this study to analyze the pressure drops of air-water two-phase flow in a 30mm internal diameter horizontal pipe with a length of 6m at different flow conditions. The study was carried out at 20C° using tap water and air. To cover the slug flow pattern, the volumetric flow rate of water varied from 30 to 80 LPM, and the volumetric flow rate of air from 40 to 200 LPM. Pressure transmitters were used to measure pressure at four different points along the test section, each 2m apart. The results of the experiments were compared to 8 models using 3 distinct methods: Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Relative Performance Factor (RPF), and the percentage of data included in the range of the 30% error band. All methods produced similar results, with the Sun-Mishima model being the most accurate.

Keywords-two-phase flow; frictional pressure drop; slug experimental model; horizontal flow; homogenous and separated flow model

I. INTRODUCTION

Many industrial applications, such as heat exchangers, pipeline network systems, refrigeration and heat pumps, thermal energy plants, environmental control, life-support systems, and fuel cells rely on the measurement of pressure drop in two phases [1, 2]. Furthermore, the pressure drop is essential because the co-current flow of liquid and gas causes design and operational problems due to the formation of various types of two-phase flow patterns. In these cases, estimating pressure drop helps the piping designer in determining the optimal line size and designing a better piping system [3-5].

During the past 60 years, investigators have been researching two-phase frictional pressure drop. A comprehensive theoretical and experimental research was carried out and various relationships were proposed in [6]. For estimating the frictional pressure drop in horizontal and vertical pipes, there are two types of models: homogeneous and separated flow models. In homogeneous flow, the two phases are considered to be intimately mixed with no relative motion between them, either locally or overall [6]. Thome suggested utilizing the homogeneous model for mass fluxes more than 2000kg/m²s at high-reduced pressures and higher mass

velocities [7]. The separated flow, on the other hand, recognizes that the two phases can exist separately, each flowing through its own pipe, with the assumption that the velocity of each phase is constant in the zone occupied by the phase [8-14].

Some researchers assessed a few correlations using limited experimental data. Authors in [15] used R134a, R123, R402A, R404A, and R502 evaporation data in two horizontal pipes with 10.92 and 12.0mm ID (Inner Diameter), with mass flux ranging from 100 to 500kg/m²s and vapor quality ranging from 0.04 to 1.0, to evaluate 7 models. Overall, authors in [16, 17] proposed the most accurate predictors, with the one in [10] being the third-best prediction. Authors in [18] validated 15 equations based on experimental data of R410A convective boiling in two pipes of 1.5 and 3mm ID, with inlet saturation temperature of 10°C, mass flux of 300 to 600kg/m²s, and heat flux of 10 to 40kW/m². They discovered that a homogeneous approach could accurately predict frictional pressure drop. Authors in [19] compared 11 correlations to empirical observations of R123, R134a, R22, R236ea, R245fa, R404A, R407C, R410A, R507, CO₂, water, and air, with hydraulic diameters ranging from 0.506 to 12mm, Re_l ranging from 10 to 37,000, and Re_g ranging from 3×10^5 to 4×10^5 . The results showed that the correlations in [8, 12, 20, 21] performed similarly in the viscous region, while the Muller-Steinhagen and Heck [17] correlation performed best in the turbulent region. Authors in [21] tested 10 correlations against a variety of experimental data sets using a separated flow approach. According to the results, the correlations of [21] had the highest accuracy. Authors in [22, 23] studied the possibility of calculating two-phase frictional pressure drop in microgravity using normal gravity two-phase frictional pressure drop correlations. Microgravity experimental data were compared to 23 two-phase frictional pressure drop correlations. The above evaluations based on normal gravity experimental data produced inconsistencies. The homogeneous model [18, 24, 21], the Chen et al. correlation [23], and the Zhang et al. formula [21] have been proposed, whereas authors in [15, 19, 25] suggested the Muller-Steinhagen and Heck [17] correlation as the best prediction. The effects of fluid refrigerant and channel geometry on the frictional pressure drop during two-phase flow of R134a, R1234ze(E), R1234yf and R600a in a horizontal tube with mass velocities varying between 100 and 1600kg/m²s, saturation temperatures of 31 and 41°C and vapor

quality from 0.05 to 0.95 was investigated in [26]. They concluded that the new method accurately predicted the database, predicting 89% of the results within an error band $\pm 20\%$. Authors in [27] studied experimentally the pressure drop of evaporative propane with mass flux of 360 to 915 kg/m²s and vapor quality of 0 to 1.0 in microchannel with 500 μ m diameter and 0.5 m length. Authors in [28] conducted an experimental analysis of the frictional pressure drop in a plate heat exchanger using the working fluid R-1233zd(E). According to the experimental findings, the frictional pressure drop increases with increasing mass flux and mean vapor quality while it decreases with increasing saturation pressure. The experimental results led to the development of correlations for the friction factor of R1233zd(E) in plate heat exchangers. The new correlation of the friction pressure drop and mixture viscosity for two phase flow in homogenous approach modeling was developed in [1] and was compared to 846 experimental data of friction pressure drop that were collected from previous studies. The experimental data including various working fluids such as R1234ze(E), R32, R-600a R717, R134a, R410A and carbon dioxide (CO₂) at various hydraulic IDs and mass flux. The discovered Mean Absolute Relative Deviation (MARD) was 30%. These new correlations of two-phase flow pressure drop were used to predict the experiment measurements of pressure drop on circular pipes, mini-channels, and micro-channels. The experimental data used for their evaluations were rare, which could be the root cause of the inconsistency. Furthermore, the number of correlations examined in each paper was limited to no more than 15 in total. A complete evaluation is therefore necessary. This article has conducted a review of the literature on two-phase frictional pressure drop correlations for homogeneous and separated flows for finding an optimal model for experimental data.

II. PRESSURE DROP IN HORIZONTAL TWO-PHASE FLOW

Two-phase pressure drop predicting methods in horizontal pipes are discussed in this article. The sum of the static pressure drop (elevation head) ΔP_{static} , momentum pressure drop (acceleration) ΔP_{acce} , and frictional pressure drop ΔP_{frict} is the total measured pressure drop ΔP_{total} of a fluid in a horizontal two-phase flow pipe [7]:

$$\Delta P_{total} = \Delta P_{static} + \Delta P_{acce} + \Delta P_{frict} \quad (1)$$

The gravitational pressure drop ΔP_{static} in a horizontal pipe is zero, and the quality is constant throughout the pipe (as a result, in adiabatic flow, the acceleration term appears to have no effect on the pressure drop and can be ignored). Only the frictional pressure drop was studied. The following two classic models are used for two-phase flows.

A. Homogeneous Flow Model

Because gas and liquid have similar velocities in the homogeneous flow model, the frictional pressure drop for two-phase flow can be rewritten as [29]:

$$\left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_{Tp,hom} = \left(\frac{2f_{Tp}G_{Tp}^2}{D\rho_{Tp}}\right)_{Tp,hom} \quad (2)$$

where f_{Tp} is the friction factor for smooth pipe based on Petukhov correlation (where: $f_{Tp} = (0.79 \ln Re_{Tp} - 1.64)^{-2}$) [23],

G_{Tp} is the two-phase mass flux (kg/m²s), D is the diameter of the pipe (m), ρ_{Tp} is the two-phase flow density (kg/m³), and Re_{Tp} is the two-phase flow Reynolds number. The values of ρ_{Tp} and Re_{Tp} are calculated as [1]:

$$\rho_{Tp} = \left(\frac{x}{\rho_g} + \frac{1-x}{\rho_l}\right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$Re_{Tp} = \frac{G_{Tp}D}{\mu_{Tp}} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\mu_{Tp} = \left(\frac{x}{\mu_g} + \frac{1-x}{\mu_l}\right)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where μ_{Tp} , μ_l , and μ_g are the dynamic viscosities of two-phase, liquid, and gas (kg/ms) respectively [30], x is the air mass quality, and ρ_g and ρ_l are the densities of gas and liquid phases (kg/m³) respectively. According to the homogeneous flow, the correlations of frictional pressure drop are: McAdams [30] and Chen et al [13]. Table I contains more information.

TABLE I. HOMOGENEOUS CORRELATIONS

Reference	Correlations
[30]	(2)
[13]	$\left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_{Tp} = \Omega_{ch} \left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_{Tp,hom}$ <p>where Ω_{ch} parameter depends on Bond number Bo:</p> $\Omega_{ch} = \begin{cases} 1.2 - 0.9 \exp(-Bo) & Bo < 2.5 \\ 1 + \frac{We_{Tp}^{0.2}}{\exp(Bo^{0.3})} - 0.9 \exp(-Bo) & Bo \geq 2.5 \end{cases}$ <p>in which, $Bo = \frac{g(\rho_l - \rho_g)(D/2)^2}{\sigma}$ and $We_{Tp} = \frac{G_{Tp}^2 D}{\sigma \rho_{Tp}}$ where g is the gravity acceleration (m/s²), We_{Tp} is the two-phase Weber No. (-), and σ is the surface tension of water (N/m).</p>

B. Separated Flow Model

This model is based on the use of the two-phase friction multiplier ϕ_i^2 , where the subscript i can be l , g , l_o , or g_o indicating liquid, gas, liquid-only, or gas-only respectively. The separated flow is divided into two branches:

1) Liquid and Gas Frictional Multipliers (ϕ_l^2 and ϕ_g^2)

Two-phase friction multiplier method depends on liquid (ϕ_l^2) and gas (ϕ_g^2). The frictional multiplier is the ratio of the two-phase frictional pressure drop to the single-phase frictional pressure drop as follows [9]:

$$\phi_i^2 = \left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_{Tp} / \left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_i \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_i = \frac{2f_i G_i^2}{D\rho_i} \quad (7)$$

where the subscript i can be l or g denoting liquid or gas respectively, $\left(\frac{dp}{dz}\right)_i$ is the single-phase frictional pressure drop (kPa/m), f_i is the friction factor, and G_i is the actual mass flux (kg/m²s). Based on [23], the friction factor of liquid and gas for a smooth pipe can be calculated as:

$$f_i = 0.25 \left[\log \left(\frac{150.39}{Re_i^{0.98865}} - \frac{152.66}{Re_i} \right) \right]^{-2} \quad (8)$$

and the Re_i values for each phase can be calculated as [1]:

$$Re_i = \frac{G_i D}{\mu_i} \quad (9)$$

Authors in [8] discovered that ϕ_l^2 and ϕ_g^2 are functions of the dimensionless variable X in the following way [8]:

$$X = \sqrt{\frac{(dp/dz)_l}{(dp/dz)_g}} \quad (10)$$

where X is the Lockhart-Martinelli parameter. Many other researchers' studies and correlations were inspired by this model. According to the separated flow model, the frictional pressure drop correlations are: Chisholm [31], and Sun-Mishima [19]. Table II contains additional information.

TABLE II. THE SEPARATED CORRELATIONS: LIQUID AND GAS FRICTIONAL MULTIPLIERS (ϕ_l^2 AND ϕ_g^2).

Reference	Correlations															
[31]	$\phi_l^2 = 1 + \frac{C}{X} + \frac{1}{X^2}$ <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>C</th> <th>Gas</th> <th>Liquid</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>20</td> <td>Turbulent</td> <td>Turbulent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>Turbulent</td> <td>Laminar</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>Laminar</td> <td>Turbulent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Laminar</td> <td>Laminar</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	C	Gas	Liquid	20	Turbulent	Turbulent	12	Turbulent	Laminar	10	Laminar	Turbulent	5	Laminar	Laminar
C	Gas	Liquid														
20	Turbulent	Turbulent														
12	Turbulent	Laminar														
10	Laminar	Turbulent														
5	Laminar	Laminar														
[19]	<p>For viscous flow:</p> $C = 26 \left(1 + \frac{Re_l}{1000} \right) \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-0.153}{0.8 + 0.27La} \right) \right]$ <p>where La is the Laplace number, for turbulent flow:</p> $\phi_l^2 = 1 + \frac{C}{X^{1.19}} + \frac{1}{X^2},$ <p>where: $C = 1.79 \left(\frac{Re_g}{Re_l} \right)^{0.4} \sqrt{\frac{1-X}{X}}$, $Re_g = G_{Tp} x D / \mu_g$, and $Re_l = G_{Tp} (1-x) D / \mu_l$</p>															

2) Liquid-Only and Gas-Only Frictional Multipliers (ϕ_{lo}^2 and ϕ_{go}^2)

The frictional multipliers in this case are defined as the ratio of the two-phase frictional pressure gradient over the pressure gradient that would arise if the phase flowed alone in the pipe to the total mass flux of the two-phase flow [31]:

$$\phi_i^2 = \left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_{Tp} / \left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_i \quad (11)$$

where the subscript i can be lo , or go , indicating liquid-only, or gas-only respectively. The single-phase frictional pressure drop is computed as follows:

$$\left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_i = \frac{2f_i G_{Tp}^2}{D \rho_i} \quad (12)$$

In this case, the Fang et al. correlation (8) was used to calculate the friction factor. Table III displays the frictional pressure drop correlations for this method.

TABLE III. THE SEPARATED CORRELATIONS: LIQUID-ONLY AND GAS- ONLY FRICTIONAL MULTIPLIERS (ϕ_{lo}^2 AND ϕ_{go}^2).

Reference	Correlations
[9]	$\phi_{lo}^2 = 1 + (Y^2 - 1) \{ B [(1-x)]^{0.875} + x^{1.75} \}$ <p>where:</p> $Y^2 = \left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_{go} / \left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_{lo}$ $\text{If } 0 < Y < 9.5, B = \begin{cases} 55/G_{Tp}^{0.5} & G_{Tp} \geq 1900 \\ 2400 & 500 < G_{Tp} < 1900 \\ 4.8 & G_{Tp} \leq 500 \end{cases}$ $\text{If } 9.5 < Y < 28, B = \begin{cases} 520/Y G_{Tp}^{0.5} & G_{Tp} \leq 600 \\ 21/Y & G_{Tp} > 600 \end{cases}$ <p>If $Y > 28, B = 15000/Y^2 G_{Tp}^{0.5}$</p>
[10]	<p>For viscous flow:</p> $\phi_{lo}^2 = (1-x)^2 + x^2 \left(\frac{\rho_l f_{go}}{\rho_g f_{lo}} \right) + \frac{3.24 x^{0.78} (1-x)^{0.224} H}{F_{Tp}^{0.45} W_e^{0.035}}$ <p>where: $H = \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} \right)^{0.91} \left(\frac{\mu_g}{\mu_l} \right)^{0.19} (1 - \mu_g / \mu_l)^{0.7}$, and, $F_{Tp} = G_{Tp}^2 / g D \rho_{Tp}^2$</p>
[16]	$\phi_{lo}^2 = 1 + \left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_{Fr} \left[\left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_g}{\mu_l} \right)^{0.25} - 1 \right]$ <p>Where:</p> $\left(\frac{dp}{dz} \right)_{Fr} = f_{Fr} [x + 4(x^{1.8} - x^{10} f_{Fr}^{0.5})],$ $f_{Fr} = \begin{cases} 1 & Fr_{lo} \geq 1 \\ F_{lo}^{0.3} + 0.0055 \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{Fr_{lo}} \right) \right]^2 & Fr_{lo} < 1 \end{cases}$ <p>and $Fr_{lo} = G_{Tp}^2 / g D \rho^2$</p>
[17]	$\phi_{lo}^2 = Y^2 x^3 + (1-x)^{1/3} [1 + 2x(Y^2 - 1)]$

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND MEASUREMENTS

The specially designed system was constructed to measure pressure drop in two-phase slug flow in a horizontal pipe. The two-phase air-water system was designed and built-up in the Multi-phase Laboratory of the Petroleum Engineering Department, College of Engineering, University of Zakho. The system's main components were the air and water supply systems, a two-phase mixer, a visual horizontal test section, pressure transmitters, and facility instrumentation. The air-water flow loop system scheme is illustrated in Figure 1.

The fluids in this system were air and water. A SHIMGE centrifugal water pump with a head of 22.5m and 600 LPM capacity was utilized to circulate water from a water storage tank to feed the test section via a water rotameter. The water rotameter was controlled by two ball valves and had a range of 20 to 150 LPM with an accuracy of $\pm 4\%$. They were both used to control the amount of flow that entered the test section, passed through a horizontal pipe, and then to a separator/first tank. In the separator tank, the air was released into the atmosphere via the separator tank's top, and the liquid settled under gravity and flowed through the bottom to return to the second tank. The water was stored in the two tanks that were linked together with PVC pipe. The first tank housed the return water from the test section, while the second tank, with a capacity of 426L, was used to feed the system via a PVC pipe connected to the pump. The second tank's function was to keep air bubbles and debris from transferring from the tank to the pump and to control the pump's excess flow.

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram of the experimental facility.

Meanwhile, the compressor supplied air to the loop, which was controlled by an air filter regulator with 0-11 bar range. An air rotameter with a measuring range of 40 to 400LPM and accuracy of $\pm 4\%$ was utilized to measure the air flow rate. At the T-junction at the test section's entrance, air and water were mixed. Water from the pump was fed into the mixer from one side, while compressed air was charged into the mixer via a 6mm diameter flexible hose parallel to the main flow. To distribute the air in the water stream, a mixer was also used. The designs of [23, 33] were used in the mixing section. The mixer section was constructed of a 6mm stainless steel pipe and was installed in the water stream using a plastic T-junction and a compression fitting. The stainless-steel pipe was soldered to prevent air flow from the end. Sixty holes with 1.3cm spacing and varying diameters were drilled in 15 columns around the stainless-steel pipe over a length of 25cm (3 rows of 1mm, 4 rows of 2mm, and 8 rows of 3mm). To prevent water from entering the air flow, the size of the holes was decreased through the internal tube. The testing section was divided into 3 parts. Each part was constructed from the acrylic pipe with a visual thickness of 5mm, a length of 2m, and an ID of 30mm. Each of the 3 parts of the test section was connected using flange connections. The total length of the test section was 6m. The flanges were mounted on fixed rigid steel frames to ensure long-term support and safe operation. Moreover, 4 different pressure transmitters from the WIKI Company with a range of 0-2bar were fixed to the top of the test section pipe by brass pipe fittings and installed to measure the pressure difference along the test section. Figure 2 depicts the experimental setup. The strategy employed at the start of each run was to start with

a fixed water discharge flow rate and gradually increase the air flow rate until slug flow appeared, then increase the water flow rate and repeat the previous steps. The Baker flow pattern map was used to determine experimental settings for the air-water flow rates [34]. These experimental conditions were scripted in Matlab (R2017b). The result is shown in Figure 3. The water and air flow rates were 30 to 80 LPM and 40 to 200 LPM respectively. The system's 4-channel voltage reader was utilized to read transient pressures from the pressure transmitter to a PC. The optimum time for all variable test requirements to exclude the influent effect on the flow was 30s. The experiments were conducted at a pressure of 1bar and a temperature of 20°C. All the experimental operating conditions are displayed in Table IV.

Fig. 2. The experimental setup.

Fig. 3. Flow pattern map produced by Matlab (R2017b) based on the experimental operating conditions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Statistical analysis was performed on the results of the two-phase pressure drop models to determine the best model among the 8 considered models. The results are shown in Table V. The analytic parameters are included in the following equations [35]:

$$e_i = \frac{\Delta P_{i\text{ cal}} - \Delta P_{i\text{ exp}}}{\Delta P_{i\text{ exp}}} \quad (13)$$

$$E_1 = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i \quad (14)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |e_i| \quad (15)$$

$$E_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\frac{(e_i - E_1)^2}{n-1}} \quad (16)$$

$$E_4 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i \quad (17)$$

$$E_5 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |e_i| \quad (18)$$

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENTAL OPERATING CONDITIONS

Fluids	Temperature (C°)	Gas Flow Rate (LPM)	Water Flow rate (LPM)	Pressure (bar)	Data rerecording time	No. of Tests
Air-water	20°	40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, and 200	30, 40, 50, 60, 70, and 80	0-1	30s	54

TABLE V. ERROR RESULTS FOR EACH MODEL

Reference	MPE (E ₁ %)	MAPE (E ₂ %)	Standard Deviation Percentage (E ₃)	Mean Error (E ₄)	Mean Absolute Error (E ₅)	Standard Deviation (E ₆)	RPF
[30]	-25.99	29.15	190.83	-0.26	0.29	1.07	2.95
[13]	-5.73	18.54	42.05	-0.06	0.19	1.23	0.47
[31]	41.61	41.90	305.57	0.42	0.42	1.88	5.74
[19]	9.64	17.54	70.82	0.10	0.18	1.30	0.76
[9]	-21.73	28.99	159.60	-0.22	0.29	1.45	2.78
[10]	31.08	35.14	228.26	0.31	0.35	2.36	4.57
[16]	-41.21	41.70	302.64	-0.41	0.42	0.51	4.95
[17]	-23.40	28.53	171.85	-0.23	0.29	1.23	2.77
E-min	5.726	17.544	42.047	0.057	0.175	0.506	
E-max	41.612	41.895	305.571	0.416	0.419	2.362	

TABLE VI. DATA POINT PERCENTAGE WITHIN THE ±30% ERROR BAND

Model	[30]	[13]	[31]	[19]	[9]	[10]	[16]	[17]
±30%	50	88.9	55.6	88.9	51.9	68.5	0.0	59.3

$$E_6 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\frac{(e_i - E_4)^2}{n-1}} \quad (19)$$

E₁ is the Mean Percentage Error (MPE), E₂ is the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), E₃ is the standard deviation percentage, E₄ is the mean error, E₅ is the mean absolute error, and E₆ is the standard deviation. According to Table V, the MAPE values for [13] and [30] were 18.54% and 29.15% respectively, for the homogeneous model, while for separated models, the model of [19] with 17.54% gives the least amount of MAPE, followed by the models of [17] with 28.53%, [9] with 28.99%, [10] with 35.14%, [16] with 41.70%, and [31] with 41.9%. It can be concluded that, out of the 8 models tested, the Sun-Mishima model [19] predicts the two-phase pressure drop with greater accuracy. The Relative Performance Factor (RPF) used to identify the best model is [36]:

$$RPF = \frac{|E_1| - |E_{1min}|}{|E_{1max}| - |E_{1min}|} + \frac{|E_2| - |E_{2min}|}{|E_{2max}| - |E_{2min}|} + \frac{|E_3| - |E_{3min}|}{|E_{3max}| - |E_{3min}|} + \frac{|E_4| - |E_{4min}|}{|E_{4max}| - |E_{4min}|} + \frac{|E_5| - |E_{5min}|}{|E_{5max}| - |E_{5min}|} + \frac{|E_6| - |E_{6min}|}{|E_{6max}| - |E_{6min}|} \quad (20)$$

For predicting two-phase pressure drop, the model with the least amount of RPF is the best, and the model with the most amount of RPF is the worst. In this method, [13] with 0.47 RPF value for homogeneous models and [19] with 0.76 RPF value for separated models produce the most accurate results, as displayed in Table V.

The third method investigates whether the data points fall within ±30% of the error band and the results are depicted in Table VI and Figures 4-9. The model of [13] results showed that most data points were within ±30% error band for homogeneous models. For the separated model, the models of [19] displayed the highest percentage of data with 88.9% of data within ±30% of the error band as illustrated in the Figures 4-9. These results differ from previous results, but the Sun-Mishima [19] model provides the best predictions of two-phase pressure drop models in each method.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the experimental data with the McAdams [30] and Chen et. al [13] correlations.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the experimental data with the Friedel correlation [10].

Fig. 5. Comparison of the experimental data with the Chisholm [31] and Sun-Mishima [19] correlations.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the experimental data with the Gronnerud correlation [16].

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimental data with the Chisholm [9] correlation.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the experimental data with the Muller-Steinhagen and Heck correlation [17].

V. CONCLUSION

The current work evaluated 8 models based on experimental data of air-water flow that were chosen to rely on Baker map in a horizontal test section 6m long and with 30mm ID, and with discharge flow rates for water and air ranging from 30 to 80 LPM and 40 to 80 LPM respectively. Four pressure transmitters were used to measure the pressure along the test section, with a 30s ideal measurement period. The 54 experimental data points were compared to 8 well-known pressure drop models using a variety of methods. Some key findings of the current study are:

- MAPE was used to compare the experimental results to previous correlations. The Sun-Mishima model was found to be the best, with 17.54%, while the Müller-Steinhagen and Heck, Chisholm, Friedel, and Gronnerud models produce acceptable results. Chisholm is the least accurate model, with 41.9% accuracy.
- The results of the RPF comparison show that the outcomes were identical to the results of MAPE. The Sun-Mishima model had the highest RPF of 0.76, while the Chisholm model had the lowest.
- To evaluate these models, the percentage of data that falls within $\pm 30\%$ of the error band was used. The results of this method differ slightly from those of the previous methods, but ultimately, the Sun-Mishima model was again the most accurate, with 88.9% of data falling within the $\pm 30\%$ error band.

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Direct ADC Controlled Asymmetric Cascaded Multilevel Inverter

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Abstract-This paper presents an asymmetric multi-level inverter with a novel direct ADC control scheme. This scheme does not use a carrier wave or a reference sinusoidal wave to generate gate pulses for power switches, but an Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) to create gate pulses. For n sources, n bit ADC will generate $2^{n+1}-1$ levels at the output voltage of the inverter. This scheme uses the ADC output for the gate pulses for power switching devices. In this topology, the inverter comprises a series of connected half-bridges to generate a more significant level. The presented topology uses binary level supply voltages. Different topologies with different parameters are compared with the proposed inverter, and the operation of the proposed control scheme is verified with a simulation in Matlab. The prototype of a 31-level inverter is developed in hardware, and the hardware results are discussed.

Keywords-analog to digital converter; cascaded inverter; reduced power switching devices; multilevel inverter

I. INTRODUCTION

For less Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) in the output voltage of an inverter, in medium power applications, multilevel inverters (MLIs) are most preferred. MLIs have become very popular due to their power topologies. They are widely used for medium voltage applications like grid-connected inverters, traction systems, and FACTS.

The current paper presents enormous topologies and their control switching pattern [1]. MLIs are classified into two categories, symmetric and asymmetric, based on their supply DC sources [5]. Here, the proposed topology is asymmetric as supplied DC voltages are different in magnitude. Simulated and hardware prototypes of four DC voltage sources were used. Four half-bridges were connected in series in a power circuit, and the series' output was connected to one full-bridge inverter.

A novel finite predictive control method was described in [2]. A three-phase inverter asymmetric fault-tolerant control scheme was illustrated in [3] to limit the fault phase's fault current. Using diode rectifiers, isolated DC-DC converters were implemented to reduce the power switching devices in [4]. A home-type cascaded inverter was presented in [6]. The authors used unidirectional and bi-directional switches in the power circuit. Without any additional structure like H-bridges, the given topology can generate a uniform positive and negative cycle at the output of the MLI. The limitation of this topology is that it requires bidirectional switches. Matlab simulation of T-type 3 level inverter is represented in [7] for the field oriented control of traction motor. PMSM motor control using multi-level inverter with active damping and current controller was described in [8].

II. POWER CIRCUIT AND OPERATION

Based on the amplitude of the supplied DC voltage sources, output voltage levels can be adjusted. MLI can be classified into two categories, depending on the DC sources: Symmetric and asymmetric. In symmetric MLI, all the supplied DC sources are equal in magnitude, while in asymmetric, the magnitudes of the supplied DC sources are different. In asymmetric MLI, binary or trinary type DC sources are used. In the binary pattern, DC sources are, for example, V_{dc} , $2V_{dc}$, $4V_{dc}$, etc. In trinary type, DC sources are like V_{dc} , $3V_{dc}$, $9V_{dc}$, etc. However, in trinary type power topologies, the control scheme is somewhat complex and requires a look-up table for switching power devices. In binary type DC sources, the reference signal can be converted directly in binary form using analog to digital conversion IC or onboard an ADC channel of processor or micro-controller chip. In some processors, such as the ARM series, floating-point ADC is available and can also give negative signals. If floating-point

ADC is unavailable, then the Vref signal is converted first in absolute value.

For n isolated binary level DC sources:

- The number of levels achieved at an output voltage of an inverter is $2^{n+1}-1$
- The number of power switching devices required is $(2*n) + 4$
- The number of gate drivers (half-bridge driver) required is $n + 2$

From the above, if we use four isolated DC sources, one can achieve a 31-level output voltage of an inverter with a total of 12 power switching devices and 6 half-bridge MOSFET / IGBT driver circuits.

In the proposed ADC-controlled MLI, binary-type DC sources are used, e.g. 12V, 24V, 48V, and 96V. All the DC sources are connected to one half-bridge circuit of the power switching device. So, 4 half-bridge circuits are used, and 1 full-bridge circuit generates the negative and positive cycle. The output of zero-crossing logic is used as a gate pulse for the full-bridge circuit. So, the switching frequency of this full H-bridge is similar to the power frequency. Gate pulses for S0 and S01 power switches are operating in inverting mode. So, in the gate pulses of these 2 switches, the dead band is generated using driver IC. Similar logic is also applied for S1-S11, S2-S21, S3-S31, and Sh1-Sh11, Sh2-Sh21. Suppose $V_{dc0} = V_{dc}$, then $V_{dc1} = 2*V_{dc}$, $V_{dc2} = 4*V_{dc}$, and $V_{dc3} = 8*V_{dc}$. Figure 1 shows the power topology for the proposed 31-level MLI. Table I shows the switching pattern for 31 levels. It is seen that switching is done like a binary conversation. So, for the +15 Vdc output level, all DC sources are connected in series. So, this is nothing but $(1111)_2$ in 4-bit binary, indicating the states of power switches S3, S2, S1, and S0 respectively. Similarly, for +10 Vdc the states are $(1010)_2$ in binary, which means switches S3 and S1 are in on state, and S2 and S0 are in off state.

Fig. 1. Power topology of the 31-level MLI.

TABLE I. SWITCHING STATES OF THE 31-LEVEL INVERTER

S3	S2	S1	S0	Sh1	Sh2	Output
1	1	1	1	1	0	+15 Vdc
1	1	1	0	1	0	+14 Vdc
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0	0	0	1	1	0	+1 Vdc
0	0	0	0	1	0	0 Vdc
0	0	0	1	0	1	-1 Vdc
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
1	1	1	1	0	1	-15 Vdc

A. Applications of the Proposed Inverter

The proposed control scheme is straightforward to implement in a grid-tied inverter. This scheme is also applicable to a solar Micro-Inverter, and isolated DC sources can be implemented using a high-frequency transformer. It can also be applied for the speed control of an induction motor. Especially in electric vehicle systems, this inverter can be used where isolated DC sources are available in the form of batteries.

III. DIRECT ADC-BASED CONTROL SCHEME

Various topologies have been invented to reduce the harmonics in the output voltage of the MLI. Different techniques are available to control amplitude, frequency, and maintain a nearly sinusoidal waveform at the output of an MLI. The Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE) method uses optimization techniques like PSO algorithm [11], Pulse Width Modulation (PWM), HPWM (Hybrid PWM), SPWM (Sinusoidal PWM), PRSPWM (Prior Switching PWM), SVPWM (Space Vector PWM), etc. In the SPWM technique, the sine wave is compared with high-frequency carrier waves, increasing switching losses. The arrangement of a triangular (carrier) wave in a different pattern is also needed, i.e. APOD (Alternate Phase Opposition Disposition), PD (Phase Disposition), POD (Phase Opposition Disposition). The direct ADC-controlled technique does not require any triangular carrier wave. Based on the look-up table of the first half cycle of the sine wave, it generates n-bit controlled signals. The generated signals are directly used as the gate pulses of the half-bridge of the inverter. In the direct ADC method, the switching frequency is less than in all the PWM methods, so the overall efficiency of an inverter increases as switching losses decrease.

The bit resolution of the ADC is essential for the generation of gate pulses. In this control scheme, the bit resolution of the ADC decides the number of levels of the output voltage of the MLI. As with 2-bit resolution, this will make only a $(2*2^2)-1=7$ level output, a 3-bit resolution will make a $(2*2^3)-1=15$ level output, and a 4-bit will give $(2*2^4)-1=31$ levels. As the number of resolutions increases, the required number of isolated DC sources also increases, which is the disadvantage of the proposed control scheme.

In the grid-connected inverter, the proposed control method is straightforward to control an inverter's output. When the grid voltage RMS value reduces, ADC conversion automatically changes, and the output of the inverter also reduces. Similarly, when there is a change in the supply frequency of the grid, the inverter output frequency also changes, which is the main advantage of the proposed MLI.

In this control method, the output of an MLI always remains in synchronization with the grid voltage. In the proposed technique, the inverter is always connected to the grid at a unity power factor, and DC link utilization is also full in. In all grid-connected topologies, a PLL block is required to synchronize the grid voltage with the inverter voltage. However, the proposed technique does not require a PLL block. In the current paper, a 4-bit control scheme is implemented in hardware. The prototype MLI is connected to

the grid to check the synchronization between the voltage of the grid and the inverter output voltage. Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the gate pulse generation through direct ADC.

Fig. 2. ADC control block diagram of the MLI.

IV. COMPARISON WITH OTHER TOPOLOGIES

The following parameters are affected for properly evaluating different MLI topologies.

- Reliability and total cost
- Efficiency
- Performance, control schemes, and applications
- Dynamic response

The reliability and the cost of the inverter generally depend on the required number of power switches, the total blocking voltage capacity of that switching device, and the required DC sources (NDC). The efficiency of the inverter depends on the total number of power switching devices (NS), its blocking

voltage capacity, and the switching frequency of the devices. Performance, control, and dynamic response of an inverter depend on power distribution, module structure, and the number of passive components.

TABLE II. SWITCHING STATES OF THE 31-LEVEL INVERTER

Ref. No.	N _L	N _S	N _{Driver}	N _{DC}	R
NPC	31	60	60	1	1.935
CHB	31	60	60	15	1.935
FC	31	60	60	1	1.935
14	31	16	12	6	0.516
17	31	10	10	5	0.322
18	33	28	28	8	0.903
19	17	12	12	5	0.387
20	31	12	12	4	0.387
Proposed	31	12	12	4	0.3871

So the proposed topology is compared with other 31-level inverters. Comparison is done considering the inverter output levels (N_L), the number of switching devices used (N_S), the total number of gate driver circuits (N_{Driver}), and the required DC sources (NDC). Table II compares the various known MLIs with the proposed 31-level inverter. The ratio (R) of switches to output level is also calculated. Topologies with a lower ratio are better than the ones with higher. From Table II, it can be seen that the proposed inverter uses fewer switches compared to other topologies. Figure 3 shows the comparison graph between the number of the required DC sources and the required number of power switching devices respectively. From all comparison graphs, it can be seen that the proposed MLI is better than the other inverters.

Fig. 3. Comparison graph of the proposed and other topologies: (a) No. of DC sources vs no. of levels, (b) no. of switching devices vs no. of levels.

V. POWER LOSS CALCULATION

Power losses in any switching device can be divided into three parts:

- Conduction losses (P_C)
- Switching losses (P_{SW})
- Blocking losses (P_B) (normally neglected)

A. Conduction Losses

Conduction losses can be found using drain-source on state resistance (R_{DS(ON)}) and drain current (I_D):

$$P_C = R_{DS(ON)} * I_D^2 \quad (1)$$

B. Switching Losses

Switching losses occur due to the fast switching of devices. They include switching on-time (t_{ON}) and off-time (t_{OFF}). Switching losses on t_{ON} can be calculated from (2):

$$P_{SWON} = f_s \int_0^{t_{ON}} V_{ds}(t) i_D(t) dt$$

$$P_{SWON} = f_s \int_0^{t_{ON}} \left(\frac{V_{ds}}{t_{ON}} t \right) \left(-\frac{1}{t_{ON}} (t - t_{ON}) \right) dt = \frac{1}{6} f_s V_{ds} i_D t_{ON} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, P_{SWOFF} can be found by:

$$P_{SWOFF} = \frac{1}{6} f_s V_{ds} i_D t_{OFF} \quad (3)$$

The total switching losses are given by:

$$P_{SW} = \frac{1}{6} f_s V_{ds} i_D (t_{ON} + t_{OFF}) t_{OFF} \quad (4)$$

where f_s =switching frequency (Hz), V_{ds} = drain to source voltage of the MOSFET, i_D =drain current, t_{ON} = switching on-time, and t_{OFF} =switching off-time.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

The proposed direct ADC control scheme is simulated in Matlab/Simulink with asymmetric DC sources Vdc, 2Vdc, 4Vdc, and 8Vdc. In simulations and prototype hardware, 12V, 24V, 48V, and 96V isolated DC sources were used. So, the total DC voltage is 180V. Table III shows the simulation parameters in Simulink.

Fig. 4. Matlab/Simulink model.

TABLE III. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameters		Simulation values
Input DC Voltage Sources	DC0	12V
	DC1	24V
	DC2	48V
	DC3	96V
Maximum Output Voltage	Voutmax	180V
Output RMS Voltage	Vourms	129V
Output current	Iourms	2.8A
Output Frequency	f_o	50Hz
Output Voltage Level at m=1	N_L	31
Power factor	pf	0.90

The 4-bit ADC control scheme is used for the control of the MLI. So, for the 31-level MLI, 4 half-bridge and 1 full-bridge power circuits are used. Figure 4 shows the complete Simulink model. Subsystems 1 to 4 are used for the half-bridge, and subsystem 5 is used for the full-bridge connection. The Matlab function block converts reference AC signal into digital output using 4 bit ADC logic from y0 to y3. z0 gives zero crossings of the reference AC signal. Figure 5 shows the output of the ADC, which works as gate pulses for each half-bridge subsystem, and the zero-crossing signal as a gate pulse for the full-bridge subsystem 5. Each bit has a different frequency, so each half-bridge works at a different switching frequency. Figure 6 shows the output voltage and current waveforms with R=42Ω and L=63.7mH at modulation index m=1. Figure 7 shows the simulated output load voltage and load current waveforms with R=100Ω and L=63.7mH at modulation index m=0.6. The THD of the output voltage varies between 3.16% and 6.42%, with a

modulation index from m=1 to 0.5. The THD of the output current is 0.82% at modulation index 1 and 1.69% at 0.5 with a load of L=63.7mH in series with R=42Ω. From Figure 8, it can be seen that the THD of the output current and voltage increase as the modulation index decreases. A passive filter can be used to decrease the THD of the voltage.

Fig. 5. Output gate pulses from Matlab function block.

Fig. 6. Output Voltage and current at R=42Ω and L=63.7mH at m=1.0.

Fig. 7. Output Voltage and current at R=100Ω and L=63.7mH at m=0.6.

Fig. 8. THD (%) of the output voltage and load current with different values of m.

B. Efficiency of the MLI

In the simulations, the total switching losses of the inverter are 19W at load R=42Ω and L=63.7mH. The input power to the inverter is 324W, and the output power is 305W. So, the efficiency of the inverter is 94.13%.

$$\text{Inverter Efficiency} = \text{Output AC power} / \text{Input DC Power} = (V_{\text{orms}} * I_{\text{orms}} * \text{pf}) / (V_{\text{dc}} * I_{\text{dc}}).$$

VII. HARDWARE RESULTS

An 8-bit AVR microcontroller was used to generate gate pulses for the prototype hardware model of the proposed MLI. It has six 10-bit on board ADC channels. A reference sine wave was implemented, giving 4-bit digital output and one zero-crossing detector for the implemented power circuit. The generated 4-bit output was used as gate pulses for 4 half-bridges, and the zero-crossing output was used as a gate pulse of a full H-bridge power circuit. An IR 2104 half-bridge driver IC was used for each half-bridge MOSFET. So, a total of 6 IR2104 driver ICs are used for the proposed MLI. IR2104 driver IC has an inbuilt dead-band facility between the upper and lower MOSFETs. No additional hardware or software was required to generate the dead band between the two inverted gate pulses. IRFP460N MOSFETs are used as power switching devices for the full h-bridge circuits, and IRFB4110 MOSFETs are used as power switching devices for the 4 half-bridge circuits. The gate pulses from the microcontroller are isolated using 817 opt-coupler IC to protect the microcontroller. The hardware prototype was tested with a resistive and inductive type of load with different modulation indexes.

The THD of the inverter's output voltage and load current was measured with a Hioki power quality analyzer PQ3198, and the waveforms were captured with a Tektronics Digital Storage oscilloscope. Figure 9(a) shows the output of the ADC of an 8-bit AVR micro-controller that is used as gate pulses (G0, G1, G2, and G3) for the half H-bridges and Figure 9(b) shows the zero crossing output Z as gate pulse of the full H-bridge. Figure 10 shows the output voltage waveform of MLI and its zoomed waveform of a positive half-cycle that clearly shows 31 levels of output.

The TDH of the output voltage was tested with a Hioki make power analyzer which gives 2.11% THD at m=1. The output of the MLI is connected with different load resistances and an inductor of 63.7mH. Figures 11 to 13 show the inverter output voltage and load current waveforms, output current RMS and peak value, total output power, and power factor.

Figure 11 shows the output waveforms and the load current THD with power at load resistance of 110Ω in series with an inductor of L=63.7mH. Figure 12 shows the output waveforms and current THD with power at load resistance of 78Ω in series with an inductor of L=63.7mH. Figure 13 shows the output waveforms and current THD with power at load resistance of 60Ω in series with an inductor of L=63.7mH. Figure 14 shows the prototype hardware set-up of complete MLI with load circuits and isolated DC power supplies.

TABLE IV. DEVICE SPECIFICATIONS OF THE HARDWARE PROTOTYPE

Device name	Device number	Specifications
MOSFET	IRFB4110	N-Channel Power MOSFET VDSS = 100V, RDS(on) = 3.7 mΩ, ID = 120 A
MOSFET	IRFP460N	N-Channel Power MOSFET VDSS = 500V, RDS(on) = 0.24 Ω, ID = 20 A
MOSFET Driver	IR2104	Half-bridge Driver IC VOFFSET = 600 V max, Io+/- = 130 mA / 270 mA, VOUT = 10-20 V, ton/off = 680 and 150 ns, Dead time = 520 ns
Photo-coupler IC	PC817	4 pin photo-coupler VCEO = 80 V, Viso(rms) = 5kV
Microcontroller	Atmega328P-PU	8-bit AVR Microcontroller

Fig. 9. Generated gate pulses using ADC: (a) Gate pulses of half-bridges, (b) gate pulse of the full h-bridge.

Hardware prototype results of the ADC-controlled 31-level inverter: (a) Output Voltage, (b) zoomed view.

Fig. 10. Prototype hardware results for R= 110Ω and L=63.7mH at modulation index m=1: (a) Output Voltage and current, (b) RMS value and THD of the output current, (c) pf, active, and reactive power.

Fig. 11. Prototype hardware results for $R=78\Omega$ and $L=63.7\text{mH}$ at modulation index $m=1$: (a) Output Voltage and current, (b) RMS value and THD of the output current, (c) pf, active, and reactive power.

Fig. 12. Prototype hardware results for $R=60\Omega$ and $L=63.7\text{mH}$ at modulation index $m=1$: (a) Output Voltage and current, (b) RMS value and THD of the output current, (c) pf, active, and reactive power.

Fig. 13. Prototype hardware set up in the laboratory.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, binary level DC sources were used to minimize the number of required DC power sources: 31 levels were achieved at the inverter output voltage using direct ADC control and only 4 DC sources. The THD of the inverter output voltage was reduced to 2.11% at $m=1$ and the THD of the output current was also reduced to 1%. Direct ADC control scheme was used to control power switching devices, which is very simple compared to other control schemes such as SPWM and SVPWM. Here, there is no need to compare the reference sine wave with any carrier (triangular) wave. An inverter's grid connection can be easily implemented using the direct ADC control scheme. The RMS value of the output voltage of the proposed MLI will change according to the changes in the RMS voltage of the grid. Grid frequency and output voltage frequency are always synchronized, which is the main advantage of this control scheme.

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